

EOSC WITHIN NATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR DIGITAL SKILLS

LANDSCAPE REPORT

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Abbreviations

AC	Associated Countries
BBSc	Business Balance Scorecard
DG CNECT	Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content & Technology
DG EAC	Directorate-General for Education & Culture
DG GROW	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship & SMEs
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research & Innovation
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESCO	European Skills, Competences, Qualifications & Occupation
EU	European Union
ICT	Information & Communications Technology
IT	Information Technology
LLL	Lifelong Learning
PESTEL	Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental & Legal
QA	Quality Assurance
SRIA	Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities & Threats
TGB	Technopolis Group Belgium

1 Executive Summary

The objective of this Landscape Report is to provide an overview of the current situation in relation to national Digital Skills Initiatives in Europe. The analysis performed targeted an extended area of these initiatives, far beyond EOSC or the research sector related mapping and lied on the findings for 9 selected Member States/ Associated countries in order to provide insights on the initiatives undertaken in the field and to serve as a baseline for performing a gap analysis on the SRIA priorities.

The landscape mapping is structured upon 5 thematic areas (sections):

- a) Digital skills policy context
- b) Digital skills governance model
- c) Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level
- d) Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks
- e) Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

Under each section, the findings per country are presented. In addition to this, a short benchmarking analysis (comparative analysis) is also performed in order to complete the mapping of the countries. The report also includes brief country reports and factsheets for each of the selected nine countries, outlining the findings in each area per country.

The analysis indicated that there seems to be a fragmentation regarding the establishment of a governance system for the upgrade of digital skills, where focus is given in different target groups per country, mainly addressing public services users, schools, students and teachers, labour force, and business digital transformation. Hence, the identification of the most suitable approach for digital skills upgrade to target is difficult. Digital skills ecosystems are complex and, in many cases, the priorities of different actors of the ecosystem lay in silos in relation to open science and open data. No single pattern related to the stakeholder's synthesis participating in the ecosystem of digital skills upgrade is identified. Many training programmes are identified, for several target groups, both in the public and private sector, while universities offer a variety of post-graduate studies in data/bid data and statistics. DigComp is endorsed, in almost all countries assessed, as the Competence Framework related to certification of digital skills. Libraries and repositories play a crucial role not only for implementing training programmes for scientists and researchers, but mainly for upgrading the necessary infrastructure and access for open data. Moreover, it has been identified that in several scientific areas emphasis is given to FAIR data rather than OPEN, in alignment with the directions of the FAIR Data Action Plan.

In a nutshell, the major findings of the landscape analysis, in the selected countries, can be summarised as follows:

1. Governance fragmentation & diverse priorities in digital skills upgrade,
2. Absence of an integrated framework for the establishment of the competent national policy,
3. Absence of a stand-alone national strategy for digital skills in almost all countries assessed,
4. Diversification in the participation of stakeholders per country,
5. A lot of training under progress,
6. A single certification framework acknowledged,
7. A major gap assessed in combined action for digital skills and education and digital skills and open science/open access,
8. Open Science Strategies are mostly focusing on research and infrastructure,
9. FAIR Data Action Plan alignment.

2 Background Information of the landscape

2.1 Background on policies at EU level

With the adoption of the Digital Single Markets strategy on 6 May 2015, the EC announced the launch of a cloud for research data – the ‘research open science cloud’. The ‘European Open Science Cloud’ (EOSC) aims to create a trusted environment for hosting and processing research data to support EU science in its global leading role.

The initiative reinforces Open Science, Open Innovation and Open Policies to the world. It aims to foster best practices of global data findability and accessibility (FAIR data), help researchers get their data skills recognised and rewarded (careers, altmetrics); help address issues of access and copyright (IPR) and data subject privacy; allow easier replicability of results and limit data wastage e.g. of clinical trial data (research integrity); contribute to clarification of the funding model for data generation and preservation, reducing rent-seeking and priming the market for innovative research services.

The **EOSC Working Group (EOSC WG) on Skills & Training** started in January 2020 and included 38 members from 24 countries, representing universities, data centers, libraries, ministries, infrastructures, policy makers as well as education/learning. Experience in both data and ICT is covered by the Members of the WG.

The “Skills and Training” Working Group is working on building competence (skills) and capabilities (training) for EOSC. The goal is to provide a framework for a sustainable training infrastructure to support EOSC in all its phases and ensure its uptake. The WG will consult and converge with existing initiatives and H2020 EOSC projects to agree upon key components for skills development and training, determine how these can be embedded in different levels of EOSC (institutional, national, EU), and identify what structures are needed to make EOSC a viable success (sustainability). Therefore, the EOSC Skills and Training Working Group focuses on:

1. Skills development framework (competences) for organizational culture change and service development
2. EOSC training framework/infrastructure (capabilities), targeting trainers and professional groups that support researchers in the stewardship of research outputs and service providers in providing their services via EOSC

Digital and Open Science skills are a cornerstone in EOSC’s operations and future. Developing and sustaining the skills of researchers, research support staff, and EOSC service providers is essential for the success of the EOSC vision. An EOSC network is actually working to bring a culture change for sharing research outcomes, policy awareness, and compliance and knowledge of ICT support services, as well as to empower individuals and institutions to develop and maintain EOSC competences science and capabilities.

SRIA: Skills Development, Training & Education

To realize its vision of a strong digital research data ecosystem with data and software at its core, EOSC launches a concerted effort in education and training to develop and up-skill its human resources. Key actions for success are:

- Promote ‘transparency and recognition of skills and qualifications’, as this is particularly relevant to the task of recognising open science skills, and consequently the challenge to provide a framework to validate these skills.
- Foster an equitable and balanced digital research labour market, with equity and inclusiveness regarding geographical (brain circulation), disciplinary, gender, ethnicity and age (early career) aspects.
- Strengthen cross-sector (research-industry-public sector) mobility and employability. Of particular importance are the transferable digital skills additional to data and ICT knowledge,

such as communication and leadership. Industry and the public sector are key contributors to digital up-skilling and improved alignment will maximise the benefits of training provided by different sectors.

- Invest in people to ultimately create an ecosystem that promotes learning, experimenting and growth. Facilitate and cultivate a digital and open science culture within research organizations (Research Performing Organizations, funding agencies, academia) for a wide researcher buy-in, by investing and prioritizing training and collaboration tools for researchers.
- Build resilience into digital skills and training, to deal with both the "shock" of a new technology coming to the fore, or in the case of COVID-19, suddenly needing a certain part of the population to increase a type of digital skills³. Design skills and training strategies that proceed at the same speed as technological developments.
- Embed the human/people factor in the design of future digital skills systems from the onset as data intensive science (EOSC will evolve as new technologies and sharing models emerge) to recognise when a step change is coming and work alongside the developing technology to develop training around it.

EOSC assesses the gaps to shift the culture of research towards openness and transparency, to build bridges between different organizational models, to approach digital literacy in various modes and settings, while working on existing initiatives and preconditions (. These refer to:

1. Lack of digital core expertise; not enough adequately trained people to meet current demand for open and data intensive science needs, let alone increasing demand, nor is there a concerted effort in skills and capacity development which is a crucial element to build and exploit the full potential of the EOSC;
2. Lack of a clear definition of digital professional profiles; Data scientists, data stewards, data curators and research software engineers are some of the different actors needed for the development of data-driven, data intensive science;
3. Existence of disparities; Although the reliance on the emerging new scholarly data and software support profiles are cornerstone elements in the implementation of FAIR data mandates there is a very diverse and uneven picture across Europe;
4. Lack of expertise: There is not sufficient support to the technological development for "FAIR-by-design";
5. Lack of legal/IPR and data ethics expertise;
6. Lack of interdisciplinarity, coordinated and coherent approaches to skills and competences building and for education and training provision;
7. Fragmentation in training resources; Quality and FAIRness of training and learning resources remains a challenge.

According to the above-mentioned gaps, EOSC will target activities to improve the skills of researchers and other relevant EOSC stakeholders, as well as improve the training offered. An important objective will be for EOSC skills and training to permeate educational curricula and competence centres. The priorities according to which EOSC main target will be achieved comprise:

Priority 1: Developing the next generation of data/EOSC professionals.

Priority 2: Educating students and researchers.

Priority 3: EOSC to become a trusted and long-lasting knowledge hub of learning materials and tooling

Priority 4: Developing an EOSC leadership programme to foster the right policy environment for skills and training.

EOSC Skills Ecosystem

Digital and Open Science skills are key into EOSC's operations and future, and the upskilling of researchers and research support staff is therefore essential for its success. A culture change for sharing research outcomes, policy awareness, and compliance and knowledge of ICT is needed to empower individuals and institutions to develop and maintain EOSC competences science and capabilities. *Digital Skills agendas and infrastructures* are emerging throughout Europe in different contexts, targeting different groups. But if someone looked carefully, they would see that the goals are very similar (creating a digital workforce), training means overlap, and organizations involved have similar stakes. Forming partnerships between such players would only bring economies of scale and allow for a cross-sectoral sustainable digital workforce

European Skills Agenda

The magnitude of the digital skills challenge requires a long-term strategy and new partnerships between European, national, regional, public, and private players including civil society. On 1 July 2020 the European Commission presented the new European Skills Agenda for sustainable competitiveness, social fairness and resilience. The Communication¹ underlines the importance of lifelong learning, lays down objectives for the skills for jobs in the digital and green transitions and it mobilises companies, social partners and organisations to take meaningful actions. The Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition contributes fully to the objectives of the Skills Agenda and will continue to play a vital role in mobilising the community and bridging the digital skills gap in Europe.

EU Digital Competence Framework²

The European Commission has prioritised and supported digital skills development through a range of policies and actions, working with Member States in supporting learners, employees, job-seekers and innovators in every setting. DigComp – the European Digital Competence Framework represents a milestone in this journey. DigComp is a reference framework that describes what it means to be digitally competent. It can be used across sectors, disciplines and systems to enable people to develop digital competence. DigComp sets out the 21 competences necessary to be digitally competent and maps these across 8 proficiency levels, from the most basic to advanced levels.

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=22832&langId=en>

² https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC110624/dc_guide_may18.pdf

Digital Skills in 2021 and beyond

To implement the actions and meet the objectives of the Skills Agenda, the EU will need estimated additional public and private investments in skills of around €48 billion annually.

In particular, to tackle the digital skills gap, significant investments are needed. In the new EU budget, the Commission proposes coherent and comprehensive support for building up the digital skills needed to support reskilling and upskilling in Europe for a successful digital transformation. Different funds will target different skills needs.

The Commission's proposal for Next Generation EU³ provides significant resources as part of a major budgetary initiative to tackle the economic and social consequences of the crisis. EU funds can act as a catalyst for investing in people's skills. In the context of the EU Recovery Plan, unprecedented financial resources are proposed to support a sustainable recovery, and investment in skills should be at the heart of these efforts. Throughout the 2021-2027 period, EU instruments such as the European Social Fund Plus with a proposed budget of €86 billion, Erasmus with a proposed budget of €26 billion and Invest EU's Social Investment and Skills window with a proposed budget of €3.6 billion can all be mobilised to help people gain better or new skills.

In particular, the European Social Fund Plus will support EU Member States to improve the quality, effectiveness and labour market relevance of national education and training systems to support the acquisition of key competences, including digital skills. It will also promote upskilling and reskilling opportunities for all, placing a particular emphasis on digital skills.

The European Global Adjustment Fund will support training, which will all have a digital skills component, to help laid-off workers find another job or set up their own business.

Erasmus+ will support digital learning from early childhood to vocational education and university education. It will also continue to support the acquisition of digital skills through cross-border experiences.

Horizon Europe will finance grants for master, PhD and post-graduate research activities in all fields including digital through Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions as well as the European Institute of Innovation & Technology.

The new Digital Europe Programme with a proposed budget €8.2 billion (€9,2 billion actual prices) will invest in advanced digital skills development to master technologies.

- Master's Programmes in cutting-edge digital technologies developed together with EU excellence centres in artificial intelligence, cyber and high-performance computing. The aim is to offer 160 new master programmes training 80,000 digital specialists.
- Short-term specialized training courses in advanced digital technologies for around 150,000 job seekers and employed people especially in SMEs. The aim is to equip them with the competences that will enable the deployment of digital technologies across all sectors of the economy.
- 35,000 job placements in companies or research centres where advanced digital technologies are developed or used. The aim is to give people the opportunity to learn specialists' skills working with the latest available technologies.

Moreover, the Recovery and Resilience Facility, powered by €560 billion in grants and loans, provides Member States with ample opportunity to fund upskilling and reskilling initiatives, with the appropriate reforms in place (https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_1196).

³ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_1196

2.2 Objectives of the Report

The objective of the landscape report is the provision of an overview of the current situation in relation to national Digital Skills Initiatives in Europe. The analysis is targeting an extended area of these initiatives, far beyond EOSC or the research sector related mapping. It lies on the findings for 9 MS/AC in order to provide insights on the initiatives under investigation and to serve as a baseline for the performing of a gap analysis on the SRIA priorities.

2.3 Landscape-Mapping of EU selected countries-Methodology

2.3.1 Methodological framework

The methodological approach for the selection of the 9 countries is presented in Annex I. Its application resulted in the following 9 countries:

1. Finland
2. Netherlands
3. Denmark
4. Switzerland
5. France
6. Lithuania
7. Portugal
8. Greece
9. Hungary

Right after the selection of the 9 countries, and based on a list of experts and reference points provided by the EOSC WG, desk research as well as interviews were conducted, and specific country reports were drafted. The analysis of each country report also results in a fact sheet, comprising a short assessment of as-is situation and an overview of the national strategy and initiatives for Digital Skills at MS/AC level. Its content is related to:

Mapping of:

- goals – short and long term;
- focus – sectors, what type of skills, what type of capacity building;
- governance scheme:
 - actors – what type of organizations are involved, at what level (e.g., policy, services, engagement);
 - coordination structures within the country but also with EC and other EU initiatives;
- implementation – what types of instruments, activities, infrastructure do they use, what has worked, what not;
- outputs of the above-mentioned activities;
- other types of initiatives that might present interest in the field;
- potential indicators in the country, is any.

Methodological Tools to be used in the task

Desk Research on ongoing Digital Skills initiatives in MS/AC

	<p>Key Informant Interviews with experts and reference national points provided by the EOSC WG</p> <p>Comparative analysis</p>
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2.3.2 The profile of the qualitative field research

The specific objectives of the qualitative field research refer to the:

- Provision of data regarding the as is situation in the selected countries
- Provision of an overview for the national Digital Skills initiatives
- Provision of qualitative insights based upon a set of questions guiding the interviews.

The agenda of the semi-structured KIIs, is driven from two thematic areas: (a) digital skills, (b) research, data & open science. The key questions for the discussion with the selected interviewees are analysed in Annex II.

2.3.3 Structure of the report

The landscape report will be structured upon 5 thematic areas (sections):

- Digital skills policy context
- Digital skills governance model
- Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level
- Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks
- Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

Under each section, the findings per country are presented. In addition to this, a short benchmarking analysis (comparative analysis) is also performed in order to complete the mapping of the countries.

On overview of the selected countries proceeds the detailed analysis chapter.

3 Countries' Overview

3.1 Countries at a glance

DENMARK

Denmark, the smallest country in Scandinavia, has been widely recognised as one of the most advanced digital economies in the EU. Ranked in the DESI scale as the fourth most digitally advanced economy in Europe, there is plenty to learn from Denmark when it comes to digitalisation. One area in which Denmark has particularly excelled, in relation to other frontrunner countries, is in its effort to ensure that all citizens benefit from digitalisation. 95% of Danes are online - well above the European average - while half of those aged 65 or above have basic digital skills (DESI). This success is driven by the country's focus on fostering innovation through partnerships and collaboration, sharing best practice and learning from others. Even though Denmark is among the most digitized nations, research shows that more than 1 million Danish citizens aged 16 to 65 years of age are lacking in digital skills. In the ICT sector, Denmark also has a critical skills gap, which seems to be growing looking into the future. Therefore, some of the main challenges that Denmark faces are the stagnating supply of ICT professionals, while demand is growing, the projection stated in Europe's Digital Progress Report (2017) that the Danish companies will face a deficit of 19,000 employees with digital skills by 2030 as well as maintaining a steady supply of expertise which is crucial to Denmark's continued success.

FINLAND

Finland is among the most advanced digital economies in the EU and has a history of ranking high on the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), including the 3rd place in 2018, with a 73.8 overall performance score in 2018. It has the highest scores in human capital, integration of digital technology and digital public services, ranking 1st, 2nd, and 1st respectively in 2018. Finland is well known for its world-class education system from primary school to lifelong education and training, which is reflected in its high rankings across the board in digital learning indicators, having one of the highest scores on the Women in Digital Scoreboard (WID 2020). The Finnish education system is one of the best globally and ICT specialists' share of the workforce (6.7%) is one of the highest as well. Digital skills remain the strongest competitive advantage of the Finnish economy. Besides, it is roughly believed that Finland needs to reskill 1 million people within the next ten years, that is a challenge to be addressed since Finland aims to be known as a front runner in technological advances, innovative procurement and the culture of experimentation.

The Nordic countries case

The Nordic countries represented in this study with Denmark and Finland are at the forefront in adopting new technologies and are experiencing accelerating digitalization of work. They have adopted digitalisation strategies or initiatives at the national level – and in some cases also at the regional and local levels – covering different areas, such as promoting individual digital competence. Within the formal Nordic education systems, the issue of digital competence is addressed by curricula at all levels aimed at strengthening individual digital competence, as well as preparing learners for the constantly reshaping work life and society skill needs. All Nordic countries have adopted digital agendas or strategies at the national level in some form or another. The following Table provides an overview of these policies, highlighting the national priorities and the regional policies in each country.

FRANCE

France ranks 17th in the EU on human capital indicators, below the EU average, as per the 2020 edition of the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI). France has embarked on a comprehensive drive for sustainable and inclusive digital transformation. Underpinning this drive is France's investment plan 2018-2022, which aims, among others to foster competitiveness and innovation, and achieve the digital transformation of the public sector. Moreover, France has played an important role in the European open access movement, particularly in the launch of the Berlin declaration. Among French research structures, the research institutions (CNRS, INSERM in particular) played a major role at the beginning of the 2000's, especially with the launch of the HAL open archive in 2001, while there are several legislative texts that set the framework for the publication and sharing of open data.

GREECE

The level of digital skills of Greek citizens is behind the EU27 average, while Greece belongs to the category of the low performing countries in the DESI Index. Greece, like the rest of southern and eastern Europe performs poorly in digital learning, which score low on European rankings related to economic performance, innovation, and digitalisation. According to the DESI Report for 2020, Greece is ranked as 23rd in the "Human Capital" dimension. Greece suffers from a Brain drain' of ICT graduates alongside a severe digital skills gap according to 2020 DESI Performances. In addition, Greece has one of lowest score on the Women in Digital Scoreboard (WID 2020). Open Access/ Science policies are slowly adopted by the Greek Higher Education Institutes. Currently, Greece does not yet have in place a specific, formally approved National strategy for Open Science.

HUNGARY

Hungary has a detailed and over-ambitious digital education strategy that together with the digital workforce programme drive the country's digital skills initiatives in education and lifelong learning, under a tight governance scheme and mainly through EU funds. The strategies strongly focus on basic digital skills in order to help the country attain its goal of reaching the EU average. Considering that there is still no formal Open Science policy, despite the significant activity in the field, it is of no surprise that few related digital skills enhancement initiatives have been recorded. A new overarching national digital strategy that includes digital skills as a pillar is about to be published so some reorientation is expected.

LITHUANIA

Lithuania has one of the best scores for connectivity and digital infrastructure in the EU but its population levels of digital skills are not as high (DESI Performances 2020), despite having early policies focusing on the 'information society' in the 2000s. The country is gradually improving in human capital

thanks to policies dedicated to reducing basic shortfalls in digital skills, narrowing the gender-gap, and investing in the up-skilling of the ICT labour force.

Even though Portugal is not far from the European median in terms of digital skills, it needs to reinforce them. Portugal's training infrastructures and the strong potential of its human resources make this a viable task. To this end, in 2017 the Portuguese government established the "National Digital Competences Initiative e.2030, Portugal INCoDe.2030", an integrated public policy to enhance and foster digital competences. Portugal INCoDe.2030 focuses on skill formation in education and training for individuals rather than for businesses: it offers schemes for citizens, the elderly and disadvantaged groups.

Switzerland has a good starting point to continue to apply the successful model of a liveable, open, and modern country in the digital future. Digital transformation enables the sustainable development of the country. In this context the "Digital Switzerland" strategy provides the guidelines for government action and indicates where and how authorities, academia, the private sector, civil society and politics must work together in order to shape the transformation process for the benefit of everyone in Switzerland. The action plan, as an integral part of the strategy, includes the specific measures to achieve the strategic goals. Finally, Switzerland has established policies for Open Science and Open Data.

Netherlands lies at the forefront of Digital Transformation in all of its aspects and is a leader in both Digital Skills and Open Science domains. Digital skills are embedded in the National Digitalization Strategy and there is a large number of stakeholders involved in its implementation, including ministries, state companies, research institutions, social partners and universities. The main challenge faced by Netherlands is the relative shortage of highly skilled personnel since the demand in the market is larger than the availability of suitably skilled professionals. Although attention is given to initiatives that target digital skills for the general population (including lower level educated persons and the elderly), a very strong higher education agenda drives important activities towards enhancement of digital skills at all levels. Even though the landscape is quite fragmented, there is strong coordination among stakeholders which ensures a continuous progress.

3.2 Countries' share of activities in digital skills by target groups⁴

Denmark

France

Greece

Hungary

Lithuania

Portugal

The Netherlands

*Finland and Switzerland have no established National Coalitions for Digital Skills & Jobs to provide the relative data

⁴ As identified by National Coalitions for Digital Skills & Jobs

3.3 Countries' positioning in DESI 2020 and IMD

3.3.1 Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI)

The Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) is a composite index that summarises relevant indicators on Europe's digital performance and tracks the evolution of EU Member States in digital competitiveness*.

The Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI)

DESI 2020

Digital Economy and Society Index Report 2020 - Human Capital

*Switzerland is not included

3.3.2 IMD-World Competitiveness Digital Ranking 2019

Digital competitiveness is defined as the capacity of an economy to adopt and explore digital technologies leading to the transformation in government practices, business models and society in general. IMD World Digital Competitiveness Ranking, which is much more focused and assesses the capabilities and readiness of economies to undertake the process of digital transformation.

4 Major Insights at Country level

4.1 Review of Digital skills policy context

The research performed in the current chapter, intends to:

- identify the various policy documents and their respective owners and determine if any priority is given now (or in a mid-term horizon) to areas linked with Open Science and EOSC objectives
- identify the various policy documents and their respective owners and determine if any priority is given now (or in a mid-term horizon) to areas linked with upgrade of digital skills in the fields of education and lifelong learning

DENMARK

Denmark, the smallest country in Scandinavia, has been widely recognised as one of the most advanced digital economies in the EU. Denmark ranks 3rd out of the 28 EU Member States in the European Commission's 2020 edition of the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI). Digitalisation strategies have been created at national, regional, and municipal levels, and the strategies are often cross-sectoral, as is the case in the field of education. A strategic priority for Denmark is that "Everyone should be equipped to operate in the digital transformation", although no national strategy on Digital Skills is in place. Digital Skills Policies are implemented in the form of a) Education and vocational training b) Company training and partnerships and c) Lifelong Learning. In 2017, an agreement has been set up between the government and social partners on strengthening adult continuing education and making it more flexible, that emphasized that the system for adult continuing education (the VEU system) must support increased efforts to boost the basic skills level of the workforce in the future to a much greater extent than today in order to meet the companies' needs and demands. The key strategies that include priorities related to the promotion of digital skills are

- The Digital Strategy 2016–2020: A Stronger and More Secure Digital Denmark (2016) sets the course for Danish public sector digitalisation efforts
- The Strategy for Digital Welfare 2013–2020 that accelerates the use of ICT and welfare technology in front-line public service delivery.
- The Strategy for Denmark's Digital Growth establishes directions for Denmark to create the best framework for digital transformation
- The Danish Cyber and Information Security Strategy (2018) aims to ensure more coordinated efforts in the information security space.
- The National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence and the Research and Innovation Strategy encompass measures in order to improve digital competence of the population

Many Danish actors share responsibility for progress in the country's digitalisation efforts:

- The Agency for digitalisation (Digitaliseringsstyrelsen) under the auspices of the Ministry of Finance, 2011 is responsible for the implementation of digitalisation in the public sector
- The Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs and the Danish Business Authority are responsible for business-focused digital initiatives in co-operation with several ministries, e.g., the Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- The Government's Disruption Council is a Partnership for Denmark's Future on how to maintain a robust labour market when many jobs are transformed by digitalisation

Some challenges to be addressed refer to the regulatory barriers that seem to be slowing progress in Denmark's education system, clarifying the governmental responsibility into driving progress in digital learning, promoting online and distance-learning courses followed by improved accreditation and enhancing organizational support.

Finland ranks first out of the 28 EU Member States with a score of 69.9 in the European Commission's Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2019. Its overall score largely surpasses the EU average of 52.5, allowing Finland, for the first time, to become the EU digital leader.

Finland is in the vanguard of education, skills, and modern learning techniques, holding the 3rd place in digital learning readiness across the EU-27. Finland aims to be known as a front runner in technological advances, innovative procurement, and the culture of experimentation, making all public services available digitally to individuals and businesses by 2023. In 2025, in the age of artificial intelligence, Finland aims to become the most relevantly educated nation, which will provide its people with protection against the wind of technological change. According to the Ministry of Education and Culture, the education system must be modified, both vocational education and training and higher education. Additionally, more investments should be made in updating the skills of workers already in the labour market, and the lifelong learning system should be reformed.

The main Finish digitalisation policies and strategies are the Digital Finland Framework, the Artificial Intelligence strategy, the digitalisation, experimentation and Deregulation programme for public sector ICT, and the digital transformation programme for the regional government, health, and social services reform. The Digital Finland Framework (2018) ensures future-oriented digital skills for all, by increasing the share of mathematics and science in all education levels, from elementary school to universities, by encouraging the use of Mass Open Online Courses (MOOC) and the train-the-trainee approach for digital skills in education but also in companies, by promoting the digital professional and by strengthening the research-company co-operation.

Overall, digitalisation is not a priority per se in Finland, but it has been identified as a key means to achieve growth in the business sector. Even though an all-encompassing digitalisation strategy does not yet exist, digitalisation is a priority in sectoral strategies (e.g., education). Digitalisation is seen as a great opportunity, with the Finnish attitude being 'full speed ahead'. The law on a new Digital and Population Data Agency was approved and the new Agency started up recently, at the beginning of 2020.

Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment and Ministry of Education and Culture are coordinating together to ensure that Finland is a leading country in future learning and inspiring education. In particular, the Ministry of Finance / Public Sector ICT Department is acting as policy coordinator and it is responsible for the overall development of eGovernment, Public Administration information management, corporate data and information management governance in central Government.

France ranks 15th out of 28 EU Member States in the 2020 edition of the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI). The national strategy / policy of France for digital skills is mainly reflected in the **National Plan for Inclusive Digital and launch of Digital in Common(s)**, launched in September 2018, with an objective to train 1.5 million people in digital literacy in order to reduce inequalities and provide equal opportunities for all throughout the country. With 13 million French people who still do not use the Internet, or only to a limited extent, including 6.7 million who never connect to the Internet, this is a real challenge for the country which is committed to carrying out the digital transformation. This national strategy is based on four main approaches:

- Detecting audiences in difficulty with digital technology
- Offer human support in the process
- Train those who wish to do so thanks to the Digital Pass
- Consolidate the players in digital mediation

In addition, since December 2012, the Ministry of National Education, Higher Education and Research has been developing an ambitious strategy to bring schools towards the digital age. This strategy aims to make the most of the opportunities offered by digital technology for the benefit of pupils' success. Actually, the French government is encouraging the creation of coding workshops outside classes and will progressively introduce a certification of digital skills for students in their last secondary school year.

France's policy framework for improving the digital skills of its population, both through formal education and inclusion measures, is underway and is expected to produce tangible results over the coming years. More targeted initiatives will be important to upskill the workforce for the digital economy and to promote advanced digital skills development, in AI and in other areas too.

The main stakeholders involved with the digital skills framework in France include the French Ministry of Labour, the Paris Descartes University, the PIX - platform for assessing and certifying digital skills, the Adecco Group France, the Digital Talents -The French Digital Agency, the Orange Great Digital School and the CFDT - French Democratic Confederation of Labour.

Greece's national policy on digital skills is currently mainly expressed through the National Digital Skills Coalition Action Plan 2017-2020: Enhancing Digital Skills and Jobs in Greece (EDSGR). The EDGSR is a multi-stakeholder initiative, providing a propitious organizational environment inside the Greek public and private sector that acts as a precondition to fully reap the benefits of digital technologies in order to enhance productivity and growth of the Greek economy. By bringing together Greek National stakeholders as members under the same umbrella, it is the first and largest of its kind in Greece. To this goal, the EDSGR coalition, under the leadership of the Ministry of Digital Governance and in

collaboration with major national stakeholders, has set off to develop a functional ecosystem that includes policy makers, academia, entrepreneurs and businesses, in order to assist in the implementation of structural reforms and actions to acquire or enhance digital skills, promote growth and help the best and brightest talents shine.

The EDSGR is comprised of four (4) key pillars: education, training, ICT professionals and citizens. The current Action Plan is based on the data received, mainly, from the major Ministries and General Secretaries and the ICT sector. The existing Digital Skills actions are in the field of the Public Sector, Education, Employment, Digital Economy and revealed a surprising positive base for the aims of this Action Plan. Based on the main issues of the Digital Skills and e-Leadership policy, 12 priorities have been defined, among which Priority 7: Promoting e-skills through RTDI activities is included, with an aim to

- Support collaborative RTDI projects between enterprises and Public Research Centres (PRC) as well as Higher Education Institutions (HEI)
- Establish specialized competence centres, Digital Innovation Hubs, and clusters
- Promote recruitment of highly qualified personnel in enterprises to conduct research for the development of innovative products/services
- Enhance extroversion of enterprises through participation in bilateral and transnational RTDI co-operation

Currently, the Digital Transformation Bible is under development, which it is expected to include specific policies for digital skills & competences. As of July 2019, the competence for the organization and functioning of the coalition at national, European and international level was transferred to the General Secretariat of Digital Governance and Simplification of Procedures of the Ministry of Digital Governance, specifically to the Department of Digital Economy, Investments and Digital Skills/Directorate of Digital Strategy.

According to the latest DESI publication⁵ Hungary ranks 21st out of 28 EU Member States. Over the last few years, its score improved broadly in line with the EU average however no progress has been made in digital skills and in advanced specialist skills in recent years.

The country's digital strategy document is the National Info-communication Strategy 2014-2020⁶ which includes a pillar on Digital Competencies for population, SMEs, public administration, and e-inclusion. Based on the above strategy, the major policy documents that guide Digital Skills development are:

The Digital Education Strategy⁷, which was launched in 2016 and forms part of the "Digital Success Program", covers the entire system of education and training, including public education, vocational training, higher education and adult learning. It also includes horizontal pillars to monitor the learning path, to help accessibility and to increase security. The most important goal of the strategy was to create the possibility of the effective dissemination of digital literacy in harmony with the sectoral strategies and professional objectives at all levels of the education system.

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=66917

⁶ https://www.kormany.hu/download/5/ff/70000/NIS_EN_clear.pdf

⁷ <https://digitalisjoletprogram.hu/files/0a/6b/0a6bfcd72ccbf12c909b329149ae2537.pdf>

The Digital Workforce Programme⁸ was launched in 2018 and includes four pillars:

- To improve how labour market needs are measured, and how the digital economy is monitored in general.
- To develop a new digital competence framework using the EU's DigComp 2.1 framework for citizens and integrate it into the input and output requirements of the training system.
- To focus on motivational factors through the lifelong learning support system, the expansion of e-learning and blended learning opportunities as well as through providing financial benefits and support for disadvantaged groups.
- To provide different training programmes, such as general IT training (short cycle), on-the-job training and specific training for career changers and for those without higher education.

In addition, the programme provides for National Digital Skills Councils to be set up to assist in analyzing skills mismatches. Hungary has set up the National Coalition for Digital Skills and Jobs (2016) to facilitate stakeholder discussions on tackling the shortage of digitally skilled people in the Hungarian labour market and help the government develop and implement adequate strategies. Alongside to that, 'digital topic weeks' are organised on a regular basis to promote digital pedagogic methodologies.

In 2020 two new regulations on vocational training, higher education and public education entered into force (11/2020, 12/2020) emphasising the importance of digital skills.

Finally, the government announced in June 2020⁹ that the existing Digital Strategy will be replaced by the National Digitalisation Strategy (NDS) 2021-2027 which will be based on four pillars: digital infrastructure, digital skills, digital economy and digital state, but no further information is available at the time of writing.

The owner of the Digital Education Strategy (and the overarching Digital Success Programme - DSP) was the Cabinet office of the prime minister, however responsibility for the DSP has been transferred to the Ministry of Innovation and Technology formed in 2018 (and DSP has been expanded to version 2.0).

To implement the strategy, the government set up the Digital Pedagogical Methodology Centre¹⁰. Its role is to support the digital transformation of public education, provide the professional background and expert base, and support applications and priority projects.

The Digital Workforce Programme is owned by the Ministry of National Economy.

Other institutions involved in the country's digital skills landscape include:

- Ministry of Human Capacities
- DJP Nonprofit (Digitális Jólét) Nonprofit Kft¹¹
- IVSZ¹², the association of the Information and Communication Technologies industry in Hungary (coordinator of the National Coalition)
- KIFÜ¹³, the e-Infrastructure provider for the entire research, education, and public collection communities in Hungary
- The Institute for Computer Science and Control (SZTAKI)¹⁴

⁸ <https://digitalisjoletprogram.hu/en/content/dwp-digital-workforce-program> - only available in Hungarian

⁹ <http://abouthungary.hu/news-in-brief/governments-new-national-digitalization-strategy-unveiled/>

¹⁰ <https://dpmk.hu/>

¹¹ <https://djnkft.hu/>

¹² <https://old.ivsz.hu/en/about-ivsz/>

¹³ <https://kifu.gov.hu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.sztaki.hu/en/about-institute>

LITHUANIA

Lithuania ranks 14th out of 28 EU Member States in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2020. In the past year, Lithuania has improved in most of the measured areas. In particular, it performed exceptionally well in the integration of digital technology and digital public services. However, some areas such as human capital are still below the EU average in spite of recent improvements.

The Information Society Development Programme 2014 – 2020 Digital Agenda for Lithuania (which is in accordance with the Europe 2020 Initiative Digital Agenda for Europe) defines the priorities, objectives, and tasks of information society development in order to maximise the advantages provided by information and communication technologies. Among the programme's priorities, the enhancement of the Lithuanian residents' ability to use the ICTs, mainly by improving their digital skills and competences is identified. The main tasks for improving digital skills in Lithuania include:

- To enable the target groups of the Lithuanian population that until now, for different reasons, have not used or barely used modern digital tools and the internet to gain the necessary digital skills and apply them in various fields, also involving local communities into these activities
- To encourage the Lithuanian population to regularly update their ICT knowledge and digital skills, to securely and purposefully use the possibilities provided by the Internet.
- To make society aware of the diversity of ICT professions and encourage citizens to choose ICT-related professions, studies, and informal education programmes.
- To provide more favourable conditions for teaching and learning, based on modern ICT, ensuring that the Lithuanian population has the possibility to be involved in life-long learning processes online.

In addition, an interinstitutional action plan for the implementation of the information society development program "Digital Agenda of the Republic of Lithuania" for 2014–2020 was launched in 2017 and updated in 2019. According to the 2019 edition the purpose of the Action Plan is to improve the quality of life of Lithuanian citizens, increase business productivity and achieve that by 2020, at least 85% of the Lithuanian population would use the Internet, and 95% of companies would use the high-speed Internet.

Moreover, the efforts in the country for improving the digital skills agenda are mainly promoted by the National Digital Coalition for the Promotion of Digital Skills for Jobs in Lithuania, who has as mission to increase employment and to achieve a more effective use of digital potential and cooperate in implementing information society development programme 2014–2020 Digital Agenda for Lithuania.

The Lithuanian Ministry of the Economy and Innovation is the main governmental body responsible for the policy setting and coordination in the digital government domain. Other institutions involved in the country's digital skills landscape include:

- The Ministry of Education, Science and Sport
- The Ministry of Social Security and Labour
- The Ministry of Culture
- Vilnius University, the largest higher education institution in Lithuania and one of the oldest higher education institutions in Northern Europe, which carries high-quality research-based studies covering almost all areas of science.
- Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), one of the largest technical universities in the Baltic States and one of the country's most prominent universities occupying a leading position in several research and study areas.

- The Association “Langas j ateitj”, which is an organization established by socially responsible business, since 2002 developing ICT skills in Lithuania
- The Lithuanian Municipal Public Library Association, uniting most of the Lithuanian public libraries, which, beside their daily activities consult the public about the ICT skills necessary for work and encourage them to acquire these skills.
- etc

Portugal ranks 19th out of the 28 EU Member States in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2020. Compared with the previous edition of DESI, progress is observed in the human capital dimension, thanks to an improvement in the basic level of digital skills and a greater proportion of ICT graduates.

The Portuguese ICT Strategy 2020, approved in 2017, is the main strategic document that reflects the digital transformation of the Portuguese Public Administration until 2020. This Strategy comprises of three main axes a) Promotion and integration and interoperability, b) Innovation and competitiveness and c) Resource sharing and investment in digital competences. The 3rd axis that focuses on improving the quality of public services and promoting public administration higher efficiency implies a better use of skills and resources. In this context, the following measure is included with regards to digital skills: Measure 9: ICT centre of competences, aiming at defining the operation model and driving the development of an ICT centre of competences and in general promoting the development of Digital Competences.

Moreover, with regards to Digital Skills, the “Portugal INCoDe.2030¹⁵” inter-ministerial action, launched in April 2017, addresses the concept of digital competences in a broad manner. It includes the notion of digital literacy (i.e. the ability to access digital media and ICT, to understand and critically assess contents, and to communicate effectively), as well as the production of new knowledge through research. It brings together the areas of Administrative Modernisation, Science, Technology and Higher Education, Education, Labour, Planning and Infrastructures and Economy, aiming to strengthen the basic skills of the population in ICT. Actually, it reflects the national policy on digital skills and is structured around five main axes: Inclusion, Education, Qualification, Specialisation and Research aggregating a variety of measures to be implemented by different institutions in collaboration with the private sector, academia, and civil society. The fifth axis specifically targets research, providing the conditions to produce new knowledge and an active participation in international R&D networks and programmes.

The big challenges for Portugal around digital competences focus on qualifying the population in digital competences. A set of goals has been established covering factors such as digital literacy, physical and cognitive access to digital services, analytical capacity in the context of big data, production and dissemination of information, privacy and security, intensive use of ICT in the process of lifelong learning and R&D aimed at the production of knowledge and advanced forms of scientific computing. The aim is to put Portugal among the leading European countries in digital competences, by overcoming one main challenge; ensure strong participation in international R&D networks and the production of knowledge in digital areas.

¹⁵ <https://www.incode2030.gov.pt/>

The Minister of the Presidency and of Administrative Modernisation is responsible for the modernisation of public administration and digital government. Other institutions involved in the country's digital skills landscape include:

- The Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security
- The Ministry of Education
- The Directorate-General for Employment and Labour Relations (DGERT)
- The Directorate General for Higher Education (DGES)
- The Directorate General for Education (DGE)
- The Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education (ANQEP)
- The Institute of Employment and Vocational Training (IEFP)
- The Administrative Modernisation Agency (AMA)
- The National Institute for Administration (INA)
- The Agency for Competitiveness and Innovation (IAPMEI)

SWITZERLAND

The Federal Council wants Switzerland to exploit the opportunities of digitalisation to the full. On 5 September 2018 it adopted its **Digital Switzerland strategy** for the next 2 years. Within the framework of this strategy the Federal Council established a working group on the subject of artificial intelligence and support initiatives in relation to Smart Cities. In addition, the federal administration intensified dialogue with interested or involved participants, and especially with the cantons.

Among its objectives the further improvement of the digital empowerment of people is included. The competencies of the Swiss population should be further strengthened so that the opportunities of digitalisation can be comprehensively exploited. Thanks to lifelong learning, people should always be in a position to participate competently in digitalised political, social, cultural, and economic processes and to assess the consequences of their own actions as appropriately as possible.

Good education is an indispensable cornerstone for each individual and for society and the economy as a whole. The process of digital transformation in Switzerland requires skills in handling the new technologies as well as creative and critical thinking. The dissemination of appropriate skills and the provision of appropriate education and further education facilities therefore assume great importance.

For Switzerland to remain among the leading countries in terms of the development and use of digital technologies, it has to promote the necessary skills - in the sense of lifelong learning - at all levels and in all areas. In addition, in order to achieve the goal of equal opportunities and the participation of all inhabitants in the opportunities of digitalisation, it is important to promote basic skills in the use of the new technologies.

Science and research have a crucial role in terms of generating, disseminating, and using knowledge. The technologies emerging from science and research constitute the essential basis of digital change and digital innovation, such as for example in the area of artificial intelligence or the processing of large amounts of data. These developments will shape economic, social, environmental and cultural development in a sustainable manner. Research and innovation as a core foundation of competitiveness and as a basis for successfully tackling structural change must be strengthened with regard to digital skills and must be further developed to meet the needs of the population, the economy and the environment.

In addition, the «Digital Switzerland» action plan includes the measures which make a concrete contribution to the achievement of the goals of the «Digital Switzerland» strategy. The starting point for this is the measures taken by the federal administration. The Departments and Federal Offices fund their implementation measures within the framework of their regular budgets and ensure evaluation of these measures where necessary. The «Digital Switzerland» action plan is published on the website of the Federal Office of Communications, OFCOM, and is regularly updated.

On 14 November 2018, the Federal Council of Switzerland approved the key value for the **eGovernment Strategy from 2020-2023**, prepared by the organisation eGovernment Switzerland. The general principle "Digital First" shows the importance of the electronic channel through which the administration will offer its information and services by default in the future. The 6 principles of the Tallinn Declaration (signed by FC Maurer on 06.10.2017) form an important basis for the new strategy. A central action field of the eGovernment Strategy from 2020 will be to ensure the possibility of interaction of the population in the activities of politics and administration. The eGovernment strategy Switzerland is a part of the strategy of the Federal Council for the Information Society in Switzerland Strategy and is based on the 'Recommendation of the Council on Digital Government Strategies' of the OECD. The Steering Committee will have the opportunity to adapt the project's portfolio and strategic direction over the next four years as in regard to the changes in the context and the progress of these eGovernment oriented measures.

Moreover, the report **on Challenges of Digitalisation for Education and Research in Switzerland**, published by SERI in July 2017 emphasises that, in order to ensure that Switzerland's education system adapts appropriately to the digital developments taking place, action must be taken by individuals, educational institutions and the education system as a whole.

Action area 1: Improving digital literacy

Action area 2: Using ICT in teaching and learning

Action area 3: Rapidly adapting the education system to market requirements

Action area 4: Improving coordination and communication in education cooperation

THE NETHERLANDS

The Netherlands ranks 4th out of 28 EU Member States in the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2020. It therefore remains one of the top performers across Europe, with solid and steady 'digital growth'. The main challenge faced by Netherlands is the relative shortage of highly skilled personnel since the demand in the market is larger than the availability of suitably skilled professionals. The major policy document that guides Digital Skills development is the 2018 Dutch Digitalization Strategy, and its updated version (Digitalization Strategy 2.0) that has been published in July 2019 and includes a brief overview of the results achieved and future goals. The strategy identifies new (digital) skills as one of the five foundations for the country's digital transformation and has planned several actions to achieve the goals set. The strategy covers digital skills enhancement for higher education, primary & secondary education, basic digital skills of aged people and of people with low literacy levels, Lifelong Learning and Development and producing sufficient numbers of ICT professionals.

Several documents accompany the strategy on the above domains, such as the Acceleration Agenda for Innovation in Education, Acceleration plan for educational innovation with ICT, Digitalization agenda for primary and secondary education, Human Capital Agenda for ICT and Technology Pact 2016-2020.

According to the updated version of the Digitalization Strategy, there are many initiatives towards the development of digital skills and lifelong learning from a lot of stakeholders, therefore the main challenge thus lies in accelerating, strengthening and connecting existing activities rather than developing or introducing new ones”.

Other policy documents include the NL DIGIbeter Digital Government Agenda on improving digital skills for the public sector employees., the Dutch Strategic Action Plan for Artificial Intelligence which stresses the importance of investing in AI relevant digital skills, the Dutch National Research Agenda, the Strategic Agenda for Higher Education and Research 2015-2025, the “Connecting Science and Society” strategy 2019-2022 of the NWO (National Research Organization), and the Digital Society Research Agenda of the VSNU (association of universities).

Responsibility for the Digitalization Strategy of the Netherlands lies within the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, whereas the responsibility for Digital Government lies with the State Secretary for the Interior and Kingdom Relations. Other institutions involved in the country’s digital skills landscape include:

- Ministry of Education, Culture and Science*
- Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment
- ECP | Platform for the Information Society
- SURF | collaborative organisation for ICTin Dutch education and research
- VSNU | association of universities
- VH | association of universities of applied science
- SBB | Foundation for Cooperation on Vocational Education, Training and Labour Market
- The National Library (Nationale bibliotheek) and the Network of Libraries (bibliotheek netwerk).

Finally, the Netherlands have also established a National Coalition on Digital Skills & Jobs. Its main partners are:

- The Ministry of Economic Affairs
- Girls love to Code
- Mediawijzer.net
- Sterk Internet Voor Iedereen - SIDN Fonds

4.2 Review of Digital skills governance models

The research performed in the current chapter, intends to:

- identify and map the overall governance scheme in the field of digital skills and determine level of fragmentation, degree of coordination, potential overlaps, etc;

DENMARK

There is not a single organisation or other authority that can claim to be the national coordinating mechanism for the digital skills policies in Denmark. Yet, there are some initiatives, entities and partnerships which perform monitoring and coordinating work on digital skills policies as follows: a) The Danish Technology Pact was formed in 2018 as an initiative of the Strategy for Denmark Digital Growth (2018 and is led by the Ministry for Economic Affairs, b) The Danish National Coalition defines common objectives, invites relevant parties to join and to co-create an action plan to bridge the skill gap, c) The Technology Covenant) is a collaboration between the government, private companies, educational institutions, organizations and other stakeholders, with the aim to strengthen the population's competencies in technology, ICT, engineering, natural science and mathematics via various projects and activities.

FINLAND

There is not a single authority that carries out the integral national responsibility for digital skills planning and implementation in Finland, although many initiatives attempt to coordinate digital skills policies design and implementation. For example, in response to increasing flows of migrants and refugees into Finland, the Liberal Adult Education Act was amended early 2018. T

he revised act gives greater responsibility to training institutions to provide language and vocational training to facilitate the integration of migrants, including refugees, into society and the labour market. Finally, the Finnish National Agency for Education launched the 'National anticipation model for adult education', which will develop and pilot an anticipation system for adult education and training.

The Nordic countries case

The Nordic Council of Ministers is the official body for inter-governmental co-operation in the Nordic Region. It seeks Nordic solutions wherever and whenever the countries can achieve more together than by working on their own. It represents the 27 million people of Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Greenland, Åland and the Faroe Islands. Networks and Councils composed from ministers are working on many development areas and unified policies for the Nordic area such as is the digitization, the education and the research and science tackling issues on digital skills and training and open science. In particular, within the digitization policy principles, a priority is the Development of advanced ICT competencies by facilitating free movement of people within the framework of the European single market and simplifying procedures for skills accreditation and use.

FRANCE

The coordination and governance for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation in France is carried out by the French digital coalition for skills and jobs that was set up in 2016 and MEDEF was appointed by the European Commission to be its coordinator and facilitator. Today, more than 200 actors from different horizons have joined this coalition and are working together. The coalition is aiming to identify and promote initiatives and good practices on digital skills, bring together all local and national actors active in digital matters (administrations, associations, NGOs, professional organizations, companies, unions, etc.) and carry out concrete actions throughout the territory that will enhance the digital skills and competences. Overall, the French coalition is:

- supporting active workers and those looking for work so that they adapt their skills and the practice of their professions to new digital processes, to develop further their employability throughout life.
- adapting initial and continuing training and higher education to digital transformation to prepare for the jobs of tomorrow, by utilising educational tools and practices.
- increasing the number of talents, especially women, in digital professions, while improving initial and continuing training.
- providing all citizens with the necessary background to access information, be connected in areas of everyday life (administrative, cultural, sports, legal, etc.) and to interact more easily with their public or private environment, by mastering digital tools.

GREECE

The General Secretariat of Digital Governance and Simplification of Procedures of the Ministry of Digital Governance, specifically to the Department of Digital Economy, Investments and Digital Skills/Directorate of Digital Strategy is the responsible body of the National Coalition for Digital Skills in Greece, hence responsible for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation in the country. Greek National Coalition for Digital Skills and Jobs is open to any body endorsing its objectives and targets Its members come both from public and private sector and participate in the work of the five groups of the Coalition. A coordinator, chosen from among its members, is appointed in each of the five groups for a term of one year.

Moreover, for each priority of the EDSGR, a stakeholder/ member of the National Coalition is responsible for the line coordination and the achievement of strategic goals through actions, the monitoring and assessment of implementation, as well for the continuous feedback and update of the Action Plan with actions in its policy area, aiming at building synergies in an horizontal and vertical way, with other stakeholders.

To enhance publicity and openness of the Action Plan and ensure the diffusion of the actions included to this, throughout the country, a mechanism of communication and feedback among the stakeholders at central and regional level will be created. This monitoring mechanism targets to act as a facilitator for the implementation of the Action Plan, through conferences and forums, as well to create a channel of interaction between the National Coalition with regional pledges and local needs for interventions. Moreover, an assessment tool has been developed, where a set of 10 key performance indicators have been identified.

HUNGARY

The digital skills governance landscape in Hungary is quite centralized under the Digital Success Program. The Ministry of National Economy plays a significant part in the overall governance as owner of the Digital Workforce programme.

DJP Ltd (Digitális Jólét), a state-owned company is responsible for the coordination of implementation of the DSP since 2017 and is therefore centrally placed in the governance model (under the auspices of Ministry of Innovation and Technology). The Digital Pedagogical Methodology Centre provides professional support for the implementation of several applications to help develop and disseminate digital education. Within the framework of this task, DPMK published digital pedagogical-methodological packages and evaluates the Institutional Digital Development Plan.

Moreover, the association of ICT enterprises is also actively involved on one hand by participating in the creation of the relevant strategies and on the other hand by coordinating the National Coalition activities.

The National Infocom Strategy includes a specific chapter on monitoring system based on (not so specific) indicators and mentions that a monitoring report will be compiled and published on the website of the Government by September each year in accordance with the provisions of the Government on strategy presentation.

No information was available on monitoring the other policy documents mentioned in section A, however it is quite safe to assume that the second version of the DSP has taken into account the results attained by that time by its predecessor.

LITHUANIA

The coordination and governance for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation in Lithuania is carried out by the Lithuanian National Digital Coalition (NDC), which was established in November 2013. The activities of the National Coalition and the relationship with other organizations are coordinated by the association "Langas į ateitį" ("Window to the Future"), an organization established by socially responsible business, since 2002 developing ICT skills in Lithuania and promoting a safe use of the Internet as well as public and private electronic services in order to improve Lithuanian people's quality of life and to raise competitiveness in Europe and in the world. The mission of NDC in short is to increase youth employment by promoting ICT knowledge and achieve more effective use of the digital potential by cooperation in implementing information society development programme Digital Agenda for Lithuania 2014-2020. The association so far has initiated and implemented projects in which over 100,000 adults participated in ICT basics training courses funded by private business and EU SF funds. 20,000 participants graduated from the online courses since 2008. Safer Internet trainings were attended by 5,000 school community members and librarians.

It is pointed out that the association "Window to the Future" was awarded the finalist medal by the European Commission's 2008 e. in the E-inclusion Award 2008 and even won the Digital Literacy

category in this competition. Over 450 projects took part in the competition, and Lithuania is the only country from the new EU member states among the winners.

The INCoDe.2030 initiative, as the main public policy tool for digital skills in Portugal, is structured as an integrated programme, bringing together, and encouraging collaboration between people with different experience and knowledge as well as multiple public and private organisations. The promotion and coordination of INCoDe.2030 involves three permanent bodies:

- The National Forum for Digital Competences, which is responsible for gathering and coordinating a broad range of private and public companies and institutions to ensure widespread mobilisation for the initiative, as well as of organising an annual conference in which the developments in each line of action are presented and analysed in the context of national and international success stories and good practices.
- The INCoDe.2030 Coordination Structure, which oversees the lines of action and also the initiative as a whole, promoting and coordinating the activities in each action line to guarantee a common focus and purpose, updating the general and specific goals and objectives.
- The INCoDe.2030 Technical Secretariat, which monitors, records and reports on the implementation of all the planned activities, developing the necessary platforms for their development and communication, in close articulation with the Coordination Structure and the Forum for Digital Competences

An Observatory for Digital Competences has been set up by the Directorate-General for Statistics in Education and Science (DGEEC), which, in collaboration with the National Institute for Statistics (INE), monitors and reports on the programme's development, through a set of indicators divided into 4 categories: access, human potential, use and investment.

The Digital Switzerland strategy is a joint task of authorities at all levels of the state, the private sector, the academic community, civil society, and politics.

The Federal Department of the Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications DETEC is responsible for coordinating the Confederation's implementation measures within the federal administration and for the ongoing development of the Digital Switzerland strategy. This work is carried out within the framework of the Confederation's «Digital Switzerland» Coordination Group. The Confederation's «Digital Switzerland» Office, based within OFCOM, supports the Coordination Group in terms of organisation and content. From 1 January 2021 onwards coordination within the federal administration will be assured by the Federal Chancellery.

The Federal Council invites all of digital Switzerland's stakeholder groups, in particular the cantons, cities and municipalities, to exchange information on their projects in relation to the implementation of this strategy and relevant cross-sectoral topics and to exploit any possible synergies. The administration also cooperates closely with the private sector, civil society and the academic community and in this way contributes to the efficient implementation of the strategy. Especially in

areas of activity with responsibilities shared between the Confederation, the cantons and private organisations (e.g. in the health and education sectors), sustainable digital integration is possible only if there are permanent forums or platforms for cooperation.

THE NETHERLANDS

The Dutch digital skills landscape is pluralistic. It includes ministries (at least 3 ministries as policy makers as seen in section A), national funding bodies as well as organizations with the responsibility for providing IT services. Even though the landscape is quite fragmented, there is strong coordination among stakeholders which ensures a continuous progress.

Alongside with the Dutch government, the National Coalition for Digital Skills and Jobs in the Netherlands is working on ensuring that all citizens have access to digital literacy initiatives. The coalition sees the inclusion of digital skills into education curricula as a base element of a digitally literate society.

ECP – Platform for the Information Society coordinates the Coalition and collaborates with public authorities across different ministries as well as with industry, teachers, researchers and non-governmental organisations to advance the digital agenda. Almost 200 ECP members work together to bolster the digital skills of citizens in all age groups.

The Dutch government updated the Digitalization Strategy in 2019 and included important information in what has been achieved during the previous year. Information on the progress of the various initiatives is also found on some of the involved institutions' annual reports.

4.3 Review of current national Digital Skills initiatives

The research performed in the current chapter, intends to:

- determine the level of maturity of the digital skills initiatives in general, but also identify the ones most relevant to EOSC objectives (e.g. up-skilling for core EOSC skills)
- identify potential infrastructures /platforms that can be exploited in national level

DENMARK

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 10% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 5% towards ICT professionals, 25% towards the labour force and 60% towards citizens in general. Many initiatives are in place or have been completed in the near past, while the most important ones are the following:

The **Digital Hub Denmark** is an independent organisation and public private partnership between the Danish Government, the Confederation of Danish Industry, the Danish Chamber of Commerce and Finance Denmark. It was formed in 2018 to support and strengthen the digital growth environment in Denmark by facilitating collaboration across private companies, researchers, and tech-entrepreneurs. There are 4 core elements to the programme:

- A digital platform, where members are matched according to specific challenges
- A national centre for research in digital technologies
- Conferences and trial projects, to improve the commercial use of data and new digital technologies for new services and business models
- International marketing, to raise awareness of Denmark's digital growth environment

By 2019, the Digital Hub Denmark has provided work for roughly 1,000 IT specialists and students on projects lasting 3-6 months, and it created a framework for outreach and activities including workshops, talks and networking events

The **SME Digital initiative** addresses the digital competence challenges that SMEs in particular are facing. SME: Digital will focus on business needs by offering economic support to SMEs seeking private consultancy and assistance in the development of digital transformation business cases, better potential for e-commerce and e-exports via an e-commerce centre, improving the skills of business leaders and a digital design consultancy.

In addition, there are several al initiatives that focus on up-skilling for Science and Research:

- The Danish inter-institutional project Skills and Competencies for Open Science and Digital Literacy in Danish Research Libraries was implemented from March 2018 - May 2020. The project designed a competency matrix that describes three levels of competence within all aspects of Open Science as defined by FOSTER's taxonomy. For each competence level, courses and other training materials were added. The aim is to provide an inspirational catalogue that will enable library managers and staff to identify competencies and reach the desired level of proficiency in the respective Open Science Activity.
- The Digital Skills for Library staff and Researchers LIBER Working Group conducted a selection process in 2018 in order to identify Open Science training programmes relying on skills identification. In April 2019, questionnaires were sent out in 28 countries, and complementary interviews were conducted for the production of country-specific case studies on Open Science skilling and training initiatives in Europe. The objective of this activity is to offer the research library community a selective landscape of inspiring methods, practices, contacts, and words of wisdom,

covering institutional cases, national initiatives as well as European project approaches. Budget: 4 million Danish kroner (approximately €535,000)

FINLAND

There are numerous initiatives at local level, implemented by schools, vocational institutions, and other educational institutions as well as on national level, providing funding frameworks, with the cooperation of the private domain such as:

- In 2017, the government proposed allocating an additional 60 million Euros in its budget for skilling the labour force, with a special focus on digital skills. According to a report from the Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra for 2018, almost 20 billion Euros public and private funds were allocated to the development of skills and education in Finland in 2017.
- In 2018, the Ministry of Education and Culture, together with the National Board of Education and the Finnish National Agency for Education, started a program with the aim of strengthening adults' digital and basic skills. By offering low-threshold education, they want to prevent inequality, provide positive learning experiences, and strengthen the civic skills needed in today's society. The government reserved an appropriation for this purpose in the supplementary budget for 2018. The Board of Education granted EUR 7 million in state support to civic institutes, folk high schools, summer universities and study centres. In higher education, while the Ministry of Education and Culture granted a total of 65 million euros for 36 development projects during 2017 and 2018.
- The skills for the digital era programme (2018-2020) is a program funded by Ministry of Education and Culture with a budget of EUR 7 million, that aims to strengthen the basic skills and digital skills of adults, especially the unemployed, those at risk of unemployment, retirees, jobseekers and immigrants. By increasing low-threshold education, it aims to prevent inequalities, give positive learning experiences, and strengthen today's civic skills. The programme provides funding for 84 training projects that strengthen the basic and digital skills of adults.

A wide variety of programs and projects have been launched aimed at specific target groups (teachers, trainers, specified vocational sectors, migrants, the unemployed, etc.). These projects include:

- **ia Digitutor 2018–2020** aims to improve the digital skills of employees in the mechanical engineering, metal and chemical industries.
- **Integrify** is a programming school integration of newly arrived immigrants into the workforce by training them as software developers. The company was founded in 2016 having major public and private partnerships in Finland, including the City of Helsinki. The primary goal of the company is to increase the chances of immigrants finding employment, by teaching programming and connecting them to employers working in tech. After the programme is finished, Integrify gives participants access to their pool of carefully selected partner companies. Currently, the company seeks to expand its service across Europe with the aim to train 10,000 people in digital skills by 2030.
- **Digipolku Work** is a project that aims to develop the skills of people with low digital skills by increasing cooperation between work-based and vocational training.
- **eOppiva** is a project aiming to improve the digital skills of state employees through online learning.

- **DigiKyky (Digi Capability)** is a project consisting of various training programmes to support the digitisation of businesses and to enhance their capabilities, productivity, and competitiveness.

Also, in the context of the implementation of the Artificial Intelligence Programme of Finland, the public sector is developing the virtual assistant Aurora that aims to create a platform for people to seamlessly connect with public and private service providers such as employment agencies and healthcare professionals. They will be able to monitor the relevance of their skills, when they need updating, and receive support to apply for jobs.

Moreover, Elements of AI Course by Finnish Centre for Artificial Intelligence (FCAI) is a free online course that aims to improve the basic AI knowledge of Finnish citizens, while Software Robotics by the Finnish Government Shared Services Centre for Finance and HR (Palkeet) is a government project to improve the development of public services through the adoption of robotics and software, and to increase the skills needed to support their use.

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 10% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 30% towards ICT professionals, 50% towards the labour force and 10% towards citizens in general.

France has launched a number of initiatives to boost the level of digital skills of its citizens, focusing on different target groups. To boost the digital skills of students, France has brought in two new compulsory courses on digital and computer sciences in secondary schools as of 2019. According to the Education Ministry, these courses are already taught in over half of France's public schools. However, in some education institutions, opportunities to experiment and learn digital skills related to coding and robotics are available only as optional courses. To boost the level of digital skills of teaching staff, France created a new inter-university diploma called Teaching ICT in upper secondary schools in 2019. So far, over 2,000 teachers have been trained in 19 universities. Other initiatives include putting in place a MOOC for upper secondary school teachers, developed by the French institute for digital sciences (INRIA). Over 13,000 teachers have registered for the course since it was rolled out in February 2019.

On adult learning, France is in the process of implementing the National Plan for Digital Inclusion, focusing on measures to promote the digital inclusion of all citizens. The plan includes outreach to the most vulnerable, an assessment phase and tailor-made offers. In March 2019, a tender was published for rolling out the digital pass, the online voucher system, and 11 territorial hubs were set up. To increase the number of digital specialists, France has launched an initiative under its national artificial intelligence (AI) strategy, opening new roles for AI experts and doctoral positions. In addition, to attract more digital talent, France has set up a tech visa system that eases the procedures for tech specialists to relocate to France.

Furthermore, the French Digital Skills & Jobs Coalition is carrying out a number of initiatives to boost digital skills. In 2019, the Coalition organised a competition for young people on the professions of the future. It established a partnership with the Ministry of Labour to support businesses and employees on AI development, and work is ongoing to improve its platform to share information with other European National Coalitions. In 2019, a good number of schools and other organisations took part in EU Code Week, a grassroots movement to encourage people of all ages to code. France held over 500 events that attracted over 90,000 participants.

In the field of scientific libraries, France has just recently signed a collaboration agreement with the Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER).

GREECE

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 34% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 2% towards ICT professionals, 34% towards the labour force and 30% towards citizens in general.

The main major initiative in Greece on Digital skills is the establishment of the National Digital Academy by the Ministry of Digital Governance which aims to gather, at an entry point, educational content that improves the digital skills of citizens. At the Digital Academy, the citizen can choose freely, free of charge and without complicated registration procedures the courses that suit his/her needs, interests and level of knowledge and skills. The monitoring is online and is done at the pace that suits everyone. With the self-assessment tool integrated in the Digital Academy platform, that follows the European assessment standard DigiComp v2.1, the citizen gets the opportunity to evaluate the level of his/her digital ability. Then, and according to the result of the self-assessment, the citizen is provided with the possibility of an individualized course proposal. Especially for specialized users or ICT professionals there is a possibility to choose and attend a significant number of courses.

The Digital Academy courses are provided free of charge to all citizens, by selected organizations with recognized academic and educational prestige: Greek academic institutions, well-known international companies, banking institutions, telecommunication providers and digital education organizations. The content of the Digital Academy courses was selected by a team of experts from the Ministry of Digital Government, in collaboration with Greek academics and experts in digital education. Greek and international experience was used so that the selection criteria ensure, a) the quality of the content and the structure of the educational platform and, b) the simplicity of use. The platform is dynamic, both the thematic units and the courses are constantly enriched, covering a wider range of educational needs, while even more content providers will offer educational material and an opportunity for more citizens to benefit from the Digital Academy.

In addition, several other activities are implemented per pillar of the EDSGR, namely for enhancing digital skills in education, training, for ICT professionals and for the citizens.

Also, the National Documentation Centre organises several seminars and activities around the development of digital skills in the fields of Research and Science. The first online seminar entitled "How digitally capable are we as learners, trainers and educational organizations? From theory to practice" was organized on May 14th, 2020 with more than 2,200 participants. It was implemented in the framework of the "Bridges of Knowledge and Cooperation" initiative and the "National Alliance for Digital Skills and Employment", in collaboration with the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission.

HUNGARY

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 35% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 30% towards ICT professionals, 30% towards the labour force and 5% towards citizens in general.

Main initiatives most relevant to the goals and objectives of the strategic documents on digital skills include:

1. The establishment of the Digital Success Coordinator Centre: assists the Ministry in developing digital ecosystems, increasing the level of digital literacy and coordinating programs in this field for non-school education and professional coordination of the DSP network results, informs relevant actors, oversees and coordinates Digital Care Program Mentors (DSP Mentors). It is engaged in training and development of the information society and adult training activities related to the professional coordination of the DSP Network.
2. The Digital Success Mentor Programme (EDIOP 3.3.1) which has set up 1,500 community digital access points ('Digital Success Programme Points') with ICT trainings for those with low digital skills using around 2.100 mentors.

For the effective management and coordination of the Network, DSP Network Regional Leaders and County DSP Network Leaders help the DSP Mentors work. DSP County Executives keep active contact with DSP Points and DSP Mentors. They contribute to disseminate best practices and solutions and help to communicate between DSP Mentors and the Digital Success Coordination Centre.

Several ESIF Operational Programmes that support the aims of the Digital Education Strategy are implemented, sometimes supplemented with a Competitive Central- Hungary Operative Programme (CCHOP) part if they involve national scale. These co-financed projects form the backbone of initiatives undertaken in the country and target development of skills and competences in education and labour.

The 'Programme your future' project continued in 2019. It aims to boost the number of students that graduate in ICT and improve cooperation between the educational institutions and the ICT sector. Within the programme, three experience centres have been created (Győr, Budapest, Debrecen) to motivate pupils of primary and secondary schools to study IT and engineering. In 2019, 1,330 activities were organised in Hungary during the EU Code Week.

The government has launched two initiatives to increase the number of women in ICT. TechGirls is organised by the German-Hungarian Chamber of Commerce and Industry, while Girls' Day is organised by the Association of Hungarian Women in Science. Digital thematic weeks are organised on a regular basis to promote digital pedagogic methodologies. The objective of the initiative is to accelerate the digital transformation in schools through technology enriched, project-based learning, to increase the digital competencies of young people and to reach the educational objectives of the subjects defined in the national framework curriculum by the effective use of digital technologies.

In relation to EOSC themes,

- The Centre for Digital Pedagogy and Methodology is planning to reset the curriculum to comply with Hungary Digital Competence Framework and to include digital culture subject. Also, it aims at redefining vocational training by adding a digital competence requirement level for each occupation through Sectoral Skill Councils based on DigKomp (the Hungarian Dig Comp)
- SZTAKI is organizing several training events on data use and open science that shall be extended towards FAIR data management.
- KIFU will also organize training events, seminars and webinars which will be essential to connect to the wide scope of data providers and users and coordinate their data management activities through standards and guidelines
- University of Debrecen offers a course on data stewardship in Biology which could serve as an example for further deployment.

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 10% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 20% towards ICT professionals, 20% towards the labour force and 50% towards citizens in general.

Lithuania's activities on e-skills are concentrating on distance learning education and PIAPs. The Lithuanian Information Society Development Programme for 2011-2019 makes explicit mention of ICT practitioner skills. Lithuania has a range of activities covering the full spectrum of digital literacy activities, with the Programme for Universal Computer Literacy at its core.

The main digital skills initiatives implemented in the country are within the project "Connected Lithuania". The goal of the project "Connected Lithuania: Efficient, Secure and Responsible Lithuanian Digital Community" is to help the population learn to use information technologies and the Internet efficiently, safely, and responsibly and the opportunities it provides. The project started in 2018, has a duration of 3 years and takes place in every municipality in Lithuania.

The activity of "Window to the Future", as an example of cooperation between private business and the state in achieving common goals, has become an excellent story of Lithuania's success in presenting our country to the world.

In addition, through the National Skills Strategy project (2020-2021) Lithuania has started collaboration with the OECD and European Commission to develop a more strategic, whole-of-government and cross-sectoral approach to skills policy. The main objective of the Skills Strategy project for Lithuania is to identify the main opportunities and develop tailored policy recommendations for improving Lithuania's skills performance in collaboration with the Lithuanian government and stakeholders. In order to achieve this objective, the representatives of 4 ministries as well as other stakeholders have agreed on 4 priority areas of focus for the Skills Strategy project. During the strategic seminar it was decided that Lithuania's Skills Strategy will focus on these broad main topics Priority 1: Equipping young people with skills for work and life Priority 2: Raising adults' and enterprises' participation in learning Priority 3: Using people's skills more effectively in workplaces Priority 4: Strengthening the governance of skills policies. The strategy will also include two horizontal themes: developing key competencies, including in non-formal learning and reducing skills imbalances in the economy.

The OECD will assess the performance of Lithuania's skills system, based on a combination of desktop research and direct engagement with officials and stakeholders. The OECD will support Lithuania with a collaborative and tailored OECD Skills Strategy project in 2020-2021.

Moreover, the main initiative specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives in Lithuania includes Project "Up2U". The key objective of the project is to bridge the gap between secondary schools and higher education & research by better integrating formal and informal learning scenarios and adapting both the technology and the methodology that students will most likely be facing in universities. The project is funded by Horizon 2020, that target groups include High school students and teachers, and the duration is from 2017 up to 2019. Project results at the end of 2018 include the Integrated Application Toolbox developed by Up2U that will facilitate the availability of tools and services for the learning community. It is expected to enable both educators and learners to create cross-boundary digital learning paths by interacting with the infrastructure services and OERs via their own devices.

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 25% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 25% towards ICT professionals, 25% towards the labour force and 25% towards citizens in general.

The INCoDe.2030 covers a wide range of measures involving the various governmental areas, as presented below. The main initiatives implemented under the inclusion, education and qualification measures include:

- Inclusion: Making sure the whole population has equal access to digital technologies to obtain information, communicate, and interact with others.
- Education: Educating the younger population by stimulating and reinforcing digital literacy and digital skills at all levels of schooling and as part of lifelong learning.
- Qualification: Qualifying the working population by providing them with the knowledge they need to become a part of a labour market that relies heavily on digital skills.

Moreover, the INCoDe.2030 initiative covers a wide range of measures on specialisation and research. The main initiatives implemented under these two measures include:

- Specialisation: Promoting specialisation in digital technologies and applications to improve employability and create higher added value in the economy.
- Research: Providing the conditions to produce new knowledge and an active participation in international R&D networks and programmes
- Advanced Computing Portugal 2030: Dynamic and evolutive process aimed to promote and expand Advanced Cyberinfrastructure (ACI) in Portugal by a factor of 100 in the coming decade and until 2030.
- AI Portugal 2030: An innovation and growth strategy to foster Artificial Intelligence in Portugal in the European context.

It is pointed out for these two initiatives in the research field, dedicated strategies have been developed.

In September 2018, the Federal Council launched a new **national research program on the theme of digital transformation**. The main objective of this program is to better understand the opportunities and risks of digitization for society and the economy. The program focuses in particular on the priority areas of research "Training, learning and digital transformation", "Ethics, reliability and governance" and "Digital economy and labour market".

- **Training, learning and digital transformation:** These modules study the impact of digitization on training (content, skills, and transmission of skills), on lifelong learning and on the main institutions in charge of training
- **Ethics, reliability, and governance:** These modules deal with the ethical, organizational, legal, and technical challenges which guarantee and reinforce confidence in infrastructures or in digital services.

- **Digital economy and the labour market:** These modules deal with the interactions and impact of the digital turn on the economy (productivity and competitiveness of the Swiss economic centre) and on the labour market

In September 2019, the **Swiss Digital Initiative (SDI)** was launched in Geneva aiming at a long-term and sustainable process with the objective of ensuring ethical standards in the digital world. The objectives of the initiative can be summarized as follows:

1. Ensuring ethical standards in the digital world
2. Fostering technology's potential to advance flourishing human societies
3. Focusing on ethical values and principles in action
4. Developing specific and action-oriented projects that will contribute to a global dialogue on the ethics of digitalisation, and aim to foster trust in digital technologies, as well as in the actors involved in the ongoing process of digital transformation

Another important initiative on digital skills is the **Digital Skills & Spaces program** of the Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK). It strengthens and cultivates skills that are particularly relevant for the digital age. This includes existing and new skills. In addition, Digital Skills & Spaces addresses the question of what physical spaces should look like in order to guarantee the best possible environment for learning and exercising these skills. Digital Skills & Spaces bundles existing projects and measures within the ZHdK that deal with this topic. In addition, new projects are initiated, and discussions are encouraged. The aim is to support members of the ZHdK in actively positioning themselves today and tomorrow in the digital age and in shaping their own everyday work - self-determined, reflective, and enjoyable.

Moreover, to strengthen skills in research and innovation, the following initiatives are implemented in the country:

The Digitization Initiative (DIZH) The aim of the digitization initiative (DIZH) is to promote collaboration between Zurich's universities in the field of digitization and thus strengthen Zurich as a research and business location. The University of Zurich (UZH), the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), the Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK) and the Zurich University of Education (PHZH) network systematically in the DIZH in order to specifically advance research and innovation in topics of digitization with interdisciplinary approaches.

The **"UZH Digital Society Initiative" (DSI)** is a scientific institution supported by all faculties of the University of Zurich (UZH) and open to all members of the UZH. It aims to promote independent scientific reflection and innovation on issues relating to the digital society, to prepare UZH students to help shape the digital society, to engage in a continuous discourse with the public and to support political decision-making.

New Informatics@School Task Force in Switzerland: In the context of a strategic initiative towards Informatics@School, the Swiss Informatics Society (SI) involves a task force that aims to establish Informatics in schools. 3D programming environments may engage a significant proportion of the next generation of students in computer programming.

THE NETHERLANDS

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 50% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 20% towards ICT professionals, 15% towards the labour force and 15% towards citizens in general. Main initiatives most relevant to the goals and objectives of the strategic documents on digital skills include:

- Dutch Technology Pact (Techniepact): A joint public-private initiative (60 stakeholders) that focuses on training more technical talent and making employment in the tech sector more attractive (opting for technology, learning in technology, working in technology).
- The Talent for Technology Platform (PTVT): The Talent for Technology Platform is a public-private partnership of employers' and employee organizations and the Ministries of OCW, EZK and SWZ committed to helping all young people in education discover their talents for technology and ICT so that more young people will opt for technology and ICT jobs.
- Dutch Digital Delta : Team Dutch digital delta's mission is to help the business community, government and knowledge institutions to realize innovations with ICT and to strengthen the international position of the Netherlands as a country to invest in and with ICT innovation.
- Knowledge Net (Kennisnet): Kennisnet is the guide and builder of the ICT foundation for schools and institutions in primary education (PO), secondary education (VO) and secondary vocational education (MBO). Kennisnet helps boards and schools further with knowledge about what works with ICT in education and supports large-scale administrative initiatives aimed at professionalizing the use of ICT.
- Digital Society Alliance (Alliantie Digitaal Samenleven): The Alliance is a public-private partnership organized around various working groups consisting of partners and experts. Each working group focuses on a group of people who are currently unable to fully participate in society.
- Make IT Work: A project that seeks to address immediate skills gaps by retraining highly educated and motivated people (non-STEM graduates) for the ICT sector.
- Safe Internet. It is a website where people can find tips, tricks and practical step-by-step explanations about what they can do and not do to use the internet safely.

In addition, there are some initiatives that are close to areas pertinent to EOSC objectives such as:

- Pass IT (Geef IT Door): The program teaches young people to become acquainted with IT by letting professionals share their experiences.
- The Human Capital Agenda for ICT (Digital Delta) builds on regional cooperation and plans to achieve and help educational institutions to make required adjustments to the curriculum due to the emergence of new technologies.
- CodePact: Important activities within the digital literacy program are the annual Code Week and the Digital Literacy Monitor, which examines the state of affairs and obstacles and the desired support at schools in primary education.
- The Dutch Consortium of University libraries together with ICT support staff and policy departments provide advice, guidance and support to researchers of their own university in the field of data management.
- As part of the NL DIGITAAL (Data Agenda Government). The Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations provides a professional development programme for creating data-driven policies via RADIO (the Governmental Academy for Digitalisation and Computerisation of the Government).

4.4 Review of Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks

The research performed in the current chapter, intends to:

- identify the existence of a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP, EOSC)
- identify potential infrastructures /platforms that can be exploited in national level, to this extend

At present, there is no formal integral digital competence framework. Although, It is worth noticing that the Centre for Digital Dannelselse (Digital Literacy digitaldannelselse.org) has created the "Digital Competency Wheel 1", "Digital Competency Wheel 2" to assess, to provide an overview and to improve the most relevant digital skills. The work is based on DigComp as a theoretical framework.

Furthermore, the Digital Strategy 2016-2020 puts emphasis on the Digital Competences for Public Employees. In particular, public employees should be qualified to deal with the digital requirements of the future. The digitalisation goals of Danish university colleges will therefore be followed through and there will be special efforts to enhance digital teaching skills for teachers and child carers. Furthermore, every public employee will be continuously informed about the requirements for information security. Digital competences for teachers are being further enhanced. The existing range of preparatory adult education (whose Danish acronym is FVU) was extended to include FVU-Digital, aiming to enable teachers to perform the digital tasks that are relevant to their job function, as to use relevant digital tools, communicate digitally, search information digitally and organize, structure and manage data. Specific new modules in the educational diploma curriculum (Pdagogisk Diplomuddannelselse) have been prepared in order to enhance competencies for teachers teaching FVU-Digital. Therefore, the new FVU Executive Order, contains provisions and curricula for different subjects, came into effect January 1, 2019.

Denmark has a bipartite accreditation system.

- The Danish Accreditation Institution plays a crucial part in ensuring the quality and relevance of higher education programmes across the country. The Danish Accreditation Institution is responsible for conducting the accreditation processes and development of the method they follow.
- The various qualifications offered in the Danish education and training system are organized in accordance with the national qualifications framework. The Danish qualifications framework for lifelong learning was developed by an interdepartmental working group with representatives from four separate ministries, as well as some other stakeholders from the Danish education system.

Denmark has not only covered digital skills in the VET curriculum but has also created courses solely focused on digital and ICT professions. In fact, the website IT-formidler.dk was created to support the many initiatives around the country aimed at improving Danish IT skills. This web site primarily aims at giving the opportunity to every teacher in the country to share experiences, produce educational materials and retrieve teaching modules. The site was launched in March 2009 as part of the project "Learn More". The Agency for Digitalisation, Ministry of Finance, is responsible for the website.

Furthermore, the DTU Learn for Life centre, established in April of this year, aims to become the Technical University of Denmark's central platform for continuing education, and will provide knowledge, support, and assistance to partners about lifelong learning. It is a collaborative effort between DTU departments, central administration, and strategic partners.

FINLAND

Digital competences are included in the national core curricula at all levels from early childhood education and care onwards. The Key Competences for Lifelong Learning identified by the European Commission are a crucial part of the content in both general education and vocational education and training (VET). Cooperation with working life is essential when defining the requirements for digital skills. Working life representatives participate in anticipation studies for learning and education needs, in the development of vocational qualifications, and in competence assessments.

The National Forum for Skills Anticipation is a tripartite expert body working with the Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC) and the Finnish National Agency for Education (EDUFI). As part of its ongoing anticipation process (2017–2019) the Forum identifies the future skills needed by specific sectors and occupational groups. The skills survey pays special attention to digital skills, and the European Commission's Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp 2.0) is utilized in the data collection and analysis

There are some assessment tools to evaluate digital skills or other skills using digital assessment tools, that are also used for teachers and schools to measure and analyse their usage of ICT. As an example, DigCompEdu is an ongoing development process to create and pilot Digital Competence for Educators framework based self-assessment tool. This tool is intended to help teachers progress towards digital age learning. Digital Competence for Educators conceptual framework describes what it means for educators to be digitally competent. The self-assessment tool is directed towards educators at all levels of education, from early childhood to higher and adult education. The self-assessment tool provides teachers a tool for reflecting on their current take up of digital technologies for innovative and effective learning. University of Jyväskylä is currently coordinating the upcoming pilot testing of DigCompEdu self-assessment tool for teachers in Finnish Schools. Pilot testing of DigCompEdu took place in Autumn 2019. Finnish schools and educational institutes will be encouraged to participate in the piloting of the new self-assessment tool.

No formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs exists actually, yet the ongoing work for the development of Open Science/Data and digital transformation policies, aiming to be concluded by mid next year, will address the issue at least for researchers.

As a related initiative, the national study credit, degree, and qualification disclosure service (Koski) aims to bring together all study credits, degrees and qualifications stored in different data warehouses. Koski will make it easier for citizens to use e-services and allow the authorities to perform their duties more efficiently. The act on national study credit and degree registers entered into force on 1 January 2018 while the new service is fully functional since 2019. National Study Credit, Degree and Qualification Disclosure Service (Koski) is the responsible organization.

The University of Helsinki, the oldest and largest university in Finland, is offering open online courses through a dedicated MOOC platform. The courses are offered by the Department of Computer Science. No prior knowledge is required — beginners can start to learn programming basics from the Programming with Java course or start to get familiar with artificial intelligence from the course Elements of AI.

French Government has endorsed a Digital Competence Framework System based on DigiComp 2.0 to develop, measure, and certify digital competences for all. In this framework, France has developed the PIX platform that allows all citizens to evaluate and also certify their digital competence. The model, which is co-designed by the Min. of Education offers to measure its digital skills on 8 levels and 5 main areas, as follows:

1. Information and data
2. Communication and collaboration
3. Content creation
4. Protection and security
5. Digital environment

In addition, PIX is a public service, created to respond to the social challenge of improving digital skills in France. Its mission is to encourage people to cultivate their digital skills and to value what they have learned throughout their lives. In 2019, France set up a national framework for digital competences (Framework for digital competences) using the European Digital Competence Framework, which covers education levels from primary school to university. This adds to the existing PIX platform for digital skills. The French platform PIX allows all citizens to evaluate and also certify their digital competence. The model, which is co-designed by the Min. of Education, uses DigComp. France will revise its certification of digital competences at the end of middle and upper secondary school on the basis of the new national framework for digital competences. The French platform Pix.fr is a free online public service open to everyone to assess and develop digital skills. Due to the interactive tests of gradual difficulty and in the form of practical exercises, it allows all citizens to take stock and improve their digital knowledge and skills. The platform prepares the participants to take the Pix Certification, the digital skills certification initiated and recognized by the State, listed in the specific directory of France's Competences (eligible for the CPF).

Currently, there is not digital competence framework formally established in the country, as per DIGICOMP guidelines. However, in the context of the Digital Transformation Bible that is currently under development, the need for introducing a digital competence framework in Greece is stated and relative actions are already being implemented within the context of Technical Assistance provided by DG Reform. As a first result, Citizen Digital Academy includes a self -assessment tool based on DigiComp v2.1 (21 competences organized in 5 areas).

EOPPEP, Greece's National Organisation for the certification of qualifications and vocational guidance, develops and implements the National Accreditation & Certification System for non-formal education, including initial and continuing vocational training and adult education, and provides scientific support to Vocational Guidance & Counselling services in Greece. EOPPEP's principal fields of activity and responsibility are:

- Accreditation/Licensing of Providers of non-formal education, accreditation of Occupational Profiles and of Curricula (in terms of standards and specifications)
- Development and implementation of the National Qualifications Framework (NQF) in correspondence with EQF & National Coordination Point for EQF (NCP)
- Development of the National System for the Certification of Qualifications
- Accreditation of Vocational Training & Certification of Vocational Training Institutes graduates
- Scientific and technical support of vocational guidance and counselling services
- Cooperation in the development and implementation of the National Framework for Quality Assurance in LLL

The government also plans to introduce a certification framework to support the National Digital Academy platform.

Moreover, the National Documentation Centre (NDC) is the main national content provider that offers courses on enhancing digital skills in Greece. NDC paves the way for knowledge transfer and reuse in research and innovation, by making scientific knowledge accessible to all while developing and strengthening its activities to disseminate, with as few limitations as possible, existing and future knowledge, so that it can be reused for research, education, development, innovation and society. It collects, documents, disseminates and provides long-term preservation of quality digital content and data produced by Greek scientific, research and cultural communities, it measures output and results of the Research, Technology, Development, Innovation (RTDI) system and its comparison to European and international equivalents, it follows through the broader national objective to exploit research results and innovation for public sector reform, developing the economy and solving social problems and ensure the continuous operation of the national electronic infrastructure, providing friendly access to reusable and reputable information, the collection and availability of data and production of statistics for RTDI in Greece, and to offer a range of services for research, academic, educational and business communities. NDC provides a range of services to the Greek research, academic and business community of the country, in the context of its three pillars of activities:

- e-content - Digital content and services
- metrics - RTD Indicators and Statistics
- innovation - Services for networking, cooperation, development

Finally, the National Digital Academy offers more than 200 online digital courses to enhance citizens' digital skills, organized around 30 thematic units. Content has been prepared and uploaded by more than 30 providers from both public and private sectors.

HUNGARY

Based on concluded projects, the Government issued the 1341/2019. (VI. 11.) Government decree about the development and implementation of a Digital Competence Framework System based on DigiComp 2.1 to develop, measure, and certify digital competences for all.

It is not clear if a formal accreditation or certification scheme based on these competencies is established, but it is certainly under consideration. Rewards for obtaining digital skills (especially ones related to Open Science) are mainly project based, rather than systematic.

Most content providers operate via funding from ESIF projects as seen above. No online digital skills platform was identified during the desk research. Potential candidates for offering such a platform include the Digital Pedagogical Methodology Centre, KIFÜ and SZTAKI.

The Translation of the DigComp framework in Lithuania is implemented by the Education Development Centre. The Education Development Centre (EDC) is the biggest institution affiliate to the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport of the Republic of Lithuania providing educational support in the field of pre-school, primary and general education. Currently in Lithuania there are no visible improvements in transparency of digital qualifications: credit transfer between formal, non-formal and industry-based ICT educations and certifications and there is no mechanism to implement discussions about the recognition of informal education on ICT/ digital skills.

Moreover, the National Association of Distance Education (NADE) was established in July 1998 with the purpose to promote the creation of the Information Society of Lithuania by developing distance education (DE) and improving its quality. The major goal of NADE is to provide equal learning opportunities to all Lithuanian citizens, despite their place of living. Among its many activities are organizing distance education courses, preparing and adapting distance education programs, promotion of research in the field of distance education and organizing workshops, seminars and conferences.

The INCoDe.2030 programme in October 2019 released the Digital Competence Dynamic Reference Framework (QDRCD) a tool for population' digital skills' evaluation. Based on the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DIGICOMP¹⁶) the QDRCD has three objectives:

- to support the definition of policies and strategies
- to design education programmes; and
- to evaluate and certificate skills, either by self-diagnosis or by certifying entities.

Information Literacy, Communication and Citizenship, Content Creation, Security and Privacy, and Solutions Development are the five competences areas addressed, which level of proficiency, including examples of daily use, ranges from basic to highly specialized.

The document was developed with the collaboration of the National Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education (ANQEP), the Directorate-General for Education (DGE), Directorate-General for

¹⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/digcomp-21-digital-competence-framework-citizens-eight-proficiency-levels-and-examples-use>

the Qualification of Public Workers (INA), Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Employment and Professional Training Institute (IEFP) and António Moreira and Margarida Lucas, both from University of Aveiro.

The National Qualifications System (SNQ) was created in December 2007 with primary objective to raise the qualification levels of the active population, through school and professional progression, as well as to structure an initial and continuous educational and training offer for young people and adults, adjusted to the needs of companies and the labour market. The National Qualifications System (SNQ) is coordinated by the National Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education (ANQEP) and works in conjunction with the European Qualifications Framework to promote the improvement of the basic training of the active population through school and professional progression. The SNQ also includes (among others) the Directorate-General for Employment and Labour Relations (DGERT), which is the coordinating body of the competent authorities for the purposes of recognition of professional qualifications, and the Institute of Employment and Vocational Training (IEFP), which is the contact point for matters regarding the recognition of professional qualifications. The Decree-Law no. 88/2006 regulates Technological Specialization Courses.

Moreover, Foundation for Science and Technology - FCT is the national funding agency for science, technology, and innovation under responsibility of the Ministry for Education and Science. FCT coordinates public policy for the Information and Knowledge Society in Portugal and ensures the development of national scientific computing resources. In this regard, it is FCT's mission to:

- Raise awareness of and engage stakeholders in Information Society public policies, through dissemination, research, and training activities
- Encourage the development of e-Science, by promoting the creation of knowledge and the scientific and technological development of businesses and R&D national institutions
- Promote cooperation with foreign organisations, namely within the European Union and Portuguese-speaking countries

FCT allocates funding to different types of activities and through various instruments: research projects, advanced training, scientific employment, research units, international cooperation.

SWITZERLAND

Currently in Switzerland, there is no national framework been established, yet based on EU DIGICOMP. To some extent the "Lehrplan 21" harmonises the curriculum and integrates media education, yet digital competences do not appear and is not given transversal status in educational policy. Only the use of digital tools in other subjects is discussed and explored. However, the connection to main transversal competencies such as problem solving is not considered.

In the above framework, the Swiss Science, and Innovation Council SSIC has proposed (position paper on digital competences 2017), a competent framework, within the EU framework. Also, Switzerland is a member of ECDL Foundation, whereas all ECDL certification programmes are fully compatible with DigComp. Also, ICDL is delivered in Switzerland by Digital Literacy AG. Apart from the Swiss Information Society, training courses and certification of digital skills are undertaken by private sector actors e.g. Digicom Academy AG.

Switzerland is taking part in the Bologna Process in the field of higher education and in the Copenhagen Process in the sphere of vocational and professional education and training. Both processes aim to

guarantee, at national and international level, permeability, transparency, and mobility and hence in the European context to work towards strengthening Europe's competitiveness as a learning location.

The Qualifications Framework for the Swiss Higher Education Area (nqf.ch-HS) describes and defines the levels of higher education in Switzerland on the basis of admission conditions and qualifications inter alia. The qualifications framework serves the higher education institutions as a guide in developing and describing their study courses and programmes. It also improves information about the Swiss higher education system, particularly with regard to teaching. Finally, it facilitates the comparability of qualifications in Europe and enhances transparency. The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) is the basis for Switzerland's National Qualifications Framework for Vocational and Professional Qualifications (NQF VPQ). The Swiss vocational and professional education and training system trains highly skilled workers. However, there is little awareness outside of Switzerland of these qualifications. The NQF VPQ is intended to make it easier for people to understand how the Swiss education system works and to be able to compare Swiss qualifications with other qualifications elsewhere in Europe. With this aim in mind, all formal vocational and professional qualifications have been assigned to one of eight reference levels within the NQF VPQ.

Last, but not least, the Swiss MOOC Service is the national Open edX platform for institutions of higher education of Switzerland and is open for other organisations and corporations as well. The platform is compatible with Swiss data protection laws and hosted in Switzerland. Swiss MOOC founded by leading Swiss universities EPFL, ETH, SUPSI, USI and HES-SO and financially supported by the Swiss universities' P5 program is a one stop shop to help Universities and other organisations kickstart their online education presence. It is based on the industry leading Open edX LMS platform with many advantages offered, including state of the art course planning management, Open Source access to source and ultra-scalability to millions of learners.

THE NETHERLANDS

The DigComp standards have been used as a reference to compare with the outcomes of "Digital Literacy" curricula in primary and secondary schools in the Netherlands. Furthermore, a digital literacy assessment framework (MDS) has been proposed by researchers in Twente University and recognized by Unesco as a useful instrument. However, it seems that there is no formally accepted Digital Competence framework established. There is no indication of whether the existing framework and accreditation system are under consideration for being expanded at the digital competencies domain.

Netherlands is quite advanced in terms of national content providers that offer courses in enhancing digital skills, although the focus rests highly on basic and average skills to support the strategic goals set in the Digitalization Strategy.

- Kennisnet offers several services related to digital content for skills such as lesopense.nl (to organize distance education), Wikiwijs (an educational platform where teachers search, find, reuse, create and share digital learning resources), Teacher24 (support the daily practice of the teacher with practically applicable articles) etc.
- The network of Libraries and National Library offer several courses through the Dutch Library and Basic Skills programme, started in 2015.
- An online education portal is planned under the Dutch Technology Pact 2020.
- According to the Acceleration Agenda for Innovation in Education by the 1st of January 2023, higher education institutions in the Netherlands shall offer lecturers and students the opportunity to determine and use an optimal mix of (digital) educational resources for learning and teaching processes.

4.5 Review of current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open Science

The research performed in the current chapter, intends to:

- identify major actors in Scientific Research in the country (promoters and users of open science)
- identify organizations that can act as “champions” in the promotion of digital skills, R&D and innovation management with respect to Open Science principles and objectives. Determine potential fragmentation of services as well as overlaps or synergies
- understand the mindset of the Research community towards Open Science principles and practices and estimate adherence to FAIR principles
- determine the level of maturity of digital infrastructures and services in Research
- form an opinion on how research and industry are linked
- prepare the ground for the gap analysis with EOSC priorities

DENMARK

Denmark has high-quality data sets and registries which are quite unique in an international perspective. In 2011, Denmark joined the international initiative “Open Government Partnership” (OGP), which serves to promote good governance and strengthen democracy by promoting transparent and inclusive governance among the currently 75 participating countries.

Denmark does not have an integrated Open Science Policy. Although, it is in place a national Open Access Strategy and a national strategy for Research data management. The Open Access strategy states that the implementation of Open Access is to take place through the green model, i.e. parallel filling of quality-assured research articles in institutional or subject-specific archives (repositories) with Open Access. The implementation of the Open Access is to support the possibility for Danish researchers to continue to publish in the most recognized national and international journals, and also the possibility to publish. The strategy, being a national one, is quite wide-ranging, covering both data and the software/protocols necessary to re-run experiments (although not publications, which are mentioned only in passing), noting also the need to foster research data management skills. The goal is 100% Open Access to publicly funded research publications by 2025. Each of the 8 Danish universities has their own local Open Science Support Unit, typically based at the university libraries. All the universities have local research support units, who in various degrees support researchers with their award applications and reporting. Six out of eight higher-education institutions have an Open Access policy, while the seventh is working to implement a more comprehensive Open Science policy.

As part of the Digital Strategy 2016-2020, the government published a common public sector White Paper on Architecture for Digitalisation in June 2017. The architecture ensures cross-organisational processes and efficient sharing of data across the public sector and between the public and private sectors. Another policy that promotes open data is the Digital Health Strategy 2018-2022. In May 2017, the Danish local, regional, and central governments agreed on a common Framework for Federal Digital Architecture (FDA) including a number of reference architectures that focuses on data sharing, cross-organisational processes, and a coherent IT-infrastructure. In spring 2019 guidelines on architecture description including common rules for concept and data modelling v.2.0 were established. The framework is supported by skill-development, architecture guidance and project reviews.

The Ministry of Higher Education and Science manages and monitors the Danish Open Access strategy, while DeIC is working on national structure for RDM support and training. A National Forum for Data Management was formed in 2015, with representatives from the Danish universities and national libraries and a secretariat from DeIC. Its vision is “to promote academic and research initiatives in research data management within universities and link them in a national and international cooperation.” Furthermore, the government created a Data Ethical Council in early 2019 to facilitate a public debate about i.e. the use of technology, data, and AI in both the public and private sector. The council includes members from universities and think tanks as well as the public and private sector. Besides, the Danish Centre for Applied Artificial Intelligence aims to offer Danish companies easy access to cutting-edge expertise in machine learning, artificial intelligence and big data by supporting networks and collaboration in the field and offering access to data platforms and human resources.

Denmark’s digital infrastructure and attitudes towards digitalisation are some of the best in Europe. The publication, "Danish Roadmap for Research Infrastructure 2015", presents the Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science's vision and strategic objectives for this policy area over the coming five years. At the same time, it presents a catalogue of specific proposals for national infrastructures, which in the short term are recommended as investment prospects. The main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes in Denmark include a) CERN-UP – Upgrading infrastructure for CERN experiments and computing, b) QUANTECH – Quantum Technology Infrastructure, c) BICLabs – Behaviour, Interaction and Cognition Labs, d) DigHumLab 2.0 – Digital Humanities Lab Denmark, e) DRDS – Danish Research Data for the Social Sciences and f) FiberLab – New Fibre Composites Laboratory.

FINLAND

Finish Parliament’s vision is to build Finland up as an attractive operating environment for the data economy. By 2023, research organizations will provide comprehensive training, support, and skills development on research data documentation for different target groups, considering the needs of different disciplines and the life cycle of research. Promotion of open science and research is a joint effort by the entire research community. In the centre of the coordination work there are four governmental expert panels and their working groups on Culture of open scholarship, Open data, Open access, Open education. In particular the Expert panel on open data contributes actively in the making of national policies and recommendations on the National Open Policy, that is expected to be completed by middle of 2021 and it is working in cooperation with the National Open Science and Research Steering Group, drafting principles for the Policy on Open Access to Research Materials and Methods and a policy component on Open Access to Research Data. This draft, that is actually under consultation, is the first part of the national Policy on Open Access to Research Materials and Methods for the Finnish higher education and research community, and it further defines the national objectives for open research materials and methods mentioned in the Finnish Declaration of Open Science and Research 2020–2025. The policy will be supplemented with a policy component on open research methods in 2021-2022.

Other related policies are the Spatial Data Policy and the Artificial Intelligence Programme, by the Ministry of Economic Affairs. Concerning the support of the researchers regarding their career path, EURAXESS Finland provides information and assistance to mobile researchers – by means of the web portal and with the support of the national EURAXESS Service Centres. The portal contains practical information concerning professional and daily life, as well as information on job and funding opportunities. At the beginning of 2020, the new Digital, and Population Data Services Agency (Finnish

Digital Agency) began its operation in Finland. It was established by the Act on the Digital and Population Data Services Agency (304/2019).

The Digital and Population Data Services Agency leads the way, reforms society, and supports citizens in their interaction with public administration. The Digital and Population Data Services Agency launched on 1 January 2020 with the merging of the Population Register Centre, the Local Register Offices and the Steering and Development Unit for the Local Register Offices, which operates at the Regional State Administrative Agency of Eastern Finland. Its aim is to promote the digitalisation of society, secures the availability of data, and provides services for the life events of its customers. In relation to the development of these policies, strong cooperation with EOSC has been set up in order Finland to exploit EOSC working results and enhance them in its undergoing policies, addressing so, the goals of SRIA. Furthermore, the Academy of Finland is the prime funding agency for basic research in Finland. For example, the Finnish Funding Agency for Innovation, is the main public funding organisation for applied research and technology, and Sitra, standing as the Finnish Innovation Fund is another key source of funding for science and technology in Finland.

The platform Fairdata.fi offers metadata tool, research dataset finder, storage areas of digital information for tens or even hundreds of years and for actual use, constituting the central point for research work applying open data science principles. The <https://findocnet.fi/> is a portal enabling research work for all researchers along the country.

Moreover, the innovation system is based on intensive collaboration between universities and industry (ranked 2nd in the world). The Digital Finland Framework aims to ensure world's best innovation and business environment for companies seeking to develop innovative products, services and solutions to challenges ranging from those in everyday life to meeting the Sustainable Development Goals.

The Nordic countries case

Nordic countries have similar ambitions on Open Science. The majority of the countries have already policies in place requiring researchers to publish their results in Open Access journals, and in the few cases where policies are not yet established, there are at the very least concrete goals. For Open Data, the vision seems to be going in the same direction, although it has not matured to the same extent as Open Access publications. In many of the countries an Open Data policy is being drawn up, while a few countries have already imposed policies and others have published guidelines.

The Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC) is hosted by NordForsk (the Nordic Council of Ministers that provides funding for and facilitates Nordic cooperation on research and research infrastructure), which provides for and facilitates cooperation on research and research infrastructure across the Nordic region. NeIC is NordForsk's main tool for implementing the Nordic eScience Action Plan 2.0. The strategy for the 2020–2025 period, recognises NeIC as a Nordic organisation dedicated to working with a wide range of Nordic partners to produce, enhance and support research e-infrastructure in the region. NeIC provides opportunities to develop skills and new knowledge for its staff, e-infrastructure providers, and researchers in the Nordic region. Especially, NeIC is seeking to drive the establishment of FAIR Data Stewardship as a new profession. In 2017 NeIC Board identified "data management" as a subject that was not being sufficiently addressed in the NeIC project portfolio. The Board recommended that NeIC should direct some effort towards data management and, given the importance of research data in general and the onset of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in the European arena, this seems timely and appropriate.

On 2018, an initiative by Science Europe and the European Research Council, named Plan-S, has vowed to accelerate the transition to Open Access by requiring that participating countries commit to a list of requirements by 2020, involving copyrights to authors and not to accept hybrid open access journals. Norway, Sweden and recently also Finland has joined this coalition-S. There are several initiatives providing opportunities for improvement in order to achieve better open science in the Nordic countries, both short-term and long-term such as a) Making legacy data findable and reusable, b) Enabling FAIR data – machine actionable protocols, templates and standards, c) Data stewardships: a fundamental pillar to aid science, d) Training the researchers, e) Preparing for the future: FAIRification of research data. In particular, on 2019 a EOSC-Nordic project has been launched, aiming at facilitating coordination of relevant EOSC initiatives within the Nordic and Baltic countries and exploiting synergies to achieve greater harmonisation of policy and service provisioning. The project seeks to establish the Nordic and Baltic countries as frontrunners in the take-up of the EOSC concept, principles, and approach.

FRANCE

France has played an important role in the European open access movement, particularly in the launch of the Berlin declaration. Among French research structures, the research institutions (CNRS, INSERM in particular) played a major role at the beginning of the 2000's, especially with the launch of the HAL open archive in 2001. There are several legislative texts that set the framework for the publication and sharing of open data.

In November 2007, the ANR (project-based funding agency for research in France) issued an open access policy, strongly encouraging the deposit of funded publications in open archives systems and in HAL in particular. It is worth noting that the Humanities and Social Sciences department has adopted a stronger policy mandating systematic deposit of publications in HAL-SHS.

The national policy of openness and sharing of public data was adopted in 2015 and acts as driver for “democratic vitality, economic innovation and modernisation of public service delivery”. In addition to this, a Digital Republic Act was passed in 2016 that includes open data as one of its cornerstones. In particular, in October 2016, the French Law for a Digital Republic Act came into force. One article is of specific concern for scholarly communication, as it relates directly to open access/open data. Article 30 is about Open Access and creates a new right for researchers which creates a legal right for authors to archive an OA copy, even if they have granted an exclusive right to a publisher.

In July 2018, the Ministry of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation adopted the ambition National Plan for Open Science. The plan presents three broad commitments under the headings: a) generalising Open Access to Publications, b) structuring Research Data and making it available through Open Access, and c) be part of a sustainable European and international open science dynamic. Each commitment is accompanied by a short Roadmap section, which outlines the steppingstones to meeting each commitment. In addition, the National Plan for Open Science ensures that data produced by government-funded research in France are gradually structured to comply with the FAIR Data Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), and that they are preserved and, whenever possible, open to all. Also, in 2019, the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) adopted the Roadmap for Open Science.

The French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) and the Open Science Committee are the main stakeholders involved with France’s Research, Data, and Open science framework.

- The French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) is an interdisciplinary public research organisation under the administrative supervision of the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research. It is among the world's leading research institutions. The CNRS conducts research that is in the interest of science as well as the technological, social, and cultural advancement of the country.
- The Open Science Committee, with 270 experts, some of whom are involved through a series of thematic colleges and project groups and a collaborative forum to identify pragmatic, collective and collaborative methods to achieve the plan’s objectives.

The 2016 edition of France’s National Strategy for the Research Infrastructures reflects the willingness of the country, through its major institutions of research and higher education, to meet the requirements of knowledge and innovation. The roadmap has been elaborated on the basis of a state-of-the-art analysis by scientists from all fields and in accordance with the National Research Strategy.

The main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes infrastructures consist of four computing infrastructures (GENCI, CCIN2P3, Grid’5000, and France Grilles) and two network infrastructures (RENATER and FIT). Most of these infrastructures are integrated into European or international infrastructures.

GREECE

Open Access/ Science policies are slowly adopted by HEI of Greece. Currently, Greece does not yet have in place a specific, formally approved National strategy for Open Science. Law 4310/2014 supports open

access to publicly funded research. On the 29 and 30 November 2018 OpenAIRE organised a Greek Open Science Symposium which aimed at understanding the current research ecosystem and prioritise actions towards the development of a National Open Science Strategy. Drawn from discussions during the 1st day, a proposal for the reformulation of a National Open Science High Level Task Force under the auspices of the General Secretariat of Research and Technology (GSRT) was made.

Open access to scientific content, has been mainly supported through the reinforcement of research and academic organisations' e-infrastructures, namely the development of scientific content repositories, but also through the successful participation of the relevant stakeholders in competitive EU programmes. Greek repositories mostly contain postgraduate dissertations/theses and doctoral theses (NDC's National Archive of PhD Theses), not peer reviewed publications. The absence of open access policies at institute/research centre level can explain the lack of peer reviewed publications in these repositories, while the same publications appear in other sectoral repositories.

The Greek national Action Plan for European Research Area - ERA (2015-2020) has been prepared by GSRT after several targeted consultations with key stakeholders of the Greek research community. It describes the guiding principles and future actions for each ERA priority in relation to EU level policies and strategic documents and in this respect the latter have been fully taken into account in designing measures and actions needed at national level to meet the targets set in the document. Despite weaknesses in implementation or slow progress detected in some areas the guiding principles of the roadmap and its perspective are aligned with the policy priorities set at EU level. The Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3) used for the programming period 2014-2020 and funding from Structural Funds (ESIF) is fully aligned with European policies and goals for research and innovation.

The General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT) is a modern public service assigned with the task of defining, as well as coordinating the implementation of, the national policy for Research, Technological Development, and Innovation. It supports the activities of research and industry bodies through competitive research programmes highlighting economic performance and a socially fair allocation of outcomes. Furthermore, it supervises research and technology bodies, which provide local communities with the skills necessary for producing knowledge and boosting innovation.

GRNET, National Infrastructures for Research and Technology, is the Greek national research network. GRNET is a state-owned company, operating under the auspices of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance. GRNET is an integrated e-infrastructure service provider and offers an environment of cutting-edge technologies providing infrastructural and technological support to academic and research institutions, to educational bodies at all levels, and agencies of the public sector. GRNET is the main infrastructure and service enabler for open science in Greece, and leads the coordinated development of e-infrastructures and services in Southeast Europe (SEEREN, SEE-GRID series, HP-SEE, VI-SEEM, NI4OS projects) and the wider region. Regarding data storage, GRNET has over 11 Petabytes of raw disk storage and 7 Petabytes of tape archive. Concerning cloud computing, GRNET operates Infrastructure as a Service via large datacentres (135 racks, 1800+ servers, 7000 Virtual Machines active, 5 Petabytes of storage). In the realm of High-Performance Computing (HPC), GRNET is currently operating the Greek national HPC Tier-1 centre – ARIS (Advanced Research Information System). The total theoretical peak performance of the whole system is 434 Tflops.

Other stakeholders involved with Research, Data, and Open science in Greece are the Research and Technology Bodies supervised by GSRT in various fields. In the area of Information Technology and Telecommunications these include:

- Athena Research & Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Science Technologies
- Centre for Nuclear Research, Demokritos
- Centre for Research and Technology Hellas / CERTH
- Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH)

- National Hellenic Research Foundation / NHRF
- National Observatory of Athens (NOA)

Research Infrastructures are recognised as key structural elements of the National Research & Innovation ecosystem in Greece. They have a prominent role within the NSRTDI 2014-2020, being recognised as 'enablers of innovation', via interdisciplinary synergy effects they create within the knowledge triangle. Therefore, research infrastructures contribute to all three priority pillars of the National Strategy of R&I, while they are also linked with Horizon 2020.

With regards to e- Infrastructures, the horizontal HELIX: National Digital Infrastructure for Research is a convergence-building instrument for the coordination of research-oriented e-Infrastructures in Greece, coordinated by GRNET aims at an overall coordination of research-oriented e-Infrastructures with a wide participation of all research centres. It comprises two independent and complementary entities - NNCRF and OpenAIRE-D - that respectively address the increasing horizontal 'big computing/networking' and 'big data' needs of the Greek academic & research community. Overall, it forms a single national ecosystem within which it provides research and advisory services, supports training activities, and offers relevant expertise on the combination of high-end communications, high-performance and high through put distributed computing, elastic cloud resource provisioning, and scalable data processing & analysis. It instruments several 'as a Service' offerings where part of the management capabilities is handed over to researchers, thereby facilitating innovation on novel frameworks delivering advanced researcher-controlled capabilities. HELIX will support the creation of open science aspects, ranging from AAI (EduGain), PID systems, an OA aggregator for publications (like OpenAIRE), a national repository for publications, a national data repository with accompanying RDM services.

HUNGARY

No policy on Open Data is yet in place, although the first steps have been taken in late 2017 with the formation of a joint experts committee for open science. The Committee, working under the National Research Development & Innovation office "NRDI" (supervised by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology) has produced a policy draft which was submitted for review, however due to organizational changes in the Office there have been long delays in producing a final document. To support this work a special grant has been awarded to KIFU and SZTAKI to create a report on Open Science as a basis for further development in the field.

Despite the lack of policy, the country is very much active on the domain with several organizations collaborating in the various Open Science Themes, including universities, government organizations and institutions, associations, and representatives of the ICT market. Several initiatives involve training and raising awareness. The objective is to try and pool together scarce resources and competencies to bring about a cultural change in regard to Open Science.

Hungary has not created any regulation on Open Science. The Act on Higher Education only declares that the doctoral dissertations (and their preliminary research theses) must be accessible for everyone (Act CCIV of 2011).

Regarding digital infrastructures and services, Hungary published its National Research Infrastructure Roadmap in 2018 and maintains a lot of repositories and services around Open Science, but there is room for improvement in terms of coordination between the parties. There is no clear utilization map of available infrastructures and it is possible that several potential users are not fully aware of all available options.

The Hungarian research landscape comprises mainly of two groups:

- There are 66 higher education institutions in the country: 22 state universities, 7 non-state universities, 5 state universities of applied sciences, 2 non-state universities of applied sciences, 1 state college, and 28 non-state colleges
- The research network of the Academy comprises 15 legally independent research institutions and more than 130 research groups at universities co-financed by the Academy.

Despite the fact that several companies have a close, long-lasting cooperation with universities and play an active role in undergraduate and PhD training, Hungary is lagging behind EU average in terms of links between the Research Community and the Industry, as is evident from the European Research Area Progress Report (2018), according to which the country's gap to the EU-28 level was growing wider. To support university-industry collaboration Centres for Higher Education and Industrial Cooperation (FIEK) were established in 2017, which will be able to adapt university research programmes in applied science and innovation to industrial needs in the years to come.

LITHUANIA

Lithuania has a Law on Higher Education and Research, which covers Open Access and research data, while the more relevant policy document on Research, Data, and Open science is the Research Council of Lithuania's "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Data" (2016), which cover both publications and data. Skills are not addressed, but responsibilities for various aspects of Open Access and Open Data are covered in detail. The focus of Lithuania's policy on Research, Data, and Open science is more on rights than on obligations, and the inference is that universities are responsible for developing their own policies, procedures, guidance, and monitoring systems.

In Lithuania, the public and private institutions are required by law to make any research results public. In particular, to ensure transparent use of funds and the quality of the research conducted using the funds from the state budget and to foster research development, all the results of research conducted in state research and education institutions should be made public (on the Internet or by other means) insofar as it is consistent with the laws regulating intellectual property rights and commercial, state and public service secrecy protection. The results of research conducted using the funds from the state budget in private research and education institutions should be made public (on the Internet or by other means) insofar as it is consistent with the laws regulating intellectual property rights, commercial and state secrecy protection. Today, the following open access databases are available in Lithuania:

- National aggregated open access repository
- Inter-institutional research publication and research data archives
- Institutional research databases

The Lithuanian research and higher education institutions participate in international projects and initiatives on open access: 7th Framework Programme projects OpenAIRE and OpenAIREplus.

The Research Council of Lithuania is the institution coordinating open access activities in Lithuania. The decision was made on the submission of the Ministry of Education and Science and in response to the 2013 request made by the Secretariat of the Lithuanian National Commission for UNESCO to appoint the institution responsible for open access to research information. The Council collects and systematises the data on open access databases used in Lithuania, on legal, financial, and other developmental aspects, participates in the open access policy formation and encourages dissemination of the open access concept. The Research Council of Lithuania and the Ministry of Education and

Science appoint Lithuanian representatives to the European Commission (EC) national representatives for research data group. The group was initiated in the end of 2013 on the EC initiative while implementing the 17 July 2012 recommendation for open access to research data and its preservation (2012/417/ES).

In 2014, the Research Council of Lithuania became a partner of the international project 'Open Access Policy Alignment Strategies for European Union Researchers'.

The working group for open access to research data and the research group under the Lithuanian National Commission for UNESCO distributed their 'Request to the Lithuanian science and higher education institutions on open access to research data', in which they stated having noticed attempts in forming the open access policy, preparing provisions and recommendations for open access to university research papers and results, organising seminars for the science community and disseminating the information on open access and its benefits to the society.

With regards to digital research infrastructures, following the European Commission and ESFRI encouragement to Member States and Associated Countries for developing national roadmaps for research infrastructures (RIs), Lithuania developed the Roadmap in 2011, which it was updated in 2015.

Portugal is showing good results in some innovation indicators (including but not limited to AI), although in many of them we have been typically placed below the average of the European Union. Portuguese institutions are particularly well positioned in terms of international research collaborations, broadband penetration, and product/process innovations in SMEs. Portugal has been relatively successful as an innovation-friendly environment and has an attractive research system. Moreover, Portuguese research has a high level of international collaboration (185% of the EU average in 2017) participating in the 10% most cited works (82.6%) and in the attraction of foreign PhD students (98.3%). Also, the R&D expenditure of the business sector has considerably improved since 2015 and represents about 52% of gross expenditure in R&D. SMEs are doing quite well in innovations in the product or the process (158.8%) and in marketing/organisation levels (112%).

A preparation of a National Policy for Open Science is underway in Portugal. The work is initiated by the Government and Ministry for Science, Technology and Higher Education. The website set up for Open Science in Portugal, describes the four pillars of the policy to be:

- (1) transparency in practices, methodology, observation, and data collection,
- (2) public availability and re-use of scientific data,
- (3) public access and transparency in scientific communication,
- (4) use of web-based tools to facilitate scientific collaboration.

Skills are not addressed in the document, and – given the soft, aspirational approach – compliance is not covered either, but the document is clear that the policy will continue to be developed in order to converge with international best practices, in particular with the initiatives of this domain that may be established within the European Union.

In 2016, Portugal adopted 'Fostering Scientific Employment' (Decree-Law 57/2016) aiming to improve researchers' working conditions, career prospects and promote the employment of PhD holders. The

measure was taken to overcome challenges associated with a high emigration rate of graduates and highly unstable research careers.

The Portuguese research system has a strong EU and international orientation. Policymakers and the research community are more engaged in societal challenge research priorities relevant to the national context due to the developing influence of Horizon 2020 and the JPP. Portugal participates in four JPIs, and is an observer in one more, four Article 185 initiatives, three EJPs and membership of more than 40 ERA-NETs in diverse scientific areas. Portugal has recently introduced public participation laboratories, a proposal that intends to involve citizens, local and regional actors, public and private entities in developing thematic R&I agendas contributing to the debate of public policies for science and technology and the dissemination of knowledge.

The Foundation for Science and Technology. FCT supports the scientific community in Portugal through a range of funding schemes, tailored for individual scientists, research teams or R&D centres. Through its funding schemes, FCT supports graduate education, research and development, establishment and access to research infrastructures, networking and international collaborations, conferences and meetings, science communication and interactions with industry. With regards to digital research infrastructures there are currently 4 underway in Portugal:

- INCD Portuguese National Distributed Computing Infrastructure
- RCTS Science, Technology and Society Network
- RNCA National Advance Computing Network
- UC-LCA Laboratory for Advanced Computing

SWITZERLAND

Switzerland has a modern, coherent legal basis regarding the legal rights relating to data, access to data and data handling. Switzerland is establishing a modern and coherent legal basis for exploiting the potential of the data economy.

Policies for Open Access in Switzerland are being developed by the research institutions, scientific academies and by the national funding organizations, with the complementary support of the government. As most Swiss research institutions signed the Berlin declaration on Open Access university libraries now run repositories enabling access of pre-prints and digital copies of PhD theses. Additionally, the main national funding agency, SNSF, endorsed a policy for open access.

The Swiss national strategy for Open Access (OA) to publications aims at ensuring the cost transparency for public funds and the coordination among stakeholders, especially higher education institutions and their libraries. The time horizon of this national strategy covers the period 2021-2028. It will be implemented across two national action plans, one for the period 2021-2024 (including the Open Access Action Plan 2021-2024), and another one for the period 2025-2028. The Swiss National Strategy on OA aims to achieve the following objective, in accordance with international benchmarks: by 2024, all scholarly publication activity in Switzerland should be OA, all scholarly publications funded by public money must be freely accessible on the internet. The OA landscape will consist of a mix of OA models.

The objectives for the period 2021-2024 include a) improving shareability and interpretability, b) leveraging decentralisation and diversity, c) strengthening the dialogue between science and the society and d) adopting Openness and FAIRness.

The main stakeholders involved with the Swiss Research, Data, and Open science area include:

- The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) supports scientific research in all academic disciplines, from history to medicine and the engineering sciences. At the end of 2019, the SNSF was funding 5750 projects involving 18,900 researchers, which makes it the leading Swiss institution for promoting scientific research.
- The Federal Council Dispatch on the promotion of education, research, and innovation for 2017-2020 as approved by the Swiss global network for education, research, and innovation
- The Swiss Science and Innovation Council (SSIC) as the advisory body to the Federal Council for issues related to science, higher education, research, and innovation policy. The goal of the SSIC, in conformity with its role as an independent consultative body, is to promote the framework for the successful development of the Swiss higher education, research and innovation system.

Research infrastructure in Switzerland is publicly or privately owned and is structured or implemented in a medium- or long-term manner (usually more than 10 years). The 2019 Swiss Roadmap for Research Infrastructures provides an overview of newly planned national infrastructures and of Switzerland's participation in international research infrastructures. It also reviews the progress made in realising the infrastructures proposed in the 2015 Roadmap. It is one of the documents forming the basis for drawing up the 2021–2024 ERI Dispatch and the dispatch on funding for the EU framework programmes (EU Dispatch) in the coming years. In the roadmap among the 41 research infrastructures proposed, 23 have been put in the highest priority group and will be funded for the 2017-2020 period. The total financial volume of these initiatives amounts to around 700 million CHF. The RI's are strongly oriented towards natural sciences, engineering (particularly IT) and health data. Funding for these infrastructures will be provided by the institutions themselves, ETH board, and through university cooperation projects. According to the Swiss Roadmap for Research Infrastructures 2019, the main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes include: a) High-Performance Computing and Networking (HPCN-24), b) Common Data Centre for Astronomy, Astroparticle and Cosmology (CDCI), and c) Swiss Centre for Musculoskeletal Biobanking and Imaging and Clinical Movement Analysis.

THE NETHERLANDS

The Netherlands is widely considered a leader in Open Science policies because of its principal role in the formulation of the FAIR-principles, and in the design of the European Open Science Cloud.

1. The National Plan for Open Science is the main policy document driving initiatives towards transition to an Open Science system. The plan concentrates on three areas:
 - Promoting open access to scientific publications (open access).
 - Promoting optimal use and reuse of research data.
 - Adapting evaluation and award systems to bring them into line with the objectives of open science (reward systems).
2. A major step in the Policy implementation is the establishment of the National Platform for Open Science (NPOS) which brings together the parties that have initiated, formulated, or support the National Plan. T
3. The Digital Society Research Agenda, formulated by the joint Dutch universities (VSNU) in accordance with the Dutch National Research Agenda, elaborates seven programme lines underlying universities' joint efforts towards a futureproofing education in a digital society.
4. VSNU has also published the Digitization in Academic Education agenda for a future-proof range of degree programmes, identifying 10 points for actions to take full advantage of the opportunities for the digitisation of education.

5. The Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO) has published its 2019-2022 Strategy “Connecting Science and Society” which promotes the Open Science principles, acknowledges the importance of new skills and describes initiatives for further developing high-grade ICT infrastructures
6. Regarding Data related policies, the government published the Data Agenda (NL Digitaal) which sets out how data can be used (even) better to improve policy-making and resolve social issues and recognizes that to adopt a data-driven approach, the government must strongly invest in enhancing special digital skills of persons involved and focus on establishing a change in corporate and employee culture, identifying relevant action plans such as the professional development programs and a Data Science training scheme.

Netherlands has a strong Open Data culture backed up by both legal and policy documents and best practices. The country is also promoting several developments regarding awarding of good research and could provide a possible model training and subsequent accreditation on research integrity rewards, which is currently lacking at EU level.

The Dutch government officially adopted an Open Access policy with respect to publications in 2013. Article 25fa of the Copyright Act allows researchers to share short scientific works (e.g. articles & book chapters), regardless of any restrictive publishers' guidelines.

The Open Science Policy is supported by a wealth of research institutes and organizations belonging to a rich R&D ecosystem (government, higher education, private-public partnerships, and technology service providers).

Regarding digital infrastructures, the country is well advanced and is still investing in its expansion.

Finally, Netherlands enjoys strong links between the Research Community and the Industry scoring high in all relevant indicators.

5 Main Findings of the digital skills mapping in the selected countries

The major findings of the research, in the selected countries, can be summarised as follows:

1. Governance fragmentation & diverse priorities in digital skills upgrade

- There seems to be a **fragmentation** regarding the establishment of a governance system for the upgrade of digital skills
- Many efforts and initiatives are in progress, however, **no single approach is identified**
- **Focus is given in different target groups** per country, mainly addressing public services users, schools, students and teachers, labour force, and business digital transformation

2. Absence of an integrated framework for the establishment of the competent national policy

- The **identification of the most suitable approach** for digital skills upgrade to target is difficult
- It is most influenced by the fact that the administration composition and the competent authorities in each country differ
- This stresses upon the **need to establish national strategies with an integrated overview of objectives**

3. Absence of a stand-alone national strategy for digital skills in almost all countries assessed

- The existence of an institutional framework (at national level) and the establishment of the competent national strategy seem to facilitate the implementation and the follow up of the embedded activities for digital skills and digital literacy
- Digital skills ecosystems are complex. In many cases, the **priorities of different actors of the ecosystem lay in silos in relation to open science and open data**

4. Diversification in the participation of stakeholders per country

- **No single pattern related to the stakeholder's synthesis** participating in the ecosystem of digital skills upgrade is identified.
- **National Coalitions gather a variety of stakeholders and represent the point of reference for the coordination of all disparate policies and initiatives.** Even though not always active, they seem to represent the driver for the next step for the majority of initiatives being integrated in a single strategy

5. A lot of training under progress

- **Many training programmes are identified**, for several target groups, both in the public and private sector
- **Universities** offer a variety of post-graduate studies in data/bid data and statistics.
- **National Information Societies and Digital Academies** also play an important role in training

6. A single certification framework acknowledged

- In a formally established or less formally working framework, **DigComp is endorsed**, in almost all countries assessed, as the Competence Framework related to certification of digital skills

7. A major gap assessed in combined action for digital skills and education and digital skills and open science/open access.

- Digital Skills as well as Digital Literacy are more focused in education, labour market, and general public, whereas **data skills are most referred in open science**
- There are **disparate initiatives on digital skills upgrade required for scientists**
- The new reward and incentive systems and career paths will have to meet the **need for new data scientists and professionals** in science systems.
- So far, **it seems to be a rather fussy objectives 'setting** on what is actually needed to be targeted

8. Open Science Strategies are mostly focusing on research and infrastructure.

- **Few references were assessed in relation to digital skills.** These skills are required at multiple levels: individual scientists, research teams, institutional services, research infrastructures etc.
- **Libraries & repositories, under LIBER initiatives, play a crucial role** not only for implementing training programmes for scientists and researchers, but mainly for upgrading the necessary infrastructure and access for open data

9. FAIR Data Action Plan alignment

- It has been identified that in several scientific areas **emphasis is given to FAIR data rather than OPEN**, in alignment with the directions of the FAIR Data Action Plan

Annex I: Methodological Framework for the selection of the 9 countries

Methodology and criteria

The sound base for structuring the criteria framework for the preselection of the 12 countries that will constitute the landscape for reviewing the national Digital Skills initiatives in Europe, comes from the envisioned EOSC Skills and Training goals and priorities proposed in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). In particular, based on the SRIA's Action Area AA11 - Skills and Training and the Priority P17: Develop Open Science training and professionalise associated roles, it is apparent that the priority areas to be considered include:

1. Career Development (skills competences, accreditation system, governance model) of EOSC professionals
2. Researchers Development to open and data-intensive science
3. Bridging of Research to Industry and Society
4. Framework Setup for building and updating digital skills and learning processes (paths) fostering open and data-intensive science.

Furthermore, following a brief initial desk research, we ended up that in most countries, a concrete national strategy on digital skills and training on open science along with a dedicated governance model, either is missing or it is not fully established.

On the other hand, the above SRIA priorities refer to a broad range of policy issues which might be covered in the following national strategies

- Education and Training Policies for Digital skills and recognition
- Active labour market policies
- Employment Policies
- Digital Strategies
- Research Strategy (including Open Science).

while the Governance and Framework for Design, Monitoring & Control, and Improve Policies is under consideration as to its application to the digital skills and training policy or initiatives (if any).

Consequently, it could be considered appropriate to include in the criteria structure for the countries landscape definition, adequate progress indicators of these abovementioned policies, that cover the aspect of digital skills and training as well as to the open science. In addition, the following studies that offer a comprehensive view of the various dimensions for assessing and/or providing recommendations for digital skills and training, have been considered in the criteria framework development:

- UNESCO 2018 - Building tomorrow's digital skills - what conclusions can we draw from international comparative indicators?
- OECD Skills Outlook 2019 - THRIVING IN A DIGITAL WORLD
- OECD Strengthening the Governance of Skills Systems
- Digital skills Rethinking education and training in the digital age: Digital skills and new models for learning by PWC.

Aiming to provide a holistic view of all the factors that affect the countries status related to the digital skills and training policies especially on the EOSC focus domain of Open Science, the following criteria areas have been outlined:

1. Digital Economy and Society, in order to indicate the digital performance of a country
2. Digital Competitiveness, in order to indicate the extent to which countries adopt and explore digital technologies leading to transformation in government practices, business models and society in general
3. Impact of ICT, in order to indicate a framework to assess the multi-faceted impact of ICT on society and the development of nations

4. Future Readiness, in order to indicate the extent to which countries are ready to be more involved in digital areas, including digital skills, and advance research and open science

Overall a separate district area, the Open Science Data Repositories availability has been added.

In the light of avoiding subjective assessment concerning these criteria areas, the approach of using quantitative indexes has been followed for measuring the progress of every country in every criteria area, by providing a binary answer depending if the country's specific index is above or below the respective EU average. Given that the reliable availability of data concerning the indexes for the high majority of the countries (member states of the EU and the associated countries) was a major issue under consideration the following studies/pool of data have been finally chosen as sources of data:

- Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2020
- International Digital Economy and Society Index 2018 SMART 2017/0052
- Horizon 2020 Key Figures and Horizon 2020 country profiles
- IMD World Digital Competitiveness Ranking 2019
- Network Readiness Index 2019
- Open Science Monitor EU.

The resulting criteria framework, comprising a set of indexes, has been calibrated, leaving the most significant and synthetic indexes, as follows:

EU Member States / Associated Countries				
Main Criteria areas	Source	Criteria	Definition	Way of scoring
1. Digital Economy and Society <i>These criteria indicate the digital performance of a country</i>	Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI)	1.1 Connectivity	Average of: 1a Fixed Broadband take-up (25%), 1b Fixed broadband coverage (25%), 1c Mobile broadband (35%) and 1d Broadband price index (15%)	Above EU average score 1 "YES" 0 "NO"
		1.2 Human Capital	Average of: 2a Internet User Skills (50%) and 2b Advanced Skills and Development (50%)	
		1.3 Use of Internet Services	Average of: 3a Internet Use (25%), 3b Activities Online (50%), 3c Transactions (25%)	
		1.4 Integration of Digital Technology	Average of: 4a Business digitisation (60%) and 4b e-Commerce (40%)	
		1.5 Digital Public Services	Average of a) scope and quality of online services, status of the development of telecommunication infrastructure and inherent human capital	
		1.6 2b3 ICT graduates	People with a degree in ICT	
		1.7 2b1 ICT Specialists	Employed ICT specialists. Broad definition based on the ISCO-08 classification and including jobs like ICT service managers, ICT professionals, ICT technicians, ICT installers and servicers	
		1.8 3b6 Doing and online course	People who have used the Internet for doing an online course (on any subject)	
		1.9 5a5 Open data	To what extent countries have an Open Data policy in place (including the transposition of the revised PSI Directive), the estimated political, social and economic impact of Open Data and the characteristics (functionalities, data availability and usage) of the national data portal	
2. Digital Competitiveness <i>These criteria indicate the extent to which countries adopt and explore digital technologies leading to transformation in government practices, business models and society in general</i>	IMD World Digital Competitiveness Ranking 2019	2.1 Knowledge	Know-how necessary to discover, understand and build new technologies.	Ranking among 63 countries 1 " The country ranks in a position lower than 15" 0 "otherwise"
		2.2 Technology	Overall context that enables the development of digital technologies.	
		2.3 Total expenditure on R&D (%)	Percentage of GDP	
		2.4 Total R&D personnel per capita	Full-time work equivalent (FTE) per 1000 people	
		2.5 Scientific and technical employment	% of total employment	
		2.6 Development & application of technology	Development and application of technology are supported by the legal environment	
		2.7 Scientific research legislation	Laws relating to scientific research do encourage innovation	
3. Impact of ICT <i>These criteria indicate a framework to assess the multi-faceted impact of ICT on society and the development of nations</i>	Network Readiness Index 2019	3.1 - 1.3.1 Availability of latest technologies	Extent to which latest technologies (IoT, AI, Big Data) are available in the country	Ranking among 121 countries The country ranks in a position lower than 35: 1 "YES" 0 "NO"
		3.2 - 1.3.4 ICT Patent applications	Number of applications for information and communication technology-related patents	
		3.3 - 2.1.6 ICT Skills	Proportion of youth and adults with ICT skills	
		3.4 - 2.3.2 Publication and use of open data.	Open Data Barometer (Readiness to secure benefits of open data & extent of timely accessible open data on government & extent of positive impact by using open data)	
		3.5 - 2.3.4 R&D expenditure by governments and higher education	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D performed by government and higher education institutions (% of GDP)	
		3.6 - 3.1.5 Online trust & safety	Internet safety and cultural acceptance of the Internet	
		3.7 - 3.2.6 ICT regulatory environment	Regulatory Quality Indicator	
		3.8		
4. Future Readiness <i>These criteria indicate the extent to which countries are ready to be more involved in digital areas, including digital skills, and advance research and open science</i>	Horizon 2020 Key Figures Horizon 2020 country profiles	4.1 Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Existence of public	
		4.2 Research Strategy	Existence of public strategy/policies/intentions/action plans on research/RIS	
		4.3 Open Science Policy	Existence of public strategy/policies/intentions/action plans on open science	
		4.4 Open data access initiatives	Existence of public strategy/policies/intentions/action plans on open science	
		4.5 R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance	1 if strong innovator, else 0	
		4.6 Technological readiness (World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index: 9th pillar, technological readiness)	1 if 1-15 to , else 0	
		4.7 Open data access (Global open data index)	1 if 1-15 to , else 0 (GODI intentionally limits its inquiry to the publication of national government data)	
		4.8 Future Readiness (IMD)	Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation	
Open Science Monitor EU	5.1 Availability of open data repositories	Number of data repositories	Equal or more than the median = 1	

blended sample comprised by EU member states and associated countries in reasonable proportion. A fourth scenario has been developed to cover the suggestions of EOSC coming from the Kick of Meeting.

Country Code	Score	Geographical position	Scenario 6-6	Scenario 7-3-2	Scenario 8-4	EOSC	Proposal of 12 Countries
FI	27	N					✓✓ FI
NL	27	W					✓✓ NL
SE	27	N					
DK	26	N					✓✓ DK
UK	23	W					
IE	21	W					✓✓ IE
AT	19	C					✓ AT *alternative to Swiss
BE	19	W					
DE	19	C					
CH	19	C					✓ CH *alternative to Austria
FR	18	W					✓✓ FR
NO	17	N					✓✓ NO
LU	16	C					
EE	14	N					
SI	14	C					
CZ	13	C					
MT	13	S					
ES	11	S					
LT	11	N					✓ LT
PT	11	S					✓ PT
IS	11						
IL	9	N					
CY	8	S					
IT	8	S					
LV	8	N					
PO	8	E					✓ PO
GR	7	S					✓ GR
HU	7	E					✓ HU
RO	7	E					
HR	7	C					
SK	5	E					
BG	5	E					
MD	2	E					
RS	2	E					
AM	1						
BA	1						
GE	1						
MK	1						
TN	1						
TR	1						
UA	1						
AL	0						
FO	0						
ME	0						

12 preselected countries

The preselected 12 countries are:

- | | |
|---|--------------|
| 1. Finland | 7. Norway |
| 2. Netherlands | 8. Lithuania |
| 3. Denmark | 9. Portugal |
| 4. Ireland | 10. Poland |
| 5. Austria and Switzerland
(as <i>alternatives</i>) | 11. Greece |
| 6. France | 12. Hungary |

9 countries proposal

After a presentation to the EOSC WG and keeping the geographical distribution, the 9 proposed countries for the sample of the qualitative field research are:

1. Finland
2. Netherlands
3. Denmark
4. Switzerland
5. France
6. Lithuania
7. Portugal
8. Greece
9. Hungary

Annex II: Agenda/ List of questions for the semi-structured interviews

I. Digital Skills Domain

Purpose:

- to map the overall governance scheme in the field of digital skills and determine level of fragmentation, degree of coordination, potential overlaps, etc.
- to identify the various policy documents and their respective owners and determine if any priority is given now (or in a mid-term horizon) to areas linked with Open Science and EOSC objectives
- to determine the level of maturity of the digital skills initiatives in general, but also identify the ones most relevant to EOSC objectives (eg up-skilling for core EOSC skills)
- to identify potential infrastructures /platforms that can be exploited in national or EU level

Q1. Which are the main organizations in your country that have legal responsibility for promoting digital skills for the population (citizens, specific target groups), and for which domains?

Examples:

- Ministry of Digital Transformation / Governance / ICT
- Ministry of Education
- Ministry of Research / Development
- Ministry of Labour
- National Documentation Center
- National Coalition

Q2. Does your country have an active (or planned) national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills? If so which organization is the owner?

Examples:

- National Digital Transformation or ICT Strategy (including Data, state-of-the art technologies like AI or IoT, and Open Governance)
- National Strategy for Research & Development
- National Education Strategy
- National Coalition Action Plans

Q3. Is there a coordinating entity among them, or is there a coordination / governance mechanism established to ensure interdisciplinarity of approaches (especially to development of skills linked to EOSC related domains such as data management)? How are performance & impact measured and presented?

- Policy supervision
- Budget allocation
- Assessment of performance & impact
- Key indicators

Q4. What are the major digital skills initiatives¹⁷ that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years in your country? Are there any initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)

- Owner
- Status
- Budget

¹⁷ Includes EU funded projects

- Main objectives
- Providers / Trainers
- Target groups
- Delivery methods & tools
- Complementarity with other initiatives

Q5. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP, EOSC)? Are there any competences that could be relevant to EOSC identified actors¹⁸?

- Clear definition of target audience profiles
- Existence of competencies relevant to digital professional profiles

Q6. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorized competences? (See Q5)

Q7. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (eg digital platforms)?

II. Research, Data & Open Science Domain

Purpose:

- *To identify major actors in Scientific Research in the country (promoters and users of open science)*
- *To identify organizations that can act as “champions” in the promotion of digital skills, R&D, and innovation management with respect to Open Science principles and objectives. Determine potential fragmentation of services as well as overlaps or synergies*
- *to understand the mindset of the Research community towards Open Science principles and practices and estimate adherence to FAIR principles*
- *To determine the level of maturity of digital infrastructures and services in Research*
- *To form an opinion on how research and industry are linked*
- *To prepare the ground for the gap analysis with EOSC priorities*

Q8. Apart from the Academia, which other organizations are responsible for promoting scientific research and innovation? How are they managed? Are there overlaps or synergies in services provided related to Open Science principles?

- Digital Innovation Hubs
- Research centers
- Scientific Libraries
- (Digital) Competence Centers

Q9. To what extent does the government (in general) as well as the Research ecosystem have an Open Science / Open Data culture?

- Open Data Policy & Practices
- Data or open science related skills in university level education curricula
- Open Science Policy
- Level of Open Access in research
- Broader skill development programs or initiatives (such as IPR management, ethics, policy making, etc.)

Q10. Are there any government digital infrastructures & services (or plans to establish them) available for research purposes? Do they include FAIR elements in their design?

¹⁸ Researcher, EOSC enabler, Data scientist, Research software engineer, Data Research Infrastructure support, Data Curator, Data Steward, Citizens, Policy Makers

- Cloud servers
- Telecom networks
- High Performance Computers
- Open data repositories
- Digital libraries & platforms
- Research management-oriented software

Q11. Are there any policies to motivate and reward good research practices and quality? Are there any clearly identified career paths with accreditation systems?

- Content
- Openness
- Integrity
- Links with innovation

Q12. Are there strong links between Research community and the industry? Has the impact of adherence to open science principles lead to successful cases?

- Entities that support or promote such links
- Tools and services offered
- Performance Assessment

Q13. Is there any legislation covering or implicating compliance to the principles of Open Science?

Annex III: List of the interviewees / participants

Country	Organisation (s)	Representative/ capacity	Interview Date
Denmark	Ministry of Science and Higher Education	<i>Mr. Thomas Midtgaard</i> , Chief Advisor, EOSC GB representative (DK) - Open Science/Research Data	28 th September 2020
Denmark	Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science	<i>Mr. Michael Sandgreen</i> , Head of Section at Danish Agency for Science and Higher Education	29 th September 2020
Denmark	AALBORG University	<i>Mr. Karsten Kryger</i> Hansen, Senior Consultant, Data Management	6 th October 2020
Finland	The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies	<i>Ms. Henriikka Mustajoki</i> , National Head of Development for Open Science	25 th September 2020
Finland	Bildningsalliansen (Education Alliance)	<i>Mr. Johanni Larjanko</i> , Coordinator Bildningsalliansen, European Expert on Adult Education, National EPALE (Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe) ambassador Finland	9 th October 2020
France	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>
Greece	ATHENA Research & Innovation Centre	<i>Ms. Elli Papadopoulou</i> , Coordinator of National Open Access Desk for Greece	30 th September 2020
Greece	Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs/ Rebrain Greece	<i>Mr. Dimitris Panopoulos</i> , Coordinator of the Rebrain Greece Initiative	20 th October 2020
Hungary	University and National Library University of Debrecen	<i>Ms. Gyongyi Karacsony</i> , General Director at University and National Library University of Debrecen / NOAD of Hungary	29 th September 2020
Lithuania	Ministry of Education, Science and Sports of the Republic of Lithuania	<i>Ms. Aušra Gribauskiėnė</i> , Chief Officer in the Division of Science, Department of Higher Education, Science and Technology in the Ministry of Education, Science and Sports of the Republic of Lithuania	13 th October 2020
	Kaunas University of Technology	<i>Ms. Gintarė Tautkevičienė</i> , Director of Library of Kaunas University of Technology	
Portugal	University of Minho	<i>Mr. Eloy Rodrigues</i> , Director of the University of Minho Libraries & Member of the EOSC Landscape WG	1 st October 2020
Switzerland	University of Zurich, Institute of Biomedical Ethics & History of Medicine	<i>Mr. Markus Christen</i> , Managing Director of the “Digital Society Initiative” and Research Group Leader at the Institute of Biomedical Ethics and History of Medicine of the University of Zurich.	27 th October 2020
The Netherlands	Delft University of Technology	<i>Mr. Karel Luyben</i> , Rector Magnificus Emeritus of the Delft University of Technology, Chairman of the Executive Board of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	28 th September 2020
The Netherlands	Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences	<i>Mr. Dr. Ruben Kok</i> , Co-Founder, Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences	30 th September 2020
The Netherlands	University of Amsterdam	<i>Ms Karen Maex</i> , Rector Magnificus of the University of Amsterdam	23 rd October 2020

Annex IV: Landscape of National Coalitions for Digital Skills and Jobs

National Coalitions for Digital Skills and Jobs are **partnerships between digital skills actors**, who work together to improve digital skills at national, regional or local level. There are currently **24 Coalitions** in the MS.

1. Belgium	2. Bulgaria	3. Croatia	4. Cyprus	5. Czech Republic	6. Denmark
Objective					
To improve, in an inclusive way, Belgians' command of digital skills for current and future jobs	To attract more people to new Technologies and to support the development of the ICT sector in Bulgaria	To harvest the growing potential of the ICT sector in Croatia and getting more skilled ICT professionals trained in Croatia	To promote the diffusion and the improvement of digital skills to address the mismatch between a low number of ICT professionals and higher number of vacancies	Raising the digital literacy of all Czech citizens through the promotion of digital skills in education, and digital skills in the labour market	To gather, strengthen and develop the skills and professionalism of IT users and IT professionals
Priorities					
1. Digitalchampions.Be 2. Digital Inclusion for all 3. Mobile Internet For Everyone	1. Breaking ICT stereotypes 2. More people with digital skills 3. More women in the tech world 4. Digitally intelligent future generation (Coding4all)	1. Digitally mature education & science for a competitive economy 2. Increasing the number of ICT experts	1. Education / Training 2. Certification 3. Awareness	1. Increasing digital literacy and digital skills of Czech citizens, 2. increasing the competitiveness of the Czech economy	1. Digital learning and teaching 2. Digital skills for children and young people 3. Digital competences for public employees
Share of activities					
ICT professionals = 30% Education = 25% All Citizens = 35% Labour Force =10%	ICT professionals = 10% Education = 60% All Citizens = 10% Labour Force =20%	ICT professionals = 55% Education = 25% All Citizens = 10% Labour Force =10%	ICT professionals = 10% Education = 70% All Citizens = 10% Labour Force =10%	ICT professionals = 20% Education =40% All Citizens = 20% Labour Force = 20%	ICT professionals = 5% Education = 10% All Citizens = 60% Labour Force = 25%
7. Estonia	8. France	9. Greece	10. Hungary	11. Ireland	12. Italy
Objective					
To bridge the digital skills gap by focusing on programmes that can train large portions of the population	To reduce the digital skills gap in France	To promote digital skills in education through coding to and to promote digital skills and IT career for women and girls	To find solutions for tackling the shortage of digitally skilled people in the Hungarian labour market	To promote inclusion for continuous integral improvement of digitisation	To educe the phenomenon of digital illiteracy and to increase the percentage of ICT specialists
Priorities					
1. Incorporating a digital culture into the learning process 2. Supporting digital learning in schools. 3. Accessing a modern digital infrastructure for learning	1. Reducing the digital skills gap; 2. Increasing ICT professional 3. Raising the level of digital skills of SMEs	1. Promote Digital Skills in Educational & Life- Long Learning 2. Promoting e-skills through RTDI activities 3. Innovation Hub for Women in Technology	No citizen, small enterprise or public administration officer should be excluded from the digital ecosystem	1. Cooperation between education and industry 2. Leverage competence frameworks, Digcomp, e-CF etc. 3. Alternative approaches to careers in IT	Promote the development of skills for digital and emerging technologies, with innovative training formats and workshops with universities, research centers and IT companies
Share of activities					
ICT professionals = 0% Education = 10% All Citizens = 80% Labour Force = 10%	ICT professionals = 30% Education = 10% All Citizens = 10% Labour Force =50%	ICT professionals= 34% Education =2% Citizens in general = 30% Labour force = 30%	ICT professionals = 30% Education = 35% All Citizens = 5% Labour Force = 30%	ICT professionals = 30% Education = 25% All Citizens = 25% Labour Force =20%	N/A

13. Latvia	14. Lithuania	15. Luxembourg	16. Malta	17. The Netherlands	18. Poland
Objective					
To achieve a more effective use of digital potential and cooperate in implementing the 2014-2020 Digital Agenda for Lithuania	To improve the quality of life for the Lithuanian population, using ICT, and increasing the efficiency of the SMEs	To close the digital skills gap in Luxembourg	To contribute to the expansion of ICT educational programmes and to promote the Maltese eSkills potential	Ensuring citizens at all levels are ready for the digital transformation and coding /digital skills become a cornerstone of the education curricula	To promote the development of Poland by using the full potential of available modern ICT and transforming all aspects of the society and economy
Priorities					
1. To reduce the shortage of IT professionals 2. To attract more young people to choose ICT and other science studies and professions	1. To reduce the digital divide of Lithuanian people 2. To encourage the citizens to choose ICT-related professions and studies	Promoting actions and measures for improving Digital Skills in Education, for the Labour Force, for ICT Professionals and for the citizens	1. IT teaching professionals and guidance 2. Quality in curriculum design 3. A framework for grading and evaluating digital competence	1. Skill development at field labs 2. Digitisation for the primary and secondary education sectors 3. Digital skills in the workplace	1. To enhance university digital skills education 2. To increase the number of ICT professionals
Share of activities					
ICT professionals = 23% Education = 27% All Citizens = 18% Labour Force = 32%	ICT professionals = 20% Education = 10% All Citizens = 50% Labour Force = 20%	N/A	ICT professionals = 30% Education = 30% All Citizens = 20% Labour Force = 20%	ICT professionals = 20% Education = 50% All Citizens = 15% Labour Force = 15%	ICT professionals = 20% Education = 50% All Citizens = 15% Labour Force = 15%
19. Portugal	20. Romania	21. Slovakia	22. Slovenia	23. Spain	24. Sweden
Objective					
Raising the digital competences of all Portuguese citizens to better respond to challenges of the digital society	Ensuring eInclusion by developing digital literacy - e-skills by supporting the development of ICT Skills	To improve the digital skills of citizens, IT specialists, all employees and in education	Improve e-skills, e-inclusion and the overall quality of life for the population	Promote digital inclusion and literacy and the training of new ICT professionals	Fostering the digital transformations among individuals, firms and in the government
Priorities					
Providing the conditions for the production of new knowledge and an active participation in international R&D networks and programmes	1. Rolling out coding and IT classes in schools, organising cybersecurity courses and educational events 2. Upgrade digital skills of the labour force	1. Development of skills in science/ technology 2. Promoting career paths and opportunities offered by the ICT sector	1. Improved digital literacy of population 2. Improved e-competencies and e-skills of the population 3. Improved e-skills for the use of ICT for new digital jobs	1. Digital training and education of new ICT professionals 2. Digital inclusion and literacy	1. Raising training incentives for individuals and firms to boost ICT skills. 2. Promoting ICT courses in education. 3. Reskilling with social partners.
Share of activities					
ICT professionals = 25% Education = 25% All Citizens = 25% Labour Force = 25%	ICT professionals = 40% Education = 30% All Citizens = 15% Labour Force = 15%	ICT professionals = 30% Education = 30% All Citizens = 10% Labour Force = 30%	ICT professionals = 20% Education = 30% All Citizens = 25% Labour Force = 25%	ICT professionals = 35% Education = 35% All Citizens = 10% Labour Force = 20%	ICT professionals = % Education = % All Citizens = % Labour Force = %

Annex V: Country Reports

<p>Denmark</p>	<p>Denmark, the smallest country in Scandinavia, has been widely recognised as one of the most advanced digital economies in the EU. Ranked in the DESI scale as the fourth most digitally advanced economy in Europe, there is plenty to learn from Denmark when it comes to digitalisation. One area in which Denmark has particularly excelled, in relation to other frontrunner countries, is in its effort to ensure that all citizens benefit from digitalisation. 95% of Danes are online - well above the European average - while half of those aged 65 or above have basic digital skills (DESI). This success is driven by the country's focus on fostering innovation through partnerships and collaboration, sharing best practice and learning from others. Even though Denmark is among the most digitized nations, research shows that more than 1 million Danish citizens aged 16 to 65 years of age are lacking in digital skills. In the ICT sector, Denmark also has a critical skills gap, which seems to be growing looking into the future. Therefore, some of the main challenges that Denmark faces are the stagnating supply of ICT professionals, while demand is growing, the projection stated in Europe's Digital Progress Report (2017) that the Danish companies will face a deficit of 19,000 employees with digital skills by 2030 as well as maintaining a steady supply of expertise which is crucial to Denmark's continued success.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?		
Yes	No	In planning
	X	
Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>Digitalisation strategies have been created at national, regional, and municipal levels, and the strategies are often cross-sectoral, as is the case in the field of education. A strategic priority for Denmark is that "Everyone should be equipped to operate in the digital transformation", although no national strategy on Digital Skills is in place. Digital Skills Policies are implemented in the form of a) Education and vocational training b) Company training and partnerships and c) Lifelong Learning. In 2017, an agreement has been set up between the government and social partners on strengthening adult continuing education and making it more flexible, that emphasized that the system for adult continuing education (the VEU system) must support increased efforts to boost the basic skills level of the workforce in the future to a much greater extent than today in order to meet the companies' needs and demands.</p> <p>The key policies/strategies that include priorities related to the promotion of digital skills are</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Digital Strategy 2016–2020: A Stronger and More Secure Digital Denmark (2016) sets the course for Danish public sector digitalisation efforts and their interaction with businesses and industries and includes 33 initiatives. It is a joint strategy created collaboratively by the government, municipalities, and regions, which therefore binds all levels of public administration. It promotes digitalisation for everyone, especially for young and children, intervening in the educational system. • Joint municipal and regional digital strategies and sector-specific strategies are also available, such as the Strategy for Digital Welfare 2013–2020 that accelerates the use of ICT and welfare technology in front-line public service delivery. 		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With the <u>Strategy for Denmark’s Digital Growth</u>, the government establishes directions for Denmark to create the best framework to enable businesses to utilise the opportunities inherent in digital transformation. The strategy has three overall objectives: 1. trade and industry must tap into the potential for growth inherent in digitalisation to ensure that Danish businesses are among the best in Europe when it comes to the use of digital technology; 2. creating the best conditions for digital transformation of business, including addressing regulatory barriers; and 3. a goal for the Danish people to become the most digitally prepared within the EU, ready to operate in the digital transformation, with education and continuous training to ensure that everyone is ready for the labour market of the future. To assist in achieving the objectives, there are six main strategic focus areas, as follows: 1. establish a digital hub for stronger digital growth; 2. digital enhancement of SMEs; 3. ensure digital skills for all; 4. utilise data as a driver of growth in trade and industry; 5. agile regulation of trade and industry; and 6. Strengthened cybersecurity in companies. A total of 38 specific initiatives are introduced with the Digital Growth Strategy. DKK 75 million has been allocated in 2018, followed by DKK 125 million each year until 2025 and DKK 75 million in perpetuity for the implementation of the strategy’s initiatives. • The <u>Danish Cyber and Information Security Strategy</u> (2018) with 25 initiatives aims to strengthen government security, improve the competences of the population, and ensure more coordinated efforts in the information security space. Furthermore, in early 2019 the government launched strategies to improve cyber and information security in critical sectors, i.e. the telecommunications, financial, energy, healthcare, transport, and maritime. • The National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence and the Research and Innovation Strategy encompass measures in order to improve digital competence of the population <p>Also, a new Legislation named ‘Digital-Ready’ was enacted in 2018. Some challenges to be addressed refer to the regulatory barriers that seem to be slowing progress in Denmark’s education system, clarifying the governmental responsibility into driving progress in digital learning, promoting online and distance-learning courses followed by improved accreditation and enhancing organizational support.</p>
Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved
<p>Many Danish actors share responsibility for progress in the country’s digitalisation efforts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Agency for digitalisation under the auspices of the Ministry of Finance, 2011 is responsible for the implementation of digitalisation in the public sector • The Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs and the Danish Business Authority are responsible for business-focused digital initiatives in co-operation with several ministries, e.g., the Ministry of Higher Education and Science • The Government’s Disruption Council is a Partnership for Denmark’s Future on how to maintain a robust labour market when many jobs are transformed by digitalisation

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?		
Yes	No	In planning
	X	
Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>There is not a single organisation or other authority that can claim to be the national coordinating mechanism for the digital skills policies in Denmark. Yet, there are some initiatives, entities and partnerships which perform monitoring and coordinating work on digital skills policies as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Danish Technology Pact (Teknologipagten) was formed in 2018 as an initiative of the Strategy for Denmark Digital Growth (2018). Led by the Ministry for Economic Affairs, the 		

initiative is a partnership between the Danish government, the business community and educational institutions. The Technology Pact is a national collective effort to ensure that more people (particularly young people) are choosing to engage in technical and digital education programmes, in order to match the private sector's demand for STEM skills and competencies. The Technology Pact will result in more than 150,000 children, adolescents and adults and 250 companies being engaged by 2020, 20% more Danes having higher education degrees within STEM, and 20% more obtaining STEM vocational education within 10 years

- The **Danish National Coalition** defines common objectives, invites relevant parties to join and to co-create an action plan to bridge the skill gap. The **Committee for Digital Competencies of the Danish Computer Society**, DANSK IT, which stands as the coordinator for the **Danish National Coalition for digital skills and training**, was formed in 2014 and has (among other things) published a "Manifesto for digital literacy" which has served as an inspiration for policymakers regarding the need for reflective digital skills and critical thinking.
- A) **Teknologipagten (the Technology Covenant)** is a collaboration between the government, private companies, educational institutions, organizations and other stakeholders, with the aim to strengthen the population's competencies in technology, ICT, engineering, natural science and mathematics via various projects and activities. This is accomplished, by running or supporting projects in the field of continuing education, or by establishing local or industry-specific collaborative actions on continuing education for both employees and the unemployed.

Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation

Indexes for measurement and performance assessment of the policies are inherent elements of the Danish policy documents themselves

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 10% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 5% towards ICT professionals, 25% towards the labour force and 60% towards citizens in general. Many initiatives are in place or have been completed in the near past, while the most important ones are the following:

- a) The Digital Hub Denmark¹⁹ is an independent organisation and public private partnership between the Danish Government, the Confederation of Danish Industry, the Danish Chamber of Commerce and Finance Denmark. It was formed in 2018 to support and strengthen the digital growth environment in Denmark by facilitating collaboration across private companies, researchers, and tech-entrepreneurs. There are 4 core elements to the programme:
 - A digital platform, where members are matched according to specific challenges
 - A national centre for research in digital technologies
 - Conferences and trial projects, to improve the commercial use of data and new digital technologies for new services and business models
 - International marketing, to raise awareness of Denmark's digital growth environment
 By 2019, the Digital Hub Denmark has provided work for roughly 1,000 IT specialists and students on projects lasting 3-6 months, and it created a framework for outreach and activities including workshops, talks and networking events
- b) The *SME Digital* initiative addresses the digital competence challenges that SMEs in particular are facing. SME: Digital will focus on business needs by offering economic support to SMEs seeking private consultancy and assistance in the development of digital transformation business cases, better potential for e-commerce and e-exports via an e-commerce centre, improving the skills of business leaders and a digital design consultancy

¹⁹ <https://digitalhubdenmark.dk/>

<p>Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)</p>
<p>Several initiatives that focus on up-skilling for Science and Research are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Danish inter-institutional project Skills and Competencies for Open Science and Digital Literacy in Danish Research Libraries was implemented from March 2018 - May 2020. The project designed a competency matrix that describes three levels of competence within all aspects of Open Science as defined by FOSTER's taxonomy. For each competence level, courses and other training materials were added. The aim is to provide an inspirational catalogue that will enable library managers and staff to identify competencies and reach the desired level of proficiency in the respective Open Science Activity. (https://libguides.cbs.dk/c.php?g=676835&p=4822103) • The Digital Skills for Library staff and Researchers LIBER Working Group conducted a selection process in 2018 in order to identify Open Science training programmes relying on skills identification. In April 2019, questionnaires were sent out in 28 countries, and complementary interviews were conducted for the production of country-specific case studies on Open Science skilling and training initiatives in Europe. The objective of this activity is to offer the research library community a selective landscape of inspiring methods, practices, contacts, and words of wisdom, covering institutional cases, national initiatives as well as European project approaches. Budget: 4 million Danish kroner (approximately €535,000)

D. Current Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?		
Yes	No	In planning
		X
Key features of the digital competence framework established Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>At present, there is no formal integral digital competence framework. Although, It is worth noticing that the Centre for Digital Dannelselse (Digital Literacy digitaldannelselse.org) has created the "Digital Competency Wheel 1", "Digital Competency Wheel 2" to assess, to provide an overview and to improve the most relevant digital skills. The work is based on DigComp as a theoretical framework.</p> <p>Furthermore, the Digital Strategy 2016-2020 puts emphasis on the Digital Competences for Public Employees. In particular, public employees should be qualified to deal with the digital requirements of the future. The digitalisation goals of Danish university colleges will therefore be followed through and there will be special efforts to enhance digital teaching skills for teachers and child carers. Furthermore, every public employee will be continuously informed about the requirements for information security. Digital competences for teachers are being further enhanced. The existing range of preparatory adult education (whose Danish acronym is FVU) was extended to include FVU-Digital, aiming to enable teachers to perform the digital tasks that are relevant to their job function, as to use relevant digital tools, communicate digitally, search information digitally and organize, structure and manage data. Specific new modules in the educational diploma curriculum (Padagogisk Diplomuddannelsen) have been prepared in order to enhance competencies for teachers teaching FVU-Digital. Therefore, the new FVU Executive Order, contains provisions and curricula for different subjects, came into effect January 1, 2019.</p> <p>Even though, some of the adults with low levels of qualifications, are not reached by the new FVU-Digital offering as it is aimed at people in employment, where the employer is prepared to support the employees' competence development directly or indirectly. Those adults with low levels of</p>		

qualifications, elderly people, the unemployed, immigrants and employees who choose not to participate in continuing education are over-represented in the group of those with insufficient levels of basic skills.

D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework

Key challenges in case of absence

Denmark has a bipartite accreditation system. A) The **Danish Accreditation Institution plays a crucial part in ensuring the quality and relevance of higher education programmes across the country**. The Danish Accreditation Institution is responsible for conducting the accreditation processes and development of the method they follow. The decision-making is the responsibility of the Accreditation Council. Through accreditations and dissemination of knowledge about transversal topics linked to higher education, aim to support the enhancement of educational quality in the higher education sector and to help create a more coherent and transparent education market. The Danish Accreditation Institution is an academically independent authority within the state administration established to contribute to the assurance and enhancement of quality at Danish higher education through accreditation of institutions and a limited amount of either new programmes that the institutions wish to establish or existing programmes. B) The **various qualifications offered in the Danish education and training system are organized in accordance with the national qualifications framework** set out below. The Danish qualifications framework for lifelong learning was developed by an interdepartmental working group with representatives from four separate ministries, as well as some other stakeholders from the Danish education system. At the end of 2006, the Minister for Education launched a project to draw up a Danish national qualifications' framework. A proposal was approved in 2009 to place existing qualifications in the framework and was completed at the end of 2010. In total, the Danish qualifications framework has eight levels covering all levels from the leaving examination of primary and lower secondary school to the PhD degree. It also covers supplementary qualifications, such as adult VET.

Only officially recognized, validated and quality-assured programmes are included in the qualification's framework. Informal and non-formal learning are only recognized to the extent that they are formalized through a process of the validation of prior learning corresponding to one of the included qualifications. Quality assurance mechanisms are part of the validation process when it comes to including new qualifications in the framework. In terms of VET, trade committees (at the upper-secondary level) and further education and training committees (adult VET) assess programmes and make recommendations for their placement in the framework to be approved by the Ministry of Education. For each educational field, guidelines have been produced to aid committees in their assessment and quality-assured through consultation with independent experts. Procedures and criteria for including VET qualifications in the framework are the subject of an evaluation report compiled by the Danish Evaluation Institute.

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills

Key challenges in case of absence

Denmark has not only covered digital skills in the VET curriculum but has also created courses solely focused on digital and ICT professions. In fact, the website IT-formidler.dk was created to support the many initiatives around the country aimed at improving Danish IT skills. This web site primarily

aims at giving the opportunity to every teacher in the country to share experiences, produce educational materials and retrieve teaching modules. The site was launched in March 2009 as part of the project “Learn More”. The Agency for Digitalisation, Ministry of Finance, is responsible for the website.

Furthermore, the DTU Learn for Life centre, established in April of this year, aims to become the Technical University of Denmark’s central platform for continuing education, and will provide knowledge, support, and assistance to partners about lifelong learning. It is a collaborative effort between DTU departments, central administration, and strategic partners. The centre was initiated to showcase DTU's innovative technologies and expertise, both within Denmark and to the rest of the world. The Learn for Life centre provides a range of continuing education programmes to partners of DTU; both long- and short-term studies, including subjects such as AI, machine learning and data analytics. The centre also supports DTU's customers in the fields of business, government, and other organisations, with advice and knowledge about lifelong learning and professional development. The opening of the Learn for Life Centre has led to the creation of a new and ambitious strategy for continuing education and lifelong learning at DTU. This strategy will be adopted by DTU’s Executive Board in the autumn of 2019. The ITTA platform which is an open e-learning platform, contains adaptive assessment, learning and certification. The platform can be used as a standalone solution or as blended learning and complementary to existing programmes (e.g. the national workforce education programme). A “freemium based” competence scan that assesses the gap between your ICT profile and each one personal skills. Digitalisation courses offered through local libraries²⁰.

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country
Key challenges in case of absence

Denmark has high-quality data sets and registries which are quite unique in an international perspective. In 2011, Denmark joined the international initiative “Open Government Partnership” (OGP), which serves to promote good governance and strengthen democracy by promoting transparent and inclusive governance among the currently 75 participating countries.

Denmark does not have an integrated Open Science Policy. Although, it is in place a national Open Access Strategy and a national strategy for Research data management. The Open Access strategy states that the implementation of Open Access is to take place through the green model, i.e. parallel filling of quality-assured research articles in institutional or subject-specific archives (repositories) with Open Access. The implementation of the Open Access is to support the possibility for Danish researchers to continue to publish in the most recognized national and international journals, and also the possibility to publish. The strategy, being a national one, is quite wide-ranging, covering both data and the software/protocols necessary to re-run experiments (although not publications, which are mentioned only in passing), noting also the need to foster research data management skills. The goal is 100% Open Access to publicly funded research publications by 2025. Each of the 8 Danish universities has their own local Open Science Support Unit, typically based at the university libraries. All the universities have local research support units, who in various degrees support researchers with their award applications and reporting. Six out of eight higher-education institutions have an

²⁰ <https://www.ekurser.nu/https://dit.dk/dsjc>

Open Access policy, while the seventh is working to implement a more comprehensive Open Science policy.

As part of the Digital Strategy 2016-2020, the government published a common public sector White Paper on Architecture for Digitalisation in June 2017. The architecture ensures cross-organisational processes and efficient sharing of data across the public sector and between the public and private sectors. Another policy that promotes open data is the Digital Health Strategy 2018-2022

The Danish government launched its National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence on 14 March 2019, which puts emphasis on an ethical and human-centred approach to artificial intelligence. The strategy aims to promote the responsible use of artificial intelligence within both the public and private sector as well as strengthening research and development of AI solutions. The strategy aims to reach these goals through 20 initiatives covering four focus areas: a) a responsible foundation for artificial intelligence, b) more and better data, c) strong competences and new knowledge and d) increased investment in artificial intelligence.

Noteworthy initiatives are the presentation of six ethical principles for the use of artificial intelligence, better access to public data as well as the development of a common Danish language resource to support and accelerate the development of language-technology solutions in Danish.

In May 2017, the Danish local, regional, and central governments agreed on a common Framework for Federal Digital Architecture (FDA) including a number of reference architectures that focuses on data sharing, cross-organisational processes, and a coherent IT-infrastructure. In spring 2019 guidelines on architecture description including common rules for concept and data modelling v.2.0 were established. The framework is supported by skill-development, architecture guidance and project reviews.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

The Ministry of Higher Education and Science manages and monitors the Danish Open Access strategy, while DeiC is working on national structure for RDM support and training. A National Forum for Data Management was formed in 2015, with representatives from the Danish universities and national libraries and a secretariat from DeiC. Its vision is "to promote academic and research initiatives in research data management within universities and link them in a national and international cooperation." Furthermore, the government created a Data Ethical Council in early 2019 to facilitate a public debate about i.e. the use of technology, data, and AI in both the public and private sector. The council includes members from universities and think tanks as well as the public and private sector. Besides, the Danish Centre for Applied Artificial Intelligence²¹ () aims to offer Danish companies easy access to cutting-edge expertise in machine learning, artificial intelligence and big data by supporting networks and collaboration in the field and offering access to data platforms and human resources.

E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes

Key challenges in case of absence

Denmark's digital infrastructure and attitudes towards digitalisation are some of the best in Europe. The publication, "Danish Roadmap for Research Infrastructure 2015", presents the Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science's vision and strategic objectives for this policy area over the coming five years. At the same time, it presents a catalogue of specific proposals for national infrastructures, which in the short term are recommended as investment prospects. The main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes in Denmark include:

- CERN-UP – Upgrading infrastructure for CERN experiments and computing
- QUANTECH – Quantum Technology Infrastructure

²¹ <https://alexandra.dk/uk/cases/danish-centre-applied-artificial-intelligence>

- BICLabs – Behaviour, Interaction and Cognition Labs
- DigHumLab 2.0 – Digital Humanities Lab Denmark
- DRDS – Danish Research Data for the Social Sciences
- FiberLab – New Fibre Composites Laboratory

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry

Key challenges in case of absence

There is a strong link between research community and the industry, implemented via partnerships such as the Technology Pact and the Digital Hub Denmark. According to the European Research Area (ERA) Progress Report for the period 2016-2018, what is probably Denmark's most noteworthy performance is the number of public-private collaborative papers per capita. A relativized count of 163 such papers was about four times higher than the EU-28 benchmark of 41 papers. On the share of firms cooperating with governmental, public, or private research institutes, Denmark decreased at a yearly average of more than 20 %, a marked loss of ground to the other Member States for whom the trend has been of moderate yearly increase. A report from the Ministry of Higher Education and Science showed that the number of businesses that engaged in collaborative activities decreased in 2014 and 2015 after a period of 2010-2014 that has seen regular increases. Despite this negative development, Danish RPOs are redesigning their technology transfer offices based on a more collaborative and interactive model. Some organisations invest in shared facilities to facilitate closer cooperation and create a space for researchers and businesses to come together. Another driving force behind this was the renegotiated (in 2016) university performance contracts for 2015-2017 that included further performance targets on knowledge transfer activities.

<p>Finland</p>	<p>Finland is among the most advanced digital economies in the EU and has a history of ranking high on the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), including the 3rd place in 2018, with a 73.8 overall performance score in 2018. It has the highest scores in human capital, integration of digital technology and digital public services, ranking 1st, 2nd, and 1st respectively in 2018. Finland is well known for its world-class education system from primary school to lifelong education and training, which is reflected in its high rankings across the board in digital learning indicators, having one of the highest scores on the Women in Digital Scoreboard (WID 2020). The Finnish education system is one of the best globally and ICT specialists’ share of the workforce (6.7%) is one the highest as well. Digital skills remain the strongest competitive advantage of the Finnish economy. Besides, it is roughly believed that Finland needs to reskill 1 million people within the next ten years, that is a challenge to be addressed since Finland aims to be known as a front runner in technological advances, innovative procurement and the culture of experimentation.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

<p>A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?</p>		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
<p>Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences Key challenges in case of absence</p>		
<p>Finland is in the vanguard of education, skills, and modern learning techniques, holding the 3rd place in digital learning readiness across the EU-27. Finland aims to be known as a front runner in technological advances, innovative procurement, and the culture of experimentation, making all public services available digitally to individuals and businesses by 2023. In 2025, in the age of artificial intelligence, Finland aims to become the most relevantly educated nation, which will provide its people with protection against the wind of technological change. According to the Ministry of Education and Culture, the education system must be modified, both vocational education and training and higher education. Additionally, more investments should be made in updating the skills of workers already in the labour market, and the lifelong learning system should be reformed.</p> <p>The main Finnish digitalisation policies and strategies are the Digital Finland Framework, the Artificial Intelligence strategy, the digitalisation, experimentation and Deregulation programme for public sector ICT, and the digital transformation programme for the regional government, health and social services reform.</p> <p>The Digital Finland Framework (2018) ensures future-oriented digital skills for all, by increasing the share of mathematics and science in all education levels, from elementary school to universities, by encouraging the use of Mass Open Online Courses (MooC) and the train-the-trainee approach for digital skills in education but also in companies, by promoting the digital professional and by strengthening the research-company co-operation.</p> <p>The Artificial Intelligence Programme 2025 launched on 2019, gives special attention to the field’s innovation activities, preparedness for changes to working life, increasing education, and upgrading the qualifications of those in the labour market. In particular, according to the recent work in the age of artificial intelligence, the policy recommendations on skills and training on AI, include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elementary skills in preparation for the artificial intelligence era for everyone • High-quality vocational education and training 		

- Higher education on AI
- Incentives for using artificial intelligence to support learning
- Reform of lifelong learning (restructure of Employment Fund by 2019)

According to Finland's Cyber Security Strategy, the Finnish Education system must see to the preservation and development of the top-level competences needed to ensure and improve the security of society's vital functions in the cyber domain. The Strategy requires basic cyber security skills to be included in the curricula at all education levels. The Implementation Program for Finland's Cyber Security Strategy for 2017–2020 addresses both the Finnish Ministry of Education and Culture and Finnish National Agency for Education with tasks aimed at strengthening skills related to both multi-literacy and cyber security. Therefore, strengthening cyber security will remain a challenge and basic cyber security skills are being included in the qualification requirements in vocational education and training,

Another national strategy, the 'Vision for higher education and research in Finland 2030', aims to develop a vision to increase tertiary attainment, improve opportunities for continuous learning, and increase resources for the research outcomes of higher quality.

Furthermore, Finland's Digital Transformation 2030 Strategy for research community is actually under development and is expected to involve specific measures for skills and training for researchers.

Overall, digitalisation is not a priority per se in Finland, but it has been identified as a key means to achieve growth in the business sector. Even though an all-encompassing digitalisation strategy does not yet exist, digitalisation is a priority in sectoral strategies (e.g., education). Digitalisation is seen as a great opportunity, with the Finnish attitude being 'full speed ahead'. The law on a new Digital and Population Data Agency was approved and the new Agency started up recently, at the beginning of 2020.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment and Ministry of Education and Culture are coordinating together to ensure that Finland is a leading country in future learning and inspiring education. In particular, the Ministry of Finance / Public Sector ICT Department is acting as policy coordinator and it is responsible for the overall development of eGovernment, Public Administration information management, corporate data and information management governance in central Government.

In particular, in Finland, the national administration of education and training has a two-tier structure. The Ministry of Education and Culture is the highest authority and is responsible for all publicly funded education in Finland. The Ministry is responsible for preparing educational legislation, all necessary decisions, and its share of the state budget for the Government. The Finnish National Agency for Education is the national development agency responsible for early childhood education and care, pre-primary, basic, general, and vocational upper secondary education as well as for adult education and training. Higher education is the responsibility of the Ministry of Education and Culture.

Furthermore, at present, national working groups and panel of experts are working on the development of the Transformation 2030 Strategy for researchers, and the Open Data Policy, producing in the meantime recommendations referring to digital skills competences and training.

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?		
Yes	No	In planning
	X	
Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation		
Key challenges in case of absence		
There is not a single authority that carries out the integral national responsibility for digital skills planning and implementation in Finland, although many initiatives attempt to coordinate digital skills policies design and implementation. For example, in response to increasing flows of migrants and refugees into Finland, the Liberal Adult Education Act was amended early 2018. The revised act gives greater responsibility to training institutions to provide language and vocational training to facilitate the integration of migrants, including refugees, into society and the labour market. Finally, the Finnish National Agency for Education launched the 'National anticipation model for adult education', which will develop and pilot an anticipation system for adult education and training.		
Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation		
Indexes for measurement and performance assessment of the policies are inherent elements of the policy documents themselves.		

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years
<p>There are numerous initiatives at local level, implemented by schools, vocational institutions, and other educational institutions as well as on national level, providing funding frameworks, with the cooperation of the private domain such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In 2017, the government proposed²² allocating an additional 60 million Euros in its budget for skilling the labour force, with a special focus on digital skills. According to a report²³ from the Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra for 2018, almost 20 billion Euros public and private funds were allocated to the development of skills and education in Finland in 2017. In 2018, the Ministry of Education and Culture, together with the National Board of Education and the Finnish National Agency for Education, started a program with the aim of strengthening adults' digital and basic skills. By offering low-threshold education, they want to prevent inequality, provide positive learning experiences, and strengthen the civic skills needed in today's society. The government reserved an appropriation for this purpose in the supplementary budget for 2018. The Board of Education granted EUR 7 million in state support to civic institutes, folk high schools, summer universities and study centres. In higher education, while the Ministry of Education and Culture granted a total of 65 million euros for 36 development projects during 2017 and 2018. The skills for the digital era programme²⁴ (2018-2020) is a program funded by Ministry of Education and Culture with a budget of EUR 7 million, that aims to strengthen the basic skills and digital skills of adults, especially the unemployed, those at risk of unemployment, retirees, retirees, jobseekers and immigrants. By increasing low-threshold education, it aims

²² <https://minedu.fi/-/lisatalousarviosta-iso-koulutuspaketti-osaavan-tyovoiman-pulaan-toisen-asteen-oppimateriaaleihin-ja-digiajan-perustaitoihin>

²³ <https://media.sitra.fi/2018/10/10132635/milla-rahalla.pdf>

²⁴ https://minedu.fi/artikkeli/-/asset_publisher/digiaikakauden-aidot-ohjelma-kaynnistyy-koulutukseen-haettavissa-7-miljoonaa

to prevent inequalities, give positive learning experiences, and strengthen today's civic skills. The programme provides funding for 84 training projects that strengthen the basic and digital skills of adults.

A wide variety of programs and projects have been launched aimed at specific target groups (teachers, trainers, specified vocational sectors, migrants, the unemployed, etc.). These projects include:

- **ia Digitutor 2018–2020**²⁵ aims to improve the digital skills of employees in the mechanical engineering, metal and chemical industries.
- **Integrify**²⁶ is a programming school integration of newly arrived immigrants into the workforce by training them as software developers. The company was founded in 2016 having major public and private partnerships in Finland, including the City of Helsinki. The primary goal of the company is to increase the chances of immigrants finding employment, by teaching programming and connecting them to employers working in tech. After the programme is finished, Integrify gives participants access to their pool of carefully selected partner companies. Currently, the company seeks to expand its service across Europe with the aim to train 10,000 people in digital skills by 2030.
- **Digipolku Work**²⁷ is a project that aims to develop the skills of people with low digital skills by increasing cooperation between work-based and vocational training.
- **eOppiva**²⁸ is a project aiming to improve the digital skills of state employees through online learning.
- **DigiKyky (Digi Capability)**²⁹ is a project consisting of various training programmes to support the digitisation of businesses and to enhance their capabilities, productivity, and competitiveness.

Some other initiatives concern the content provision and upskilling, such as:

- A series of free online courses that introduces participants to the basics of artificial intelligence. The course was developed by the University of Helsinki and the company Reaktor in Finland, and aims to be rolled out to the rest of Europe, in order to educate 1% of Europeans in the basics of artificial intelligence
- Cybersecurity Education and Training Programme³⁰. Laurea University of Applied Sciences is offering a comprehensive 60 ECTS education in information and cyber security within Business Information Technology and Security Management degree programme curriculum.
- Osaava Tredu - Making knowledge visible: collaborative web site for teachers and students in Tampere Vocational College Tredu : The project is a part of Tampere Digitalisation Programme, which aims that in 2025 all the citizens of Tampere will use digital services if available.

Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)

In the context of the implementation of the Artificial Intelligence Programme of Finland, the public sector is developing the virtual assistant Aurora that aims to create a platform for people to seamlessly connect with public and private service providers such as employment agencies and

²⁵ <http://digitutor.utu.fi/>

²⁶ <https://www.integrify.io/>

²⁷ <https://www.ok-sivis.fi/hankkeet/digipolku-toihin.html>

²⁸ <http://www.eoppiva.fi/>

²⁹ <http://portal.savonia.fi/amk/en/rdi/rdi-projects-and-entrepreneurship/digikyky-enhancing-companys-digital-capabilities-order>

³⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-skills-initiatives/cybersecurity-education-and-training-programme>

healthcare professionals. They'll be able to monitor the relevance of their skills, when they need updating, and receive support to apply for jobs³¹.

Moreover, Elements of AI Course by Finnish Centre for Artificial Intelligence (FCAI)³² is a free online course that aims to improve the basic AI knowledge of Finnish citizens, while Software Robotics by the Finnish Government Shared Services Centre for Finance and HR (Palkeet)³³ is a government project to improve the development of public services through the adoption of robotics and software, and to increase the skills needed to support their use.

Headai³⁴ is a job tech company that uses artificial intelligence to map skills needs and provision in Finland. At the core of its operation is the Micro-competencies service launched in April 2018, which is also part of the government's Aurora programme. Headai won the main prize in the Ratkaisuu 100 Challenge Prize in 2017 and was awarded 500,000 euros by the Finnish Innovation Foundation Sitra. Headai is working in collaboration with the Finnish Social Insurance Institution and Tax Administration and has started a pilot with the Government Workforce Development Agency. In addition to this, the company is preparing a National Implementation Plan for the Aurora programme and is thus involved in setting the landscape for the AI goals of the next government programme.

D. Current Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?

Yes	No	In planning
	X	

Key features of the digital competence framework established
Key challenges in case of absence

Digital competences are included in the national core curricula at all levels from early childhood education and care onwards. The Key Competences for Lifelong Learning identified by the European Commission are a crucial part of the content in both general education and vocational education and training (VET). Cooperation with working life is essential when defining the requirements for digital skills. Working life representatives participate in anticipation studies for learning and education needs, in the development of vocational qualifications, and in competence assessments.

The National Forum for Skills Anticipation is a tripartite expert body working with the Ministry of Education and Culture (MoEC) and the Finnish National Agency for Education (EDUFI). As part of its ongoing anticipation process (2017–2019) the Forum identifies the future skills needed by specific sectors and occupational groups. The skills survey pays special attention to digital skills, and the European Commission's Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DigComp 2.0) is utilized in the data collection and analysis

There are some assessment tools to evaluate digital skills or other skills using digital assessment tools, that are also used for teachers and schools to measure and analyse their usage of ICT. As an example, DigCompEdu³⁵ is an ongoing development process to create and pilot Digital Competence for Educators framework based self-assessment tool. This tool is intended to help teachers progress towards digital age learning. Digital Competence for Educators conceptual framework describes what it means for educators to be digitally competent. The self-assessment tool is directed towards

³¹ <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/06/finland-is-building-a-robot-that-will-help-you-get-a-job>

³² <http://www.elementsofai.com>

³³ <https://suomidigi.fi/pelikirja/digikarkihankkeet/talous-ja-henkilostohallinnon-palvelukeskuksen-ohjelmistorobotiikka/>

³⁴ <https://headai.com/>

³⁵ <https://www.jyu.fi/it/en/research/research-areas/cognitive-science-and-educational-technology/ile/projects/digcomp>

educators at all levels of education, from early childhood to higher and adult education. The self-assessment tool provides teachers a tool for reflecting on their current take up of digital technologies for innovative and effective learning. University of Jyväskylä is currently coordinating the upcoming pilot testing of DigCompEdu self-assessment tool for teachers in Finnish Schools. Pilot testing of DigCompEdu took place in Autumn 2019. Finnish schools and educational institutes will be encouraged to participate in the piloting of the new self -assessment tool.

D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?

Yes	No	In planning
	X	

Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework
Key challenges in case of absence

Despite development of digital materials and online training in adult and vocational education, there is not enough evidence of how widely these trainings are accredited and this remains an obstacle for higher education, hence requiring further attention.

No formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs exists actually, yet the ongoing work for the development of Open Science/Data and digital transformation policies, aiming to be concluded by mid next year, will address the issue at least for researchers.

As a related initiative, the national study credit, degree, and qualification disclosure service (**Koski**) aims to bring together all study credits, degrees and qualifications stored in different data warehouses. Koski will make it easier for citizens to use e-services and allow the authorities to perform their duties more efficiently. The act on national study credit and degree registers entered into force on 1 January 2018 while the new service is fully functional since 2019. National Study Credit, Degree and Qualification Disclosure Service (Koski) is the responsible organization³⁶.

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?

Yes	No	In planning
	X	

Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills
Key challenges in case of absence

One of the main priorities in the public sector is to develop the digital-based curriculum, new learning environments and digital materials at comprehensive schools as well as an expansion in digitising public services. In fact, there are different projects for specific groups. In fact, as part of the FINISH EDUCATION DIGITAL VISION 2030, Digivisio is a joint project of all Finnish higher education institutions, which opens up national data resources for learning for the use of the individual and society. Long-term digital television work supports learners' learning throughout life and enables the development of pedagogy and the renewal of higher education institutions. In 2030, Finland will have an open and recognized learning ecosystem, which will also benefit both research and innovation activities and working life. (<https://digivisio2030.fi/>)

The University of Helsinki, the oldest and largest university in Finland, is offering open online courses through a dedicate MOOC platform (<https://www.mooc.fi/en#courses>), The courses are offered by the Department of Computer Science. No prior knowledge is required — beginners can start to learn programming basics from the Programming with Java course or start to get familiar with artificial intelligence from the course Elements of AI.

³⁶ <https://www.oph.fi/kehittamishankkeet/koski>

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?		
Yes	No	In planning
		X
Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>Finish Parliament's vision is to build Finland up as an attractive operating environment for the data economy. By 2023, research organizations will provide comprehensive training, support, and skills development on research data documentation for different target groups, considering the needs of different disciplines and the life cycle of research. Promotion of open science and research is a joint effort by the entire research community. In the centre of the coordination work there are four governmental expert panels and their working groups on Culture of open scholarship, Open data, Open access, Open education. In particular the Expert panel on open data contributes actively in the making of national policies and recommendations on the National Open Policy, that is expected to be completed by middle of 2021³⁷ and it is working in cooperation with the National Open Science and Research Steering Group, drafting principles for the Policy on Open Access to Research Materials and Methods and a policy component on Open Access to Research Data. This draft, that is actually under consultation, is the first part of the national Policy on Open Access to Research Materials and Methods for the Finnish higher education and research community, and it further defines the national objectives for open research materials and methods mentioned in the Finnish Declaration of Open Science and Research 2020–2025. The policy will be supplemented with a policy component on open research methods in 2021-2022³⁸.</p> <p>Other related policies are the Spatial Data Policy and the Artificial Intelligence Programme, by the Ministry of Economic Affairs. Concerning the support of the researchers regarding their career path, EURAXESS Finland³⁹ provides information and assistance to mobile researchers – by means of the web portal and with the support of the national EURAXESS Service Centres. The portal contains practical information concerning professional and daily life, as well as information on job and funding opportunities. At the beginning of 2020, the new Digital, and Population Data Services Agency (Finnish Digital Agency) began its operation in Finland. It was established by the Act on the Digital and Population Data Services Agency (304/2019).</p> <p>Furthermore, Finland has set in place a set of legislations concerning digital governance issues, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Act on the Openness of Government Activities (with amendments up to 1060/2002 included) provides for a general right to access any official document (including electronic records) in the public domain held by public authorities and private bodies that exercise public authority. • The Act on Shared Support Services for eGovernment (571/2016) along with the Ministry of Finance's "Decree on providing certain shared support services for e- Government (607/2016)" entered into force on 15 July 2016. In the Act on Shared Support Services for eGovernment, the current responsibilities for providing support services for eGovernment were specified, so that they were in accordance with the national architecture for digital services. 		

³⁷ <https://avointiede.fi/en/open-science-expert-panels>

³⁸ <https://avointiede.fi/en/news/draft-policy-component-open-access-research-data-now-open-comments>

³⁹ <https://www.euraxess.fi/>

- The Act on the Information Management Governance in the Public Sector (634/2011), in Section 10, refers to authorities in public administration who organise their activities in such a way that they use the information deposited in the information systems if their activities require use of this information.
- The purpose of the Act on Secondary Use of Health and Social Data is to facilitate the effective and safe processing and access to the personal social and health data for steering, supervision, research, statistics and development in the health and social sector. A second objective is to guarantee an individual's legitimate expectations as well as their rights and freedoms when processing personal data.
- In the Act on Public Administration Information Management, there is a requirement for government agencies to utilise datasets of other government agencies whenever possible, if they by law have access to such data via electronic interfaces. Regular exchange of data between agencies has to be organised via electronic interfaces.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

The Digital and Population Data Services Agency leads the way, reforms society, and supports citizens in their interaction with public administration. The Digital and Population Data Services Agency launched on 1 January 2020 with the merging of the Population Register Centre, the Local Register Offices and the Steering and Development Unit for the Local Register Offices, which operates at the Regional State Administrative Agency of Eastern Finland. Its aim is to promote the digitalisation of society, secures the availability of data, and provides services for the life events of its customers. In relation to the development of these policies, strong cooperation with EOSC has been set up in order Finland to exploit EOSC working results and enhance them in its undergoing policies, addressing so, the goals of SRIA. Furthermore, the Academy of Finland is the prime funding agency for basic research in Finland. For example, the Finnish Funding Agency for Innovation, is the main public funding organisation for applied research and technology, and Sitra, standing as the Finnish Innovation Fund is another key source of funding for science and technology in Finland.

E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes Key challenges in case of absence

The platform Fairdata.fi⁴⁰ offers metadata tool, research dataset finder, storage areas of digital information for tens or even hundreds of years and for actual use, constituting the central point for research work applying open data science principles. The <https://findocnet.fi/> is a portal enabling research work for all researchers along the country

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry Key challenges in case of absence

The innovation system is based on intensive collaboration between universities and industry (ranked 2nd in the world). The Digital Finland Framework aims to ensure world's best innovation and business environment for companies seeking to develop innovative products, services and solutions to challenges ranging from those in everyday life to meeting the Sustainable Development Goals. The Framework combines key perspectives together:

- 1) The digital innovations exploiting the benefits of platform economy and the transformation of the spearhead industry sectors
- 2) Seamless support for sustainable digital transformation
- 3) Responses to global megatrends and sustainable development goals

The most important mechanism for joining research to industry, is SITRA, that was founded in 1967 and is focused on building a better future for Finland through innovation. SITRA is Finland's innovation fund, and aims to increase the nation's competitiveness on the world stage, ensuring well-being and prosperity for Finnish citizens. It operates independently from the government and brings together networks of legislators, researchers, businesses, and NGOs to conduct trials, provide training and develop preconditions for reform.

An example of cooperation among research, public and private domains, is the CSC⁴¹ that is a non-profit state enterprise with special tasks. As part of the national research system, it develops, integrates, and provides high-quality information technology services and ensures that Finland remains at the forefront of development. CSC has an important role as an instrument for steering and developing the Ministry of Education and Culture's education, science, and cultural policy. It is owned by the Finnish state (70% shareholding) and higher education institutions (30% shareholding). Its primary "customers" are the Ministry of Education and Culture and organizations in the field, higher education institutions (universities and universities of applied sciences), research institutes and public administration.

⁴⁰ <https://www.fairdata.fi/en/>

⁴¹ <https://csc.fi/en/web/guest/csc>

FRANCE 	<p>France ranks 17th in the EU on human capital indicators, below the EU average, as per the 2020 edition of the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI). France has embarked on a comprehensive drive for sustainable and inclusive digital transformation. Underpinning this drive is France's investment plan 2018-2022, which aims, among others to foster competitiveness and innovation, and achieve the digital transformation of the public sector. Moreover, France has played an important role in the European open access movement, particularly in the launch of the Berlin declaration. Among French research structures, the research institutions (CNRS, INSERM in particular) played a major role at the beginning of the 2000's, especially with the launch of the HAL open archive in 2001, while there are several legislative texts that set the framework for the publication and sharing of open data.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The national strategy / policy of France for digital skills is mainly reflected in the National Plan for Inclusive Digital and launch of Digital in Common(s), launched in September 2018, with an objective to train 1.5 million people in digital literacy in order to reduce inequalities and provide equal opportunities for all throughout the country. With 13 million French people who still do not use the Internet, or only to a limited extent, including 6.7 million who never connect to the Internet, this is a real challenge for the country which is committed to carrying out the digital transformation. This national strategy is based on four main approaches:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detecting audiences in difficulty with digital technology • Offer human support in the process • Train those who wish to do so thanks to the Digital Pass • Consolidate the players in digital mediation <p>In addition, since December 2012, the Ministry of National Education, Higher Education and Research has been developing an ambitious strategy to bring schools towards the digital age. This strategy aims to make the most of the opportunities offered by digital technology for the benefit of pupils' success. Actually, the French government is encouraging the creation of coding workshops outside classes and will progressively introduce a certification of digital skills for students in their last secondary school year.</p> <p>France's policy framework for improving the digital skills of its population, both through formal education and inclusion measures, is underway and is expected to produce tangible results over the coming years. More targeted initiatives will be important to upskill the workforce for the digital economy and to promote advanced digital skills development, in AI and in other areas too.</p>		
Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • French Ministry of Labour • Paris Descartes University • PIX - platform for assessing and certifying digital skills • Adecco Group France 		

- Digital Talents -The French Digital Agency
- Orange Great Digital School
- CFDT - French Democratic Confederation of Labour

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The coordination and governance for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation in France is carried out by the French digital coalition for skills and jobs that was set up in 2016 and MEDEF was appointed by the European Commission to be its coordinator and facilitator. Today, more than 200 actors from different horizons have joined this coalition and are working together. The coalition is aiming to identify and promote initiatives and good practices on digital skills, bring together all local and national actors active in digital matters (administrations, associations, NGOs, professional organizations, companies, unions, etc.) and carry out concrete actions throughout the territory that will enhance the digital skills and competences.</p> <p>Overall, the French coalition is:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • supporting active workers and those looking for work so that they adapt their skills and the practice of their professions to new digital processes, to develop further their employability throughout life. • adapting initial and continuing training and higher education to digital transformation to prepare for the jobs of tomorrow, by utilising educational tools and practices. • increasing the number of talents, especially women, in digital professions, while improving initial and continuing training. • providing all citizens with the necessary background to access information, be connected in areas of everyday life (administrative, cultural, sports, legal, etc.) and to interact more easily with their public or private environment, by mastering digital tools. 		
Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation		
<p>Currently there are not in place formal tools for performance & impact measurement of the digital skills initiatives in Lithuania. However, the French National Coalition is systematically monitoring and assessing the results and impacts of the digital skills initiatives/projects implemented in the country, with an aim to utilise lessons learnt and avoid past mistakes, hence improve the overall digital skills policy planning framework.</p>		

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years
<p>According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 10% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 30% towards ICT professionals, 50% towards the labour force and 10% towards citizens in general.</p> <p>France has launched a number of initiatives to boost the level of digital skills of its citizens, focusing on different target groups.</p>

To boost the digital skills of students, France has brought in two new compulsory courses on digital and computer sciences in secondary schools as of 2019⁴². According to the Education Ministry, these courses are already taught in over half of France's public schools. However, in some education institutions, opportunities to experiment and learn digital skills related to coding and robotics are available only as optional courses.

To boost the level of digital skills of teaching staff, France created a new inter-university diploma called Teaching ICT in upper secondary schools in 2019. So far, over 2,000 teachers have been trained in 19 universities⁴³. Other initiatives include putting in place a MOOC for upper secondary school teachers, developed by the French institute for digital sciences (INRIA). Over 13,000 teachers have registered for the course since it was rolled out in February 2019⁴⁴.

On adult learning, France is in the process of implementing the National Plan for Digital Inclusion, focusing on measures to promote the digital inclusion of all citizens. The plan includes outreach to the most vulnerable, an assessment phase and tailor-made offers. In March 2019, a tender was published for rolling out the digital pass, the online voucher system, and 11 territorial hubs were set up.

To increase the number of digital specialists, France has launched an initiative under its national artificial intelligence (AI) strategy, opening new roles for AI experts and doctoral positions. In addition, to attract more digital talent, France has set up a tech visa system that eases the procedures for tech specialists to relocate to France.

Furthermore, the French Digital Skills & Jobs Coalition is carrying out a number of initiatives to boost digital skills. In 2019, the Coalition organised a competition for young people on the professions of the future. It established a partnership with the Ministry of Labour to support businesses and employees on AI development, and work is ongoing to improve its platform to share information with other European National Coalitions. In 2019, a good number of schools and other organisations took part in EU Code Week, a grassroots movement to encourage people of all ages to code. France held over 500 events that attracted over 90,000 participants.

Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)

In the field of scientific libraries, France has just recently signed a collaboration agreement with the Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER).

In addition, Ambition Inria 2023, the French national research institute for digital science and technology, which goal is to accelerate, through digital research and innovation, the construction of France's scientific, technological, and industrial leadership in European dynamics has launched:

- Partnerships with industry through the founding of joint laboratories with leading industry players in France and Europe (Nokia, Orange, EDF, PSA etc.) and with global leaders who invest in France (Microsoft);
- a wide range of internal programs, whether to encourage scientific risk-taking, the cross-fertilization of expertise or the development of technologies;
- Activities to support the diversity of innovation pathways: from open-source software publishing to the creation of technological startups (Deeptech).

⁴² <https://www.education.gouv.fr/cid133192/le-numerique-service-ecole-confiance.html>

⁴³ <https://www.education.gouv.fr/cid133192/lenumerique-service-ecole-confiance.html>

⁴⁴ <https://www.education.gouv.fr/cid133192/lenumerique-service-ecole-confiance.html>

D. Current Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of the digital competence framework established		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>French Government has endorsed a Digital Competence Framework System based on DigiComp 2.0 to develop, measure, and certify digital competences for all. In this framework, France has developed the PIX platform that allows all citizens to evaluate and also certify their digital competence. The model, which is co-designed by the Min. of Education offers to measure its digital skills on 8 levels and 5 main areas, as follows:</p> <p>1. Information and data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1.1 Conduct research and information monitoring: Web and navigation; Search engine and query; Information watch, flow and curation; Information evaluation; Source and citation; Internet governance and web openness; Abundance of information, filtering and personalization; Critical retreat from information and the media; Copyright. • 1.2 Manage data: Folder and file; Storage and compression; Transfer and synchronization; Research and metadata; Semantic indexing and label (tag); Data structuring; Information system ; Location of data and applicable law; Economic models and strategies; Information system security. • 1.3 Process data: Quantitative data, type and format of data; Calculation, statistical processing and graphic representation; Data flow, Big data collection and use; Algorithmic and computer thinking; Privacy and confidentiality; Interoperability <p>2. Communication and collaboration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2.1. Interact: Protocols for interaction; Interaction modalities and roles; Applications and services for interaction; Privacy and confidentiality; Digital identity and signals; Connected life; Communication codes and netiquette • 2.2. Share and publish: Sharing protocols and modalities; Applications and services for sharing; Rules of publication and visibility; Social networks; Freedom of expression and the right to information; Online formation ; Privacy and confidentiality; Digital identity and signals; Social practices and citizen participation; e- Reputation and influence; Writing for the web; Communication codes and netiquette; Copyright • 2.3. Collaborate: Methods of collaboration and roles; Online document sharing and editing applications and services; Versions and revisions; Access rights and access conflict; Project management; Copyright; Connected life; Privacy and confidentiality • 2.4. Fit into the digital world: Digital identity and signals; e-Reputation and influence; Communication codes and netiquette; Social practices and citizen participation; Economic models and strategies; Ethical issues and values; Internet governance and web openness; Freedom of expression and the right to information <p>3. Content creation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.1. Develop textual documents: Textual document editing applications; Structure and separation form and content; Illustration and integration; Graphic charter and visual identity; Interoperability; Ergonomics and reusability of the document; Accessibility; Copyright 		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3.2. Develop multimedia documents: Multimedia document editing applications; Sound, image and video capture and digitization; Interoperability; Accessibility; Copyright; Graphic charter and visual identity • 3.3. Adapt documents to their purpose: Licenses; Distribution and posting of a document Ergonomics and reusability of the document; Writing for the web; Interoperability; Accessibility; Privacy and confidentiality • 3.4. Program: Algorithm and program; Representation and coding of information; Complexity; Algorithmic and computer thinking; Big data collection and use; Artificial intelligence and robots <p>4. Protection and security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4.1. Securing the digital environment: Attacks and threats; Encryption; Prevention and protection software; Authentication; Information system security; Privacy and confidentiality • 4.2. Protect personal data and privacy: Personal data and law; Traces; Privacy and confidentiality; Big data collection and use • 4.3. Protect health, well-being, and the environment: Ergonomics of the workstation; Wireless communication and waves; Environmental impact; Accessibility; Connected life; Sensors; Artificial intelligence and robots; Health; Privacy and confidentiality <p>5. Digital environment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5.1. Solve technical problems: IT breakdown and support; Administration and configuration; Maintenance and updating; Backup and restore; Interoperability; Complexity • 5.2. Building a digital environment: Computer history; IT and hardware; Software, applications, and services; Operating system, Computer network; Offer (hardware, software, service); Economic models and strategies <p>PIX is a public service, created to respond to the social challenge of improving digital skills in France. Its mission is to encourage people to cultivate their digital skills and to value what they have learned throughout their lives.</p> <p>In 2019, France set up a national framework for digital competences (Framework for digital competences)⁴⁵ using the European Digital Competence Framework, which covers education levels from primary school to university. This adds to the existing PIX platform for digital skills.</p>
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D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework		
The French platform PIX allows all citizens to evaluate and also certify their digital competence. The model, which is co-designed by the Min. of Education, uses DigComp. France will revise its certification of digital competences at the end of middle and upper secondary school on the basis of the new national framework for digital competences.		

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		

⁴⁵ <https://eduscol.education.fr/pid38816/certification-des-competences-numeriques.html>

Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills
Key challenges in case of absence
The French platform Pix.fr is a free online public service open to everyone to assess and develop digital skills. Due to the interactive tests of gradual difficulty and in the form of practical exercises, it allows all citizens to take stock and improve their digital knowledge and skills. The platform prepares the participants to take the Pix Certification, the digital skills certification initiated and recognized by the State, listed in the specific directory of France's Competences (eligible for the CPF).

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country

Key challenges in case of absence

France has played an important role in the European open access movement, particularly in the launch of the Berlin declaration. Among French research structures, the research institutions (CNRS, INSERM in particular) played a major role at the beginning of the 2000's, especially with the launch of the HAL open archive in 2001. There are several legislative texts that set the framework for the publication and sharing of open data.

In November 2007, the ANR (project-based funding agency for research in France) issued an open access policy, strongly encouraging the deposit of funded publications in open archives systems and in HAL in particular. It is worth noting that the Humanities and Social Sciences department has adopted a stronger policy mandating systematic deposit of publications in HAL-SHS.

The national policy of openness and sharing of public data was adopted in 2015 and acts as driver for "democratic vitality, economic innovation and modernisation of public service delivery". In addition to this, a Digital Republic Act was passed in 2016 that includes open data as one of its cornerstones. In particular, in October 2016, the French Law for a Digital Republic Act came into force. One article is of specific concern for scholarly communication, as it relates directly to open access/open data. Article 30 is about Open Access and creates a new right for researchers which creates a legal right for authors to archive an OA copy, even if they have granted an exclusive right to a publisher.

In July 2018, the Ministry of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation adopted the ambition **National Plan for Open Science**. The plan presents three broad commitments under the headings: a) generalising Open Access to Publications, b) structuring Research Data and making it available through Open Access, and c) be part of a sustainable European and international open science dynamic. Each commitment is accompanied by a short Roadmap section, which outlines the steppingstones to meeting each commitment. In addition, the National Plan for Open Science ensures that data produced by government-funded research in France are gradually structured to comply with the FAIR Data Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable), and that they are preserved and, whenever possible, open to all.

In 2019, the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) adopted the Roadmap for Open Science It focuses on:

- Keeping control of the scientific production and achieve 100% open access to CNRS publications
- Developing a culture of data management/sharing among all stakeholders in the data life cycle: researchers, engineers, computer scientists, librarians, etc. based on the

<p>implementation of the FAIR principles (findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing and promoting infrastructures and tools for fully independent mining and analysis activities on scientific contents • Transforming the individual assessment of researchers by making it compliant with the goals of Open Science together with taking their contributions to Open Science into account in assessments.
<p>Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved</p> <p>The French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) and the Open Science Committee are the main stakeholders involved with France's Research, Data, and Open science framework.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) is an interdisciplinary public research organisation under the administrative supervision of the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research. It is among the world's leading research institutions. The CNRS conducts research that is in the interest of science as well as the technological, social, and cultural advancement of the country. The CNRS's aim is for society to benefit from the advances it achieves, whether they relate to technologies, sustainable development, or societal issues. Numerous measures for technology transfer and application have been implemented to that effect, notably with industrial partners. The CNRS gives access to research results and data, and this sharing of knowledge is intended for different audiences, including the scientific community, the media, and the general public. The CNRS participates in the national research strategy with its partners, notably at major French university locations. It also carries out evaluations and expert assessments on scientific matters. • The Open Science Committee, with 270 experts, some of whom are involved through a series of thematic colleges and project groups and a collaborative forum to identify pragmatic, collective and collaborative methods to achieve the plan's objectives. They also have a French Open Science Monitoring framework and according to the first results based on open data, 36% of French research outputs are openly available online. The main objective is to identify pragmatic and useful mechanisms to coordinate efforts across the myriad of institutes and agencies in the French landscape. RDA is specifically cited in the Open Science Plan, with a commitment to support RDA in France.

<p>E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes</p> <p>Key challenges in case of absence</p>
<p>The 2016 edition of France's National Strategy for the Research Infrastructures reflects the willingness of the country, through its major institutions of research and higher education, to meet the requirements of knowledge and innovation. The roadmap has been elaborated on the basis of a state-of-the-art analysis by scientists from all fields and in accordance with the National Research Strategy.</p> <p>The main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes infrastructures consist of four computing infrastructures (GENCI, CCIN2P3, Grid'5000, and France Grilles) and two network infrastructures (RENATER and FIT). Most of these infrastructures are integrated into European or international infrastructures.</p>

 **LIST OF RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES
DIGITAL SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGIES; MATHEMATICS**

TYPE	NAME	FULL NAME	ESFRI
VLRI	GENCI	Grand Équipement National de Calcul Intensif	
VLRI	RENATER	National Telecommunications network for Technology, Education and Research	
RI	CCIN2P3	IN2P3/CNRS Computing Center	
RI	FIT	Future Internet of Things	
RI	France Grilles	France Grilles	
RI	Grid 5000	Grid'5000	
Project	GERM	Grand Équipement pour la Recherche en Mathématiques	
Project	RNRVA	National Network platforms Augmented and Virtual Reality	

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry Key challenges in case of absence

According to the European Research Area (ERA) Progress Report for the period 2016-2018, one of the main moves to improve the coordination of innovation policy in France since 2015 has been to concentrate competences in very few operators – ANR (National Research Agency), Bpifrance, Caisse des Dépôts et Consignations (CDC) and ADEME (Agency for Environment and Energy Management). These four institutions have become the main operators in the French R&I system. In addition, the new Ministry of Higher Education is responsible for managing R&D and innovation areas that were previously managed by the High Commission for Investments (CGI). In addition, the streamlining of existing knowledge transfer procedures and policy mechanisms has been taking place: simplification measures, mainly based on digitalised procedures that should simplify calls for tenders and intellectual property rights management, were introduced in 2016. Moreover, the “SME innovation savings plan” created in January 2017 introduces individual tax exemptions to incentivise business angels. This measure aims to encourage entrepreneurs who sell shares of their company to reinvest the capital gains in young SMEs or innovative companies.

Moreover, France performed particularly well for its share of life science papers with Open Access datasets. On this indicator, the country’s score placed it above both the EU-28 benchmark and the ERA average.

Also, French firms’ propensity to cooperate with either universities or higher education institutions, or with governmental, public, or private research institutes, is similar to the EU-28 score, according to the 2018 ERA progress report.

<p>Greece</p>	<p>The level of digital skills of Greek citizens is behind the EU27 average, while Greece belongs to the category of the low performing countries in the DESI Index. Greece, like the rest of southern and eastern Europe performs poorly in digital learning, which score low on European rankings related to economic performance, innovation, and digitalisation. According to the DESI Report for 2020, Greece is ranked as 23rd in the “Human Capital” dimension. Greece suffers from a Brain drain’ of ICT graduates alongside a severe digital skills gap according to 2020 DESI Performances. In addition, Greece has one of lowest score on the Women in Digital Scoreboard (WID 2020). Open Access/ Science policies are slowly adopted by the Greek Higher Education Institutes. Currently, Greece does not yet have in place a specific, formally approved National strategy for Open Science.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

<p>A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?</p>		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
<p>Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences Key challenges in case of absence</p>		
<p>Greece’s national policy on digital skills is currently mainly expressed through the National Digital Skills Coalition Action Plan 2017-2020: Enhancing Digital Skills and Jobs in Greece (EDSGR). The EDGSR is a multi-stakeholder initiative, providing a propitious organizational environment inside the Greek public and private sector that acts as a precondition to fully reap the benefits of digital technologies in order to enhance productivity and growth of the Greek economy. By bringing together Greek National stakeholders as members under the same umbrella, it is the first and largest of its kind in Greece. To this goal, the EDSGR coalition, under the leadership of the Ministry of Digital Governance and in collaboration with major national stakeholders, has set off to develop a functional ecosystem that includes policy makers, academia, entrepreneurs and businesses, in order to assist in the implementation of structural reforms and actions to acquire or enhance digital skills, promote growth and help the best and brightest talents shine.</p> <p>They EDSGR is comprised of four (4) key pillars: education, training, ICT professionals and citizens.</p> <p>The current Action Plan is based on the data received, mainly, from the major Ministries and General Secretaries and the ICT sector. The existing Digital Skills actions are in the field of the Public Sector, Education, Employment, Digital Economy and revealed a surprising positive base for the aims of this Action Plan. Based on the main issues of the Digital Skills and e-Leadership policy, the following priorities have been defined:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Priority 1: Enhance Public Administration capacity towards promotion of e-skills of civil servants as a key enabler for the digital transformation of Public Sector • Priority 2: Development of a learning mechanism that will offer free online courses for civil servant’s digital skills and e-Leadership development • Priority 3: Creating & Fostering Employment Conditions and Structures for Digital Talent within organizations • Priority 4: Up-skilling Small and Medium Enterprises with Digital Skills • Priority 5: Promote Digital Skills in all Educational levels and Life -Long Learning • Priority 6: Up-grading Greek teachers' skills • Priority 7: Promoting e-skills through RTDI activities 		

- Support collaborative RTDI projects between enterprises and Public Research Centres (PRC) as well as Higher Education Institutions (HEI)
- Establish specialized competence centres, Digital Innovation Hubs, and clusters
- Promote recruitment of highly qualified personnel in enterprises to conduct research for the development of innovative products/services
- Enhance extroversion of enterprises through participation in bilateral and transnational RTDI co-operation
- Priority 8: Mapping Digital Skills Data on Greek labour market.
- Priority 9: Creating & Fostering Employment Conditions and Structures for Digital Talent within organizations
- Priority 10: Up-skilling Small and Medium Enterprises with Digital Skills
- Priority 11: Empower Women & Girls to Go Digital in Greece.
- Priority 12: Better Employment Conditions for Female Talent with Digital Skills

The Coalition has also been promoting several Education and Training activities / initiatives during the last years.

Currently, the Digital Transformation Bible is under development, which it is expected to include specific policies for digital skills & competences.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

As of July 2019 the competence for the organization and functioning of the coalition at national, European and international level was transferred to the General Secretariat of Digital Governance and Simplification of Procedures of the Ministry of Digital Governance, specifically to the Department of Digital Economy, Investments and Digital Skills/Directorate of Digital Strategy. Other stakeholders involved include:

- Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs / REBRAIN GREECE
- Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs.
- Public Employment Service (Greek PES)
- Hellenic Open University
- Municipality of Athens
- Municipality of Soufli
- Municipality of Thessaloniki
- Municipality of Trikala
- Region of Crete
- Athena Research & Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Science Technologies
- Athens Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ACCI)
- Technical Chamber of Greece
- Federation of Hellenic Information Technology and Communications Enterprises (SEPE)
- Hellenic Federation of Enterprises (SEV)
- Labour Institute of the General Confederation of Greece
- Stegi - Onassis Foundation
- Hellenic Telecommunications Organisation (OTE) Academy
- Microsoft
- Google Hellas
- CISCO
- Oracle Academy
- Educational Robotics & Science Organization – WRO Hellas
- Rebrain Greece initiative
- Open Technologies Organization (ELLAK)
- etc

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>As already discussed, the General Secretariat of Digital Governance and Simplification of Procedures of the Ministry of Digital Governance, specifically to the Department of Digital Economy, Investments and Digital Skills/Directorate of Digital Strategy is the responsible body of the National Coalition for Digital Skills in Greece, hence responsible for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation in the country.</p> <p>Greek National Coalition for Digital Skills and Jobs is open to any body endorsing its objectives and targets Its members come both from public and private sector and participate in the work of the five groups of the Coalition.</p> <p>A coordinator, chosen from among its members, is appointed in each of the five groups for a term of one year. For the year 2020 the group coordinators are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onassis Foundation for the Education Group • Rebrain Greece initiative in which participate various bodies, for the Training Group • Federation of Hellenic Information Technology and Communications Enterprises (SEPE), for the ICT Professionals Group. • Municipality of Athens for the Citizens Group • National Documentation Centre (EKT)/ Ministry of Digital Governance for the Funding and Communications Group 		
Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation		
<p>The EDSGR as mentioned before, includes 12 priorities. For each priority, a stakeholder/ member of the National Coalition is responsible for the line coordination and the achievement of strategic goals through actions, the monitoring and assessment of implementation, as well for the continuous feedback and update of the Action Plan with actions in its policy area, aiming at building synergies in an horizontal and vertical way, with other stakeholders.</p> <p>To enhance publicity and openness of the Action Plan and ensure the diffusion of the actions included to this, throughout the country, a mechanism of communication and feedback among the stakeholders at central and regional level will be created. This monitoring mechanism targets to act as a facilitator for the implementation of the Action Plan, through conferences and forums, as well to create a channel of interaction between the National Coalition with regional pledges and local needs for interventions.</p> <p>Moreover, an assessment tool has been developed, where the following 10 key performance indicators have been identified:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation Policy Labs (number): Innovation Labs to promote bench learning and transfer of best practices on the development of innovation skills for the civil servants • On -line courses for Civil Servants (number): Dedicated to critical governmental organizations on- line courses. • Civil servants' participation to the on -line courses (number): The attractiveness and the evaluation of the outcomes of the on- line courses will be part of the overall evaluation of the relative priority/ action 		

- **Women that used on- line courses for a carrier path in public sector** (number): It is important to improve women's participation in leading positions of the Greek public sector. Specific courses and actions will be used to evaluate and monitor the overall performance of this priority/ actions.
- **Dedicated Training Programs for Digital Skills** (number of programmes): Accumulated with all the other partners of the National Coalition
- **Bridging the Digital Skills gap in all Industries** (Conference/workshop proceedings/Training programmes): Workshops and other knowledge-sharing yearly based events
- **Training and Certification of Employees of ICT sector professions** (Number of employees): Certification of employees in the ICT sector
- **Expand and promote mentorship programs including connecting newcomers and young entrepreneurs to opportunities to network, share knowledge and learn from peers** (number of programmes): In collaboration with the expertise in entrepreneurship members, specific actions will be implemented targeting to boost networking and mentoring.
- **Specific scientific workshops for new opportunities** (number of workshops): Workshops, with experts proposing new strategies to promote Digital Skills and Leadership
- **Global report on status and trends in Digital Skills match in five major industry sectors** (number of publications): A status report per year will be issued to guidance stakeholders on local employment trends and European and International best practices.

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 34% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 2% towards ICT professionals, 34% towards the labour force and 30% towards citizens in general. The main activities implemented per pillar of the EDSGR are as follows:

Education

- Universal design and specialized educational support for integration of pupils with disabilities and / or special educational needs – Development of accessible digital educational material, Start-End: Ongoing Beneficiaries: 57,854 Participants
- State Accredited Certificate of ICT Use (Organization: Ministry of Education), Start-End: Ongoing Beneficiaries: 10,788 Participants
- Open technology classes (Organization: EELLAK), Start-End: April 2019, Beneficiaries: 30 Participants
- Code and Create (Organization: EELLAK), Start-End: Ongoing, Beneficiaries: 53 Participants
- Open Schools (Organization: Municipality of Athens), Start-End: Ongoing, Beneficiaries: 160 Participants
- Innovathens (Organization: Municipality of Athens), Start-End: Ongoing, Beneficiaries: 350 Participants
- Start Project (Organization: Social Innov), Start-End: Ongoing, Beneficiaries: 353 Participants
- Tech Talent School (Organization: Social Innov), Start-End: Ongoing, Beneficiaries: 293 Participants
- Seminars in Universities for the Future Travel Professionals, Start-End: Ongoing, Beneficiaries: 2,129 Participants
- Hyperlocal Projects (Organization: Google Greece – Grow Greek Tourism Online Program), Start-End: January 2019 - May 2019, Beneficiaries: 1,156 Participants
- Introduce My City, Start-End: 30 March 2019, Beneficiaries: 88 pupils and teachers

- Workshop about learning ancient Greek games-toys using digital tools: “Greektots children’s revolution, Start-End: 23-24 February, Beneficiaries: 65 primary school pupils
- “Let’s code, girls ‘n’ boys!!!”, Start-End: May - to be continued, Beneficiaries:108 Pupils- 21 Teachers- 15 Schools
- Invitation to the workshop “Getting Started with Java using Alice”, Start-End: 29 September 2018, Beneficiaries: Teachers of 18 Primary Schools
- Open Schools, Start-End: July 2018, Beneficiaries: 372 Students
- Seminars and educational activities, Start-End: May 2018 - June 2018, Beneficiaries: 2,000 beneficiaries
- Open Schools, Start-End: May 2018 - June 2018, Beneficiaries: 500
- Active participation in research programs – DCDS – Digital Skills Development System- Hellenic Open University, Start-End: May 2018:

Training

- Promoting digital opportunity traineeships in SMES Organization: Unit of Innovation and Best Practices – Ministry of Administrative Reconstruction), Start-End: Ongoing, Beneficiaries: 40 applicants (28 accepted), 13 SMEs (asking for students applying for digital job positions). The objective of action to support the digital capabilities of SMEs with apprenticeship in digital jobs is to disseminate the DOT, strengthen the local economy, promote transparency, competitiveness, cultural exchanges, mutual understanding through digital skills.
- Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs has launched via the National Institute for Labour and Human Resources an initiative called “Labour market needs diagnostic mechanism”⁴⁶ which is a system that draws data from major registries to present needs for skills. Based on the mechanism a pilot project is being launched called “Lifelong learning account” which is closely linked to upskilling of digital skills by providing motivation for individuals to complete advanced online training and get credits that can be used in securing a job in the ICT market.

ICT professionals

- Boosting Digital Skills on job – “Digital Opportunity Traineeship” Programme, Start-End: 16 May 2019, Beneficiaries: 35 persons, including 23 business representatives and 12 institutional representatives and officials
- Promote Digital Skills in the region of Central Macedonia, Start-End: 28 March 2019, Beneficiaries: 50 attending institutional and public sector and tourist business officials
- Training program for small and medium-sized tourism businesses on digital skills through the “Grow Greek Tourism Online” initiative, Start-End: September 2018 - March 2019. The aim of the program is to enhance the online presence of these businesses to attract more visitors, making the city of Thessaloniki an attractive destination for the whole year. The training takes place with the support of Google Greece specialists, Online Advisors, who have received special and extensive training on Internet tools for tourism.
- Seminars, programme for certification and upgrading of ICT skills, Start-End: June 2018 Beneficiaries: 2,862 trainees and 10,783 counselling sessions having been implemented/ 566 beneficiaries
- Event for the expansion of the tourist season in Crete with the collaboration of Google Hellas and the Region of Crete, Beneficiaries: 900 small and medium-sized enterprises in 4 peripheral units of Crete.
- Digital Skills on Tourism Development in the Region of Crete – GROW GREEK TOURISM ONLINE, Start-End: On going, Beneficiaries: 1,400 SMEs in 4 peripheral units of Crete

⁴⁶ <https://lmd.eiead.gr/>

<p>Citizens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Citizen Digital Academy https://nationaldigitalacademy.gov.gr • Pan-Hellenic Open Educational Robotics Competition (Organization: GFOSS – Open Technologies Alliance (EELLAK), Start-End: 15/12/2018-17/05/2019, Beneficiaries: 1,000 Students and 200 Teachers) • Patras Science Festival (Organization: Hellenic Open University), Start-End: 10-13 May 2019, Beneficiaries: 6,500 Participants) • MOOC platforms – Promoting teleworking and mass-open e-learning (MOOC) to increase cluster competitiveness and employment – Inaugural Meeting, Start-End: July 2018 - to be continued • Organization and Dissemination or Multiplier Value Events – Science Festival 2018 Patras-Organization of summer courses for professionals-Hellenic Open University, Start-End: May 2018, Beneficiaries: 6,000 Visitors
Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)
NDC organises several seminars and activities around the development of digital skills in the fields of Research and Science. The first online seminar entitled "How digitally capable are we as learners, trainers and educational organizations? From theory to practice" was organized on May 14th, 2020 with more than 2,200 participants. It was implemented in the framework of the "Bridges of Knowledge and Cooperation" initiative and the "National Alliance for Digital Skills and Employment", in collaboration with the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission.

D. Current Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?		
Yes	No	In planning
		X
Key features of the digital competence framework established		
Key challenges in case of absence		
Currently, there is not digital competence framework formally established in the country, as per DIGICOMP guidelines. However, in the context of the Digital Transformation Bible that is currently under development, the need for introducing a digital competence framework in Greece is stated and relative actions are already being implemented within the context of Technical Assistance provided by DG Reform. As a first result, Citizen Digital Academy includes a self- assessment tool ⁴⁷ based on DigiComp v2.1 (21 competences organized in 5 areas).		
D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework		
Key challenges in case of absence		
EOPPEP, Greece's National Organisation for the certification of qualifications and vocational guidance, develops and implements the National Accreditation & Certification System for non-formal education, including initial and continuing vocational training and adult education, and		

⁴⁷ <https://nationaldigitalacademy.gov.gr/ergaleio-autoaksiologhshs>

provides scientific support to Vocational Guidance & Counselling services in Greece. EOPPEP’s principal fields of activity and responsibility are:

Providers and Educational Framework:

- Accreditation/Licensing of Providers of non-formal education (Free Studies Workshops, Private Vocational Training Institutes, Vocational Training Centres, Special Centres for vulnerable social groups)
- Accreditation of Occupational Profiles
- Accreditation of Curricula (in terms of standards and specifications)

National Qualifications Framework (NQF)

- Development and implementation of the National Qualifications Framework (NQF) in correspondence with EQF & National Coordination Point for EQF (NCP)
- National Reference Point for ECVET
- National Centre for EUROPASS in Greece
- Equivalencies & Occupational Rights for VET education title holders

Certification of Qualifications:

- Development of the National System for the Certification of Qualifications
- Accreditation of Vocational Training & Certification of Vocational Training Institutes graduates
- Certification of teaching qualification of Trainers for Adults of non-formal education
- Licensing of Providers for the certification of qualifications & Providers for computer skills certification

Vocational Guidance and Counselling

- Scientific and technical support of vocational guidance and counselling services
- Networking of providers and vocational guidance professionals
- Career development for youth & adults
- National Centre of Euro guidance
- National delegate in the European Lifelong Learning Guidance Policy Network (ELGPN)

Quality Assurance in LLL

- Cooperation in the development and implementation of the National Framework for Quality Assurance in LLL
- National Reference Point in EQAVET

The government also plans to introduce a certification framework to support Citizen Digital Academy platform.

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills
Key challenges in case of absence

The National Documentation Centre (NDC) is the main national content provider that offer courses on enhancing digital skills in Greece. NDC paves the way for knowledge transfer and reuse in research and innovation, by making scientific knowledge accessible to all while developing and strengthening its activities to disseminate, with as few limitations as possible, existing and future knowledge, so that it can be reused for research, education, development, innovation and society. It collects,

documents, disseminates and provides long-term preservation of quality digital content and data produced by Greek scientific, research and cultural communities, it measures output and results of the Research, Technology, Development, Innovation (RTDI) system and its comparison to European and international equivalents, it follows through the broader national objective to exploit research results and innovation for public sector reform, developing the economy and solving social problems and ensure the continuous operation of the national electronic infrastructure, providing friendly access to reusable and reputable information, the collection and availability of data and production of statistics for RTDI in Greece, and to offer a range of services for research, academic, educational and business communities. NDC provides a range of services to the Greek research, academic and business community of the country, in the context of its three pillars of activities:

- **e-content** - Digital content and services
- **metrics** - RTD Indicators and Statistics
- **innovation** - Services for networking, cooperation, development

In particular:

e-content- Digital content and services

[a] Digital Library Services of Science Technology & Culture

- Bibliographic Reference Services
- Citation Index & Bibliometric Indicators Services
- Document delivery Services & Interlibrary Loans
- Reading Room K.Th. Dimaras
- Electronic Reading Room
- Educational Activities
- National Union Catalogue of Scientific Journals
- National Network of Science & Technology Libraries

[b] Search Services - Digital collections & platforms

- Open access journals & selected sources of NDC
- National Archive of PhD Theses
- Argo Portal – bibliographic databases & national / international indexes
- SearchCulture.gr - discover open digital content
- Digital libraries and Library Automation of NDC e-opac
- Humanities & Social Sciences Index – grissh.gr
- MITIDA – Online Learning Repository for Educational Resources
- NDC digital database
- NDC library e-journals
- NDC e-Publishing – e-journals, books, conference proceedings
- openarchives.gr
- Digital Repositories

[c] Services for Organisations

- National Archive of Greek PhDTheses – helpdesk
- NDC publishing – journals, books, conference proceedings
- CRIS Systems – Current Research Information Systems
- openarchives.gr - available content
- Argo portal – available content

metrics - RTD Indicators and Statistics

- Statistics & indicators for Research & Development in Greece

- Bibliometric analysis of Greek publications in international scientific journals
- Special Reports on Greek research activities and participation in European programmes
- Interactive Charts - geographical documenting of data and indicators per region

innovation - Services for networking, cooperation, development

- Tenders – national & European research programmes
- Business and technology co-operation – Greece & Europe
- Automatic updates – Business & Technology Co-operation
- Research & Development Issues (e-Newsletter)

As mentioned above, Citizen Digital Academy offers at the time of writing (September 2020) more than 200 online digital courses to enhance citizens' digital skills, organized around 30 thematic units. Content has been prepared and uploaded by more than 30 providers from both public and private sectors.

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?

Yes	No	In planning
		X

Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country
Key challenges in case of absence

Research in Greece is carried out primarily by Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and Research Centres (RC). HEIs and public RCs are independent public-law bodies meaning they are self-administered but supervised and financed by the state. Currently, there are 25 HEIs with several departments and 40 public RCs including institutes and units that they are comprised of. As of 2019, HEIs activities fall under the supervision of the Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs and RCs are supervised by the General Secretariat of Research and Technology (GSRT) of the Ministry of Development and Investments. A number of specialized research centres are nonetheless supervised by other ministries. In addition to the above, research is carried out within other organisations like public and private hospitals, museums, private companies, etc. albeit to a smaller extent when compared to universities and research centres. The GSRT, the main public funder, supports the activities of research organisations and productive sectors of the economy through competitive funding.

Greece has not implemented a national Open Access/ Open Science policy yet. However, Law 4310/2014 supports open access to publicly funded research. Also, article 4 of Law N. 4485/2017 on Organisation and operation of higher education, arrangements for research and other provisions, mentions "open resources" as one of its mission without however specifying the type of resources. There are ongoing efforts by the National Open Science Task Force that worked to produce a National Open Science Plan. The plan includes provisions for open access to scientific outputs produced from publicly funded streams and for better access to and FAIR-aligned infrastructures and services also according to EOSC standards and rules of participation as they are coming. It also proposes a roadmap for implementation. On the 29 and 30 November 2018 OpenAIRE organised a Greek Open Science Symposium which aimed at understanding the current research ecosystem and prioritise actions towards the development of a National Open Science Strategy. Drawn from discussions during the 1st day, a proposal for the reformulation of a National Open Science High Level Task Force under the auspices of the General Secretariat of Research and Technology (GSRT) was made.

In terms of open data, the Greek Law already supports Open Data activities containing provisions that are similar to Open Science in nature, such as licensing of outputs. Law N. 3979/2011 on E-

government and relevant regulations with amendments up to Law N. 4483/2017 and Law N. 4305/2014 on Open Access to and Further Use of Public Sector Documents, Information and Data with amendments up to Law N. 4483/2017 include specifications for public bodies' infrastructures and introduce Creative Commons licenses to some outputs, respectively.

Open access to scientific content, has been mainly supported through the reinforcement of research and academic organisations' e-infrastructures, namely the development of scientific content repositories, but also through the successful participation of the relevant stakeholders in competitive EU programmes. Greek repositories mostly contain postgraduate dissertations/theses and doctoral theses (NDC's National Archive of PhD Theses), not peer reviewed publications. The absence of open access policies at institute/research centre level can explain the lack of peer reviewed publications in these repositories, while the same publications appear in other sectoral repositories.

The Greek national Action Plan for European Research Area - ERA (2015-2020) has been prepared by GSRT after several targeted consultations with key stakeholders of the Greek research community. It describes the guiding principles and future actions for each ERA priority in relation to EU level policies and strategic documents and in this respect the latter have been fully taken into account in designing measures and actions needed at national level to meet the targets set in the document. Despite weaknesses in implementation or slow progress detected in some areas the guiding principles of the roadmap and its perspective are aligned with the policy priorities set at EU level. The Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3) used for the programming period 2014-2020 and funding from Structural Funds (ESIF) is fully aligned with European policies and goals for research and innovation.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

The General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT) is a modern public service assigned with the task of defining, as well as coordinating the implementation of, the national policy for Research, Technological Development, and Innovation. It supports the activities of research and industry bodies through competitive research programmes highlighting economic performance and a socially fair allocation of outcomes. Furthermore, it supervises research and technology bodies, which provide local communities with the skills necessary for producing knowledge and boosting innovation. GSRT actively follows EU and international developments in the field of RDI and represents the country to the EU and International Organisations. The GSRT mandate consists in:

- Defining and promoting a comprehensive strategy for research, technology, and innovation
- Fully exploiting the highly qualified research staff to boost economic growth, generate new employment and reverse the current trend of expert Greek scientists migrating abroad
- Transferring and facilitating the uptake of innovative technologies by the country's industry, through targeted use of research outcomes.
- Supporting initiatives to raise awareness among Greek people in the fields of Research and Technology
- Supervising and funding Research and Technology Bodies across the country
- Promoting international S&T cooperation with EU and third countries and making best use of the opportunities to participate in relevant EU, bilateral and international initiatives
- Evaluating the outcomes of research & innovation projects, with a view to adjusting research policy on an ongoing basis

GRNET, National Infrastructures for Research and Technology, is the Greek national research network. GRNET is a state-owned company, operating under the auspices of the Greek Ministry of Digital Governance. GRNET is an integrated e-infrastructure service provider and offers an environment of cutting-edge technologies providing infrastructural and technological support to academic and research institutions, to educational bodies at all levels, and agencies of the public sector. GRNET is the main infrastructure and service enabler for open science in Greece, and leads the coordinated development of e-infrastructures and services in Southeast Europe (SEEREN, SEE-

GRID series, HP-SEE, VI-SEEM, NI4OS projects) and the wider region. Regarding data storage, GRNET has over 11 Petabytes of raw disk storage and 7 Petabytes of tape archive. Concerning cloud computing, GRNET operates Infrastructure as a Service via large datacentres (135 racks, 1800+ servers, 7000 Virtual Machines active, 5 Petabytes of storage). In the realm of High-Performance Computing (HPC), GRNET is currently operating the Greek national HPC Tier-1 centre – ARIS (Advanced Research Information System). The total theoretical peak performance of the whole system is 434 Tflops.

Other stakeholders involved with Research, Data, and Open science in Greece are the Research and Technology Bodies supervised by GSRT in various fields. In the area of Information Technology and Telecommunications these include:

- Athena Research & Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Science Technologies
- Centre for Nuclear Research, Demokritos
- Centre for Research and Technology Hellas / CERTH
- Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH)
- National Hellenic Research Foundation / NHRF
- National Observatory of Athens (NOA)

E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes Key challenges in case of absence

The European Commission and ESFRI encourage Member States and Associated Countries to develop national roadmaps for research infrastructures (RIs). These roadmaps are vital blueprints which enable countries to set national priorities and to earmark funds for both national and pan-European RIs including ESFRI ones. In this context, in Greece the Roadmap was updated in 2014. Since the beginning of 2013, the General Secretariat for Research & Technology (GSRT), supported by the National Council for Research and Technology (NCRT), has endeavoured to develop a long-term, visionary National Strategy for Research, Technological Development and Innovation (2014-2020), which will build on the competitive position of Greece in specific research areas - at the EU and international level – and maximizes its potential, through R&D investment on strategic areas of national priority, identified on the basis of the principles of Smart Specialization (RIS3), fostering innovation and entrepreneurship.

Research Infrastructures are recognised as key structural elements of the National Research & Innovation ecosystem. They have a prominent role within the NSRTDI 2014-2020, being recognised as 'enablers of innovation', via interdisciplinary synergy effects they create within the knowledge triangle. Therefore, research infrastructures contribute to all three priority pillars of the National Strategy of R&I, while they are also linked with Horizon 2020.

With regards to e- Infrastructures, the horizontal HELIX: National Digital Infrastructure for Research is a convergence-building instrument for the coordination of research-oriented e-Infrastructures in Greece, coordinated by GRNET aims at an overall coordination of research-oriented e-Infrastructures with a wide participation of all research centres. **It comprises two independent and complementary entities - NNCRI and OpenAIRE-D** - that respectively address the increasing horizontal 'big computing/networking' and 'big data' needs of the Greek academic & research community. Overall, it forms a single national ecosystem within which it provides research and advisory services, supports training activities, and offers relevant expertise on the combination of high-end communications, high-performance and high through put distributed computing, elastic cloud resource provisioning, and scalable data processing & analysis. It instruments several 'as a Service' offerings where part of the management capabilities is handed over to researchers, thereby facilitating innovation on novel frameworks delivering advanced researcher-controlled capabilities. HELIX will support the creation

of open science aspects, ranging from AAI (EduGain), PID systems, an OA aggregator for publications (like OpenAIRE), a national repository for publications, a national data repository with accompanying RDM services.

HELIX boosts innovation by contributing to the formulation and implementation of a consolidated e-Science strategy in Greece that will ensure cost-effective solutions and support for training and advisory activities in line with advances in the field. This large-scale federated research infrastructure provides powerful tools for the design and deployment of the network of the future and big-data processing allowing for unprecedented levels of flexibility, adaptability, elasticity, and eventually cost reduction. It significantly enhances the competitive advantage of Greek institutions and facilities in line with the principles of the Innovation Union and the Digital Agenda.

- **NNCRI (National Networking and Computing Research Infrastructure)**, includes all academic and research institutions and will be coordinated by GRNET, pioneer in research networking in SE Europe. It will significantly augment and extend the existing infrastructures of GRNET, a massive national e-Infrastructure that operates large data centres and provides a variety of e-services to the Greek academic & research institutions. Furthermore, it will incorporate HELNET, a national infrastructure for experimental networking research lead by the University of Thessaly, with its NITOS testbed facility and integrated experimental facilities of several research institutions across the country. With GRNET being a member of GÉANT Association (the pan-European R&E communications infrastructure) and PRACE (the pan-European HPC infrastructure) and by motivating a vast assembly of research and academic partners, NNCRI will play a leading role in the field of networking and cloud brokering/ middleware infrastructures and work with other e-infrastructure providers around Europe to gain insight into new networking requirements posed by cloud computing, the data deluge and HPC developments. The national HPC system as foreseen by the NNCRI will also be integrated with the Tier-1 European HPC ecosystem strengthening Greece's role in PRACE. Boosting complementarity and fostering linkage of research networking and future internet communities, NNCRI will capitalise on HELNET's federated and highly heterogeneous and large-scale experimental facility, which will offer 'Testbeds as a Service', with a wide range of technologies including 4G/3G cellular networks, wireless Internet, Software Defined Networking, cloud networking and Software Defined Radios. The HELNET experimental facility will empower innovation at national and international level and significantly upgrade the competitive advantage of the Greek institutions and facilities for the industrial development and innovation.
- **OpenAIRE-D** will provide a cost-effective scalable cloud-based data infrastructure in support of the entire life cycle of data intensive research, spearheading Greek research activities in the areas of Big Data and the Data Economy, outlined by the EC in the Digital Agenda. OpenAIRE-D is coordinated by the ATHENA Research Centre and involves several core Academic and Research partners as service & technology integrators. It offers services for storing, managing, discovering, processing, analysing, visualizing, and archiving diverse scientific data that are shared and reused in a collaborative fashion across domains and disciplines. Further, in close interaction with the Research Data Alliance (RDA), it capitalizes on open data and their liaisons to relevant EU initiatives, linking corresponding infrastructures for open government data of heightened research interest. In addition, OpenAIRE-D assumes the role of the EU infrastructure OpenAIRE for Greece, implementing specific EU-initiated Open Access policies, interlinking research data and publications, and maximizing visibility and marketability of scientific output. **OpenAIRE-D thus assists in defragmentation of national research efforts by introducing policies and regimes for data intensive cross domain research and collaboration, establishing Greece as the leading regional data-intensive research hub.**

Moreover, for managing and analysing biological data, ELIXIR-GR, addresses the needs of the Greek research community and other stakeholders of the public and the private sector such as hospitals, diagnostic centres and biotech companies, for open, integrated and state-of-the-art bioinformatics and biocomputing resources. ELIXIR-GR is the Greek National Node of the ESFRI European RI ELIXIR, a distributed e-Infrastructure aiming at the construction of a sustainable European infrastructure for biological information. Its main missions are to (a) secure storage of and access to very large datasets such as primary high throughput nucleotide sequence data and imaging data in a way that guarantees protection of sensitive personal data and of data ownership; (b) provide computational power for the analysis of very large datasets; (c) integrate available and develop new tools for analysis of biological data, based on the needs of its users; and (d) provide training in bioinformatic. The training activities of the Node cover a spectrum of topics for which there is considerable expertise, such as next-generation sequencing, non-coding RNA computational functional analysis, functional imaging data analysis, PPI network analysis, training activities related to the GALAXY environment (pipelines, virtualization, HPC), databases and knowledge discovery, data mining, large-scale genome analysis, proteomics, biomedical informatics, biostatistics, phylogenetics as well as data structures and algorithms, software engineering, programming languages, Grid/Cloud computing, and distributed/parallel algorithms. Courses are aimed primarily at the Greek community, but they are also open to international participants. Moreover, Software and Data Carpentry certified instructors from the participating institutions provide targeted courses on selected topics (Data Analysis and Visualization in R, Genomics workshops etc.) for the wider Greek community.

In addition, **ARIS (Advanced Research Information System)** is the most powerful computer system in Greece for scientific applications. It was put into operation in July 2015 by GRNET offering a powerful research tool to the Greek scientific community. The system at the beginning of its operation was included in the list of the 500 most powerful computers in the world (top500.org) and put Greece on the world map of high-performance systems. The ARIS computer system today has a maximum theoretical computing power of 535 TFlops (trillions of mathematical operations per second) and offers multiple data processing capabilities.

To date, Greece participates to the following already established and operational European RIs: PRACE, BBMRI-ERIC, EMBRC-ERIC, IINFRAFRONTIER, SHARE-ERIC, CLARIN-ERIC, DARIAH-ERIC, Euro ARGO- ERIC, CESSDA AS, EMSO, LIFEWATCH and HL-HLC. Greece participates as observer or has issued letters of support for several others under the preparatory phase and Greece fares well in EU's "Research Infrastructures" programme of Horizon 2020. RIs that are included in the National RI Roadmap are funded with approx. € 140 million from Structural Funds/ESIF and one of the criteria for funding was the relevance with the ESFRI Roadmap.

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry Key challenges in case of absence

According to the European Research Area (ERA) Progress Report for the period 2016-2018, Greece obtained its best scores on Priority 2b (Make optimal use of public investments in research infrastructures). Participating in 61 % of developing Projects, the country positioned among countries well above ERA average. Greece's performance on the share of public R&D funded privately was 7.3%, marginally above the EU-28 benchmark (7.0 %). In its national action plan for ERA, Greece planned to improve knowledge circulation, "open innovation", and the links between research, business, and education (knowledge triangle) for the benefit of the economy and society. In this area, the law for Research, Technological Development and Innovation was adopted, which aims not only to simplify procedures for subsidising research centres, but also to establish a link between the latter, universities, and the industry. In addition, according to ERA report, recently the "Research – Create – Innovate" action was set-up in Greece that promotes the collaboration between research laboratories and businesses. Furthermore, clusters, the creation of spin off companies, science parks and Technology Transfer Offices are also being promoted.

<p>HUNGARY</p>	<p>Hungary has a detailed and over-ambitious digital education strategy that together with the digital workforce programme drive the country’s digital skills initiatives in education and lifelong learning, under a tight governance scheme and mainly through EU funds. The strategies strongly focus on basic digital skills in order to help the country attain its goal of reaching the EU average. Considering that there is still no formal Open Science policy, despite the significant activity in the field, it is of no surprise that few related digital skills enhancement initiatives have been recorded. A new overarching national digital strategy that includes digital skills as a pillar is about to be published so some reorientation is expected.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

<p>A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?</p>		
Yes	No	In planning
X		X (new Digital Strategy 2021)
<p>Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences Key challenges in case of absence</p>		
<p>According to the latest DESI publication⁴⁸ Hungary ranks 21st out of 28 EU Member States. Over the last few years, its score improved broadly in line with the EU average. Hungary ranks 19th among EU countries on Human capital and is below the EU average, however no progress has been made in digital skills and in advanced specialist skills in recent years. ICT specialists account for a slightly lower proportion of the workforce as in the rest of the EU, nevertheless, 4.3% of graduates study ICT, which exceeds the EU average of 3.6%.</p> <p>The country’s digital strategy document is the National Info-communication Strategy 2014-2020⁴⁹ which includes a pillar on Digital Competencies for population, SMEs, public administration and e-inclusion with the following structure:</p>		

⁴⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=66917

⁴⁹ https://www.kormany.hu/download/5/ff/70000/NIS_EN_clear.pdf

Pillar	P2. Digital competences	type of instrument
Set of instruments	E1. Development of digital competences within the population	
Measures (actions)	A1. Reduction of the digital divide between various groups of society A2. Promotion of the dissemination of online government, public administration and e-health services to reduce the secondary digital divide; A3. Improving the quality of life of citizens with the help of ICT; A4. Development of the community internet service spaces and strengthening the correlation between public education and public internet access points	public policy, fiscal public policy, fiscal public policy, fiscal public policy, fiscal
Pillar	P2. Digital competences	type of instrument
Set of instruments	E2. Measures aiming at the enhancement of internet penetration and online presence of micro and small enterprises	
Measures (actions)	A1. Training and motivation programmes targeted at the owners and managers of micro and small enterprises	public policy, fiscal public policy, fiscal
Pillar	P2. Digital competences	type of instrument
Set of instruments	E3. Development of digital competences among public sector employees	
Measures (actions)	A1. Integration of practical e-administration skills in the public administration training (basic and high level) programmes designed for public service employees and other public sector workers A2. Support of acquiring basic and high level digital competences among public education and higher education employees (teachers, tutors working in higher education) and launch of training programmes providing special infocommunications methodology information A3. Review and repositioning of the infocommunications education	public policy, fiscal public policy, fiscal public policy

Based on the above strategy, the major policy documents that guide Digital Skills development are the **Digital Education Strategy** and the **Digital Workforce Programme**.

The **Digital Education Strategy**⁵⁰, which was launched in 2016 and forms part of the “**Digital Success Program**”, covers the entire system of education and training, including public education, vocational training, higher education, and adult learning. It also includes horizontal pillars to monitor the learning path, to help accessibility and to increase security. The most important goal of the strategy was to create the possibility of the effective dissemination of digital literacy in harmony with the sectoral strategies and professional objectives at all levels of the education system. The main strategic goals per target audience are:

- **Public education:** a high-quality and equitable public education system that prepares young people to adapt to the European and global social and economic environment for successful participation on the labour market, in higher education, and in lifelong learning, to be achieved among others via the supply of digital content, methodological support and knowledge sharing
- **Vocational education and training:** to ensure that students completing vocational education and training acquire general and vocational digital competences required by the labour market and necessary for continuing education, to be achieved among others via developing the digital competences of teachers and vocational instructors, improving infrastructures and ensuring availability of digital content.
- **Higher education:** to enable the digital preparedness, use of tools and digital work experience of higher education graduates to reach the international standards, via development of a learning platform and university life supported with digital tools that help both students and teachers and, in addition, the building of a digital learning community and development of the suitable infrastructure
- **Adult learning:** to enhance the competitiveness of the labour force, the active social participation of citizens and social inclusion by increasing society’s digital literacy level and

⁵⁰ <https://digitalisjoletprogram.hu/files/0a/6b/0a6bfcd72ccb12c909b329149ae2537.pdf>

the participation of adults in digital learning, via – among others - development of digital competences throughout the entire adult life path and increase in volume and updating of as well as easy access to high- quality digital contents and open educational aids

The strategy was highly ambitious as it aimed at Hungary reaching and exceeding the EU average by 2020. Also, according to Europe Digital Progress Report 2017, while it identifies the problem itself, the strategy did not offer means to address the low number of STEM graduates.

The Digital Workforce Programme⁵¹ was launched in 2018 and includes four pillars:

- To improve how labour market needs are measured, and how the digital economy is monitored in general.
- To develop a new digital competence framework using the EU's DigComp 2.1 framework for citizens, and integrate it into the input and output requirements of the training system.
- To focus on motivational factors through the lifelong learning support system, the expansion of e-learning and blended learning opportunities as well as through providing financial benefits and support for disadvantaged groups.
- To provide different training programmes, such as general IT training (short cycle), on-the-job training and specific training for career changers and for those without higher education.

In addition, the programme provides for National Digital Skills Councils to be set up to assist in analysing skills mismatches.

Hungary has set up the **National Coalition for Digital Skills and Jobs** (2016) to facilitate stakeholder discussions on tackling the shortage of digitally skilled people in the Hungarian labour market and help the government develop and implement adequate strategies. Alongside to that, 'digital topic weeks' are organised on a regular basis to promote digital pedagogic methodologies.

In 2020 two **new regulations** on vocational training, higher education and public education entered into force (11/2020, 12/2020) emphasising the importance of digital skills.

Finally, the government announced in June 2020⁵² that the existing Digital Strategy will be replaced by the **National Digitalisation Strategy (NDS) 2021-2027** which will be based on four pillars: digital infrastructure, digital skills, digital economy and digital state, but no further information is available at the time of writing.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

The owner of the Digital Education Strategy (and the overarching Digital Success Programme - DSP) was the **Cabinet office of the prime minister**, however responsibility for the DSP has been transferred to the **Ministry of Innovation and Technology** formed in 2018 (and DSP has been expanded to version 2.0).

To implement the strategy, the government set up the **Digital Pedagogical Methodology Centre**⁵³. Its role is to support the digital transformation of public education, provide the professional background and expert base, and support applications and priority projects.

The Digital Workforce Programme is owned by **the Ministry of National Economy**.

Other institutions involved in the country's digital skills landscape include:

⁵¹ <https://digitalisjoletprogram.hu/en/content/dwp-digital-workforce-program> - only available in Hungarian

⁵² <http://abouthungary.hu/news-in-brief/governments-new-national-digitalization-strategy-unveiled/>

⁵³ <https://dpmk.hu/>

- Ministry of Human Capacities
- DJP Nonprofit (Digitális Jólét) Nonprofit Kft⁵⁴
- IVSZ⁵⁵, the association of the Information and Communication Technologies industry in Hungary (coordinator of the National Coalition)
- KIFÜ⁵⁶, the e-Infrastructure provider for the entire research, education, and public collection communities in Hungary
- The Institute for Computer Science and Control (SZTAKI)⁵⁷

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?

Yes	No	In planning
X		
Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The digital skills governance landscape in Hungary is quite centralized, since the main policy documents are owned by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology, under the Digital Success Program. It must be noted however that Ministry of National Economy also plays a significant part in the overall governance as owner of the Digital Workforce programme.</p> <p>DJP Ltd (Digitális Jólét), a state owned company is responsible for the coordination of implementation of the DSP since 2017 and is therefore centrally placed in the governance model (under the auspices of Ministry of Innovation and Technology).</p> <p>The Digital Pedagogical Methodology Center provides professional support for the implementation of several applications to help develop and disseminate digital education. Within the framework of this task, DPMK published digital pedagogical-methodological packages and evaluates the Institutional Digital Development Plan.</p> <p>Finally, the association of ICT enterprises is also actively involved on one hand by participating in the creation of the relevant strategies and on the other hand by coordinating the National Coalition activities.</p>		
Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation		
<p>The National Infocom Strategy includes a specific chapter on monitoring system based on (not so specific) indicators and mentions that a monitoring report will be compiled and published on the website of the Government by September each year in accordance with the provisions of the Government on strategy presentation.</p> <p>No information was available on monitoring the other policy documents mentioned in section A, however it is quite safe to assume that the second version of the DSP has taken into account the results attained by that time by its predecessor.</p>		

⁵⁴ <https://djnkft.hu/>

⁵⁵ <https://old.ivsz.hu/en/about-ivsz/>

⁵⁶ <https://kifu.gov.hu/>

⁵⁷ <https://www.sztaki.hu/en/about-institute>

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018)⁵⁸, 35% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 30% towards ICT professionals, 30% towards the labour force and 5% towards citizens in general.

Main initiatives most relevant to the goals and objectives of the strategic documents on digital skills include⁵⁹:

The establishment of the **Digital Success Coordinator Center**: assists the Ministry in developing digital ecosystems, increasing the level of digital literacy and coordinating programs in this field for non-school education and professional coordination of the DSP network results, informs relevant actors, oversees and coordinates Digital Care Program Mentors (DSP Mentors). It is engaged in training and development of the information society and adult training activities related to the professional coordination of the DSP Network. Its priority tasks include:

- guiding, supervising and monitoring the functioning of the DSP Points through a unified system of requirements, assisting the work of DSP Mentors;
- professionally supporting the training and further training of DSP Mentors based on centrally developed licensed training programs;
- participation of citizens in programs and projects related to digital competence development;
- engagement in lobbying to create the operating resources of the DSP Network;
- collecting and providing data for program makers continuously

The **Digital Success Mentor Programme** (EDIOP 3.3.1) which has set up 1,500 community digital access points ('Digital Success Programme Points') with ICT trainings for those with low digital skills using around 2.100 mentors.

For the effective management and coordination of the Network, DSP Network Regional Leaders and County DSP Network Leaders help the DSP Mentors work. DSP County Executives keep active contact with DSP Points and DSP Mentors. They contribute to disseminate best practices and solutions and help to communicate between DSP Mentors and the Digital Success Coordination Centre.

Several **ESIF Operational Programmes** that support the aims of the Digital Education Strategy are implemented, sometimes supplemented with a Competitive Central- Hungary Operative Programme (CCHOP) part if they involve national scale⁶⁰.

- In STEM education the project HRDOP-3.2.5-17 "Career orientation, especially the development of MTMI skills and competences in the public education system" promotes STEM careers and new approaches in STEM education. The budget of this program is 8,00 billion HUF.
- In HRDOP - 3.2.2- CCHOP- 15 "Development of curriculum and pedagogical- methodological tools for public education" the Esterházy Károly University checks up and further develops

⁵⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=55793

⁵⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/image/document/2019-32/country_report_-_hungary_-_final_2019_0D30BE02-9661-9403-6F972D2CCBB689B0_61210.pdf

⁶⁰ http://www.eun.org/documents/411753/839549/Country+Report_Hungary_2018.pdf/50adb080-9b4b-4e91-bb32-6f5b9e3ae64e

textbooks and digital content. The budget of this program is 2,00 billion HUF. More information: <http://ofi.hu/efop-322-vekop-15-2016-00001> (in EN and HU)

- In the project HRDOP- 3.2.4-16 “Digital Competence Development” the implementing consortium aims to develop some educational administration platforms and teacher CPD courses. The sum funding of this project is 45,35 billion HUF.
- The HRDOP- 3.2.15 - CCHOP- 17 “Public educational framework-related assessment-evaluation and digital developments; development and renewal of innovative procedures in educational organization” defines the required digital competency levels to be reached by pupils at different stages of their study; this innovation affects the core curriculum. The project also develops media literacy measurement tools and prepares a nation-wide introduction. It is also an aim of the project to prepare the digital implementation of other national measurements. Besides that, the project develops benchmarks and measurement tools for institutions and teachers and affects teachers’ career advancement. The sum funding of this project is 10,56 billion HUF
- HRDOP 3.2.3-17 - CCHOP.7.3.3–17 „Digital environment in public education” is a project that helps the digital shift on the institutional level, as it supports the involved schools to develop and implement their own Institutional Digital Development Plan. The sum funding of this project is 6,36 billion HUF
- The EDIOP 6.1.2 programme “Reducing the digital divide” focusing on the digital skills development of disadvantaged persons, especially persons not possessing digital skills, of active working age (aged between 16 and 65 years), with low levels of educational attainment. The training programmes are provided on the basis of standard training programmes entitled “First steps into the digital world” (IKER, level 1) and “I use my IT device independently” (IKER, level 2), developed by the Governmental Information Technology Development Agency (KIFÜ), each with a duration of 35 contact classes. It has provided some 200,000 people with digital skills training until 2020.
- GINOP 3.3.3 program implements Digital Experience Center, such as the Alba Innovar ⁶¹ which aims to enable schoolchildren to learn about innovative digital technologies such as robotics and smart devices.

The ‘**Programme your future**’ project continued in 2019. It aims to boost the number of students that graduate in ICT and improve cooperation between the educational institutions and the ICT sector. Within the programme, three experience centres have been created (Győr, Budapest, Debrecen) to motivate pupils of primary and secondary schools to study IT and engineering. In 2019, 1,330 activities were organised in Hungary during the EU Code Week.

The government has launched two initiatives to increase the number of women in ICT. **TechGirls** is organised by the German-Hungarian Chamber of Commerce and Industry, while **Girls’ Day** is organised by the Association of Hungarian Women in Science.

Digital thematic weeks⁶² are organised on a regular basis to promote digital pedagogic methodologies. The objective of the initiative is to accelerate the digital transformation in schools through technology enriched, project-based learning, to increase the digital competencies of young people and to reach the educational objectives of the subjects defined in the national framework curriculum by the effective use of digital technologies.

⁶¹ <https://albainnovar.hu/#rolunk>

⁶² <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-skills-initiatives/digital-thematic-week-digitalis-temahet-dth>

Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)

The Centre for Digital Pedagogy and Methodology is planning to reset the curriculum to comply with Hungary Digital Competence Framework and to include digital culture subject. Also, it aims at redefining vocational training by adding a digital competence requirement level for each occupation through Sectoral Skill Councils based on DigKomp (the Hungarian Dig Comp)⁶³.

SZTAKI is organizing several training events on data use and open science that shall be extended towards FAIR data management.

KIFU will also organize training events, seminars and webinars which will be essential to connect to the wide scope of data providers and users and coordinate their data management activities through standards and guidelines

D. Current Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of the digital competence framework established:
Key challenges in case of absence

As part of the Digital Education strategy, the project “Bridge the Digital Gap” (GINOP-6.1.2) aims to provide training on basic digital skills to 260,000 people by 2020, in six regions of Hungary. The project also aims to test DigComp as a general, novel framework for digital skills. The project included a pilot phase, which translated DigComp 1.0 in Hungarian language and developed a training package for the basic two levels of DigComp with study materials and a self-assessment tool, approved by the National Office for Vocational Training and Adult Learning in May 2016. Three pilot groups tested the training package IKER I-II before it went public. IKER was redesigned and updated in 2015 based on EQF/MKKR (the national Quality Framework). By the end of 2017, almost 90,000 people had already been trained by about 280 training providers (public VET Centres, adult education providers, NGOs, for profit training institutions, language schools and even some universities⁶⁴.

The Government issued the 1341/2019. (VI. 11.) Government decree about the development and implementation of a Digital Competence Framework System based on DigiComp 2.1 to develop, measure, and certify digital competences for all.

D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?

Yes	No	In planning
	X	

Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework
Key challenges in case of absence

According to the Situation Analysis of the Digital Education Strategy (2016): The HAC (Hungarian Accreditation Committee) programme accreditation procedure does not support the national and

⁶³ https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/files/14_a.horvath_b1_digital_competences_national_examples_hungary.pdf

⁶⁴ <https://www.ikanos.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/05/DigComp-Guide-may18.pdf>

institutional accreditation (and thus independent student work in foreign languages) of national and international online programmes (online courses available to masses).

Regarding abilities, one of the most important elements is the Hungarian Qualifications Framework (HuQF), which aims at establishing a link with the European Qualifications Framework (EQF). The concept is essentially about achieving the comparability of obtained certificates and diplomas within Europe. In the long term, the HuQF aims at classifying each Hungarian qualification in a system consisting of eight levels, from public education through vocational education and training and adult learning until higher education. The Framework is still being implemented, but a number of education documents already include the HuQF classification number. Along with the denomination of the educational attainment level, the elements describing each level indicate the skills and abilities of persons holding the specific level certificate or diploma. HuQF is featured as a competence-framework.

Even though the IKER project mentions certification for the digital competences identified, information accessed did not provide any conclusive statement on the availability of such a scheme.

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?

Yes	No	In planning
	X	
Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills		
Key challenges in case of absence		
Most content providers operate via funding from ESIF projects as seen above. No online digital skills platform was identified during the desk research.		
Potential candidates for offering such a platform include the Digital Pedagogical Methodology Centre, KIFÜ and SZTAKI.		

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?

Yes	No	In planning
		X
Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country		
Key challenges in case of absence		
According to the SPARC Europe "Analysis of Open Science Policies in Europe v6" ⁶⁵ , no policy is yet in place , although the first steps have been taken in late 2017 with the formation of a joint experts committee for open science ⁶⁶ . The Committee has produced a policy draft which is currently being discussed.		
The Committee has been initiated by the President of the National Research Development Innovation Office (NRDI) with the aim of elaborating proposals for national solutions to policy and strategy tasks in relation to Open Access and Open Science, in line with the efforts of the OECD and the EU. Following organizations changes in NRDI there have been delays in producing a final recommendation document, however the Open Science Expert Committee is now beginning to be active again by drafting proposals and concepts in the following thematic areas: legislation, governmental policy, strategy, finance, organisation, communication and science assessment tasks.		

⁶⁵ <https://zenodo.org/record/4005612#.X3FUwi17EWo>

⁶⁶ <https://nkfih.gov.hu/english-2017/boards-and-committees/open-science-expert>

To support this work a special grant has been awarded to KIFU and SZTAKI to create a report on Open Science as a basis for further development in the field.

Even though there is no unified open learning policy, there are several interesting initiatives.

- Debrecen University and National Library coordinates the institutional repository DEA and the profile and research database of the University of Debrecen, which offers up-to-date information about researchers' academic achievements, scientific work and open access awareness⁶⁷ as well as advanced courses on open science practices such as research data management, open access publishing models, open access routes, open peer review, altimetric. The institution uses a MOOC platform to provide the services and prioritizes on Scholarly Publishing, Research Integrity and Metrics & Rewards.
- The Carpathian Basin Online Education Center (K-MOOC) part of the University Research and Innovation Center at Óbuda University opened in 2014, receiving support from ministerial level⁶⁸. It has achieved significant growth since then. To date, 22 Hungarian higher education institutions have joined the system, with a total of 49 courses available. 14 universities across the border participate in the initiative. This initiative has a complementary system at videotorium.hu, where some universities share their courses via multimedia form.
- Regarding other Open Science aspects, the members of the HUNOR (HUNGarian Open Access Repositories) consortium are dedicated to promoting Hungarian research both nationally and internationally and to achieving effective dissemination of scientific outputs through the implementation of a national infrastructure of open access repositories⁶⁹
- The Hungarian Research Data Alliance and its members⁷⁰ participate in several open science related activities including awareness raising, trainings, creation of the Hungarian data repository network, standardization of data services and AI research
- KIFU the Governmental Information Technology Development Agency is offering a complete spectrum of e-infrastructure services for the wide and complex user community comprising practically all of the Hungarian research, education, and public collection institutions/organizations. The rich service portfolio covers networked communication, cloud and HPC processing, FAIR storage of research data, as well as multimedia applications and provision of virtual research environments
- The Open Science portal could serve as a platform for providing digital skills training in the field, as it is quite informative and is already offering a lot of information on the subject.

The main objective of the above initiatives is to try and pool together scarce resources⁷¹ and competencies to bring about a cultural change in regard to Open Science.

Hungary has not created any regulation on Open Science. The Act on Higher Education only declares that the doctoral dissertations (and their preliminary research theses) must be accessible for everyone (Act CCIV of 2011). Furthermore, rewards for related to principles of Open Science or good research are mainly project based, rather than systematic.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved :

The owner of the forthcoming policy appears to be the National Research Development and Innovation Office.

Taking into account that there is yet no formal Open Science policy, the closest entity currently involved in open science is **the HUNOR Consortium** established by the Hungarian higher education

⁶⁷ <https://zenodo.org/record/3251731#.X3FIGi17EWo>

⁶⁸ <https://www.kmooc.uni-obuda.hu>

⁶⁹ <https://www.openaire.eu/os-hungary>

⁷⁰ <http://hrda.hu/activities>

⁷¹ At the time of writing there is only one data steward in Hungary, according to information provided during the interviews.

institutes and the Library and Information Centre of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences in 2008. The 24-member cooperation's goal is to build the national infrastructural network of the open access repositories, set up a methodological centre, implement international know-how and standards, build partnerships and implement complementary methods of scientific communication. HUNOR is coordinated by the **Debrecen University and National Library**, which has been serving as NOAD (National Open Access Desk) for the OpenAIRE project series since 2010 and is hosting the national Open Science portal⁷².

Hungarian research institutions are organized into two groups:

- There are 66 higher education institutions in the country: 22 state universities, 7 non-state universities, 5 state universities of applied sciences, 2 non-state universities of applied sciences, 1 state college, and 28 non-state colleges
- The research network of the Academy comprises 15 legally independent research institutions and more than 130 research groups at universities co-financed by the Academy

The **Library and Information Center of the Hungarian Academy of Sciences** (MTA KIK) is also a stakeholder (as a provider of eLibrary and database services) and is represented in the aforementioned Committee. It operates the Hungarian Science Bibliography (MTMT), the official state registry of research production of the country, a CRIS-like service, listing research publications as well as published datasets and citations to those. The national policy-based repository certification system is operated within the framework of MTMT. Together with SZTAKI, MTA KIK operates the national aggregator service for repositories and OJS (Open Journal Systems) based Open Access journals

The Institute for Computer Science and Control (SZTAKI) is responsible for conducting basic and application-oriented research in an interdisciplinary setting in the fields of computer science, engineering, information technology, intelligent systems, process control, wide-area networking and multimedia. Contract-based target research, development, training and expert support for domestic and foreign industrial, governmental and other partners are important activities at the Institute. The mission of SZTAKI includes the transfer of up-to-date research results and state-of-the-art technology to university students. The Institute is very active in graduate and postgraduate education, co-operating with most technical universities in Hungary and operating common chairs, postgraduate programs with them.

KIFU, is the Hungarian NREN (National Research and Education Network), representing the developers, operators, and also the users of the KIFÜ-NIIF e-Infrastructure.

E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes Key challenges in case of absence

In 2018 Hungary published its National Research Infrastructure Roadmap⁷³. It aims to identify the major research infrastructures in Hungary, provides an insight into their operation, presents the nature and diversity of domestic capacities, draws the attention of the national and international research community to Hungarian research capacities and opportunities, provides background information for setting further development directions, and outlines connection points to European infrastructures and cooperation relationship.

There is no clear utilization map of available infrastructures and it is possible that several potential users are not fully aware of all available options.

⁷² <https://openscience.hu/>

⁷³ <https://nkfih.gov.hu/national-research-infrastructure-roadmap>

Further details can be found in the “Landscape of EOSC-Related Infrastructures and Initiatives” document.

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry Key challenges in case of absence

Hungary is lagging EU average in terms of links between the Research Community and the Industry, as is evident from the European Research Area Progress Report (2018), according to which

- It suffers from a very wide gap in terms of number of academic job ads per 1000 research (2 vs 42 EU Average!)
- A low portion (35%) of the country’s researchers felt that hiring processes were open, transparent and merit-based. This performance is also far from the EU-28 benchmark
- Stable scores on researcher satisfaction with academic hiring processes meant that the country’s gap to the EU-28 level was growing wider

Cooperation between industry and academia is being facilitated by programmes managed by NRD/Office.

In Hungary, there are R&D-intensive companies that have established close, long-lasting cooperation with universities and play an active role in undergraduate and PhD training. Several multinational companies and large domestic firms triggered a remarkable growth both in expenditure and in the number of R&D personnel.

To support university-industry collaboration Centres for Higher Education and Industrial Cooperation (FIEK) were established in 2017, which are able to adapt university research programmes in applied science and innovation to industrial needs.

<p>Lithuania</p>	<p>Lithuania has one of the best scores for connectivity and digital infrastructure in the EU but its population levels of digital skills are not as high (DESI Performances 2020), despite having early policies focusing on the ‘information society’ in the 2000s. The country is gradually improving in human capital thanks to policies dedicated to reducing basic shortfalls in digital skills, narrowing the gender-gap, and investing in the up-skilling of the ICT labour force.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The Information Society Development Programme 2014 – 2020 Digital Agenda for Lithuania (which is in accordance with the Europe 2020 Initiative Digital Agenda for Europe) defines the priorities, objectives, and tasks of information society development in order to maximise the advantages provided by information and communication technologies. Among the programme’s priorities, the enhancement of the Lithuanian residents’ ability to use the ICTs, mainly by improving their digital skills and competences is identified. The main tasks for improving digital skills in Lithuania include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To enable the target groups of the Lithuanian population that until now, for different reasons, have not used or barely used modern digital tools and the internet to gain the necessary digital skills and apply them in various fields, also involving local communities into these activities • To encourage the Lithuanian population to regularly update their ICT knowledge and digital skills, to securely and purposefully use the possibilities provided by the Internet. • To make society aware of the diversity of ICT professions and encourage citizens to choose ICT-related professions, studies, and informal education programmes. • To provide more favourable conditions for teaching and learning, based on modern ICT, ensuring that the Lithuanian population has the possibility to be involved in life-long learning processes online. <p>In addition, an interinstitutional action plan for the implementation of the information society development program “Digital Agenda of the Republic of Lithuania” for 2014–2020 was launched in 2017⁷⁴ and updated in 2019⁷⁵. According to the 2019 edition the purpose of the Action Plan is to improve the quality of life of Lithuanian citizens, increase business productivity and achieve that by 2020, at least 85% of the Lithuanian population would use the Internet, and 95% of companies would use the high-speed Internet.</p> <p>The main measures foreseen in the action plan for enhancing digital skills include:</p>		
No.	Name of objective, target, measure	Participating institution/potential operators
1.	The aim is to reduce the digital divide of the Lithuanian population and to encourage them to acquire more knowledge and skills to use information and communication technologies (ICT) in a safe, intelligent, and useful way	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport, Ministry of Culture, Ministry of Economy and Innovation

⁷⁴ [https://eimin.lrv.lt/uploads/eimin/documents/files/30310_LRV%20nutarimas\(en\).pdf](https://eimin.lrv.lt/uploads/eimin/documents/files/30310_LRV%20nutarimas(en).pdf)

⁷⁵ <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/b29fd8a0fa0811e4877aa4fe9d0c24b0/asr>

1.2.	The challenge is to facilitate training and learning conditions based on modern ICT, to ensure access for Lithuanians to lifelong learning in the digital space	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport
1.2.1.	<i>Measure: Equip libraries with equipment and tools for social and information exclusion population groups</i>	Ministry of Culture
1.2.2.	<i>The tool is to enable higher and study institutions and educational institutions to use ICT through the LITNET network</i>	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport
1.2.3.	<i>The measure is to implement the Lithuanian Science and Studies Information Infrastructure Development programme (including e-LABA, EDINA, ŠVIS, etc.)</i>	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport
1.2.4.	<i>Measure: Adapt education to the needs of the information society</i>	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport
3.	The aim is to foster Lithuanian culture and Lithuanian language through ICT measures: to develop digital content based on the cultural and spoken language interfaces of Lithuanians, and to develop digital products and electronic services	Ministry of Culture, State Commission for the Lithuanian Language
3.1.	The challenge is to digitise Lithuanian cultural objects and develop publicly available digital products and electronic services on their basis, to ensure that digitized Lithuanian cultural objects are preserved for a long time, and their dissemination in Lithuania and the EU is uniform	Ministry of Culture, Ministry of Education, Science and Sport
3.1.1.	<i>The tool is to preserve and disseminate modern electronic content</i>	Ministry of Transport; Lithuanian national library of Martynas
3.1.5.	<i>Tool – To create an Electronic Archive Information System Service (EAIS) Digital Reading Room</i>	Ministry of Transport; possible executor – Office of the Lithuanian Chief Archiver
3.2.	The challenge is to develop and develop publicly available digital resources for language and writing, to deploy them to ICT and electronic services	State Lithuanian Language Commission
3.2.1.	<i>Tool – To develop the public services of the Syntax-Semantic Analysis Information System of the Lithuanian language text (SEMANTIKA 2)</i>	Ministry of Transport; potential principal – Public Institution Magnus University
3.2.2.	<i>The tool is to improve machine translation systems, develop new linguistic resources and services in order to make machine translation as relevant to the needs of society as possible, attractive, and user-friendly in everyday activities for both Lithuanian and foreign users</i>	Ministry of Transport; potential principal – Public Institution Vilnius University

Moreover, the efforts in the country for improving the digital skills agenda are mainly promoted by the National Digital Coalition for the Promotion of Digital Skills for Jobs in Lithuania, who has as mission to increase employment and to achieve a more effective use of digital potential and cooperate in implementing information society development programme 2014–2020 Digital Agenda for Lithuania. To this end, the main objectives of the Lithuanian Digital Skills policy framework include:

- 1. To substantially reduce the shortage of IT professionals, to improve the conditions for the private and public sector employees as well as all inhabitants to learn and continuously improve the necessary ICT skills for job, the establishment of IT business and development of the digital market:**
 - To (re)skill the ICT professionals according to market requirements and to encourage professionals from other fields to specialize in ICT
 - To promote e-leadership, ICT start-ups and the use of new digital opportunities in multifarious Lithuanian economy fields
 - To promote a more efficient use of available ICT infrastructure and existing services
 - To promote the development and use of open educational resources, to encourage institutions, companies, and organizations to develop and provide Internet courses
- 2. To attract more young people to choose ICT and other science studies and professions, to ensure the acquisition of digital skills also when learning other professions:**
 - To continuously improve general education, higher education, and vocational training programmes according to the labour market requirements

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To seek that the professionals that are being trained had necessary ICT skills required by the labour market ○ To reinforce the framework of digital skills training by cooperation between the representatives of business, education and other organizations ○ To include ICT training to the system of non-formal youth education <p>3. To raise public awareness of the importance of digital skills and competences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To involve the society in the dissemination activities of digital skills and competences. ○ To constantly keep the Lithuanian society informed about the importance of digital skills and competences. ○ Reaching every resident of Lithuania, jointly organize public informational campaigns and regional activities.
Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved
<p>The Lithuanian Ministry of the Economy and Innovation is the main governmental body responsible for the policy setting and coordination in the digital government domain. Other institutions involved in the country's digital skills landscape include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Ministry of Education, Science and Sport ● The Ministry of Social Security and Labour ● The Ministry of Culture ● Vilnius University, the largest higher education institution in Lithuania and one of the oldest higher education institutions in Northern Europe, which carries high-quality research-based studies covering almost all areas of science. ● Kaunas University of Technology (KTU), one of the largest technical universities in the Baltic States and one of the country's most prominent universities occupying a leading position in several research and study areas. ● The Association "Langas į ateitį", which is an organization established by socially responsible business, since 2002 developing ICT skills in Lithuania ● The Lithuanian Municipal Public Library Association, uniting most of the Lithuanian public libraries, which, beside their daily activities consult the public about the ICT skills necessary for work and encourage them to acquire these skills. ● etc

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The coordination and governance for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation in Lithuania is carried out by the Lithuanian National Digital Coalition (NDC), which was established in November 2013. The activities of the National Coalition and the relationship with other organizations are coordinated by the association "Langas į ateitį" ("Window to the Future") ,an organization established by socially responsible business, since 2002 developing ICT skills in Lithuania and promoting a safe use of the Internet as well as public and private electronic services in order to improve Lithuanian people's quality of life and to raise competitiveness in Europe and in the world. The mission of NDC in short is to increase youth employment by promoting ICT knowledge and achieve more effective use of the digital potential by cooperation in implementing information society development programme Digital Agenda for Lithuania 2014-2020. The association so far has initiated and implemented projects in which over 100,000 adults participated in ICT basics training courses funded by private business and EU SF funds. 20,000 participants graduated from the online</p>		

courses since 2008. Safer Internet trainings were attended by 5,000 school community members and librarians.

It is pointed out that the association "Window to the Future" was awarded the finalist medal by the European Commission's 2008 e. in the E-inclusion Award 2008 and even won the Digital Literacy category in this competition. Over 450 projects took part in the competition, and Lithuania is the only country from the new EU member states among the winners.

Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation

Currently there are not in place formal tools for performance & impact measurement of the digital skills initiatives in Lithuania. However, the coordinator association "Langas į ateitį" ("Window to the Future") is systematically monitoring and assessing the results and impacts of the digital skills initiatives/projects implemented in the country, with an aim to utilise lessons learnt and avoid past mistakes, hence improve the overall digital skills policy planning framework. It is pointed out that for monitoring KPIs of Lithuanian Digital agenda statistics⁷⁶ are used.

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 10% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 20% towards ICT professionals, 20% towards the labour force and 50% towards citizens in general.

Lithuania's activities on e-skills are concentrating on distance learning education and PIAPs. The Lithuanian Information Society Development Programme for 2011-2019 makes explicit mention of ICT practitioner skills. Lithuania has a range of activities covering the full spectrum of digital literacy activities, with the Programme for Universal Computer Literacy at its core.

The main digital skills initiatives implemented in the country are within the project "**Connected Lithuania**". The goal of the project "Connected Lithuania: Efficient, Secure and Responsible Lithuanian Digital Community" is to help the population learn to use information technologies and the Internet efficiently, safely, and responsibly and the opportunities it provides. The project started in 2018, has a duration of 3 years and takes place in every municipality in Lithuania (<http://prisijungusi.lt>).

The project is implemented throughout Lithuania and is intended for a large target group of the population - about 500,000 individuals, who still do not use the Internet or whose digital skills are insufficient. To train so many people, "digital leaders" and a "e. Scouts" (volunteer) network of at least 2,000 people are mobilised. In addition, 1,200 librarians of the country are also invited to join this network, who advise the population on renewable public Internet access points. The project is extremely large - about 750 local communities are invited to it, 10,000 counselling and training events in public Internet access point libraries will be organised, where about 100,000 people will take part in these events. To ensure the continuity of the activities launched, "digital leaders" and "e. Scouts" will be able to further counsel members of the community on their own. This decision was made based on the experience of previous years, when at the end of the training a significant part of the project participants "dropped out" and did not use the acquired skills. In this case, project participants will be able to constantly seek help and receive consultations. Various community events and EU-wide national actions to promote digital skills, such as Safer Internet Week, Safer Internet Week, Programming Week and Senior Citizens' Day on the Internet, will help to strengthen

⁷⁶ <https://ivpk.lrv.lt/lt/veiklos-sritys-1/informacines-visuomenes-statistika>

the interest of communities and individuals involved in projects. "Girls and Technology" and so on. Another group of events is dedicated to young people. The project will organize creative ICT competitions, creative workshops ("hackathons") and other events for young people. They will encourage students to take a more detailed interest in information technology, programming, develop creativity and self-expression; and will also promote volunteering by inviting you to become part of the project "e. scouts" network and contribute to the development of digital skills of members of the local community in public Internet access points. Training materials are being developed or updated to achieve all these goals. Much of it is published in a learning website of the responsible body, i.e. the association "Langas j ateitj" ("Window to the Future"). The project envisages the use of the infrastructure of public Internet access points in libraries for the digital education of the population, which will be renewed during the LNL project "Encouraging the population to use the Internet intelligently in the renewed public Internet access infrastructure". The project is financed by the European Regional Development Fund and the state budget of the Republic of Lithuania.

The activity of "Window to the Future", as an example of cooperation between private business and the state in achieving common goals, has become an excellent story of Lithuania's success in presenting our country to the world.

In addition, through the National Skills Strategy project (2020-2021)⁷⁷, Lithuania has started collaboration with the OECD and European Commission to develop a more strategic, whole-of-government and cross-sectoral approach to skills policy. The main objective of the Skills Strategy project for Lithuania is to identify the main opportunities and develop tailored policy recommendations for improving Lithuania's skills performance in collaboration with the Lithuanian government and stakeholders. In order to achieve this objective, the representatives of 4 ministries as well as other stakeholders have agreed on 4 priority areas of focus for the Skills Strategy project. During the strategic seminar it was decided that Lithuania's Skills Strategy will focus on these broad main topics Priority 1: Equipping young people with skills for work and life Priority 2: Raising adults' and enterprises' participation in learning Priority 3: Using people's skills more effectively in workplaces Priority 4: Strengthening the governance of skills policies. The strategy will also include two horizontal themes: developing key competencies, including in non-formal learning and reducing skills imbalances in the economy.

OECD and Lithuania will proceed with the development of National Skills Strategy by:

- Mapping the main actors and responsibilities and interactions in Lithuania's skills system
- Undertaking in-depth analysis of international and national data and evidence
- Facilitating constructive whole-of-government and cross-sectoral dialogue and engagement in Lithuania
- Identifying relevant national and international best practices for Lithuania
- Testing and refining specific recommendations for Lithuania's skills system; and
- Raising awareness of the importance of and opportunities for improving Lithuania's skills performance.

The OECD will assess the performance of Lithuania's skills system, based on a combination of desktop research and direct engagement with officials and stakeholders. The OECD will support Lithuania with a collaborative and tailored OECD Skills Strategy project in 2020-2021.

Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)

⁷⁷ <https://strata.gov.lt/en/news/29-news/692-lithuania-has-launched-lithuanian-skills-strategy-project>

The main initiative specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives in Lithuania includes **Project “Up2U”⁷⁸**. The key objective of the project is to bridge the gap between secondary schools and higher education & research by better integrating formal and informal learning scenarios and adapting both the technology and the methodology that students will most likely be facing in universities. The project is funded by Horizon 2020, that target groups include High school students and teachers, and the duration is from 2017 up to 2019. Project results at the end of 2018 include the Integrated Application Toolbox developed by Up2U that will facilitate the availability of tools and services for the learning community. It is expected to enable both educators and learners to create cross-boundary digital learning paths by interacting with the infrastructure services and OERs via their own devices.

D. Current Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?

Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of the digital competence framework established		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The Translation of the DigComp framework in Lithuania is implemented by the Education Development Centre. The Education Development Centre (EDC) is the biggest institution affiliate to the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport of the Republic of Lithuania providing educational support in the field of pre-school, primary and general education. Its areas of activity include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participates in the development and implementation of educational content, coordinates the adaptation of educational content to groups of learners with different needs. Coordinates and initiates the development, search, systematization, implementation, and dissemination of educational methodological material. • Analyses the tendencies of changes in the curriculum of Lithuania and other countries and educational innovations, prepares measures for the improvement of the curriculum. Initiates and prepares measures for teachers' career planning, initiates innovations in the field of pedagogical qualification improvement. • Implements the quality assurance of educational content, by organising and carrying out the assessment of the suitability of textbooks and other teaching aids for use in the educational process as well as submitting proposals to the Ministry of Education and Science regarding quality assurance measures in education and their implementation. • Provides information, consulting and other educational assistance to education providers implementing educational programs. Provides consulting services and educational assistance to the educational community and partners. • Implements the quality assurance of in-service training of pedagogical staff, initiates and implements in-service training programs for pedagogical staff • Participates in the development of a system of continuous (continuous) learning and in-service training of pedagogical staff. Organizes in-service training of pedagogical staff. 		

D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?

Yes	No	In planning
	X	
Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework		

⁷⁸ Website: <https://up2university.eu>

Key challenges in case of absence
Currently in Lithuania there are no visible improvements in transparency of digital qualifications: credit transfer between formal, non-formal and industry-based ICT educations and certifications and there is no mechanism to implement discussions about the recognition of informal education on ICT/digital skills.

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?

Yes	No	In planning
		X

Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills
Key challenges in case of absence

<p>The National Association of Distance Education (NADE) was established in July 1998 with the purpose to promote the creation of the Information Society of Lithuania by developing distance education (DE) and improving its quality. The major goal of NADE is to provide equal learning opportunities to all Lithuanian citizens, despite their place of living. Among its many activities are organizing distance education courses, preparing, and adapting distance education programs, promotion of research in the field of distance education and organizing workshops, seminars and conferences. NADE is also involved in the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • collects and disseminates information about distance education events, projects, and methods to ensure distance education efficiency • explores regional supply and demand for studies and courses in the field of pre-qualification, vocational education, post-secondary, and higher education • collaborates with public information providers and disseminators, other institutions and enterprises, persons concerned • organizes distance education courses, carries out efficiency research and other applied distance education research in regional study and study support centers, other institutions • organizes workshops, seminars, conferences for distance education tutors and organizers • takes care of the preparation, adaptation and improvement of distance education programs • disseminates information about distance education development in the world, Europe, Lithuania • carries out research in the field of distance education organization, management and academic affairs • informs University, Lithuanian Distance Education Study Centre, and other partners about significant distance education events
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E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country
Key challenges in case of absence

Lithuania has a Law on Higher Education and Research, which covers Open Access and research data, while the more relevant policy document on Research, Data, and Open science is the Research Council of Lithuania's "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Data" (2016) ⁷⁹ , which cover both publications and data. Skills are not addressed, but responsibilities for various aspects of

⁷⁹ Research Council of Lithuania, Resolution regarding the approval of the Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Data, 29 February 2016, No. VIII-2, Vilnius

Open Access and Open Data are covered in detail. The focus of Lithuania's policy on Research, Data, and Open science is more on rights than on obligations, and the inference is that universities are responsible for developing their own policies, procedures, guidance, and monitoring systems.

In Lithuania, the public and private institutions are required by law to make any research results public⁸⁰. In particular, to ensure transparent use of funds and the quality of the research conducted using the funds from the state budget and to foster research development, all the results of research conducted in state research and education institutions should be made public (on the Internet or by other means) insofar as it is consistent with the laws regulating intellectual property rights and commercial, state and public service secrecy protection. The results of research conducted using the funds from the state budget in private research and education institutions should be made public (on the Internet or by other means) insofar as it is consistent with the laws regulating intellectual property rights, commercial and state secrecy protection.

Today, the following open access databases are available in Lithuania:

- **National aggregated open access repository** – the Lithuanian Academic Electronic Library eLABa; this information system includes e-documents, such as theses and dissertations ETD. The installation of the repository and its development is the responsibility of the Lithuanian Research Library Consortium (LMBA) and the Lithuanian Research Library Informational Research and Study Infrastructure Maintenance and Development Consortium (LABIIMSPPK); The data stored in the Lithuanian Academic Electronic Library eLABa becomes accessible in international aggregated databases DART-Europe, DRIVER, NDLTD and others;
- **Inter-institutional research publication and research data archives:** The Lithuanian humanities and social sciences research data archive LIDA, the full-text database Litanistika, the national open access research data archive (MIDAS);
- **Institutional research databases:** The Registry of Open Access Repositories Mandatory Archiving Policies, ROARMAP, states that there are 3 institutional repositories in Lithuania: the Lithuanian University of Health Sciences, Vytautas Magnus University and Mykolas Romeris University open access databases.

The Lithuanian research and higher education institutions participate in international projects and initiatives on open access: 7th Framework Programme projects OpenAIRE and OpenAIREplus.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

The Research Council of Lithuania is the institution coordinating open access activities in Lithuania. The decision was made on the submission of the Ministry of Education and Science and in response to the 2013 request made by the Secretariat of the Lithuanian National Commission for UNESCO to appoint the institution responsible for open access to research information. The Council collects and systematises the data on open access databases used in Lithuania, on legal, financial, and other developmental aspects, participates in the open access policy formation and encourages dissemination of the open access concept. The Research Council of Lithuania and the Ministry of Education and Science appoint Lithuanian representatives to the European Commission (EC) national representatives for research data group. The group was initiated in the end of 2013 on the EC initiative while implementing the 17 July 2012 recommendation for open access to research data and its preservation (2012/417/ES).

In 2014, the Research Council of Lithuania became a partner of the international project 'Open Access Policy Alignment Strategies for European Union Researchers'. The working group for open access to research data and the research group under the Lithuanian National Commission for UNESCO distributed their 'Request to the Lithuanian science and higher education institutions on

⁸⁰ Republic of Lithuania Law on Science and Studies, Article 45

open access to research data', in which they stated having noticed attempts in forming the open access policy, preparing provisions and recommendations for open access to university research papers and results, organising seminars for the science community and disseminating the information on open access and its benefits to the society.

E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes Key challenges in case of absence

The European Commission and ESFRI encourage Member States and Associated Countries to develop national roadmaps for research infrastructures (RIs). These roadmaps are vital blueprints which enable countries to set national priorities and to earmark funds for both national and pan-European RIs including ESFRI ones. In this context, in Lithuania the Roadmap was published in 2011 and updated in 2015.

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry Key challenges in case of absence

According to the European Research Area (ERA) Progress Report for the period 2016-2018, Lithuania's performances are consistently just below ERA averages in several priorities, including Priority 2b (Make optimal use of public investments in research infrastructures), Priority 3 (An open labour market for researchers) and Priority 5b (Open access). Lithuania's performance in terms of knowledge transfer indicators is mixed. The country's score on the share of public R&D funded privately placed it in Cluster 1. At 13.2%, it was almost 90% higher than the EU-28 score. At the same time, the number of public-private collaborative papers per capita was about 90% less than the EU-28 average, placing Lithuania in the group of countries just below the ERA average. Noteworthy annual average decrease in scores were found for shares of firms cooperating with governmental, public, or private research institutes (33% decrease), and for shares of firms collaborating with universities or higher education institutions (35% decrease). These contrasted with marginal growths recorded at the EU-28 level. Additionally, the strong performance on the share public R&D funded privately appeared to be at risk for Lithuania, with a 10.5 % average annual decline observed over the 2013-2015 period, compared to a much smaller decline for the Member States taken together.

Moreover, the links between the research community and the Industry activity are also supported by Lithuania's vibrant cluster community. Clusters first appeared in Lithuania several decades ago, but the pace of clusterisation increased dramatically during the period 2010–2015, with the implementation of EU financial instruments supporting their development. Although the majority of Lithuania's clusters are still young and relatively small, with an average of 13 members, the largest clusters comprise 30 members or more. Clusters are mainly composed of small and medium-sized companies. Members are located in 34 cities and towns, with the greatest concentration in Lithuania's largest cities, Vilnius, and Kaunas. Overall Lithuania's clusters and their spheres of activity is depicted in the figure below:

<p>Portugal</p>	<p>Even though Portugal is not far from the European median in terms of digital skills, it needs to reinforce them. Portugal's training infrastructures and the strong potential of its human resources make this a viable task. To this end, in 2017 the Portuguese government established the "National Digital Competences Initiative e.2030, Portugal INCoDe.2030", an integrated public policy to enhance and foster digital competences. Portugal INCoDe.2030 focuses on skill formation in education and training for individuals rather than for businesses: it offers schemes for citizens, the elderly and disadvantaged groups.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The Portuguese ICT Strategy 2020, approved in 2017, is the main strategic document that reflects the digital transformation of the Portuguese Public Administration until 2020. This Strategy comprises of three main axes a) Promotion and integration and interoperability, b) Innovation and competitiveness and c) Resource sharing and investment in digital competences. The 3rd axis that focuses on improving the quality of public services and promoting public administration higher efficiency implies a better use of skills and resources. In this context, the following measure is included with regards to digital skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure 9: ICT centre of competences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Define the operation model and drive the development of an ICT centre of competences ○ Promote the development of Digital Competences <p>Moreover, with regards to Digital Skills, the "Portugal INCoDe.2030⁸¹" inter-ministerial action, launched in April 2017, addresses the concept of digital competences in a broad manner. It includes the notion of digital literacy (i.e. the ability to access digital media and ICT, to understand and critically assess contents, and to communicate effectively), as well as the production of new knowledge through research. It brings together the areas of Administrative Modernisation, Science, Technology and Higher Education, Education, Labour, Planning and Infrastructures and Economy, aiming to strengthen the basic skills of the population in ICT. Actually, it reflects the national policy on digital skills and is structured around five main axes: Inclusion, Education, Qualification, Specialisation and Research aggregating a variety of measures to be implemented by different institutions in collaboration with the private sector, academia, and civil society. The fifth axis specifically targets research, providing the conditions to produce new knowledge and an active participation in international R&D networks and programmes.</p> <p>The big challenges for Portugal around digital competences focus on qualifying the population in digital competences. A set of goals has been established covering factors such as digital literacy, physical and cognitive access to digital services, analytical capacity in the context of big data, production and dissemination of information, privacy and security, intensive use of ICT in the process of lifelong learning and R&D aimed at the production of knowledge and advanced forms of scientific computing. The aim is to put Portugal among the leading European countries in digital competences,</p>		

⁸¹ <https://www.incode2030.gov.pt/>

by overcoming one main challenge; ensure strong participation in international R&D networks and the production of knowledge in digital areas.
Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved
The Minister of the Presidency and of Administrative Modernisation is responsible for the modernisation of public administration and digital government. Other institutions involved in the country's digital skills landscape include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Labour, Solidarity and Social Security • The Ministry of Education • The Directorate-General for Employment and Labour Relations (DGERT) • The Directorate General for Higher Education (DGES) • The Directorate General for Education (DGE) • The Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education (ANQEP) • The Institute of Employment and Vocational Training (IEFP) • The Administrative Modernisation Agency (AMA) • The National Institute for Administration (INA) • The Agency for Competitiveness and Innovation (IAPMEI)

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation		
Key challenges in case of absence		
The INCoDe.2030 initiative, as the main public policy tool for digital skills in Portugal, is structured as an integrated programme, bringing together and encouraging collaboration between people with different experience and knowledge as well as multiple public and private organisations. The promotion and coordination of INCoDe.2030 involves three permanent bodies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Forum for Digital Competences, which is responsible for gathering and coordinating a broad range of private and public companies and institutions to ensure widespread mobilisation for the initiative, as well as of organising an annual conference in which the developments in each line of action are presented and analysed in the context of national and international success stories and good practices. • The INCoDe.2030 Coordination Structure, which oversees the lines of action and also the initiative as a whole, promoting and coordinating the activities in each action line to guarantee a common focus and purpose, updating the general and specific goals and objectives. • The INCoDe.2030 Technical Secretariat, which monitors, records and reports on the implementation of all the planned activities, developing the necessary platforms for their development and communication, in close articulation with the Coordination Structure and the Forum for Digital Competences 		
Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation		
An Observatory for Digital Competences has been set up by the Directorate-General for Statistics in Education and Science (DGEEC), which, in collaboration with the National Institute for Statistics (INE), monitors and reports on the programme's development, through a set of indicators divided into 4 categories: access, human potential, use and investment, as follows: <u>Access</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of households with internet access • % of individuals who have never used the internet 		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of individuals who frequently use the internet
<u>Human Capital</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of individuals with basic or better-than-basic digital skills • % of ICT specialists in employment
<u>Use</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of employees who use computers with an internet connection at work • % of SMEs with a high level of digital intensity • % of individuals who have used the internet to use online public services (last 12 months)
<u>Investment</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total expenditure on R&D as a function of GDP (GERD) - % • Business expenditure on R&D as a function of GDP (BERD) - %

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018), 25% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 25% towards ICT professionals, 25% towards the labour force and 25% towards citizens in general.

The INCoDe.2030 covers a wide range of measures involving the various governmental areas, as presented below. The main initiatives implemented under the inclusion, education and qualification measures include:

Inclusion: Making sure the whole population has equal access to digital technologies to obtain information, communicate, and interact with others.

- Digital Skills for Citizenship Training: Partnership between the Portuguese Electrotechnical Institute, the Administrative Modernization Agency and the Training Centre of Electronic, Energy, Telecommunication, and Information Technology.
- Inclusion training – basic skills: Made available by the Institute for Employment and Vocational Training
- Digital expertise self-diagnosis tool – disadvantaged groups: Developed by the School of Technology and Management of Viseu.
- Mentors for Digital Inclusion – National Programme: Promoted by the Faculty of Psychology and Education Sciences of the University of Porto.
- Creative Communities for Digital Inclusion: Fundamental structure of the 1st action line, they are essential in the development of pilot projects to be promoted around the country. Currently, there are 10 CCDI, integrating 750 people who benefit from training given by 40 different mentors.

Education: Educating the younger population by stimulating and reinforcing digital literacy and digital skills at all levels of schooling and as part of lifelong learning.

- Computing: Development of “computational thinking” programmes for primary education, in collaboration with the Ministry of Education and with the Portuguese Association of Computing Teachers.
- Primary School: Development of pilot projects in ICT education for primary schools, municipalities, in partnership with the Ministry of Education, Higher Schooling institutions and companies.
- Special Needs: Digital inclusion in special needs’ programmes in education and practical training, namely at 25 resources centres, which provide support to 1047 students.

- Information and Communication Technologies: Curricular integration of ICT in primary and secondary courses, including programming, robotics, and digital literacy.

Qualification: Qualifying the working population by providing them with the knowledge they need to become a part of a labour market that relies heavily on digital skills.

- Capacitar i4.0: Qualification programme to prepare people and organizations for the 4th Industrial Revolution's challenges.
- Qualifica IT: Retraining course for graduates in areas not related to IT, promoted by the School of Engineering of the University of Minho.
- SWitCH: Requalification programme for STEM graduates, promoted by Porto Tech Hub and Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto.
- Acertar o Rumo: IT training programme for graduates in insecure work conditions.
- Apostar em TI: Requalification programme for people interested in IT.
- Code Academy: Code training bootcamps for youth and adults.
- Low Code Developer: Technical course for STEM graduates' new skills, by Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco.
- "Infoexclusion Zero" Project: Online self-diagnosis tool to identify Public Administration workers' digital literacy level.

Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)

As already discussed, the INCoDe.2030 initiative covers a wide range of measures on specialisation and research. The main initiatives implemented under these two measures include:

Specialisation: Promoting specialisation in digital technologies and applications to improve employability and create higher added value in the economy.

- Companies and Polytechnics: Promotion of Technical Courses for Professional Specialization, through a partnership between Business Association of Baixo Ave and Polytechnic Institutes.
- Plataforma NAU: Distance learning and training for Public Administration, including Massive Open Online Courses, with topics such as Bullying and Cyber Bullying, curricular autonomy, and flexibility.
- Cursos Técnicos de Especialização Profissional: Significant increase of IT Technical Courses for Professional Specialization, and significant increase of IT and STEM, outside Lisbon and Oporto.

Research: Providing the conditions to produce new knowledge and an active participation in international R&D networks and programmes

- Advanced Computing Portugal 2030: Dynamic and evolutive process aimed to promote and expand Advanced Cyberinfrastructure (ACI) in Portugal by a factor of 100 in the coming decade and until 2030.
- AI Portugal 2030: An innovation and growth strategy to foster Artificial Intelligence in Portugal in the European context.

It is pointed out for these two initiatives in the research field, **dedicated strategies have been developed.** In particular:

Advanced Computing Portugal 2030⁸² is a dynamic and evolutive process aimed to promote and expand Advanced Cyberinfrastructure (ACI) in Portugal by a factor of 100 in the coming decade and

⁸² https://www.incode2030.gov.pt/sites/default/files/triptico_acp_4jul_v2.pdf

until 2030. It considers close international collaborative actions and has been planned in a way to foster all advanced scientific computing fields, as well as mobilizing data processing in an effective and diversified way, among industry and academic communities and in all areas of knowledge and the economy, including health, climate, energy, mobility, and the study of social processes. ACP.2030 is a science, innovation, and growth strategy that aims to foster Advanced Computing in Portugal in the European context, oriented **towards building a high-performance computing world-reference network infrastructure**. The strategy comprehends three main areas of intervention:

- to create an infrastructure of supercomputing in the country at the service of research and innovation
- to develop and retain high valued people with strong advanced computing skills; and
- to put in place an info-structure of public policies to fill the gap between the infrastructures and people in a way that fosters the creation of high valued services and software.

The main general objectives of the **AI Portugal 2030 strategy** are to reach by 2030 the following.

- **Added Economic Growth:** the added value brought by AI technologies to the economic growth should be significant.
- **Scientific Excellence:** improve the front-line position in fundamental and applied AI research of the Portuguese Academia (universities, polytechnic schools, and research institutions) measured in terms of publication impact, international leaderships, and international collaborations.
- **Human Development:** Increase dramatically the qualifications of the labour force, in particular the technological qualifications, while promoting inclusion and awareness at all levels of education.

In this context, the strategy revolves around four main interacting processes.

- The attractiveness of Portugal for knowledge intensive young companies and international production units is high and has the conditions for improvement. These units work in different sectors but have the need for development of specialised AI software and high-tech devices for export in common. The collaboration with academia is growing in two axes: joint research uptake (joint projects and CoLabs) and the qualification pipeline.
- The development of this ecosystem will motivate the increase of the currently developing innovation levels for a vast number of companies and organisations, including start-ups, SMEs, and the Government Sector through business networking and by benefiting from the maturing collaboration platforms with academia. These include AI-on-demand pipelines and Digital Innovation Hubs. Expected outcomes include an increase in the number of patents and the multiplication of innovation-based businesses.
- The research potential in AI and other areas will grow due to the larger share of private investment and because of the added value induced by the challenges brought by innovating companies. Moreover, researchers will gain insight into the future of AI itself as a fundamental scientific field. **Expected outcomes are a higher attraction of research talent, a higher impact of scientific publications and an increased ability to join international research networks of excellence.** These scientific results will in turn revert to the productive sectors.
- Academia alone and in collaboration with the Industry will increase its capacity and develop different levels of qualification programmes in AI and related areas. **Other educational institutions working at different education levels will also be motivated to invest in skilling, reskilling and lifelong learning aiming at tailored qualifications.** As an outcome, Portugal will increase the qualification levels of its professionals and increase the level of knowledge-intensive employment.

D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of the digital competence framework established Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The INCoDe.2030 programme in October 2019 released the Digital Competence Dynamic Reference Framework (QDRCD) a tool for population' digital skills' evaluation. Based on the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens (DIGICOMP⁸³) the QDRCD has three objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to support the definition of policies and strategies • to design education programmes; and • to evaluate and certificate skills, either by self-diagnosis or by certifying entities. <p>Information Literacy, Communication and Citizenship, Content Creation, Security and Privacy, and Solutions Development are the five competences areas addressed, which level of proficiency, including examples of daily use, ranges from basic to highly specialized. The document was developed with the collaboration of the National Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education (ANQEP), the Directorate-General for Education (DGE), Directorate-General for the Qualification of Public Workers (INA), Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Employment and Professional Training Institute (IEFP) and António Moreira and Margarida Lucas, both from University of Aveiro.</p>		

D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The National Qualifications System (SNQ) was created in December 2007 with primary objective to raise the qualification levels of the active population, through school and professional progression, as well as to structure an initial and continuous educational and training offer for young people and adults, adjusted to the needs of companies and the labour market. The National Qualifications System (SNQ) is coordinated by the National Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education (ANQEP) and works in conjunction with the European Qualifications Framework to promote the improvement of the basic training of the active population through school and professional progression. The SNQ also includes (among others) the Directorate-General for Employment and Labour Relations (DGERT), which is the coordinating body of the competent authorities for the purposes of recognition of professional qualifications, and the Institute of Employment and Vocational Training (IEFP), which is the contact point for matters regarding the recognition of professional qualifications. The Decree-Law no. 88/2006 regulates Technological Specialization Courses.</p>		

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills		

⁸³ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-research-reports/digcomp-21-digital-competence-framework-citizens-eight-proficiency-levels-and-examples-use>

Key challenges in case of absence
<p>Foundation for Science and Technology - FCT is the national funding agency for science, technology, and innovation under responsibility of the Ministry for Education and Science. FCT coordinates public policy for the Information and Knowledge Society in Portugal and ensures the development of national scientific computing resources. In this regard, it is FCT's mission to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of and engage stakeholders in Information Society public policies, through dissemination, research, and training activities • Encourage the development of e-Science, by promoting the creation of knowledge and the scientific and technological development of businesses and R&D national institutions • Promote cooperation with foreign organisations, namely within the European Union and Portuguese-speaking countries <p>FCT allocates funding to different types of activities and through various instruments: research projects, advanced training, scientific employment, research units, international cooperation. With regards to advanced training, FCT supports around 5,560 PhD, post-doctoral and other scholarship grant holders. In 2019, advanced training grants represented an investment of 98M €. The number of postdoctoral fellowships has decreased over the past 3 years with its progressive replacement by scientific employment contracts under Decree-Law 57/2016, amended by Law 57/201, reflecting better working conditions for doctoral researchers.</p> <p>Moreover, IDTFF - Centre for Research in Didactics and Technology in the Training of Trainers, is a Research Unit based in the Department of Education and Psychology of the University of Aveiro which mission anchored in the responsibility of research in education: to produce knowledge capable of contributing to the formation of capable and critical citizens and to the creation of a better world. CIDTFF is financed by National Funds through FCT, within the scope of related projects⁸⁴.</p> <p>Furthermore, Project NAU is a national initiative, led by FCT, which includes the development and operation of a platform for distance education and training for large audiences. Thus, this technical and operational infrastructure allows the publication and promotion of distance courses for large audiences, usually called MOOC courses 'Massive Open Online Course', oriented to Public Administration and Higher Education. The platform can be used by all citizens and professional groups to who public administration intends to deliver training and strengthen competencies, or for those who would like to pursue lifelong learning. The platform contents are multilingual (Portuguese and English), but with predominance of the Portuguese language and include, among others, courses with scientific content, such as data processing, for researchers and university students; courses aimed at health professionals or welcoming foreign workers are some possible examples. NAU will bring the public administration closer to citizens and it can be a privileged vehicle for dissemination and expansion of the Portuguese culture, as well as a reference in distance education, where anyone can expand their knowledge and learn about the world.</p>

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?		
Yes	No	In planning
		X
Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country		
Key challenges in case of absence		
Portugal is showing good results in some innovation indicators (including but not limited to AI), although in many of them we have been typically placed below the average of the European Union.		

⁸⁴ The UIDB / 00194/2020 and UIDP / 00194/2020 projects (<https://www.ua.pt/pt/cidtff/>)

Portuguese institutions are particularly well positioned in terms of international research collaborations, broadband penetration, and product/process innovations in SMEs. Portugal has been relatively successful as an innovation-friendly environment and has an attractive research system.

Moreover, Portuguese research has a high level of international collaboration (185% of the EU average in 2017) participating in the 10% most cited works (82.6%) and in the attraction of foreign PhD students (98.3%). Also the R&D expenditure of the business sector has considerably improved since 2015 and represents about 52% of gross expenditure in R&D. SMEs are doing quite well in innovations in the product or the process (158.8%) and in marketing/organisation levels (112%).

A preparation of a National Policy for Open Science is underway in Portugal. The work is initiated by the Government and Ministry for Science, Technology and Higher Education. The website set up for Open Science in Portugal, describes the four pillars of the policy to be:

- (1) transparency in practices, methodology, observation, and data collection,
- (2) public availability and re-use of scientific data,
- (3) public access and transparency in scientific communication,
- (4) use of web-based tools to facilitate scientific collaboration.

The Foundation for Science and Technology - FCT (the national research funder) has a policy on management and sharing of data and other results arising from FCT-funded research. In practice this is a general, aspirational call for researchers to share their data, and not a mandatory policy. The policy document is brief, at under two pages in length, and very much on the soft (suggest and encourage) end of the scale. It “encourages researchers to make available the data resulting from R&D projects it finances in appropriate Open Access databases, where possible,” with scope for opting out if the nature of the data does not lend itself to open sharing. The focus is on sharing data (and other research outputs, such as samples and software models) with other researchers. The policy suggests that a data management plan should be produced, proposing a basic template/table of contents, and that best practice be followed for whichever scientific discipline the research sits closest to. The only mandatory element of the policy is that FCT must be credited as a funder of any dataset made openly available.

Skills are not addressed in the document, and – given the soft, aspirational approach – compliance is not covered either, but the document is clear that the policy will continue to be developed in order to converge with international best practices, in particular with the initiatives of this domain that may be established within the European Union.

In 2016, Portugal adopted ‘Fostering Scientific Employment’ (Decree-Law 57/2016) aiming to improve researchers' working conditions, career prospects and promote the employment of PhD holders. The measure was taken to overcome challenges associated with a high emigration rate of graduates and highly unstable research careers.

Moreover, according to the European Research Area (ERA) Progress Report for the period 2016-2018m Portugal had 43 % of its 2016 scientific papers published under Open Access (OA) arrangements, irrespective of the mechanism. This score is below the ERA average and the EU-28 benchmark. A similar pattern was found for the country for its share of Gold OA articles. The gap in performance to the EU-28 benchmark was smaller from Green OA papers, and here Portugal positioned itself above the ERA average. Portugal's share of life science papers with OA datasets experienced a downward trend since the last ERA monitoring exercise, seven percentage points below the EU-28 trajectory, bringing about further loss in ground to the other Member States.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

- Ministry for Science, Technology and Higher Education
- Foundation for Science and Technology. FCT supports the scientific community in Portugal through a range of funding schemes, tailored for individual scientists, research teams or R&D centres. Through its funding schemes, FCT supports graduate education, research and development, establishment and access to research infrastructures, networking and international collaborations, conferences and meetings, science communication and interactions with industry.

**E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes
Key challenges in case of absence**

The European Commission and ESFRI encourage Member States and Associated Countries to develop national roadmaps for research infrastructures (RIs). These roadmaps are vital blueprints which enable countries to set national priorities and to earmark funds for both national and pan-European RIs including ESFRI ones. In this context, in Portugal the Roadmap was published in 2014 and updated in 2020. Its main objectives is to act as a reference document on a national scale, aiming to guide and prioritize national and regional investments, safeguarding future infrastructures of strategic relevance, fostering their ability for international insertion, and thereby increasing the capacity for Research and Innovation, both nationally and regionally. There are in total 56 research infrastructures (RIs) in the Portuguese Roadmap that have the potential to be, or to become in the near future, national and international reference hubs, in many cases in close coordination with the respective European infrastructures, notably those included in the ESFRI Roadmap. With regards to digital research infrastructures there are currently 4 underway in the country:

- **INCD Portuguese National Distributed Computing Infrastructure** (Total Public Investment: 2,742,246 €). INCD provides computing and data-oriented services aimed to support leading edge research in all scientific domains. INCD offers a comprehensive portfolio of services that includes among others: cloud computing, high throughput computing and high -performance computing. INCD services are federated with other European and international digital infrastructures
- **RCTS Science, Technology and Society Network** (Total Public Investment:17,243,185 €). The Science, Technology and Society Network (RCTS) is the Portuguese National Research and Education Network (NREN). A dedicated high-performance network intended to serve researchers with greater demands, teachers, and students, acting as a platform for advanced communications services and applications. RCTS interconnects with other research and higher education networks through GÉANT. It provides a privileged collaboration channel for Portuguese researchers to access foreign research infrastructures, data sets and services. RCTS is managed by FCCN, a FCT unit dedicated to horizontal research digital infrastructure.
- **RNCA National Advance Computing Network** (Total Public Investment: n/a). The National Advanced Computing Network (RNCA) offers advanced computing services to research and innovation communities. Created in 2018 as part of the Portuguese digital competence's initiative INCoDe.2030, was integrated in the National Research Infrastructures Roadmap in 2019, as the Portuguese counterpart of the future Iberian Network for Advanced Computing, agreed between Portugal and Spain. The main operational centre of RNCA is the Minho Advanced Computing Centre (MACC). RNCA is responsible for implementing EuroHPC infrastructure projects in Portugal, namely the acquisition, hosting and operation of a petascale supercomputer.
- **UC-LCA Laboratory for Advanced Computing** (Total Public Investment 1,398,908 €). UC-LCA provides High Performance Computing (HPC) services to the broad range of scientific fields which rely on heavy computational simulations. Because of the recent convergence between data and HPC, UC-LCA aims also to support those scientific fields that require intense data processing, like Genomics, bioimaging and Artificial Intelligence. It offers support to specialized training in HPC techniques and methods as well as on the effective use of the RI by its users. It

seeks cooperation with small and medium enterprises that need HPC services to improve their business. UC-LCA is the national node of the European HPC infrastructure PRACE – Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe.

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry Key challenges in case of absence

According to the European Research Area (ERA) Progress Report for the period 2016-2018, Portugal's performances are generally above the ERA average in Priority 2b (Make optimal use of public investments in research infrastructures) and Priority 4 (Gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research).

The Portuguese research system has a strong EU and international orientation. Policymakers and the research community are more engaged in societal challenge research priorities relevant to the national context due to the developing influence of Horizon 2020 and the JPP. Portugal participates in four JPIs, and is an observer in one more, four Article 185 initiatives, three EJPs and membership of more than 40 ERA-NETs in diverse scientific areas. Portugal has recently introduced public participation laboratories, a proposal that intends to involve citizens, local and regional actors, public and private entities in developing thematic R&I agendas contributing to the debate of public policies for science and technology and the dissemination of knowledge.

Portuguese firms cooperated with either universities or higher education institutions, or with governmental, public, or private research institutes at a rate of 10 %. This score was below both the EU-28 level and the ERA average. Cooperation between business and academia in Portugal remains low. The Portuguese institutional framework does not include incentives or an integrated strategy to foster cooperation between academia and industry. The inefficient governance and finance systems of Portuguese universities when it comes to university business cooperation and innovation and the absence of large technology-intensive firms that might absorb more graduates from science and technology studies are also factors contributing to the issue. Furthermore, experience in the private sector is not valued and academics have low incentives to follow dual careers or to engage in cooperation with industry. Recently a partnership between Innovation Agency and the business association for innovation (COTEC) was launched to encourage cooperation between academia and business. However, to date no concrete results were identified.

<p>Switzerland</p>	<p>Switzerland has a good starting point to continue to apply the successful model of a liveable, open, and modern country in the digital future. Digital transformation enables the sustainable development of the country. In this context the "Digital Switzerland" strategy provides the guidelines for government action and indicates where and how authorities, academia, the private sector, civil society and politics must work together in order to shape the transformation process for the benefit of everyone in Switzerland. The action plan, as an integral part of the strategy, includes the specific measures to achieve the strategic goals. Finally, Switzerland has established policies for Open Science and Open Data.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

<p>A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?</p>		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
<p>Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences Key challenges in case of absence</p>		
<p>The Federal Council wants Switzerland to exploit the opportunities of digitalisation to the full. On 5 September 2018 it adopted its Digital Switzerland strategy for the next 2 years. Within the framework of this strategy the Federal Council established a working group on the subject of artificial intelligence and support initiatives in relation to Smart Cities. In addition, the federal administration intensified dialogue with interested or involved participants, and especially with the cantons.</p> <p>Among its objectives the further improvement of the digital empowerment of people is included. The competencies of the Swiss population should be further strengthened so that the opportunities of digitalisation can be comprehensively exploited. Thanks to lifelong learning, people should always be in a position to participate competently in digitalised political, social, cultural, and economic processes and to assess the consequences of their own actions as appropriately as possible.</p> <p>Good education is an indispensable cornerstone for each individual and for society and the economy as a whole. The process of digital transformation in Switzerland requires skills in handling the new technologies as well as creative and critical thinking. The dissemination of appropriate skills and the provision of appropriate education and further education facilities therefore assume great importance.</p> <p>For Switzerland to remain among the leading countries in terms of the development and use of digital technologies, it has to promote the necessary skills - in the sense of lifelong learning - at all levels and in all areas. In addition, in order to achieve the goal of equal opportunities and the participation of all inhabitants in the opportunities of digitalisation, it is important to promote basic skills in the use of the new technologies.</p> <p>Science and research have a crucial role in terms of generating, disseminating and using knowledge. The technologies emerging from science and research constitute the essential basis of digital change and digital innovation, such as for example in the area of artificial intelligence or the processing of large amounts of data. These developments will shape economic, social, environmental and cultural development in a sustainable manner. Research and innovation as a core foundation of competitiveness and as a basis for successfully tackling structural change must be strengthened with</p>		

regard to digital skills and must be further developed to meet the needs of the population, the economy and the environment.

In addition, the «Digital Switzerland» action plan includes the measures which make a concrete contribution to the achievement of the goals of the «Digital Switzerland» strategy. The starting point for this is the measures taken by the federal administration. The Departments and Federal Offices fund their implementation measures within the framework of their regular budgets and ensure evaluation of these measures where necessary. The «Digital Switzerland» action plan is published on the website of the Federal Office of Communications, OFCOM, and is regularly updated.

On 14 November 2018, the Federal Council of Switzerland approved the key value for the **eGovernment Strategy from 2020-2023**, prepared by the organisation eGovernment Switzerland. The general principle "Digital First" shows the importance of the electronic channel through which the administration will offer its information and services by default in the future. The 6 principles of the Tallinn Declaration (signed by FC Maurer on 06.10.2017) form an important basis for the new strategy. A central action field of the eGovernment Strategy from 2020 will be to ensure the possibility of interaction of the population in the activities of politics and administration. The eGovernment strategy Switzerland is a part of the strategy of the Federal Council for the Information Society in Switzerland Strategy and is based on the 'Recommendation of the Council on Digital Government Strategies' of the OECD. The Steering Committee will have the opportunity to adapt the project's portfolio and strategic direction over the next four years as in regard to the changes in the context and the progress of these eGovernment oriented measures.

Moreover, the report **on Challenges of Digitalisation for Education and Research in Switzerland**, published by SERI in July 2017 emphasises that, in order to ensure that Switzerland's education system adapts appropriately to the digital developments taking place, action must be taken by individuals, educational institutions and the education system as a whole.

Action area 1: Improving digital literacy

Action area 2: Using ICT in teaching and learning

Action area 3: Rapidly adapting the education system to market requirements

Action area 4: Improving coordination and communication in education cooperation

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

The Federal Department of the Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications DETEC is responsible for coordinating the Confederation's implementation measures within the federal administration and for the ongoing development of the Digital Switzerland strategy.

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation

Key challenges in case of absence

The Digital Switzerland strategy is a joint task of authorities at all levels of the state, the private sector, the academic community, civil society, and politics.

The Federal Department of the Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications DETEC is responsible for coordinating the Confederation's implementation measures within the federal administration and for the ongoing development of the Digital Switzerland strategy. This work is carried out within the framework of the Confederation's «Digital Switzerland» Coordination Group.

The Confederation's «Digital Switzerland» Office, based within OFCOM, supports the Coordination Group in terms of organisation and content. From 1 January 2021 onwards coordination within the federal administration will be assured by the Federal Chancellery.

The Federal Council invites all of digital Switzerland's stakeholder groups, in particular the cantons, cities and municipalities, to exchange information on their projects in relation to the implementation of this strategy and relevant cross-sectoral topics and to exploit any possible synergies. The administration also cooperates closely with the private sector, civil society and the academic community and in this way contributes to the efficient implementation of the strategy. Especially in areas of activity with responsibilities shared between the Confederation, the cantons and private organisations (e.g. in the health and education sectors), sustainable digital integration is possible only if there are permanent forums or platforms for cooperation.

Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation

The Digital Switzerland strategy is systematically monitored and assessed. The results and impacts of the digital skills initiatives/projects implemented in the country are reviewed, with an aim to utilise lessons learnt and avoid past mistakes, hence improve the overall digital skills policy planning framework.

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years

In September 2018, the Federal Council launched a new **national research program on the theme of digital transformation**. The main objective of this program is to better understand the opportunities and risks of digitization for society and the economy. The program focuses in particular on the priority areas of research "Training, learning and digital transformation", "Ethics, reliability and governance" and "Digital economy and labour market".

- **Training, learning and digital transformation:** These modules study the impact of digitization on training (content, skills, and transmission of skills), on lifelong learning and on the main institutions in charge of training
- **Ethics, reliability, and governance:** These modules deal with the ethical, organizational, legal, and technical challenges which guarantee and reinforce confidence in infrastructures or in digital services.
- **Digital economy and the labour market:** These modules deal with the interactions and impact of the digital turn on the economy (productivity and competitiveness of the Swiss economic centre) and on the labour market

In September 2019, the **Swiss Digital Initiative (SDI)** was launched in Geneva aiming at a long-term and sustainable process with the objective of ensuring ethical standards in the digital world. The objectives of the initiative can be summarized as follows:

5. Ensuring ethical standards in the digital world
6. Fostering technology's potential to advance flourishing human societies
7. Focusing on ethical values and principles in action
8. Developing specific and action-oriented projects that will contribute to a global dialogue on the ethics of digitalisation, and aim to foster trust in digital technologies, as well as in the actors involved in the ongoing process of digital transformation

The SDI is primarily, but not exclusively, aimed at companies with a global presence.

Another important initiative on digital skills is the **Digital Skills & Spaces program** of the Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK)⁸⁵. It strengthens and cultivates skills that are particularly relevant for

⁸⁵ <https://www.zhdk.ch/digital/digital-skills>

the digital age. This includes existing and new skills. In addition, Digital Skills & Spaces addresses the question of what physical spaces should look like in order to guarantee the best possible environment for learning and exercising these skills. Digital Skills & Spaces bundles existing projects and measures within the ZHdK that deal with this topic. In addition, new projects are initiated, and discussions are encouraged. The aim is to support members of the ZHdK in actively positioning themselves today and tomorrow in the digital age and in shaping their own everyday work - self-determined, reflective, and enjoyable.

The basis for this is the ZHdK competence model for the digital age. The model focuses on the person as an individual and as part of a group. The person is surrounded by the competence areas digital participation, digital creation, and teamwork. The conscious handling of competencies for the digital age can be consolidated in a culture of digitality. In such a culture, aspects of the digital age are actively discussed, and value judgments are negotiated together. The model is used as a basis for discussion and for planning and analyzing the program and individual projects. In the first phase of the program in 2019 and 2020, the focus will be on personality, which is reflected in projects such as Design your Future or Destination Digital.

Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)

To strengthen skills in research and innovation, the following initiatives are implemented in the country:

The Digitization Initiative (DIZH)⁸⁶. The aim of the digitization initiative (DIZH) is to promote collaboration between Zurich's universities in the field of digitization and thus strengthen Zurich as a research and business location. The University of Zurich (UZH), the Zurich University of Applied Sciences (ZHAW), the Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK) and the Zurich University of Education (PHZH) network systematically in the DIZH in order to specifically advance research and innovation in topics of digitization with interdisciplinary approaches. The DIZH funds research on digitization through the three areas of research clusters, innovation program and program for promoting education. The Cantonal Council of the Canton of Zurich approved the development of the digitization initiative of all Zurich universities (DIZH) in January 2020.

The "**UZH Digital Society Initiative" (DSI)⁸⁷** is a scientific institution supported by all faculties of the University of Zurich (UZH) and open to all members of the UZH. It aims to promote independent scientific reflection and innovation on issues relating to the digital society, to prepare UZH students to help shape the digital society, to engage in a continuous discourse with the public and to support political decision-making. To this end, the DSI promotes the intensive cooperation of scientists from different disciplines and institutions who are working together for a limited time on research selected topics of the digital society. The Digital Society

- promotes research on the digital society
- promotes national and international cooperation between all scientific disciplines that deal with issues related to the digital society
- develops courses on the digital society for students of all faculties
- uses findings from basic research to shape future developments in society, culture, politics, business and science
- strengthens cooperation with society, culture, politics and business and enter into dialogue with the public

⁸⁶ <http://www.dizh.ch/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.dsi.uzh.ch/en.html>

New Informatics@School Task Force in Switzerland: In the context of a strategic initiative towards Informatics@School, the Swiss Informatics Society (SI) involves a task force that aims to establish Informatics in schools. 3D programming environments may engage a significant proportion of the next generation of students in computer programming. With access to programming environments that are able to model interesting social, natural and imagined phenomena, the students are more likely to see computer programming as an essential skill for rendering their worlds.

Other initiatives under the National Research Programme «Digital Transformation» (NRP 77):

- **Digital Lives** is aimed at researchers in Switzerland whose current research activities are in the humanities and social sciences.
- **Digital Society Initiative.** The DSI wants to promote research within the Challenge Areas and Cross Cutting Topics and support the members of the DSI network in this.

D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?

Yes	No	In planning
		X

Key features of the digital competence framework established

Key challenges in case of absence

Currently in Switzerland, there is no national framework been established, yet based on EU DIGICOMP. To some extent the “Lehrplan 21” harmonises the curriculum and integrates media education, yet digital competences do not appear and is not given transversal status in educational policy. Only the use of digital tools in other subjects is discussed and explored. However, the connection to main transversal competencies such as problem solving is not considered.

In the above framework, the Swiss Science, and Innovation Council SSIC has proposed (position paper on digital competences 2017⁸⁸), a competent framework, within the EU framework. It suggests, among others, that:

1. A national digital competence framework as a spiral curriculum with transversal educational policy status should be developed. Developing this kind of curriculum will be essential but it will be challenging to inject a new competence framework into the existing curriculum landscape in Switzerland (e.g., Lehrplan 21). Switzerland is still in the lengthy process to adopt the current Lehrpan 21 in the 21 German speaking Kantons. However, with relatively small conceptual shift, the suggested digital competence framework could be constructively aligned with the “Informatik” and “Medien” subject areas of the Lehrplan 21. The Lehrplan 21 does provide the necessary flexibility to enable this kind of adaptation.
2. Research: Digital competences at an organizational level need further investigation: Closing the “Society-in-the- loop” gap and learning analytics or academic analytics are examples of the new research field “digital competences at organizational level.” This research field is extremely important but vast and completely underdeveloped in Switzerland. The following section provides an elaboration of this point providing some suggestions on how Switzerland could transform its research potential in this field.

Last, but not least, Switzerland is a member of ECDL Foundation, whereas all ECDL certification programmes are fully compatible with DigComp. Also, ICDL is delivered in Switzerland by Digital

Literacy AG. Apart from the Swiss Information Society, training courses and certification of digital skills are undertaken by private sector actors e.g. DigiComp Academy AG.

D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework
Key challenges in case of absence

Switzerland is taking part in the Bologna Process in the field of higher education and in the Copenhagen Process in the sphere of vocational and professional education and training. Both processes aim to guarantee, at national and international level, permeability, transparency, and mobility and hence in the European context to work towards strengthening Europe's competitiveness as a learning location.

National Qualifications Framework for the higher education sector (nqf.ch-HS)

The Qualifications Framework for the Swiss Higher Education Area (nqf.ch-HS) describes and defines the levels of higher education in Switzerland on the basis of admission conditions and qualifications inter alia. The qualifications framework serves the higher education institutions as a guide in developing and describing their study courses and programmes. It also improves information about the Swiss higher education system, particularly with regard to teaching. Finally, it facilitates the comparability of qualifications in Europe and enhances transparency. The nqf.ch-HS provides an overview of Swiss higher education. It includes the cycles 1-3 Bachelor, Master and Doctorate as well as part of CET. In general, the cycles 1–3 are consecutive and the prerequisite for admission to the next level is a subject-specific degree in the preceding cycle. The Federal Act on Funding and Coordination of the Higher Education Sector provides for compulsory institutional accreditation. Within this context it is verified whether the qualifications framework is being considered by and integrated in the higher education institutions.

National Qualifications Framework for vocational and professional education and training

The European Qualifications Framework (EQF) is the basis for Switzerland's National Qualifications Framework for Vocational and Professional Qualifications (NQF VPQ). The Swiss vocational and professional education and training system trains highly skilled workers. However, there is little awareness outside of Switzerland of these qualifications. The NQF VPQ is intended to make it easier for people to understand how the Swiss education system works and to be able to compare Swiss qualifications with other qualifications elsewhere in Europe. With this aim in mind, all formal vocational and professional qualifications have been assigned to one of eight reference levels within the NQF VPQ. The following types of qualifications are referenced to the NQF VPQ:

- Vocational education and training (VET): Federal VET Certificate and Federal VET Diploma.
- Tertiary level professional education: Federal Diploma of Higher Education with, Advanced Federal Diploma of Higher Education, federally recognised courses of education at Colleges of Higher Education leading to a Federal Diploma of Higher Education, and qualifications for VET professionals.

A certificate supplement is drawn up for each referenced vocational education and training (VET) leaving certificate, and a diploma supplement for each referenced tertiary level professional education leaving certificate. These documents contain information about the corresponding qualification. They enable potential employers both in Switzerland and abroad to better assess the professional competences of qualification holders.

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills Key challenges in case of absence.		
<p>Swiss MOOC Service is the national Open edX platform for institutions of higher education of Switzerland and is open for other organisations and corporations as well. The platform is compatible with Swiss data protection laws and hosted in Switzerland. Swiss MOOC founded by leading Swiss universities EPFL, ETH, SUPSI, USI and HES-SO and financially supported by the Swiss universities' P5 program is a one stop shop to help Universities and other organisations kickstart their online education presence. It is based on the industry leading Open edX LMS platform with many advantages offered, including state of the art course planning management, Open Source access to source and ultra-scalability to millions of learners. Additional features are tailored to the needs of Universities. Its developers from EPFL, ETH, USI, SUPS and HES-SO work on adapting and extending functionalities of the platform to best serve the needs of its members. Swiss MOOC Service is helping to accelerate the online presence of Swiss HEIs by offering access to a community of MOOC creators with experience, training sessions and studios available.</p> <p>The service is live and available as a beta platform to early adopter partners by contacting Swiss MOOC Service. General availability and official launch is scheduled for September 2020.</p>		

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>Switzerland has a modern, coherent legal basis regarding the legal rights relating to data, access to data and data handling. Switzerland is establishing a modern and coherent legal basis for exploiting the potential of the data economy. Policies for Open Access in Switzerland are being developed by the research institutions, scientific academies and by the national funding organizations, with the complementary support of the government. As most Swiss research institutions signed the Berlin declaration on Open Access university libraries now run repositories enabling access of pre-prints and digital copies of PhD theses. Additionally, the main national funding agency, SNSF, endorsed a policy for open access.</p> <p>The Swiss national strategy for Open Access (OA) to publications aims at ensuring the cost transparency for public funds and the coordination among stakeholders, especially higher education institutions and their libraries. The time horizon of this national strategy covers the period 2021-2028. It will be implemented across two national action plans, one for the period 2021-2024 (including the Open Access Action Plan 2021-2024), and another one for the period 2025-2028. The Swiss National Strategy on OA aims to achieve the following objective, in accordance with international benchmarks: by 2024, all scholarly publication activity in Switzerland should be OA, all scholarly publications funded by public money must be freely accessible on the internet. The OA landscape will consist of a mix of OA models.</p> <p>The objectives for the period 2021-2024 include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving shareability and interpretability • Leveraging decentralisation and diversity 		

- Strengthening the dialogue between science and the society
- Adoption of Openness and FAIRness

The fields of activity for the period 2021-2024 include Open Access, Research Assessment, FAIR Data and Services, Exploratory and Integrative Projects and Research Data Digital Infrastructures.

Some additional initiatives in the area include:

- The adoption of a new Federal Council Bill for education, research, and innovation for the period 2017-2020 (Swiss Education, Research and Innovation Policy for 2017–2020). The Swiss Parliament approved new set of measures aimed at reinforcing the Swiss research and innovation sector
- A call for supporting digital books open access publications was launched in 2015. The aim of this initiative was to collect information on the use and production costs of open access book publications, particularly in the field of humanities
- The ‘Scientific information: Accessing, processing and saving’ program launched by the Swiss Confederation for the 2013- 2016 aimed to develop and implement a national strategy concerning scientific information, covering access to scientific publications, data repositories, licensing, e-learning and cloud computing.
- The Swiss edu-ID and the Swiss Academic Cloud managed by SWITCH aimed at upgrading the Swiss university network, establishing a Swiss edu-ID as a common identity management platform for the entire higher education system and developed a cloud infrastructure for the Swiss academic community.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

The main stakeholders involved with the Swiss Research, Data, and Open science area include:

- The **Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF)** supports scientific research in all academic disciplines, from history to medicine and the engineering sciences. At the end of 2019, the SNSF was funding 5750 projects involving 18,900 researchers, which makes it the leading Swiss institution for promoting scientific research. To ensure its independence, the SNSF was established as a private foundation in 1952. Its core task is the evaluation of research proposals. In 2019, it awarded CHF 1056 million to the most promising project proposals. By allocating public research money based on the principle of competition, the SNSF contributes to the high quality of research in Switzerland.
- The **Federal Council Dispatch** on the promotion of education, research, and innovation for 2017-2020 as approved by the Swiss global network for education, research, and innovation
- The **Swiss Science and Innovation Council (SSIC)** as the advisory body to the Federal Council for issues related to science, higher education, research, and innovation policy. . The goal of the SSIC, in conformity with its role as an independent consultative body, is to promote the framework for the successful development of the Swiss higher education, research and innovation system. As an independent advisory body to the Federal Council, the SSIC pursues the Swiss higher education, research, and innovation landscape from a long-term perspective.

E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes Key challenges in case of absence

Research infrastructure in Switzerland is publicly or privately owned and is structured or implemented in a medium- or long-term manner (usually more than 10 years). The 2019 Swiss Roadmap for Research Infrastructures provides an overview of newly planned national infrastructures and of Switzerland’s participation in international research infrastructures. It also reviews the progress made in realising the infrastructures proposed in the 2015 Roadmap. It is one of the documents forming the basis for drawing up the 2021–2024 ERI Dispatch and the dispatch on funding for the EU framework programmes (EU Dispatch) in the coming years. In the roadmap among the 41 research infrastructures proposed, 23 have been put in the highest priority group and will be

funded for the 2017-2020 period. The total financial volume of these initiatives amounts to around 700 million CHF. The RI's are strongly oriented towards natural sciences, engineering (particularly IT) and health data. Funding for these infrastructures will be provided by the institutions themselves, ETH board, and through university cooperation projects.

According to the Swiss Roadmap for Research Infrastructures 2019, the main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes include:

- a) High-Performance Computing and Networking (HPCN-24),
- b) Common Data Centre for Astronomy, Astroparticle and Cosmology (CDCI), and
- c) Swiss Centre for Musculoskeletal Biobanking and Imaging and Clinical Movement Analysis

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry Key challenges in case of absence

According to the European Research Area (ERA) Progress Report for the period 2016-2018, Switzerland's performances placed the country among the groups of the best performing countries for all indicators in Priority regarding the more effective national research systems and the priority regarding transnational cooperation. These were the areas in which Switzerland performed the best. Notable example of Switzerland's progress in enhancing effectiveness of national research system is the Federal Council Dispatch on the promotion of education, research and innovation for 2017- 2020 approved by the Swiss global network for education, research, and innovation. It serves as a basis for expenditure planning and developing new research priorities. Remarkably high scores are also found for Switzerland on transnational cooperation indicators, although information on public-to-public partnerships are not available for the country.

Also, Switzerland scored very highly on one indicator: the number of public-private collaborative papers per capita, at 261. This figure was more than six times higher than the EU-28 score of 41. On the knowledge transfer indicator, performance was less impressive; with about 10 % of private firms collaborating with universities, governments, or research institutes.

<p>NETHERLANDS</p>	<p>Netherlands lies at the forefront of Digital Transformation in all of its aspects and is a leader in both Digital Skills and Open Science domains. Digital skills are embedded in the National Digitalization Strategy and there is a large number of stakeholders involved in its implementation, including ministries, state companies, research institutions, social partners, and universities. The main challenge faced by Netherlands is the relative shortage of highly skilled personnel since the demand in the market is larger than the availability of suitably skilled professionals. Although attention is given to initiatives that target digital skills for the general population (including lower level educated persons and the elderly), a strong higher education agenda drives important activities towards enhancement of digital skills at all levels. Even though the landscape is quite fragmented, there is strong coordination among stakeholders which ensures a continuous progress.</p>
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A. Current Digital skills policy context

<p>A.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for digital skills, or a strategy or policy that includes specific initiatives for digital skills?</p>		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
<p>Main objectives - Short term and long -term goals- Focused areas & target audiences Key challenges in case of absence</p>		
<p>According to the latest DESI publication the Netherlands ranks 4th among EU countries on Human capital and well above the EU average. Basic and advanced digital skills are above the EU average. The number of ICT specialists has increased slightly and is also above the EU average. Despite this positive trend, the growth rate will arguably not be sufficient to meet labour market demands. The major policy document that guides Digital Skills development is the 2018 Dutch Digitalization Strategy⁸⁹, and its updated version (Digitalization Strategy 2.0⁹⁰) that has been published in July 2019 and includes a brief overview of the results achieved and future goals.</p> <p>Digital skills development is fully integrated and plays a significant role in the strategy, one of the “ambitions” of which is the “Everyone can participate, and we work together” motto. The strategy recognizes that this will require everyone to learn basic skills as soon as possible and continue to learn and develop in later life. The strategy identifies new (digital) skills as one of the five foundations for the country’s digital transformation and has planned several actions to achieve the goals set.</p>		

⁸⁹ <https://www.nederlanddigitaal.nl/documenten/publicaties/2019/09/30/english-version-of-the-dutch-digitalisation-strategy>
⁹⁰ <https://www.nederlanddigitaal.nl/documenten/publicaties/2019/11/13/english-version-of-the-dutch-digitalisation-strategy-2.0>

Changes in work, new skills and lifelong learning		
Up-to-date curriculum in education	Young people should have good basic ICT and information skills and are media literate.	In the curriculum for primary and secondary education, attention will be paid to digital literacy and practical skills to better equip pupils for the future.
Adequate basic level of digital skills	Everyone can participate in the digital society.	We are working on training initiatives for people with limited digital skills.
A learning workforce	People can keep developing themselves, so that they can continue to do their work well and with pleasure in a changing environment.	Before the summer, the government will present an action plan for a breakthrough in the field of lifelong development.
Sufficient ICT professionals	Companies should be able to find sufficient well-qualified staff.	Further development of the Human Capital Agenda ICT and continuation of the Technology Pact (<i>Techniekpact</i>).
Clarity about working via platforms	Providing better support to people in finding the right employment relationship and giving employers a clearer framework.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The government carried out a survey on the position of employees carrying out work via platforms and recently sent it to Dutch parliament. In the coalition agreement, measures were announced to provide more clarity for the self-employed and employers, and to prevent pseudo self-employment.

One important aspect of the Digital Skills strategic approach is the emphasis on **improving higher education** through the use of digital technologies. This is guided by the “Acceleration Agenda for Innovation in Education⁹¹”, a joint effort by the Association of Research Universities, the Netherlands Association of Universities of Applied Sciences and SURF (the collaborative organization for ICT in Dutch education and research). According to the Agenda, digital skills is an integral part of the curriculum and an effort to define which skills are relevant to each offered course is under way. The Acceleration Agenda has been expanded into a four-year (2019-2022) **Acceleration plan for educational innovation** with ICT⁹² under eight zones (themes) in which 39 universities and universities of applied sciences collaborate among others towards digital (open) educational resources, secure and reliable use of learning analytics and evidence-informed educational innovation with ICT. The program’s ambitions are improving the connection to the labour market, stimulating the flexibility of education and achieving smarter and better learning with technology.

The Strategy also aims at increasing the digital skills for **primary and secondary education** by reviewing and establishing a formal, updated curriculum by 2021. There is also a national training programme, ‘Digital Teacher’ (‘Digileerkracht’), which aims to strengthen the digital skills of primary school teachers, as well as the recently introduced “**Digitalization agenda for primary and secondary education**⁹³” which aims to promote effective cooperation between parties within and outside the education field, including private sector and – among others – focuses on “digitally literate pupils and teachers” and “digital teaching materials that work for users”.

Furthermore, the government places strong emphasis on **enhancing basic digital skills of aged people and of people with low literacy levels**, by supporting several initiatives at both local and national levels, for example via the national Library and Basic Skills programme⁹⁴ (Bibliotheek en basisvaardigheden). The programme has built on the developing role of Dutch libraries as non-formal education and information centres, service providers for people at risk of digital and social exclusion. In 2019, support from the Ministry of Internal Affairs led to the creation of a network of Government Digital Service Information Desks in public libraries across the Netherlands. Since July 2019, libraries not only offer ICT skills training but also serve as the first point of information service about the digital government⁹⁵.

⁹¹ <https://www.vsnul.nl/files/documenten/Acceleration%20agenda%202017.pdf>

⁹² <https://versnellingsplan.nl/english/>

⁹³ <https://www.nederlanddigitaal.nl/english/digitalisation-agenda-for-primary-and-secondary-education>

⁹⁴ <https://www.bibliotheeknetwerk.nl/basisvaardigheden-volwassenen>

⁹⁵ <https://librarymap.ifla.org/stories/Netherlands/DUTCH-LIBRARIES-ARE-EQUIPPING-CITIZENS-WITH-THE-DIGITAL-SKILLS-NEEDED-TO-ACCESS-GOVERNMENT-DIGITAL-SERVICES-/147>

Regarding **Lifelong Learning and Development**, the government wants people to regard learning and developing their skills as natural aspects of their work and life, rather than updating their skills only when they become unemployed or are at risk of losing their job⁹⁶. According to the Strategy, the focus is on a broad approach to stimulate a positive learning culture, together with social partners, educational institutions and parties in the field. Part of this is the individual learning account and a digital overview of training opportunities in order to give individuals more control over their own learning pathway.

Finally, taking into account that one of the main challenges faced by the country is that the number of STEM graduates is among the lowest in the EU, and that companies face difficulties in finding highly qualified people⁹⁷ (for example there were an estimated 66,400 vacancies in technology at the beginning of 2018, compared to 41,200 at the beginning of 2016)⁹⁸ a significant part of the strategy focuses at creating the conditions for **producing sufficient numbers of ICT professionals**, by means of the **Human Capital Agenda for ICT**⁹⁹ (an action plan to meet the growing demand for ICT professionals by knowledge institutions, education sector parties, government agencies and businesses) and **the Technology Pact 2016-2020**¹⁰⁰ (which contains concrete agreements between business, education and government to improve the connection between education and the labor market in the technology sector and thus reduce the shortage of technical personnel).

According to the updated version of the Digitalization Strategy, “the government, business sector, public organisations and knowledge institutions have already initiated numerous initiatives towards the development of digital skills and lifelong learning. Collaborations between the business community and education sector, are being strengthened through initiatives such as the Technology Pact, human capital agendas and Smart Industry action programme. Public, private and public organisations will be working together to promote digital inclusion as a part of the Digital Society Alliance ¹⁰¹(Alliantie Digitaal Samenleven). The main challenge thus lies in accelerating, strengthening and connecting existing activities rather than developing or introducing new ones”.

The **NL DIGIbeter Digital Government Agenda**¹⁰² tightly linked to the Strategy, includes useful information on improving **digital skills for the public sector employees**. It indicates for example, that the programme of the Dutch National Academy for Digitalisation and Computerisation of Government will provide general basic knowledge modules for all civil servants, irrespective of their position or the sector in which they work, including knowledge of the secure and functional use of ICT and the Internet. The government is also encouraging the development of user-friendly digital products and services that require minimum digital skills to be accessed. Furthermore, collaboration with the private sector is also being investigated as a source for supporting digital skills enhancement for citizens. Finally, the Digital Inclusion letter¹⁰³ published in December 2018, clearly stated goals to helping people go digital and presents several actions to be undertaken by the government.

The Dutch Strategic Action Plan for Artificial Intelligence¹⁰⁴ also stresses the importance of investing in digital skills (AI-relevant) and mentions supporting actions from smart industry hubs and the ministry of education.

⁹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/2019-european-semester-national-reform-programme-netherlands_en.pdf

⁹⁷ Digital Economy and Society Index 2019 (DESI 2019), Netherlands

⁹⁸ Techniekpact Monitor (Technology Pact Monitor) <https://www.techniekpactmonitor.nl>

⁹⁹ https://dutchdigitaldelta.nl/uploads/pdf/ECP1610-HCA_infographic-english-HR.PDF

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.techniekpact.nl>

¹⁰¹ <https://digitaalsamenleven.nl/over-de-alliantie/>

¹⁰² <https://www.nldigitalgovernment.nl/digital-government-agenda/>

¹⁰³ <https://www.nldigitalgovernment.nl/wp-content/uploads/sites/11/2019/02/digital-inclusion-everyone-must-be-able-to-participate.pdf>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.government.nl/documents/reports/2019/10/09/strategic-action-plan-for-artificial-intelligence>

Strategic focus on digital skills development is also included or strongly implied in several other domain policy documents, such as the Dutch National Research Agenda¹⁰⁵, the Strategic Agenda for Higher Education and Research 2015-2025¹⁰⁶, the “Connecting Science and Society” strategy 2019-2022 of the NWO (National Research Organization)¹⁰⁷, and the Digital Society Research Agenda of the VSNU (association of universities)¹⁰⁸ - **see also Part E** of this report.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved

Responsibility for the Digitalization Strategy of the Netherlands lies within the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy¹⁰⁹, whereas the responsibility for Digital Government lies with the State Secretary for the Interior and Kingdom Relations. Other institutions involved in the country’s digital skills landscape include:

- Ministry of Education, Culture and Science*
- Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment
- ECP | Platform for the Information Society
- SURF | collaborative organisation for ICT in Dutch education and research (key enabler & service provider)
- VSNU | association of universities
- VH | association of universities of applied science
- SBB | Foundation for Cooperation on Vocational Education, Training and Labour Market
- The National Library (Nationale bibliotheek) and the Network of Libraries (bibliotheek netwerk).

*See also **section E** on institutes involved in the Open Science ecosystem which offer digital skills enhancement programs.

B. Current Digital skills governance model

B.1. Is there a coordinating entity or is there a coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation?

Yes	No	In planning
	X	
Description of coordination / governance mechanism/ partnership established for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The Dutch digital skills landscape is pluralistic. It includes ministries (at least 3 ministries as policy makers as seen in section A), national funding bodies as well as organizations with the responsibility for providing IT services.</p> <p>Alongside with the Dutch government, the National Coalition for Digital Skills and Jobs in the Netherlands is working on ensuring that all citizens have access to digital literacy initiatives. The coalition sees the inclusion of digital skills into education curricula as a base element of a digitally literate society.</p>		

¹⁰⁵ <https://surfdrive.surf.nl/files/index.php/s/2xMaupfh1u4X06o>

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.government.nl/binaries/government/documents/reports/2015/07/01/the-value-of-knowledge/the-value-of-knowledge.pdf>

¹⁰⁷ https://www.nwo.nl/binaries/content/documents/nwo-en/common/documentation/application/nwo/strategy/nwo-strategy-2019-2022/NWO_strategy_2019-2022_Connecting_Science_and_Society-pdf.pdf

¹⁰⁸ <https://www.vsnu.nl/files/documenten/Domeinen/Onderzoek/DigitaleSamenleving/VSNU%20Digital%20Society%20Research%20Agenda.pdf>

¹⁰⁹ <https://www.government.nl/documents/reports/2018/06/01/dutch-digitalisation-strategy>

ECP – Platform for the Information Society coordinates the Coalition and collaborates with public authorities across different ministries as well as with industry, teachers, researchers and non-governmental organisations to advance the digital agenda. Almost 200 ECP members work together to bolster the digital skills of citizens in all age groups.

Tools for performance & impact measurement and presentation

The Dutch government updated the Digitalization Strategy in 2019 and included important information in what has been achieved during the previous year.

Information on the progress of the various initiatives is also found on some of the involved institutions' annual reports.

The National Steering Group Technology Pact coordinates, follows and monitors the implementation of the national strategy, the goals and the agreements made in the Technology Pact. The steering group is composed of representatives from the five parts of the country, the national government, employers, employees, top sectors and education.

The Technology Pact Monitor is a yearly impact report that monitors the progress towards the objectives of the Technology Pact on the national and regional level. The Technology Pact Monitor is prepared by the Dutch ministry of Economic Affairs (EZ) and the Talent for Technology Platform (PTVT) and relies on datasets of the National Statistics Agency (CBS), the Education Executive Agency of the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (DUO) and the Employee Insurance Agency (UWV) and various partners in the field.

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level

C.1. Description of major digital skills initiatives that are currently active or planned for the next 3-5 years

According to the National Digital Coalition Factsheet (August 2018)¹¹⁰, 50% of digital skills initiatives are targeted towards Education, 20% towards ICT professionals, 15% towards the labour force and 15% towards citizens in general.

Main initiatives most relevant to the goals and objectives of the strategic documents on digital skills include¹¹¹:

Dutch Technology Pact (Techniepact - <https://www.techniepact.nl>): A joint public-private initiative (60 stakeholders) that focuses on training more technical talent and making employment in the tech sector more attractive (opting for technology, learning in technology, working in technology). The pact's members have agreed on 22 national actions to create a sustainable workforce for the technology sectors. The initiative has demonstrated positive impact and while receiving some funding from the government for its organization, it heavily relies on funding from regions, schools and businesses for its operation. According to the organization¹¹², the business community will establish an online technology education portal (techniek-onderwijs.nl) to

- allow primary schools and secondary schools to register a need for support from the business community for their technology teaching either on site or in the classroom;
- enable young people studying technology-related fields to find an internship or combined work-study place;
- enable vocational schools to find a specialist teacher or guest teacher from within industry;

¹¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=55793

¹¹¹ Information retrieved mainly from https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/Digital_Fronrunners_Country_Spotlights.pdf and <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/digital-skills-jobs-coalition-initiatives>

¹¹² <https://investinholland.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Summary-Dutch-Technology-Pact-2020.pdf>

- enable schools to find internships for their science teachers

The Talent for Technology Platform (PTVT - <https://ptvt.nl/over/>): The Talent for Technology Platform is a public-private partnership of employers' and employee organizations and the Ministries of OCW, EZK and SWZ committed to helping all young people in education discover their talents for technology and ICT so that more young people will opt for technology and ICT jobs. It offers the Jet-Net & TechNet service (the network for cooperation between schools and companies in primary and secondary education), as well as the Catapult service (the network for cooperation between schools and companies in vocational education). PTvT also collects, analyzes and publishes education and labor market figures in the field of science technology. Finally, PTvT carry out various programs on behalf of various ministries with objectives such as ensuring sufficiently qualified science technicians, improving the connection between education and the labor market and stimulating lifelong development.

Dutch Digital Delta (<https://dutchdigitaldelta.nl/en/>): Team Dutch digital delta's mission is to help the business community, government and knowledge institutions to realize innovations with ICT and to strengthen the international position of the Netherlands as a country to invest in and with ICT innovation. This is done through cooperation, knowledge sharing and offering financing routes on specific themes. Digital Delta is responsible for The Human Capital Agenda ICT government action plan to ensure a continuous supply of trained ICT professionals in the labour market and better digital skills in education. The granting organization is Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, and there are many participating organizations in the initiative, such as ECP, Nederland ICT, NOW, Centric, CIO Platform Nederland, TNO¹¹³.

Knowledge Net (Kennisnet - <https://www.kennisnet.nl/wie-wij-zijn/>): Kennisnet is the guide and builder of the ICT foundation for schools and institutions in primary education (PO), secondary education (VO) and secondary vocational education (MBO). Kennisnet helps boards and schools further with knowledge about what works with ICT in education and supports large-scale administrative initiatives aimed at professionalizing the use of ICT. Kennisnet is funded by the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (OCW) – 12M€ in 2018.

Digital Society Alliance (Alliantie Digitaal Samenleven - <https://digitaalsamenleven.nl/over-de-alliantie/>): The Alliance is a public-private partnership, of which more than 30 parties are now members. The alliance is an initiative of VodafoneZiggo in conjunction with the Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations, the ECP Platform for the Information Society and the Number Five Foundation. It considers inclusive digital society as a social task and is organized around various working groups consisting of partners and experts. Each working group focuses on a group of people who are currently unable to fully participate in society.

Make IT Work (<https://www.it-omscholing.nl/nl/>): A project that seeks to address immediate skills gaps by retraining highly educated and motivated people (non-STEM graduates) for the ICT sector. In parallel, employers participating in the fast-track training partnerships gain access to the high-quality specialists they need. Make IT work is an initiative of the Hogeschool van Amsterdam, leading ICT companies, the municipality of Amsterdam, and the Amsterdam Economic Board. After being funded by the Dutch government until September 2017, Make IT Work is now independent and sustainable, with funding coming from candidates and the participating companies who recruit graduates from the programme.

¹¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/image/document/2019-32/country_report_-_netherlands_-_final_2019_0D31373F-EEDB-493C-6014AE7DC2FC1E6A_61214.pdf

Safe Internet <https://veiliginternetten.nl/> Safe internet is a website where people can find tips, tricks and practical step-by-step explanations about what they can do and not do to use the internet safely. They will find tips on how to handle their online privacy safely, how to use Wi-Fi safely, what to do and not do on social media, and they will find an explanation of how they help children to be safe online. It is part of the Digibewust (digital awareness) program that has been recently extended to stimulate digital skills.

Description of initiatives specifically targeting up-skilling for Science and Research, particularly in the areas pertinent to EOSC objectives (e.g. data management / analysis / visualization / sharing, numerical processing, research software engineering, research infrastructure engineering)

There are some initiatives that are close to areas pertinent to EOSC objectives such as:

Pass IT (Geef IT Door - <https://www.geefitdoor.nl/wat-is-geef-it-door/>): The program teaches young people to become acquainted with IT by letting professionals share their experiences. Pass IT brings practical knowledge to secondary schools and introduces young people to digital literacy and the professional opportunities available in the ICT sector, including: Computer Programming, Big Data, Cyber Security and Privacy.

The Human Capital Agenda for ICT (Digital Delta) builds on regional cooperation and plans to achieve and help educational institutions to make required adjustments to the curriculum due to the emergence of new technologies.

CodePact (<https://saferinternetcentre.nl/activiteiten/codepact/>) Since 2019, CodePact has been part of the Better Internet for children program. Since 2006, this program has tackled public-private use of digital resources by children and young people in the Netherlands. The program is part of the Dutch Safer Internet Center, an initiative of the European Commission. Important activities within the digital literacy program are the annual Code Week and the Digital Literacy Monitor, which examines the state of affairs and obstacles and the desired support at schools in primary education.

The Dutch Consortium of University libraries (<https://www.ukb.nl/english>) together with ICT support staff and policy departments provide advice, guidance and support to researchers of their own university in the field of data management. The relevant knowledge is exchanged through the UKB.

As part of the NL DIGITAAL (Data Agenda Government)¹¹⁴, The Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations provides a professional development programme for creating data-driven policies via RADIO (Rijksacademie voor Digitalisering en Informatisering Overheid, the Governmental Academy for Digitalisation and Computerisation of the Government).

See also section E on initiatives undertaken within the Open Science National Plan.

D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks

D.1. Is there a digital competence framework established in the country, and if so, is it based on EU guidelines (e.g. DIGICOMP)?

Yes	No	In planning
	X	

¹¹⁴ <https://www.nldigitalgovernment.nl/wp-content/uploads/sites/11/2019/04/data-agenda-government.pdf>

Key features of the digital competence framework established: Key challenges in case of absence

The DigComp standards have been used as a reference to compare with the outcomes of "Digital Literacy" curricula in primary and secondary schools in the Netherlands by SLO (the institute for curriculum development)¹¹⁵.

Furthermore, a digital literacy assessment framework (MDS) has been proposed by researchers in Twente University and recognized by Unesco as a useful instrument¹¹⁶. However, it seems that there is no formally accepted Digital Competence framework established.

A private consulting company has developed a self-assessment test for digital skills, based on the DigiComp 2.1 Framework. **According to their study**¹¹⁷ Digital Upskilling concerns about 3 million working people (300K Specialists, 400K Advanced and 2300 Basic / Average) and claims that in the next 10 years, the digital skills of this group must rise one level.

¹¹⁵ L. A. Siiman, M. Mäeots, M. Pedaste, R. J. Simons, Ä. Leijen, M. Rannikmäe & M. Timm. An instrument for measuring students' perceived digital competence according to the Digcomp framework. International Conference on Learning and Collaboration Technologies (s.233-244). Springer International Publishing, 2016

¹¹⁶ http://gaml.uis.unesco.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2018/12/4.4.2_02-Assessment-tools-for-monitoring-digital-literacy.pdf

¹¹⁷ https://denkwerk.online/media/1056/english_background.pdf

The Specialists
~300,000 employees
Think of:
Database and network specialists;
Software and application developers

The Advanced
~400,000 employees
Engineers;
Architecture and construction technicians;
Financial specialists;

Basic / Average
~2.3 million employees
Instructors;
Business service providers;
Administrative assistants; Managers

A notable example of a related competence framework is the Media Literacy Competence Model developed by the Dutch network for media literacy (Netwerk Mediawijsheid)¹¹⁸.

D.2. Is there a formal certification or accreditation framework to cover digital up-skilling processes and outputs, and if so under which model? Are these linked to categorised competences?		
Yes	No	In planning
	X	
Key features of digital up-skilling formal certification or accreditation framework		
Key challenges in case of absence		
<p>The country has established a formal National Qualifications Framework (NLQF) for the classification of all possible qualifications in the Netherlands (from basic education to a PhD doctorate)¹¹⁹. NLQF makes it possible to compare formally regulated qualifications to non-formal qualifications (often provided by private institutions).</p> <p>The framework consists of eight levels each one defined by a set of descriptors indicating the learning outcomes relevant to qualifications at that level. The levels are based on descriptions of what someone knows and is able to do after completion of a learning process, regardless of where and, to an extent, in what timeframe this took place. These descriptions of the levels of knowledge, skills, autonomy and responsibility are referred to as learning outcomes. Qualifications are regulated by the Ministry of Education. The Accreditation Organization of the Netherlands and Flanders (NVAO) is responsible for monitoring the framework and keeping it up to date.</p> <p>There is no indication of whether the existing framework and accreditation system are under consideration for being expanded at the digital competencies domain.</p>		

D.3. Are there any national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills, and if so for which target groups and under which delivery channel (e.g. digital platforms)?		
Yes	No	In planning
X		
Key features of national content providers that offer courses on enhancing digital skills		
Key challenges in case of absence		

¹¹⁸ <https://www.mediawijzer.net/op-mediawijzer-net/competentiemodel/>

¹¹⁹ <https://www.nlqf.nl/english>

Netherlands is quite advanced in terms of national content providers that offer courses in enhancing digital skills, although the focus rests highly on basic and average skills to support the strategic goals set in the Digitalization Strategy. Most of the initiatives mentioned above also offer online courses as for example:

- **Kennisnet** offers several services related to digital content for skills such as lesopsence.nl (to organize distance education), Wikiwijs (an educational platform where teachers search, find, reuse, create and share digital learning resources), Teacher24 (support the daily practice of the teacher with practically applicable articles) etc.
- **The network of Libraries and National Library**¹²⁰ offer several courses through the Dutch Library and Basic Skills programme, started in 2015.
- **An online education portal** is planned under the Dutch Technology Pact 2020.
- **According to the Acceleration Agenda for Innovation in Education** by the 1st of January 2023, higher education institutions in the Netherlands shall offer lecturers and students the opportunity to determine and use an optimal mix of **(digital) educational resources** for learning and teaching processes.

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science

E.1. Is there an active national strategy or policy for Research, Data, and Open science? Are there any initiatives for digital up-skilling included?

Yes	No	In planning
X		

Key features of the current Open Science / Open Data culture in the country
Key challenges in case of absence

The Netherlands is widely considered **a leader in Open Science policies** because of its principal role in the formulation of the FAIR-principles, and in the design of the European Open Science Cloud.

Open Science is governed by a National Steering Group chaired by the Ministry of Science & Education and supported by an Advisory Board (chaired by SURF and including representatives from 14 bodies).

According to the 2017 Open Science Declaration, the government confirmed its commitment to contribute to the transition towards an open science system in the Netherlands by ensuring implementation and participating actively in the National Plan for Open Science. The Netherlands consistently holds a very high position in **Open Access** rankings (10% - 20% above the EU benchmark), according to the European Research Area Progress Report¹²¹.

The following are the main policy documents relevant to promoting digital skills in the R&D and Open Science Domains:

The National Plan for Open Science¹²² is the main policy document driving initiatives towards transition to an Open Science system. Its key ambitions are:

- Full open access to publications in 2020: continue the Dutch approach for all Dutch research organisations and research areas whilst recognising their differences and similarities.
- To make research data optimally suited for reuse: Set clear and agreed technical and policy-related preconditions to facilitate reuse of research data, including provision of the necessary expertise and support.

¹²⁰ <https://www.bibliotheeknetwerk.nl/basisvaardigheden-volwassenen/digitaal>

¹²¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f5476f4f-34c2-11e9-8d04-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

¹²² https://www.openscience.nl/files/openscience/2019-02/nationalplanopenscience_en.pdf

- Recognition and rewards: examine how open science can be an element of the evaluation and reward system for researchers, research groups and research proposals. A Rewards & Recognition position paper currently discussed in all universities is regarded as a very important step forward towards this direction¹²³.
- To promote and support: establish a 'clearing house' for all information regarding all available research support.

The plan concentrates on three areas:

- Promoting open access to scientific publications (open access), which is currently very highly ranked in the Netherlands.
- Promoting optimal use and reuse of research data (towards FAIR data).
- Adapting evaluation and award systems to bring them into line with the objectives of open science (reward systems).

The National Steering Group for Open Science is currently elaborating the new Open Plan for 2020-2030. As part of the plan several **training courses and tools** are being developed to support the above objectives:

- Training courses for researchers through universities and universities of applied sciences.
- Research Data Netherlands (RDNL)¹²⁴, a partnership involving 4TU. Research Data¹²⁵, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)¹²⁶ and SURFsara¹²⁷, offers the "Essentials 4 Data Support" online course an introductory course for those who (want to) support researchers in storing, managing, archiving and sharing their research data.
- Training courses for research are also provided through SURF. In addition to training courses, SURF also provides consultancy.
- The eScience Center¹²⁸ offers training courses such as 'data carpentry' and 'software carpentry' which focus entirely on open science and open source. Such training courses, in particular those aimed at making data FAIR, are also provided by Dutch Center for Life Sciences (DTL) in the context of ELIXIR (part of the strategic roadmap for scientific infrastructure of the Dutch government).
- The PhD Candidates Network of the Netherlands actively emphasises the importance of providing researchers in the Netherlands with the best possible training in the skills required to be able to carry out open science.

Since 2018 a National Coordinator for Open Science has been appointed.

A major step in the Policy implementation is the establishment of the **National Platform for Open Science (NPOS)**¹²⁹ which brings together the parties that have initiated, formulated, or support the National Plan. The focus for the Platform is to create acceleration with regard to the three key areas of the National Plan Open Science. In this regard we have the following focus points:

- Set quantitatively and qualitatively measurable elements in line with the existing national and European monitoring. This should not involve a heavy administrative burden.
- Share knowledge and experience with each other and establish links.
- Respond to new developments in the field of open science, which may involve additional actions being taken.

¹²³ <http://vsnu.nl/recognitionandrewards/recognition-and-rewards/index.html>

¹²⁴ <https://researchdata.nl>

¹²⁵ https://www.4tu.nl/en/about_4tu/

¹²⁶ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en>

¹²⁷ <https://userinfo.surfsara.nl>

¹²⁸ <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/>

¹²⁹ <https://www.openscience.nl/en/national-platform-open-science>

Several projects are launched within the NPOS initiative¹³⁰ and part of them are **related to the area of digital skills for open science**. More specifically, Project F “Professionalising data stewardship: competences, training and education” integrates the challenges, efforts and output of various national initiatives and organisations into recommendations for a national approach on professionalising data stewardship in the Netherlands, building upon outcomes and recommendations of two previous projects (2019), the ZonMw data stewardship project¹³¹ and the LCRDM data stewardship project¹³². It also aligns with projects currently taking place, such as the RDA 23 things project, the NPOS E project (Exploring the Dutch data landscape) and the NPOS H project (Accelerate Open Science).

An EU study published in early 2019 titled “The Netherlands’ Plan on Open Science”¹³³ recommends that *“the operationalization of NPOS policies needs to be translated into actions at the institutional and individual level at Dutch universities. VSNU will need targeted action plan and open science agreement with every university and faculty, to lay out concrete activities regarding open access publishing, training in data management, institutional update on library repository, monitor and evaluate researchers in all aspect of the research cycle, and include fixed percentages of working time on digital infrastructural work”*.

It should be noted however that NPOS relies currently on project- oriented activities and thus its sustainability as an operational entity is currently being studied.

The Digital Society Research Agenda¹³⁴, formulated by the joint Dutch universities (VSNU) in accordance with the Dutch National Research Agenda, elaborates seven programme lines underlying universities’ joint efforts towards a futureproofing education in a digital society, including “Responsible Data Science” (how to enable full and responsible use of big data) and “Learning and education” (how to enable people to participate meaningfully in all stages of life), the latter of which recognizes that “being up-to date in knowledge and skills thus critically depend on digital tools demanding for life-long learning. Those digital tools enable personalised content delivery and for example personalised assessment related to the knowledge level of the student or work”. Although initiatives are planned under the Acceleration Agenda for Innovation in Education, most of them are targeted at society at large. To this end, the Digital Society Research Agenda plans a set of initiatives to focus more on science-driven tools and digital skills.

VSNU has also published the **Digitization in Academic Education agenda**¹³⁵ for a future-proof range of degree programmes, identifying 10 points for actions to take full advantage of the opportunities for the digitisation of education, including strengthening graduates’ digital skills, digital resilience, and lecturers’ digital skills.

The Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO) has published its 2019-2022 Strategy **“Connecting Science and Society”** which promotes the Open Science principles, acknowledges the importance of new skills and describes initiatives for further developing high-grade ICT infrastructures (high-performance computing, in networks, data facilities and in cyber security).

Regarding Data related policies, the government published the **Data Agenda (NL Digitaal)** which sets out how data can be used (even) better to improve policy-making and resolve social issues and recognizes that to adopt a data-driven approach, the government must strongly invest in enhancing special digital skills of persons involved and focus on establishing a change in corporate and

¹³⁰ <https://www.openscience.nl/en/projects>

¹³¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3471707>

¹³² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2669149>

¹³³ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/20d4026e-4478-11e9-a8ed-01aa75ed71a1>

¹³⁴ <https://www.thedigitalsociety.info/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/VSNU-Digital-Society-Research-Agenda.pdf>

¹³⁵ <https://www.thedigitalsociety.info/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/VSNU-Digitisation-in-academic-education.pdf>

employee culture, identifying relevant action plans such as the professional development programs and a Data Science training scheme.

Netherlands has a strong **Open Data culture** backed up by both legal and policy documents and best practices¹³⁶.

Regarding **awarding of good research**, developments which are already underway include:

- The SEP - the methodology used to evaluate institutes, institutions and universities is being updated to promote open data and reproducibility
- The Protocol for Research Quality Assurance in Higher Professional Education (BKO) for universities of applied sciences contains elements of open science, but also other criteria allowing institutions an option to choose.
- To support the general research evaluation systems, DANS, in collaboration with DTL, is developing a system for the assessment of research data in accordance with the FAIR principles.

Furthermore, a new scheme for accreditation is currently under development through collaboration of Ministry of Science & Education, representatives of all academic associations, as well as the scientific community to create clear career paths related to Open Science.

According to the report “Progress on Open Science: Towards a Shared Research Knowledge System” by the EU¹³⁷, the Data Stewardship training programme that Dutch National funders are supporting across universities in the Netherlands could provide a possible model training and subsequent accreditation on research integrity rewards, which is currently lacking at EU level.

NPOS aims to reform the manner in which researchers are assessed in such a way that the assessment actually stimulates open science. Recently, the VSNU, NWO, NFO and ZonMw have already begun laying the groundwork for a renewal of scholarly recognition and reward frameworks¹³⁸.

Regarding legislation

- The Dutch government officially adopted an Open Access policy with respect to publications in 2013 (<https://www.openaccess.nl/en/in-the-netherlands/what-does-the-government-want>).
- Article 25fa of the Copyright Act allows researchers to share short scientific works (e.g. articles & book chapters), regardless of any restrictive publishers' guidelines.

Owner/ Responsibility and Main Stakeholders involved :

Research & Innovation policies in the Netherlands are mainly centralised at the national level. The central government remains the main financing body, but policymaking and focus areas are gradually becoming more regionalised. Direct support to business R&I is also increasingly provided at the regional level, partly because R&I have become more prominent in the EU Structural Funds. The main policy actors in R&I are the Ministries of Economic Affairs and Climate (EAC) and Education, Culture and Science (ECS). EAC and ECS share the responsibility for enterprise policy, which includes innovation policy. ECS is responsible for science and education policies and the allocation of institutional funding to the universities. The main R&I policy implementation bodies are the Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and

¹³⁶ https://www.europeandataportal.eu/sites/default/files/country-factsheet_netherlands_2018.pdf

¹³⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/ec_rtd_osp-final-report.pdf

¹³⁸ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/news-and-events/news/2018/11/drive-change-in-recognition-and-reward-of-academics.html>

Sciences (KNAW), and the Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO). Non-profit organisations and foundations do not play a large role in R&I funding in the Netherlands¹³⁹

The Open Science policy participants include: Data Archiving and Networking Services (DANS), The Young Academy, Dutch Techcentre for Life Sciences, Global Open Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (GO FAIR), National Library of the Netherlands (KB), Royal Netherlands Academy of Sciences (KNAW), National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM), Netherlands eScience Center, Dutch Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU), Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), PhD Candidates Network of the Netherlands (PNN), SURF, 4TU.Centre for Research Data, Consortium of Dutch University Libraries and the National Library (UKB), Netherlands Association of Universities of Applied Sciences (VH), Association of universities in the Netherlands (VSNU) and Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development (ZonMw).

Several of the above organizations form a part of the R&D ecosystem in Netherlands.

Furthermore, on a national level Netherlands has 40 Digital Innovation Hubs¹⁴⁰ (18 fully operational and 22 in preparation status) covering various market domains through a large spectrum of technology areas.

NWO has published a call for Universities, academic medical centres and the NWO and KNAW institute organisation to apply for one-off impulse funding for the establishment or further development of a locally based Digital Competence Centre (DCC). The funding is intended to stimulate research institutions to further develop an existing centralised DCC, or to set up a DCC at a central level within the institution¹⁴¹. Furthermore, NWO provides substantial funding for Digital Competence Centers to promote Open Science principles.

E2. Key features of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes Key challenges in case of absence

The Netherlands established a Permanent Committee for large scale research infrastructures. It was announced in the 2025 Vision for Science of the Dutch government and has been appointed by NWO on behalf of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science.

The Advisory Report on the national digital infrastructure for scientific research issued by NOW states that “Digital infrastructure includes five elements: Networks, Computing facilities; Data, eScience and Authorisation and authentication (cybersecurity). All of these elements include the support of highly skilled professionals. Three organisations are key to providing digital infrastructure at the Dutch national level: SURF, the Netherlands eScience Centre, and DANS. But universities, public research organisations, and discipline-specific collaborations also have their own important facilities, and equipment and software may also be provided by commercial organisations”.

In 2019, a decision on EUR20 M annual investments in digital infrastructure was made which includes a network of so-called Digital Competence Centres at RPOs. NWO strategy states that “science has an increasing need for the rapid analysis of research data, its storage and access to it. A strong ICT infrastructure provides the foundation for large-scale scientific infrastructure. NWO plans to make additional investments possible in high-performance computing, in networks, data facilities and in cyber security. NWO also acknowledges the need for extra investments in large computing facilities and the development of research software and support of its use”.

¹³⁹ https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/bitstream/JRC111333/jrc111333_rio_cr_nl_2017_pubsy_final.pdf

¹⁴⁰ <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/documents/20182/318091/Netherlands.pdf/14ed2388-0074-451b-850b-19a92d419cb4>

¹⁴¹ <https://www.nwo.nl/en/funding/our-funding-instruments/enw/local-digital-competence-centres/local-digital-competence-centres.html>

Further details can be found in the EOSC – Synergy Landscaping Country Report for the Netherlands, as well as the “Landscape of EOSC-Related Infrastructures and Initiatives”.

E3. Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry Key challenges in case of absence

Netherlands enjoys strong links between the Research Community and the Industry, as is evident from the European Research Area Progress Report (2018), according to which:

- it enjoys a high number of academic job ads per 1000 research (104 vs 42 EU Average)
- A large portion (67 %) of the country’s researchers felt that hiring processes were open, transparent and merit-based. This performance was very close to the EU-28 benchmark and above ERA average
- The majority of Dutch universities were recognised by the European Commission with the HR Excellence in Research Award. There is a Dutch website called Academic Transfer. It combines vacancies in all academic institutions in the Netherlands and is interlinked with EURAXESS. All the vacancies that are uploaded on the national website are transferred to EURAXESS

Furthermore, several partners of important stakeholders (such as DTL) are actively seeking collaboration with academic institutions to promote FAIR principles by raising awareness and building communities. Health funds also play an important role, as they are after “good” data (especially under the CoVID situation) so several initiatives have taken place to link research and industry.

Annex VI: Country Factsheets

 Denmark	<p>Denmark, the smallest country in Scandinavia, has been widely recognised as one of the most advanced digital economies in the EU. Ranked in the DESI scale as the fourth most digitally advanced economy in Europe, there is plenty to learn from Denmark when it comes to digitalisation. One area in which Denmark has particularly excelled, in relation to other frontrunner countries, is in its effort to ensure that all citizens benefit from digitalisation. 95% of Danes are online - well above the European average - while half of those aged 65 or above have basic digital skills (DESI). This success is driven by the country's focus on fostering innovation through partnerships and collaboration, sharing best practice and learning from others. Even though Denmark is among the most digitized nations, research shows that more than 1 million Danish citizens aged 16 to 65 years of age are lacking in digital skills. In the ICT sector, Denmark also has a critical skills gap, which seems to be growing looking into the future. Therefore, some of the main challenges that Denmark faces are the stagnating supply of ICT professionals, while demand is growing, the projection stated in Europe's Digital Progress Report (2017) that the Danish companies will face a deficit of 19,000 employees with digital skills by 2030 as well as maintaining a steady supply of expertise which is crucial to Denmark's continued success.</p>
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	16,46	12,51	Knowledge	6	Availability of latest technologies	18
Human Capital	15,32	12,32	Technology	11	ICT Patent applications	16
Use of Internet Services	11,27	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	8	ICT Skills	5
Integration of Digital Technology	13,03	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	1	Publication and use of open data.	13
Digital Public Services	13,07	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	21	R&D expenditure by government & HE	1
ICT graduates	4,80	3,60	Development & application of technology	6	Online trust & safety	48
ICT Specialists	4,30	3,90	Scientific research legislation	6	ICT Regulatory environment	42
Doing an online course	12,27	11,17				
Open data	0,78	0,66				
Future Readiness						Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS						Yes
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science						Yes
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not						Yes
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index						6
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index						11
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index						2
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories						16

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	No
Key features / challenges	Some challenges to be addressed refer to regulatory barriers that seem to be slowing progress in Denmark's education system, clarification of the governmental responsibility into driving progress in digital learning, promotion of Online and distance-learning courses followed by improved accreditation and enhanced organizational support.
Main Stakeholders involved:	Many Danish actors share responsibility for progress in digitalization, but mainly the Danish Ministry of Finance, Local Government Denmark and Danish Regions, and the Danish Agency for Digitization of Danish Ministry of Finance. The Danish National coalition defines common objectives, invites relevant parties to join and to co-create an action plan to bridge the skill gap.
B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	No
Key features / challenges	There is not a single organisation responsible for the national coordination of digital skills policies in Denmark. Yet, there are some initiatives, entities and partnerships which perform monitoring and coordinating work on digital skills policies: The Danish Technology Pact, formed in 2018 as an initiative of the Strategy for Denmark Digital Growth (2018), the Danish National Coalition, that defines common objectives, invites relevant parties to join and to co-create an action plan to bridge the skill gap and the Technology Covenant, a collaboration between the government, private companies, educational institutions, organizations and other stakeholders, with the aim to strengthen the population's competencies in ICT.

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	The Digital Hub Denmark - The SME Digital initiative
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	a) The Digital Hub Denmark, formed in 2018, aims to support and strengthen the digital growth environment in Denmark by facilitating collaboration across private companies, researchers, and tech-entrepreneurs. b) The SME Digital initiative addresses the digital competence challenges that SMEs in particular are facing, with a strong focus on improving the skills of business leaders and a digital design consultancy.

D. Current Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	No
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	At present, there is no formal integral digital competence framework, yet the Centre for Digital Dannelse has created the "Digital Competency Wheel 1", "Digital Competency Wheel 2" to assess, to provide an overview and to improve the most relevant digital skills. The work is based on DigComp as a theoretical framework.
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	Yes
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	Denmark has a bipartite accreditation system: The Danish Accreditation Institution plays a crucial part in ensuring the quality and relevance of higher education programmes across the country and the various qualifications offered in the Danish education and training system are organized in accordance with the national qualifications framework

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	Yes
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	Denmark does not have an integrated Open Science Policy, yet a national Open Access Strategy and a national strategy for Research data management are in place.
Main Stakeholders involved	The Ministry of Higher Education and Science manages and monitors the Danish Open Access strategy, while DeIC is working on national structure for RDM support and training.
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	Denmark's digital infrastructure and attitudes towards digitalisation are some of the best in Europe. The main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes in Denmark include: CERN-UP – Upgrading infrastructure for CERN experiments and computing, QUANTECH – Quantum Technology Infrastructure, BICLabs – Behaviour, Interaction and Cognition Labs, DigHumLab 2.0 – Digital Humanities Lab Denmark, DRDS – Danish Research Data for the Social Sciences, FiberLab – New Fibre Composites Laboratory
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	There is a strong link between research community and the industry, implemented via partnerships such as the Technology Pact and the Digital Hub Denmark. According to the European Research Area (ERA) Progress Report for the period 2016-2018, what is probably Denmark's most noteworthy performance is the number of public-private collaborative papers per capita

<p>Finland</p>	<p>Finland is among the most advanced digital economies in the EU and has a history of ranking high on the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), including the 3rd place in 2018, with a 73.8 overall performance score in 2018. It has the highest scores in human capital, integration of digital technology and digital public services, ranking 1st, 2nd, and 1st respectively in 2018. Finland is well known for its world-class education system from primary school to lifelong education and training, which is reflected in its high rankings across the board in digital learning indicators, having one of the highest score on the Women in Digital Scoreboard (WID 2020). The Finnish education system is one of the best globally and ICT specialists' share of the workforce (6.7%) is one the highest as well. Digital skills remain the strongest competitive advantage of the Finnish economy. Besides, it is roughly believed that Finland needs to reskill 1 million people within the next ten years, that is a challenge to be addressed since Finland aims to be known as a front runner in technological advances, innovative procurement and the culture of experimentation.</p>
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	14,79	12,51	Knowledge	9	Availability of latest technologies	1
Human Capital	19,61	12,32	Technology	8	ICT Patent applications	4
Use of Internet Services	11,45	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	11	ICT Skills	10
Integration of Digital Technology	13,40	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	7	Publication and use of open data.	21
Digital Public Services	13,04	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	11	R&D expenditure by government & HE	4
ICT graduates	6,30	3,60	Development & application of technology	2	Online trust & safety	44
ICT Specialists	7,20	3,90	Scientific research legislation	3	ICT Regulatory environment	22
Doing an online course	22,25	11,17				
Open data	0,76	0,66				
Future Readiness						Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS						Yes
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science						N/A
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not						Yes
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index						7
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index						5
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index						7
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories						20

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Yes
Key features / challenges	Finland is in the vanguard of education, skills, and modern learning techniques, holding the 3rd place in digital learning readiness across the EU-27. Finland aims to be known as a front runner in technological advances, innovative procurement, and the culture of experimentation, making all public services available digitally to individuals and businesses by 2023. The main Finnish digitalisation policies and strategies are the Digital Finland Framework, the Artificial Intelligence strategy, the digitalisation, experimentation and Deregulation programme for public sector ICT, and the digital transformation programme for the regional government, health, and social services reform.
Main Stakeholders involved:	Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment and Ministry of Education and Culture are coordinating together to ensure that Finland is a leading country in future learning and inspiring education.

B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	No
Key features / challenges	There is not a single authority that carries out the integral national responsibility for digital skills planning and implementation in Finland, although many initiatives attempt to coordinate digital skills policies design and implementation.

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	Various initiatives implemented
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	There are numerous initiatives at local level, implemented by schools, vocational institutions, and other educational institutions as well as on national level, providing funding frameworks, with the cooperation of the private domain. In 2017, the government allocated an additional 60 million Euros in its budget for skilling the labour force, with a special focus on digital skills, in 2018, the Ministry of Education and Culture, together with the National Board of Education and the Finnish National Agency for Education, started a program with the aim of strengthening adults' digital and basic skills, while the digital era programme (2018-2020) is a program funded by Ministry of Education and Culture that aims to strengthen the basic skills and digital skills of adults, especially the unemployed.

D. Current Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	No
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	Despite development of digital materials and online training in adult and vocational education, there is not enough evidence of how widely these trainings are accredited and this remains an obstacle for higher education, hence requiring further attention. Although, there is lack of a national Digital Skills certification / accreditation / competence framework, the ongoing work for the development of Open Science/Data and digital transformation policies, aiming to be concluded by mid next year, will address the issue at least for researchers.
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	No
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	Even though a certification / accreditation framework is lacking, there are some assessment tools to evaluate digital skills or other skills using digital assessment tools. These tools are also used for teachers and schools to measure and analyse their usage of ICT.

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	In planning
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	Promotion of open science and research is a joint effort by the entire research community. In the centre of the coordination work are our four expert panels and their working groups on Culture of open scholarship, Open data, Open access and Open education. The Expert panel on open data contributes actively in the making of national policies and recommendations on the national Open policy that is expected to be completed by middle of 2021 and working in cooperation with the National Open Science and Research Steering Group, drafted principles for the Policy on Open Access to Research Materials and Methods and a policy component on Open Access to Research Data. Strong cooperation with EOSC has been set up in order Finland to exploit EOSC working results and enhance them in its undergoing policies, addressing so, the goals of SRIA.
Main Stakeholders involved	The Digital and Population Data Services Agency leads the way in the field, while national working groups and panel of experts are actually working on the development of the Transformation 2030 Strategy for researchers, and the Open Data Policy.
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	The platform Fairdata.fi offers metadata tool, research dataset finder, storage areas of digital information for tens or even hundreds of years and for actual use, constituting the central point for research work applying open data science principles.
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	Strong emphasis is given on the partnerships among research community and the industry. Key facilitator is the CSC a non-profit state enterprise with special tasks, along with SITRA. Headai is also another example of cooperation between public and private domain as a job tech company that uses artificial intelligence to map skills needs and provision in Finland.

<p>France</p>	<p>France ranks 17th in the EU on human capital indicators, below the EU average, as per the 2020 edition of the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI). France has embarked on a comprehensive drive for sustainable and inclusive digital transformation. Underpinning this drive is France’s investment plan 2018-2022, which aims, among others to foster competitiveness and innovation, and achieve the digital transformation of the public sector. Moreover, France has played an important role in the European open access movement, particularly in the launch of the Berlin declaration. Among French research structures, the research institutions (CNRS, INSERM in particular) played a major role at the beginning of the 2000’s, especially with the launch of the HAL open archive in 2001, while there are several legislative texts that set the framework for the publication and sharing of open data.</p>
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	12,46	12,51	Knowledge	20	Availability of latest technologies	19
Human Capital	11,86	12,32	Technology	16	ICT Patent applications	19
Use of Internet Services	7,96	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	13	ICT Skills	18
Integration of Digital Technology	8,41	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	18	Publication and use of open data.	3
Digital Public Services	11,51	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	16	R&D expenditure by government & HE	15
ICT graduates	3,00	3,60	Development & application of technology	29	Online trust & safety	4
ICT Specialists	3,90	3,90	Scientific research legislation	11	ICT Regulatory environment	11
Doing an online course	8,40	11,17				
Open data	0,89	0,66				
Future Readiness						Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS						Yes
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science						Yes
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not						Yes
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index						18
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index						4
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index						29
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories						5

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Yes
Key features / challenges	The national strategy / policy of France for digital skills is mainly reflected in the National Plan for Inclusive Digital and launch of Digital in Common(s), launched in September 2018, with an objective to train 1.5 million people in digital literacy in order to reduce inequalities and provide equal opportunities for all throughout the country. With 13 million French people who still do not use the Internet, or only to a limited extent, including 6.7 million who never connect to the Internet, this is a real challenge for the country which is committed to carrying out the digital transformation
Main Stakeholders involved:	The French National Coalition coordinated and led by MEDEF, established in 2017, has already involved more than 50 organisations such as Ministry of Labour, Paris Descartes University, PIX - platform for assessing and certifying digital skills, Adecco Group France, Digital Talents - The French Digital Agency, Orange Great Digital School, CFDT - French Democratic Confederation of Labour, etc.
B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	Yes
Key features / challenges	The coordination and governance for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation in France is carried out by the French digital coalition for skills and jobs that was set up in 2016 and MEDEF was appointed by the European Commission to be its coordinator and facilitator. Today, more than 200 actors from different horizons have joined this coalition and are working together. The collation is aiming to identify and promote initiatives and good practices on digital skills, bring together all local and national actors active in digital matters (administrations, associations, NGOs, professional organizations, companies, unions, etc.) and carry out concrete actions throughout the territory that will enhance the digital skills and competences.
C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	French Digital Skills & Jobs Coalition activities
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	The French Digital Skills & Jobs Coalition is carrying out several initiatives to boost digital skills. In 2019, the Coalition organised a competition for young people on the professions of the future. It established a partnership with the Ministry of Labour to support businesses and employees on AI development, and work is ongoing to improve its platform to share information with other European National Coalitions. In 2019, a good number of schools and other organisations took part in EU Code Week, a grassroots movement to encourage people of all ages to code. France held over 500 events that attracted over 90,000 participants. France’s measures to improve the digital skills of its population, both through formal education and inclusion measures, are underway and should produce tangible results over the coming years. More targeted initiatives will be important to upskill the workforce for the digital economy and to promote advanced digital skills development, in AI and in other areas too.
D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	Yes
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	French Government has endorsed a Digital Competence Framework System based on DigiComp 2.0 to develop, measure, and certify digital competences for all. In this framework, France has developed the PIX platform that allows all citizens to evaluate and also certify their digital competence.
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	The French platform PIX allows all citizens to evaluate and also certify their digital competence. The model, which is co-designed by the Min. of Education, uses DigComp.
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	The French platform Pix.fr is a free online public service open to everyone to assess and develop digital skills and it allows all citizens to take stock and improve their digital knowledge and skills.
E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	Yes
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	In July 2018, the Ministry of Higher Education, Research, and Innovation adopted the ambition National Plan for Open Science. The plan presents three broad commitments under the headings: a) generalising Open Access to Publications, b) structuring Research Data and making it available through Open Access, and c) be part of a sustainable European and international open science dynamic. Each commitment is accompanied by a short Roadmap section, which outlines the steppingstones to meeting each commitment.
Main Stakeholders involved	The French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS) and the Open Science Committee, with 270 experts, some of whom are involved through a series of thematic and project groups and a collaborative forum to identify pragmatic, collective and collaborative methods to achieve the plan’s objectives.
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	The main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes infrastructures consist of four computing infrastructures (GENCI, CCIN2P3, Grid’5000, and France Grilles) and two network infrastructures (RENATER and FIT). Most of these infrastructures are integrated into European or international infrastructures.
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	French firms’ propensity to cooperate with either universities or higher education institutions, or with governmental, public, or private research institutes, is similar to the EU-28 score, according to the 2018 ERA progress report.

<p>Greece</p>	<p>The level of digital skills of Greek citizens is behind the EU27 average, while Greece belongs to the category of the low performing countries in the DESI Index. Greece, like the rest of southern and eastern Europe performs poorly in digital learning, which score low on European rankings related to economic performance, innovation, and digitalisation. According to the DESI Report for 2020, Greece is ranked as 23rd in the “Human Capital” dimension. Greece suffers from a Brain drain’ of ICT graduates alongside a severe digital skills gap according to 2020 DESI Performances. In addition, Greece has one of lowest score on the Women in Digital Scoreboard (WID 2020). Open Access/ Science policies are slowly adopted by the Greek Higher Education Institutes. Currently, Greece does not yet have in place a specific, formally approved National strategy for Open Science.</p>
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	8,34	12,51	Knowledge	53	Availability of latest technologies	60
Human Capital	8,70	12,32	Technology	54	ICT Patent applications	34
Use of Internet Services	6,91	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	33	ICT Skills	39
Integration of Digital Technology	5,64	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	28	Publication and use of open data.	36
Digital Public Services	7,73	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	20	R&D expenditure by government & HE	28
ICT graduates	2,90	3,60	Development & application of technology	55	Online trust & safety	55
ICT Specialists	1,80	3,90	Scientific research legislation	52	ICT Regulatory environment	27
Doing an online course	7,46	11,17				
Open data	0,66	0,66				
Future Readiness						Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS						Yes
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science						Yes
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not						No
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index						43
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index						35
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index						53
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories						20

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Yes
Key features / challenges	Greece’s national policy on digital skills is currently mainly expressed through the National Digital Skills Coalition Action Plan 2017-2020: Enhancing Digital Skills and Jobs in Greece (EDSGR). The EDGSR is a multi-stakeholder initiative, comprised of 4 key pillars: education, training, ICT professionals and citizens. 12 priorities have been defined, among which Priority 7: Promoting e-skills through RTDI activities is included, with an aim to support collaborative RTDI projects between enterprises and Public Research Centres as well as Higher Education Institutions, to establish specialized competence centres, Digital Innovation Hubs, and clusters, to promote recruitment of highly qualified personnel in enterprises to conduct research for the development of innovative products/services and to enhance extroversion of enterprises through participation in bilateral and transnational RTDI co-operation.
Main Stakeholders involved:	The responsible body is the General Secretariat of Digital Governance and Simplification of Procedures of the Ministry of Digital Governance. Other stakeholders involved include the members of the National Digital Skills Coalition, such as Ministry Labour and Social Affairs, Ministry of Education and Religious Affairs, Public Employment Service, Hellenic Open University, Municipalities, Athena Research & Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Science Technologies, etc.
B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	Yes
Key features / challenges	The General Secretariat of Digital Governance and Simplification of Procedures under Ministry of Digital Governance is responsible for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation. Greek National Coalition for Digital Skills and Jobs members come both from public and private sector and participate in the work of the five groups of the Coalition. A coordinator, chosen from among its members, is appointed in each of the five groups for a term of one year.
C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	National Digital Academy & Greek Digital Skills Coalition activities
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	The National Digital Academy aims to gather, at an entry point, educational content that improves the digital skills of citizens. At the Digital Academy, the citizen can choose freely, free of charge and without complicated registration procedures the courses that suit his/her needs, interests and level of knowledge and skills. The monitoring is online and is done at the pace that suits everyone.

D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	In planning
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	Currently, there is not digital competence framework formally established in the country, as per DIGICOMP guidelines. However, in the context of the Digital Transformation Bible that is currently under development, the need for introducing a digital competence framework in Greece is stated and relative actions are already being implemented within the context of Technical Assistance provided by DG Reform. As a first result, Citizen Digital Academy includes a self -assessment tool based on DigiComp v2.1 (21 competences organized in 5 areas).
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	Yes
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	EOPPEP, Greece’s National Organisation for the certification of qualifications and vocational guidance, develops and implements the National Accreditation & Certification System for non-formal education, including initial and continuing vocational training and adult education, and provides scientific support to Vocational Guidance & Counselling services in Greece

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	Yes (Research strategy) / Open Data/ Science (In planning)
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	Open Access/ Science policies are slowly adopted by HEI of Greece. Currently, Greece does not yet have in place a specific, formally approved National strategy for Open Science. The Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3) used for the programming period 2014-2020 and funding ESIF is fully aligned with European policies and goals for research and innovation.
Main Stakeholders involved	The General Secretariat for Research and Technology (GSRT), GRNET, National Infrastructures for Research and Technology, Athena Research & Innovation Centre in Information, Communication and Science Technologies, Centre for Nuclear Research, Demokritos, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas / CERTH, Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas (FORTH), National Hellenic Research Foundation / NHRF and National Observatory of Athens (NOA)
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	With regards to e- Infrastructures, the horizontal HELIX: National Digital Infrastructure for Research is a convergence-building instrument for the coordination of research-oriented e-infrastructures in Greece, coordinated by GRNET aims at an overall coordination of research-oriented e-infrastructures with a wide participation of all research centres. It comprises two independent and complementary entities - NNCR and OpenAIRE-D - that respectively address the increasing horizontal 'big computing/networking' and 'big data' needs of the Greek academic & research community
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	Recently the “Research – Create – Innovate” action was set-up in Greece that promotes the collaboration between research laboratories and businesses. Furthermore, clusters, the creation of spin off companies, science parks and Technology Transfer Offices are also being promoted.

<p>Hungary</p>	<p>Hungary has an incredibly detailed and over-ambitious digital education strategy that together with the digital workforce programme drive the country's digital skills initiatives in education and lifelong learning, under a tight governance scheme and mainly through EU funds. The strategies strongly focus on basic digital skills to help the country attain its goal of reaching the EU average. Considering that there is still no formal Open Science policy, despite the significant activity in the field, it is of no surprise that few related digital skills enhancement initiatives have been recorded. A new overarching national digital strategy that includes digital skills as a pillar is about to be published so some reorientation is expected.</p>
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	14,95	12,51	Knowledge	44	Availability of latest technologies	42
Human Capital	10,46	12,32	Technology	36	ICT Patent applications	23
Use of Internet Services	8,38	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	26	ICT Skills	27
Integration of Digital Technology	5,06	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	30	Publication and use of open data.	63
Digital Public Services	8,67	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	34	R&D expenditure by government & HE	53
ICT graduates	4,30	3,60	Development & application of technology	47	Online trust & safety	82
ICT Specialists	3,70	3,90	Scientific research legislation	49	ICT Regulatory environment	2
Doing an online course	6,96	11,17				
Open data	0,32	0,66				
Future Readiness						Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS						Yes
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science						N/A
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not						No
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index						38
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index						N/A
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index						57
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories						28

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Yes
Key features / challenges	The country's digital strategy document is the National Infocommunication Strategy 2014-2020, which includes a pillar on Digital Competencies for population, SMEs, public administration and e-inclusion. Based on the above strategy, the major policy documents that guide Digital Skills development are the Digital Education Strategy and the Digital Workforce Programme. Hungary has set up the National Coalition for Digital Skills and Jobs (2016) to facilitate stakeholder discussions on tackling the shortage of digitally skilled people in the Hungarian labour market and help the government develop and implement adequate strategies.
Main Stakeholders involved:	Ministry of Innovation and Technology formed in 2018 has the responsibility for the Digital Education Strategy in Hungary. To implement the strategy, the government set up the Digital Pedagogical Methodology Centre. The Digital Workforce Programme is owned by the Ministry of National Economy. Other institutions involved include Ministry of Human Capacities, DJP Non-profit (Digitális Jólét) Nonprofit Kft, IVSZ, the association of the Information and Communication Technologies industry in Hungary (coordinator of the National Coalition), KIFÜ, the e-Infrastructure provider and the Institute for Computer Science and Control.
B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	Yes
Key features / challenges	The digital skills governance landscape in Hungary is quite centralized, since the main policy documents are owned by the Ministry of Innovation and Technology, under the Digital Success Program. It must be noted however that Ministry of National Economy also plays a significant part in the overall governance as owner of the Digital Workforce programme. The Digital Pedagogical Methodology Centre provides professional support for the implementation of several applications to help develop and disseminate digital education.
C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	Six major initiatives
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	The establishment of the Digital Success Coordinator Centre : assists the Ministry in developing digital ecosystems, increasing the level of digital literacy and coordinating programs in this field for non-school education and professional coordination of the DSP network results, informs relevant actors, oversees and coordinates Digital Care Program Mentors. The Digital Success Mentor Programme , which has set up 1,500 community digital access points with ICT trainings for those with low digital skills using around 2.100 mentors. Several ESIF Operational Programmes that support the aims of the Digital Education Strategy are implemented, sometimes supplemented with a Competitive Central-Hungary Operative Programme (CCHOP) part if they involve national scale. The 'Programme your future' project aims to boost the number of students that graduate in ICT and improve cooperation between the educational institutions and the ICT sector. The government has launched two initiatives to increase the number of women in ICT. TechGirls is organised by the German-Hungarian Chamber of Commerce and Industry, while Girls' Day is organised by the Association of Hungarian Women in Science. Also, Digital thematic weeks are organised on a regular basis to promote digital pedagogic methodologies.
D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	Yes
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	As part of the Digital Education strategy, the project "Bridge the Digital Gap" aims to test DigComp as a general, novel framework for digital skills. In this context, the government issued the 1341/2019. (VI. 11.) Government decree for the development and implementation of a Digital Competence Framework System based on DigiComp 2.1.
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	No
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	According to the Situation Analysis of the Digital Education Strategy (2016): The HAC (Hungarian Accreditation Committee) programme accreditation procedure does not support the national and institutional accreditation (and thus independent student work in foreign languages) of national and international online programmes (online courses available to masses).
E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	In planning
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	According to the SPARC Europe "Analysis of Open Science Policies in Europe v6, no policy is yet in place, although the first steps have been taken in late 2017 with the formation of a joint experts committee for open science. The Committee has produced a policy draft which is currently being discussed.
Main Stakeholders involved	The owner of the forthcoming policy appears to be the National Research Development and Innovation Office.
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	In 2018 Hungary published its National Research Infrastructure Roadmap, aiming to identify the major research infrastructures in Hungary.
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	Hungary is lagging EU average in terms of links between the Research Community and the Industry, as is evident from the European Research Area Progress Report (2018), according to which the country suffers from a very wide gap in terms of number of academic job ads per 1000 researches (2 vs 42 EU Average!) while a low portion (35%) of the country's researchers felt that hiring processes were open, transparent and merit-based. This performance is also far from the EU-28 benchmark.

<p>Lithuania</p>	<p>Lithuania has one of the best scores for connectivity and digital infrastructure in the EU but its population levels of digital skills are not as high (DESI Performances 2020), despite having early policies focusing on the ‘information society’ in the 2000s. The country is gradually improving in human capital thanks to policies dedicated to reducing basic shortfalls in digital skills, narrowing the gender-gap, and investing in the up-skilling of the ICT labour force.</p>
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	12,22	12,51	Knowledge	26	Availability of latest technologies	30
Human Capital	10,96	12,32	Technology	25	ICT Patent applications	42
Use of Internet Services	8,60	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	41	ICT Skills	22
Integration of Digital Technology	9,89	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	31	Publication and use of open data.	N/A
Digital Public Services	12,22	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	32	R&D expenditure by government & HE	30
ICT graduates	2,70	3,60	Development & application of technology	30	Online trust & safety	N/A
ICT Specialists	2,70	3,90	Scientific research legislation	27	ICT Regulatory environment	5
Doing an online course	9,07	11,17				
Open data	0,53	0,66				

Future Readiness	Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS	Yes
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science	Yes
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not	No
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index	31
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index	N/A
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index	32
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories	29

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Yes
Key features / challenges	The Information Society Development Programme 2014 – 2020 Digital Agenda for Lithuania among its priorities includes the enhancement of the Lithuanian residents’ ability to use the ICTs, mainly by improving their digital skills and competences is identified. In addition, an interinstitutional action plan for the implementation of the information society development program “Digital Agenda of the Republic of Lithuania” for 2014–2020 was launched in 2017 and updated in 2019.
Main Stakeholders involved:	The Lithuanian Ministry of the Economy and Innovation is the main governmental body responsible for the digital skills policy setting and coordination, while other institutions involved are: Ministry of Education, Science & Sport, Ministry of Social Security & Labour, Ministry of Culture, Vilnius University, Kaunas University of Technology, Association “Langas į ateitį”, Lithuanian Municipal Public Library Association, etc

B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	Yes
Key features / challenges	The coordination and governance for Digital Skills policy planning and implementation in Lithuania is carried out by the Lithuanian National Digital Coalition (NDC), which was established in November 2013. The activities of the National Coalition and the relationship with other organizations are coordinated by the association “Langas į ateitį” (“Window to the Future”).

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	Project "Connected Lithuania"
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	The goal of the project “Connected Lithuania: Efficient, Secure and Responsible Lithuanian Digital Community” is to help the population learn to use information technologies and the Internet efficiently, safely, and responsibly and the opportunities it provides. The project started in 2018, has a duration of 3 years, takes place in every municipality in Lithuania and is intended for a large target group of the population - about 500,000 individuals, whose digital skills are insufficient.

D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	Yes
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	The Translation of the DigComp framework in Lithuania is implemented by the Education Development Centre. The Education Development Centre (EDC) is the biggest institution affiliate to the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport of the Republic of Lithuania providing educational support in the field of pre-school, primary and general education.
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	No
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	Currently in Lithuania there are no visible improvements in transparency of digital qualifications: credit transfer between formal, non-formal and industry-based ICT educations and certifications and there is no mechanism to implement discussions about the recognition of informal education on ICT/ digital skills.

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	In planning
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	Lithuania has a Law on Higher Education and Research, which covers Open Access and research data, while the more relevant policy document on Research, Data, and Open science is the Research Council of Lithuania’s “Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Data” (2016), which cover both publications and data. Skills are not addressed, but responsibilities for various aspects of Open Access and Open Data are covered in detail. The focus of Lithuania’s policy on Research, Data, and Open science is more on rights than on obligations, and the inference is that universities are responsible for developing their own policies, procedures, guidance, and monitoring systems.
Main Stakeholders involved	The Research Council of Lithuania is the institution coordinating open access activities in Lithuania. The Council collects and systematises the data on open access databases used in Lithuania, on legal, financial, and other developmental aspects, participates in the open access policy formation and encourages dissemination of the open access concept.
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	With regards to digital research infrastructures, following the European Commission and ESFRI encouragement to Member States and Associated Countries for developing national roadmaps for research infrastructures (RIs), Lithuania developed the Roadmap in 2011, which it was updated in 2015.
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	Lithuania’s performance in terms of knowledge transfer indicators is mixed. The number of public-private collaborative papers per capita was about 90% less than the EU-28 average, also, annual average decrease in scores were found for shares of firms cooperating with governmental, public, or private research institutes (33% decrease), and for shares of firms collaborating with universities or higher education institutions (35% decrease).

<p>Portugal</p>	<p>Even though Portugal is not far from the European median in terms of digital skills, it needs to reinforce them. Portugal’s training infrastructures and the strong potential of its human resources make this a viable task. To this end, in 2017 the Portuguese government established the “National Digital Competences Initiative e.2030, Portugal INCoDe.2030”, an integrated public policy to enhance and foster digital competences. Portugal INCoDe.2030 focuses on skill formation in education and training for individuals rather than for businesses: it offers schemes for citizens, the elderly and disadvantaged groups.</p>
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	13,48	12,51	Knowledge	31	Availability of latest technologies	20
Human Capital	9,44	12,32	Technology	38	ICT Patent applications	30
Use of Internet Services	7,21	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	27	ICT Skills	28
Integration of Digital Technology	8,17	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	24	Publication and use of open data.	34
Digital Public Services	11,27	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	31	R&D expenditure by government & HE	20
ICT graduates	1,90	3,60	Development & application of technology	19	Online trust & safety	14
ICT Specialists	2,40	3,90	Scientific research legislation	35	ICT Regulatory environment	11
Doing an online course	7,69	11,17				
Open data	0,42	0,66				

Future Readiness	Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS	Yes
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science	Yes
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not	No
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index	28
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index	45
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index	34
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories	26

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Yes
Key features / challenges	The “Portugal INCoDe.2030” inter-ministerial action, launched in April 2017, reflects the national policy on digital skills and is structured around five main axes: Inclusion, Education, Qualification, Specialisation and Research. It addresses the concept of digital competences in a broad manner and it brings together the areas of Administrative Modernisation, Science, Technology and Higher Education, Education, Labour, Planning and Infrastructures and Economy, aiming to strengthen the basic skills of the population in ICT.
Main Stakeholders involved:	Ministry of the Presidency and of Administrative Modernisation is responsible for the digital skills policy. Other stakeholders involved are a) Ministry of Education, b) Directorate-General for Employment and Labour Relations, c) Directorate General for Higher Education, d) Directorate General for Education, e) Agency for Qualification and Vocational Education, f) Institute of Employment and Vocational Training, g) Administrative Modernisation Agency, h) National Institute for Administration and i) Agency for Competitiveness and Innovation.

B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	Yes
Key features / challenges	The promotion and coordination of INCoDe.2030 initiative, involves three permanent bodies: the National Forum for Digital Competences , responsible for gathering and coordinating the relative private and public companies and institutions, the INCoDe.2030 Coordination Structure , which oversees the lines of action and the initiative as a whole and the INCoDe.2030 Technical Secretariat , which monitors, records and reports on the implementation of all the planned activities.

C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	The INCoDe.2030 initiative
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	The main initiatives implemented under the Research measure include a) Advanced Computing Portugal 2030: Dynamic and evolutive process aimed to promote and expand Advanced Cyberinfrastructure (ACI) in Portugal by a factor of 100 in the coming decade and until 2030 and b) AI Portugal 2030: An innovation and growth strategy to foster Artificial Intelligence in Portugal in the European context. For these two initiatives dedicated strategies have been developed.

D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	Yes
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	The INCoDe.2030 programme in October 2019 released the Digital Competence Dynamic Reference Framework (QDRCD) a tool for population' digital skills' evaluation. Based on the Digital Competence Framework for Citizens the QDRCD has three objectives: a) to support the definition of policies and strategies, b) to design education programmes; and c) to evaluate and certificate skills, either by self-diagnosis or by certifying entities.
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	Yes
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	The National Qualifications System (SNQ) was created in December 2007 with primary objective to raise the qualification levels of the active population, through school and professional progression, as well as to structure an initial and continuous educational and training offer for young people and adults, adjusted to the needs of companies and the labour market..

E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	In planning
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	A preparation of a National Policy for Open Science is underway in Portugal. The work is initiated by the Government and Ministry for Science, Technology and Higher Education. The website set up for Open Science in Portugal, describes the four pillars of the policy to be: (1) transparency in practices, methodology, observation, and data collection, (2) public availability and re-use of scientific data, (3) public access and transparency in scientific communication, (4) use of web-based tools to facilitate scientific collaboration.
Main Stakeholders involved	Ministry for Science, Technology and Higher Education and Foundation for Science and Technology. that supports the Portuguese scientific community via a range of funding schemes, for scientists, research teams or R&D centres.
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	There are currently 4 digital research infrastructures underway in Portugal: a) INCD Portuguese National Distributed Computing Infrastructure, b) RCTS Science, Technology and Society Network, c) RNCA National Advance Computing Network & d) UC-LCA Laboratory for Advanced Computing.
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	Portuguese firms cooperate with either universities or higher education institutions, or with governmental, public, or private research institutes at a rate of 10 %. This score is below both the EU-28 level and the European Research Area average. Cooperation between business and academia in Portugal remains low. The Portuguese institutional framework does not include incentives or an integrated strategy to foster cooperation between academia and industry.

 Switzerland	Switzerland has a good starting point to continue to apply the successful model of a liveable, open, and modern country in the digital future. Digital transformation enables the sustainable development of the country. In this context the "Digital Switzerland" strategy provides the guidelines for government action and indicates where and how authorities, academia, the private sector, civil society and politics must work together in order to shape the transformation process for the benefit of everyone in Switzerland. The action plan, as an integral part of the strategy, includes the specific measures to achieve the strategic goals. Finally, Switzerland has established policies for Open Science and Open Data.
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	<12,51	12,51	Knowledge	2	Availability of latest technologies	3
Human Capital	>12,32	12,32	Technology	10	ICT Patent applications	9
Use of Internet Services	>8,70	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	3	ICT Skills	12
Integration of Digital Technology	>8,27	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	3	Publication and use of open data.	19
Digital Public Services	<10,8	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	3	R&D expenditure by government & HE	6
ICT graduates	<3,60	3,60	Development & application of technology	7	Online trust & safety	42
ICT Specialists	N/A	3,90	Scientific research legislation	2	ICT Regulatory environment	15
Doing an online course	N/A	11,17				
Open data	N/A	0,66				
Future Readiness						Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS						N/A
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science						N/A
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not						Yes
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index						5
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index						47
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index						10
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories						7

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Yes
Key features / challenges	The Federal Council wants Switzerland to exploit the opportunities of digitalisation to the full. On 5 September 2018 it adopted its Digital Switzerland strategy for the next 2 years. Within the framework of this strategy the Federal Council established a working group on the subject of artificial intelligence and support initiatives in relation to Smart Cities. In addition, the federal administration intensified dialogue with interested or involved participants, and especially with the cantons. Among its objectives the further improvement of the digital empowerment of people is included.
Main Stakeholders involved:	The Federal Department of the Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications DETEC is responsible for coordinating the Confederation's implementation measures within the federal administration and for the ongoing development of the Digital Switzerland strategy.
B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	Yes
Key features / challenges	The Digital Switzerland strategy is a joint task of authorities at all levels of the state, the private sector, the academic community, civil society, and politics. The Federal Department of the Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications DETEC is responsible for coordinating the Confederation's implementation measures within the federal administration and for the ongoing development of the Digital Switzerland strategy. This work is carried out within the framework of the Confederation's «Digital Switzerland» Coordination Group. The Confederation's «Digital Switzerland» Office, based within OFCOM, supports the Coordination Group in terms of organisation and content. From 1 January 2021 onwards coordination within the federal administration will be assured by the Federal Chancellery.
C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	Swiss Digital Initiative, National research program on the theme of digital transformation
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	The Swiss Digital Initiative is aimed at a long-term and sustainable process with the objective of ensuring ethical standards in the digital world. The objectives of the initiative are: a) ensuring ethical standards in the digital world, b) fostering technology's potential to advance flourishing human societies, c) focusing on ethical values and principles in action, d) developing specific and action-oriented projects that will contribute to a global dialogue on the ethics of digitalisation, and aim to foster trust in digital technologies, as well as in the actors involved in the ongoing process of digital transformation and e) the SDI is primarily, but not exclusively, aimed at companies with a global presence. The national research program on the theme of digital transformation focuses on the priority areas of research "Training, learning and digital transformation", "Ethics, reliability and governance" and "Digital economy and labour market".
D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	In planning
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	Currently in Switzerland, there is no national framework been established, yet based on EU DIGICOMP. To some extent the "Lehrplan 21" harmonises the curriculum and integrates media education, yet digital competences do not appear and is not given transversal status in educational policy.
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	Yes
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	Switzerland is taking part in the Bologna Process in the field of higher education and in the Copenhagen Process in the sphere of vocational and professional education and training. Both processes contribute to the national established Qualifications Framework for the higher education sector (nqf.ch-HS) and Qualifications Framework for vocational and professional education and training.
E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	Yes
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	Switzerland has a National strategy for Open Access (OA) to publications with goals the cost transparency for public funds and the coordination among stakeholders, especially higher education institutions and their libraries. The time horizon of this national strategy covers the period 2021-2028. It will be implemented across two national action plans, one for the period 2021-2024 (including the Open Access Action Plan 2021-2024), and another one for the period 2025-2028. The Swiss National Strategy on OA aims to achieve the following objective, in accordance with international benchmarks: by 2024, all scholarly publication activity in Switzerland should be OA, all scholarly publications funded by public money must be freely accessible on the internet. The OA landscape will consist of a mix of OA models.
Main Stakeholders involved	The Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) supports scientific research in all academic disciplines, from history to medicine and the engineering sciences. At the end of 2019, the SNSF was funding 5750 projects involving 18,900 researchers, which makes it the leading Swiss institution for promoting scientific research.
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	According to the Swiss Roadmap for Research Infrastructures 2019, the main digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes include a) High-Performance Computing and Networking (HPCN-24) , b) Common Data Centre for Astronomy, Astroparticle and Cosmology (CDCI) , and c) Swiss Centre for Musculoskeletal Biobanking and Imaging and Clinical Movement Analysis (Balgrist campus) .
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	According to the 2018 ERA progress report, Switzerland scored very highly on one indicator: the number of public-private collaborative papers per capita, at 261. This figure was more than six times higher than the EU-28 score of 41. On the knowledge transfer indicator, performance was less impressive; with about 10 % of private firms collaborating with universities, governments or research institutes.

<p>The Netherlands</p>	<p>Netherlands lies at the forefront of Digital Transformation in all its aspects and is a leader in both Digital Skills and Open Science domains. Digital skills are embedded in the National Digitalization Strategy and there are many stakeholders involved in its implementation, including ministries, state companies, research institutions, social partners, and universities. The main challenge faced by Netherlands is the relative shortage of highly skilled personnel since the demand in the market is larger than the availability of suitably skilled professionals. Although attention is given to initiatives that target digital skills for the general population (including lower level educated persons and the elderly), a very strong higher education agenda drives important activities towards enhancement of digital skills at all levels. Even though the landscape is quite fragmented, there is strong coordination among stakeholders which ensures a continuous progress.</p>
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Scoreboard

Digital Economy and Society	Score	EU average	Digital Competitiveness	Ranking among 163 countries	Impact of ICT	Ranking among 121 countries
Connectivity	15,08	12,51	Knowledge	13	Availability of latest technologies	7
Human Capital	16,04	12,32	Technology	6	ICT Patent applications	12
Use of Internet Services	11,28	8,70	Total expenditure on R&D (%)	17	ICT Skills	8
Integration of Digital Technology	13,15	8,27	Total R&D personnel per capita	12	Publication and use of open data.	9
Digital Public Services	12,14	10,8	Scientific and technical employment	12	R&D expenditure by government & HE	12
ICT graduates	2,50	3,60	Development & application of technology	5	Online trust & safety	62
ICT Specialists	5,40	3,90	Scientific research legislation	9	ICT Regulatory environment	18
Doing an online course	14,02	11,17				
Open data	0,78	0,66				
Future Readiness						Status (Yes/No) - Ranking
Research Strategy: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on research/RIS						Yes
Open data access initiatives: Existence of public strategy/policies/interventions/action plans on open science						Yes
R&D Landscape H2020/ Innovation Performance: Being a strong innovator or not						Yes
Technological readiness Ranking as per World Economic Forum-Global Competitiveness Index						3
Open data access: Ranking as per Global open data index						20
Future Readiness (Level of country preparedness to exploit digital transformation): Ranking as per IMD World Digital Competitiveness Index						3
Availability of open data repositories: Number of data repositories						9

Digital Skills Policy Context

A. Current Digital skills policy context	
Digital skills Strategy/Policies	Yes
Key features / challenges	The major policy document that guides Digital Skills development is the 2018 Dutch Digitalization Strategy, and its updated version (Digitalization Strategy 2.0) that has been published in July 2019 and includes a brief overview of the results achieved and future goals. Digital skills development is fully integrated and plays a significant role in the strategy, one of the “ambitions” of which is the “Everyone can participate, and we work together” motto. The strategy recognizes that this will require everyone to learn basic skills as soon as possible and continue to learn and develop in later life.
Main Stakeholders involved:	Responsibility for the Digitalization Strategy of the Netherlands lies within the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy, whereas the responsibility for Digital Government lies with the State Secretary for the Interior and Kingdom Relations. Other institutions involved in the country’s digital skills landscape include: Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, Ministry of Social Affairs and Employment, ECP Platform for the Information Society, SURF collaborative organisation for ICT in Dutch education and research, VSNU association of universities, VH association of universities of applied science, SBB Foundation for Cooperation on Vocational Education, Training and Labour Market, The National Library and the Network of Libraries.
B. Current Digital skills governance model	
Digital Skills governance mechanism	No
Key features / challenges	The Dutch digital skills landscape is pluralistic. It includes ministries (at least 3 ministries as policy makers), national funding bodies as well as organizations with the responsibility for providing IT services. ECP – Platform for the Information Society coordinates the Coalition and collaborates with public authorities across different ministries as well as with industry, teachers, researchers and non-governmental organisations to advance the digital agenda. Almost 200 ECP members work together to bolster the digital skills of citizens in all age groups.
C. Current Digital skills initiatives at national and regional level	
Number of major digital skills initiatives	Seven major initiatives
Key features/ challenges of initiatives for Science & Research up-skilling	Main initiatives most relevant to the goals and objectives of the strategic documents on digital skills include: a) Dutch Technology Pact (Techniepact - https://www.techniepact.nl), b) The Talent for Technology Platform (PTVT - https://ptvt.nl/over/), c) Dutch Digital Delta (https://dutchdigitaldelta.nl/en/), d) Knowledge Net (Kennisnet - https://www.kennisnet.nl/wie-wij-zijn/), e) Digital Society Alliance (https://digitaalsamenleven.nl/over-de-alliantie/), f) Make IT Work (https://www.it-omscholing.nl/nl/), g) Safe Internet (https://veiliginternetten.nl/).
D. Current Digital Skills certification /accreditation / competence frameworks	
Digital competence framework	No
Key features / challenges on the digital competence framework	The DigComp standards have been used as a reference to compare with the outcomes of "Digital Literacy" curricula in primary and secondary schools in the Netherlands. Furthermore, a digital literacy assessment framework (MDS) has been proposed by researchers in Twente University and recognized by Unesco as a useful instrument. However, it seems that there is no formally accepted Digital Competence framework established
Digital skills formal certification / accreditation framework	No
Key features / challenges on the certification / accreditation framework	The country has established a formal National Qualifications Framework (NLQF) for the classification of all possible qualifications in the Netherlands (from basic education to a PhD doctorate). NLQF makes it possible to compare formally regulated qualifications to non-formal qualifications (often provided by private institutions). There is no indication of whether the existing framework and accreditation system are under consideration for being expanded at the digital competencies domain however.
E. Current Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	
National strategy / policy on Research, Data, and Open science	Yes
Key features / challenges for Digital skills interventions on Research, Data, and Open science	The Netherlands is widely considered a leader in Open Science policies because of its principal role in the formulation of the FAIR-principles, and in the design of the European Open Science Cloud. According to the 2017 Open Science Declaration, the government confirmed its commitment to contribute to the transition towards an open science system in the Netherlands by ensuring implementation and participating actively in the National Plan for Open Science. Also, the National Plan for Open Science is the main policy document driving initiatives towards transition to an Open Science system.
Main Stakeholders involved	Research & Innovation policies in the Netherlands are mainly centralised at the national level. The central government remains the main financing body, but policymaking and focus areas are gradually becoming more regionalised.
Key features/ challenges of government digital infrastructures & services available for research purposes	The Netherlands established a Permanent Committee for large scale research infrastructures. It was announced in the 2025 Vision for Science of the Dutch government and has been appointed by NWO on behalf of the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. Three organisations are key to providing digital infrastructure at the Dutch national level: SURF, the Netherlands eScience Centre, and DANS.
Key features of current links between the Research community and the Industry	Netherlands enjoys strong links between the Research Community and the Industry, as is evident from the European Research Area Progress Report (2018), according to which it enjoys a high number of academic job ads per 1000 researches (104 vs 42 EU Average).

Annex VII: Overview of the Digitalisation policies in the Nordic countries

Country	Relevant agendas and programmes (for a full list, check each country separately)	Main themes and focus areas	Regional agenda
Denmark	Digital Strategy 2016–2020: A Stronger and More Secure Digital Denmark Strategy for Denmark's Digital Growth (2018)	Boosting growth (trade and industry) Effective and user-centric public sector and services to businesses and citizens Digital skills for all	Regional digital agendas contribute to national goal setting. These are often sector-specific, e.g. e-health, digital enhancement of SMEs and digital skills development in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
Finland	The Finnish Government Programme (2015) Digital Agenda 2011–2020: Productive and Inventive Finland	Digitalised public services Growth environment for future digital businesses; includes information security	No push for special regional digital agendas from the national level. Some regions and municipalities have drawn up digital agendas by their own initiative
Iceland	Iceland 2020 National Cyber Security Strategy 2015–2026 Green Paper on Statistics Registration and Information (2018)	Focus on e-participation and e-government Better and more digital public services Digital infrastructure including interoperability between IT systems	No specific focus on digitalisation in the municipalities, but high-speed broadband for everyone by 2020 is a priority.
Norway	Digital Agenda for Norway: ICT for an Easier Everyday Life and Increased Productivity (2016) White Paper 27 (2016–2017): The Industry—Greener, Smarter and Creative Digitalisation Strategy for Municipalities and Counties 2017–2020 Digital21 (2017–2018) is the government's cross-sectoral expert group, recommending strategies for furthering digitalisation in the area of growth in industry and businesses	Digital public services and efficient public sector Develop the digital technological infrastructure that the business sector will require in the future Digital competencies and skills Cybersecurity	The Association of Local and Regional Authorities has encouraged municipalities and regions to formulate digital strategies individually or in collaboration. Regional or municipal digital agendas contribute to national goal setting
Sweden	Digital Agenda, For a Sustainable Digitalised Sweden (2017) Digital First Policy for the Digitalisation of the Public Sector (2015–2018) Digital Agenda, ICT for Everyone (2011) Digilyft (2016–2019) stimulates increased digitalisation of SMEs in the industrial sector	Digital skills Digital security Digital innovation Digital management Digital infrastructure	Regions were encouraged to develop their own digital agendas drawing from the 2011 National Digital Agenda, and almost all regions have done it. Regional agendas' biggest priority areas lay in infrastructure and e-services
Greenland	The Digital Society: National Digitalisation Strategy 2018–2021	Digitalisation of public services to promote quality of life and business development Security and privacy One IT architecture	The implementation of the digitalisation strategy is expected to lead to increasing connectivity and accessibility of services and increasing digital opportunities for citizens and businesses across Greenland
The Faroe Islands	The National Digitalisation Programme of the Faroe Islands (2015)	Digitalisation of public services, Increasing efficiency in the public sector, Increasing the competitiveness, growth, and production strength, IT architecture	Digitalisation efforts in the municipalities are focused on addressing the demographic changes and promoting growth in the IT industry
Åland islands	The Digital Agenda (2012) The IT Strategy (2018) The IT Strategy 2018–2020 for the Education Sector on Åland	E-administration and digitalising public services Co-operation in IT support and IT services Green IT and developing digital infrastructure	Digitalisation is seen as a tool to increase the attractiveness of the Åland Islands in general, including e.g., young people

